

GVU

JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, HEALTH
AND TECHNOLOGY

GVU JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, HEALTH AND TECHNOLOGY

(GVU-J. SHT, formerly Gvu Sci. – Tech J.)

E-mail: gvuscitechj@gmail.com

Tel: 08121833236; 08034553580

**A JOURNAL PUBLICATION OF
GLORIOUS VISION UNIVERSITY**

Km 1, Ogwa-Ehor Road, P.M.B. 001, Ogwa, Edo State, NIGERIA.

p-ISSN: 2536 - 6866

e-ISSN:2659 - 1529

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13209225>

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

Professor Michael O. Osuide

SUB EDITORS-IN-CHIEF

Dr. Kingsley E. Enerijiofi

Glorious Vision University
University, Ogwa

Prof. S. O. Azi

University of Benin
Benin City

EDITORIAL SECRETARY/ONLINE MANAGER

Dr. Adriel A. Ekozin

Glorious Vision University, Ogwa

ASSISTANT EDITORIAL SECRETARIES

Dr. Moses O. Onigbinde

Glorious Vision University, Ogwa

EDITORIAL BOARD

Prof Omon S. Isikhuemehen (Microbiology, Mushroom Science), North Carolina and Technical State University, USA

Prof. C. O. Adetunji (Microbiology and Biotechnology), Edo State University, Edo State

Prof. J. O. Otaigbe (Chemistry), University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt Nigeria

Prof. F.O. Ikpotokin (Computer Sciences), Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria

Prof. C. I. Ajuwa (Mechanical Engineering) Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun

Prof. E. Aiyuhunyi (Physics) University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria.

Prof. A. I. Akinmoladun (Computer Education) City University, New York, USA.

Prof. P. O. Agbaire (Chemistry), Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria

Prof. C. C. Osuor (Biochemistry), University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria

Prof. G. R.A. Okogun (Medical Laboratory Science), Ambrose Ali University, Ekpoma, Nigeria
 Prof. A. A. Oshodi (Chemistry) Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria.
 Prof. F. O. Ekhaise (Microbiology), University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria
 Prof. F. M. Okoro (Mathematics), Ambrose Ali University, Ekpoma, Nigeria
 Prof. O. Obodeh (Mechanical Engineering) Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma.
 Prof. A. Ogbeibu (Zoology), University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria
 Prof. O. N. Oigiangbe (Zoology) Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria.
 Prof. M. D. Mukhtar (Pharmaceutical Microbiology, Medical and Public Health,), Bayero University Kano
 Prof. O. Okhiai (Nursing) University of Delta, Agbor, Delta State
 Prof. F. N. Ogwueleka (Computer Science), Nigeria Defence Academy, Kaduna
 Dr. Abdulrafii Raj (Physics), College of Sci. Engin. And Tech., University of South Africa, South Africa
 Dr. Peter I. Imoesi (Molecular Biology), University of Aberdeen, Scotland, UK
 Dr. J. O. Abayomi (Chem. & Biol.), University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK
 Dr. Rotimi Fasimoye (Parasitology), University of Dundee, Scotland, UK

Description

GVU Journal of Science, Health and Technology (GVU-J. SHT) is the official Journal of the College of Basic, Applied and Health Sciences (COLBAHS), Glorious Vision University, Ogwa. GVU-J. SHT is a multidisciplinary international peer-reviewed journal that provides rapid publication of research papers, review articles, notes, and short communications that are of high-quality, original and relevant to fundamental and applied aspects of all areas of science and technology. The journal is published biannually. Its contents are organized into four sections: Mathematical, Computational & Information Sciences; Physical sciences; Biological & Health Sciences, and Technology.

Aims and Scope

GVU-J. SHT aims to provide a platform for scientists and academics to promote, share, and discuss fundamental and applied aspects of all areas of sciences & technology provided that there is some advance in knowledge presented by the work. The Journal provides an articulate and formidable platform to drive and actualize the mission and vision of Glorious Vision University through Science and Technology.

Subject areas include, but are not limited to the following fields:

- Biochemistry
- Biotechnology
- Artificial intelligence, Cybersecurity
- Botany
- Microbiology /
- Nutrition
- Nursing Science
- Zoology /Environmental Biology
- Chemistry
- Computer Science and Information Technology
- Mathematics/ Actuarial Science
- Physics
- Public Health
- Sport Sciences
- Statistics

- Medical Lab. Science
-

- Technology

Instructions for Authors

GVU Journal of Science, Health and Technology (GVU-J. SHT) invites scholars and researchers to submit their scholarly articles that have *not been and will not be* published elsewhere for publishing in the forthcoming issue. GVU-J. SHT requests the manuscript should be written in English of publishable standard. Authors should compile manuscript in MS word with Times New Roman font type, 12 point font size and double line spacing on A4 sized papers using the following layout.

Title should be concise, describing the contents of the paper. The Title Page should include the authors' full names (*with Surname(s) first & clearly demarcated with a coma*) and affiliations, the name of the corresponding author along with e-mail and phone number.

Abstract should be informative and self-explanatory, briefly introduce and state the scope of the research, indicate significant data, and point out major findings and conclusions. The abstract should not exceed 200 words. Standard nomenclature should be used and abbreviations should be avoided. No literature should be cited. Graphical abstract where necessary should be direct and clear with regards to the results.

Keywords should be provided immediately after the abstract for indexing purpose. A maximum of five (5) words *in italics* are required.

Introduction should provide a clear statement of the problem, an adequate background on the subject, and the objectives of the work. It should be understandable to audience from a broad range of scientific disciplines.

Materials and Methods should provide sufficient detail to allow the procedures to be reproduced. However, methods already published should only be cited. New procedures and modifications of published procedure should be described in details.

Results should be presented with clarity and precision. Results should be explained, but largely without referring to the literature.

Discussion should provide detailed interpretation and significance of the findings in the results obtained. State the conclusions in a few sentences at the end of the paper.

Conclusion should include the most important idea of the experiment, the author's own findings, possible solutions to the problem, recommendations for further research, etc.

The Acknowledgments of people, grants, funds, laboratories etc is required but should be brief.

Tables should be kept to a minimum and be designed to be as simple as possible. Tables should be prepared in Microsoft Word and included directly in text and numbered consecutively in Arabic numerals and supplied with a heading above the Table. Tables should be self-explanatory without reference to the text.

Figures should be numbered and are included directly in text. Graphics should be prepared using applications capable of generating high resolution before pasting in the Microsoft Word manuscript file. Use Arabic numerals to designate Figures along with concise titles at the bottom of the Figure.

References: The latest edition of APA reference style is required.

Submission and Peer Review of Manuscripts

Manuscripts and evidence of payment of review fee of Five thousand (N5, 000.00) Naira should accompany the manuscript submission and sent as email attachment and addressed to the editor at the email address: gvuscitechj@gmail.com and you will receive a confirmation of receipt within 48 hours of submission. Please note that fully typed work on A4 paper that exceeds ten (10) pages will attract extra charge(s) per extra page. Authors are to pay to SAU Science-Tech Journal. **Bank:** First Bank plc; **Name of Account:** SAU Science-Tech Journal; **Account Number:** 2030 810 989.

Acceptance and Publication of Manuscripts

Authors will be notified via an Acceptance Letter after the final acceptance of the manuscripts by the editor. The accepted manuscripts will be immediately copyedited, typeset, paginated and proofread for eventual publication in the next issue of the journal. Authors of accepted manuscripts are to pay article publication fee of Twenty Five Thousand Naira (N25, 000.00) only to SAU Science-Tech Journal. **Bank:** First Bank plc; **Name of Account:** SAU Science-Tech Journal; **Account Number:** 2030 810 989.

Disclaimer: The information provided and the opinions given in this publication are not necessarily those of COLBAHS, Glorious Vision University or those of the editors, and should not be acted upon without independent consideration and professional advice. Glorious Vision University and the editors of GVU-JST. will not accept responsibility for any loss or damage suffered by any person(s) acting or refraining from acting upon any material, methods, products, or ideas contained in this publication.

Volume 9 Number 1 Table of Contents

January - July, 2024

No.	Authors	Title	Pages
1	Akin-Osanaiye B. C., Dahunsi A. A.	Antibacterial Activity of Emperor Scorpion (<i>Pandinus imperator</i>) Venom against Some Selected Bacteria	1 - 17
2	Ugoh S. C., Dahunsi A. A.	Antibacterial Activities of Blowfly (<i>Lucilla sericata</i>) and Housefly (<i>Musca domestica</i>) Maggots Extract on Some Selected Isolates	18 - 34
3	D. O. Babayemi, T. F. Akinhanmi, B. O. Onunkwor, H. O. Ozeomena, M. A. Adeleke, O. I. Akanni, O. O. Keyede, M. O. Michael, F. E. Idhove, S. A. Mukaila, & O. Ademuyiwa	Sodium Selenite Ameliorates the Effects of Sodium Arsenite on Some Biomolecules and Enzymes of Energy Metabolism in the Testes of Albino Rats	35-48
4	Afolabi S. O.	Medicinal Value of African Pear (<i>Dacryodes edulis</i>): Implication for Agricultural Extension Activities	49-54
5	Uwaya O. D.	Evaluation of the Analgesic Effect of Aqueous Root Extract of <i>Combretum platypterum</i> (Welw) Hutch and Dalziel on Rodent	55 - 60
6	Uwaya O. D.	Free Radical Scavenging and Antioxidant Capacity of Leaf of <i>Combretum platypterum</i> (Welw) Hutch and Dalziel	61-69
7	Isah A., Odia A. E., Obrifor E. E., Ikhenemue O. O., & Suleiman A.	Phytochemical Screening and Antioxidant Investigation of <i>Persea americana</i>	70 - 77
8	Obrifor E. B., Egbon E. E., Isah A., Erhabor D. O., Ogonegbu A. C.	Comparison of the Concentration of PAHs in Raw and Roasted Beef Samples from Ekpoma	78 - 85
9	Ogidi O. I., & Addy P. S.	Comparative Analysis of Nutrients and Phytochemical Properties of Matured and Young Leaves of <i>Manihot esculenta</i> , <i>Arachis hypogeal</i> , and <i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	86 - 93
10	Tubotu K. F., Agbaire P. O., Akporhonor E. E., Odagwe A. A.	Phytoremediation of Cd, Pb, and Ni-co-contaminated Soil of the Niger Delta Using Local Maize (<i>Zea mays</i>) Plant	94 - 105
11	Udinyiwe C. O., & Omorieg A. E.	Physiochemical Properties and Biodegradation Potentials of Soil Microbes Isolated from Mechanic Workshops in Benin Metropolis	106 - 112
12	Wangboje O. M. & Omozogie C.	A Preliminary Investigation of Microplastic Levels in a Commercially Important Clariid Fish Species from Ikpoba River, Benin City, Nigeria	113 - 120

13	Ebhohon S. O., Emelike A. P., Onyenze C. C., Ikenna J. C., Ngwuta C. R., Ejue P. O., & Ogbu C. A.	Phytochemical Characterization and Toxicity Assessment of Acute and Sub-Acute Oral Administration of Aqueous Extract of <i>Jatropha tanjorensis</i> Leaf	121 - 144
14	Ekozin A. A., Isola O. B., Inetianbor O. C., Omondiale S. O., Omojoyegbe R. T., Okanlawon T. S.	Green Synthesized Iron Nanoparticles Using <i>Gongronema latifolium</i> Leaf Extract: Characterization, Antioxidant, and Antidiabetic Activities	145 - 157
15	Lawani M. O., Enerijiofi K. E.	Gene Therapy for Sickle Cell Disease: Present Insights	158 - 165
16	Emuokhonun G. A., Unuigbe C. A., Okodugha V. O., Madu P. C.	Determination of Levels of Heavy Metal in Sub-Soil Around Incinerator in University of Benin Health Centre	166 - 175

Antibacterial Activity of Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) Venom against Some Selected Bacteria

AKIN-OSANAIYE B. C.¹; DAHUNSI A. A.*²

¹Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria.

²Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria

Corresponding author: ayodeji.dahunsi2022@uniabuja.edu.ng; 08066761700

Abstract: Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are essential components of the innate immune system that display potent antimicrobial activity against a wide range of microorganisms. Scorpion venoms, known for their diverse molecular compositions, have been identified as rich sources of AMPs. This study focused on the antimicrobial potential of Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) venom against selected bacteria isolated from drinking water sources. The physicochemical characteristics of the venom were analyzed, revealing a colorless, odorless, transparent liquid with a pH of 4.5 that dries easily at room temperature. The study involved the collection of 50 Emperor Scorpions, with venom extracted through electrical stimulation. The venom was purified and tested against bacterial isolates, including *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii*. Analytical Profile Index (API) kits confirmed bacterial identification. The results revealed concentration-dependent antibacterial activity, with the highest zone of inhibition at 11.5mm (100% concentration) against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values ranged from 25% to 50%, while minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) was determined at 75%. The venom's effectiveness was comparable to commercial antibiotics. Physicochemical analysis, bacterial identification, and antimicrobial assays collectively support the potential of Emperor Scorpion venom as a non-toxic antibacterial agent. This research contributes valuable insights for further exploration of scorpion venom in therapeutic applications and suggests avenues for scorpion farming, extraction expertise, and public awareness to maximize the benefits of this natural resource.

Key Words: Emperor Scorpion, *Pandinus imperator*, Scorpion Venom, Antimicrobial Peptides, Antibacterial Activity.

1 Introduction

Antimicrobial is a substance that kills or inhibits the growth of microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, protozoan, and viruses (Enerijiofi and Isola, 2019; Ovuru, et al., 2023). The discovery of antimicrobials like penicillin and tetracycline paved the way for better health for millions around the world. Before 1941, the year where penicillin was discovered, there were no true cure for some diseases such as gonorrhoea (a venereal disease involving inflammatory discharge from the urethra or vagina), strep throat (a painful infection in the throat caused by group A streptococcus), or pneumonia (a lung infection in which the air sacs are filled with fluid) (Cosgrove et al., 2003). The resistance to antibiotics is a rising concern among health care professionals, driving the search for peptides with antimicrobial activities in plants, bacteria, and animals (Adesina et al., 2013; Shaini et al., 2010; Enerijiofi and

Isola, 2019). Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are key effector of the innate immune response of animals and show antimicrobial therapy potency (Yibao et al., 2009; Ramamoorthy, 2009). Most AMPs that display hydrophobic and cationic properties have a molecular mass below 25 to 30 kDa (Marsh et al., 2009). So far, more than 2,000 natural AMPs have been isolated, sequenced and submitted (Jupeng et al., 2021). Some natural antimicrobial peptides are being developed for use either as antibiotics for topical use in healthcare or as preservatives in the food industry. Apart from the extreme diversity in their primary and secondary structures, AMPs have in vitro effects on a wide spectrum of bacteria (Gram-negative and Gram-positive) and cells, including parasites, tumor cells, fungi and viruses (Bulet et al., 2004). AMPs have non-specific processes involved in the antimicrobial action. The unique property of an antimicrobial peptide is its ability to interact selectively with bacterial lipid membrane and cause disruption.

This property could decrease the likelihood of microbes acquiring resistance to AMPs. This could give AMPs a major advantage over conventional antibiotics, and in response, these peptides have been extensively investigated as potential antimicrobial agents (Harris et al., 2009; Thennarasu et al., 2010a, b; Ramamoorthy et al., 2010). Scorpions are particularly resistant to bacterial aggressions, and it is of interest to analyze the molecules responsible for this resistance (Sabatier et al., 1996). The scorpion venoms have three different groups of ingredients and peptides, based on their molecular mass with enzyme activity such as hyaluronidases, phospholipases, and sphingomyelinase (Chao et al., 2008). The second group contains mainly a peptide fraction with molecular mass around and lower than 10 kDa such as toxins and cytolytic compounds. The third group is composed of components such as ions, free amino acids, biogenic amines, neurotransmitters, acylpolyamines, heterocyclic compounds and alkaloids (Ma et al., 2010; Kuhn-Nentwig, 2003). Different antimicrobial peptides such as micropores have been identified from plants and animals (He et al., 2008; Zhao et al., 2009), BmKb1 and BmKn2 (Zeng et al., 2004), Hadrurin (Torres-Larios et al., 2000) and Mucroporin (Chao et al., 2008). Caerin is an antimicrobial peptide that was first found in amphibian, Australian green tree frog (Wong et al., 1997). Later different variants were isolated from a number of Australian frogs of the *Litoria* genus (Brian et al., 2000; Steinborner et al., 1998) and African frog (Gottler and Ramamoorthy, 2009). In recent years, caerin and caerin-like antimicrobial peptides were been found in scorpions such as *Mesobuthus lupus* and *Mesobuthus martensii* (Luo et al., 2005). Antibacterial activity of caerin on Gram-positive and negative bacteria has been shown with only small variation in their minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values (Boland and Separovic, 2006; Chia et al., 2011).

The venom or antimicrobial peptides found in scorpion has shown a broad-spectrum activity against a wide range of pathogenic microorganisms. Viral, bacterial, fungal and parasitic infections ranging from malaria, hepatitis C, meningitis, tetanus, and many nosocomial infections, etc have been treated successfully with scorpion venom. Scorpion venom is also used for treatment of non-communicable and neurological disease such as stroke, rheumatism,

diabetes, cancer, brain tumor, human neuroblastoma cells etc (Attarde and Pandit, 2016; El-Bitar et al., 2015; Petricerich et al., 2013). The emperor scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) and several additional venom peptides had been characterized as antibacterial peptides with a broad-spectrum of bacterial targets against even the antibiotic-resistant strains (Baradaran et al., 20112).

The purpose of this study was to determine the possibility of using The Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) venom as an alternative to conventional antibacterial agent against some bacterial isolates.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study Area

Gwagwalada is one of the six area councils of the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria. Gwagwalada is also the name of the main town in the Local Government Area, which has an area of 1,043 km² and a population of 157,770 as of the 2006 census. It is located at an elevation of 210 meters above sea level. Its coordinates are 8°56'29" N and 7°05'31" E in DMS (Degree Minutes Seconds) or 8.94139 and 7.09194 in decimal degrees. Its Universal Transverse Mercator position is KQ98 and its Joint Operation Graphics reference is NC32-13 (Wikipedia, 2016).

2.2 Media and Preparation

All media used were prepared according to the manufacturer's standard preparation procedures.

2.3 Sample Collection

In the Zoology Department of the Faculty of Science at the University of Abuja, fifty Emperor Scorpions (*Pandinus imperator*) were selected for venom collection. The venoms were harvested using the electrical stimulation technique outlined by Ozkan and Filazi in 2004. A series of regular currents were applied to shock the scorpions until the venom was ejected. For this purpose, the scorpions were immersed in a saline solution for better electrical conduction and shocked with electrodes using a simple 12-volt battery. The venom droplets were collected in sterile test tubes, with part of the venom stored in ice and used within 30 minutes, while the rest was frozen until further use. The venom was recovered using distilled water and centrifuged at 10,000 g. The supernatant was freeze-dried and stored at -20°C until use. All venom collected was

passed through a membrane filter.

2.4 Collection of Test Organisms

Drinking water samples, each totaling 20 ml, were collected from various sources of drinking water supply across the University of Abuja, including the main site, mini campus, and staff quarters. These samples were transported to the Microbiology Laboratory at the University of Abuja for culturing, isolation, and identification of specific test bacteria.

2.5 Preparation of Samples

2.5.1 Preparation of The Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) Venom

The venom of *Pandinus imperator* was collected and measured in percentage since the venom is in liquid state. Raw venom represents 100%, while 50%, 25%, and 12.5% were diluted with 50%, 75%, and 87.5% of appropriate neutral diluents (sterile water) respectively, and also at concentrations of 10, 20, 30, and 40 mg/ml.

2.5.2 Preparation of Test Organisms

The samples collected were taken to the laboratory in a sterile plastic container. Using the serial dilution method, bacteria from the drinking water samples were cultured on an enrichment medium, incubated, and plated on MacConkey agar at 37°C for 24 hours. Suspected colonies were further sub-cultured on selective media (CHROM agar, Eosin methylene blue (EMB), and Cetrimide agar). Colonies were identified based on their color: red, metallic green sheen, and blue-green/yellow-green. A single colony was picked, screened, and identified based on the Analytical Profile Index (API). The organism was sub-cultured on selective media and confirmed using standard biochemical techniques (Cheesbrough, 1998).

2.6 Antibacterial Activity of The Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) Venom (Peptides)

Antimicrobial sensitivity tests of the isolates were performed using the standard agar well diffusion method described by Bauer et al. (1996). The venom was tested at different concentrations (12.5%, 25%, 50%, and 100%) and (10, 20, 30, and 40 mg/ml) to determine antibacterial activity by measuring the zones of inhibition.

2.7 Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined by preparing various concentrations (12.5%, 25%, 50%, and 100%) and (10, 20, 30, and 40 mg/ml) of the venom using the dilution method. Test tubes were set up with 2 ml of nutrient broth, with control tubes including venom control, organism control, and negative control. A 0.2 ml suspension of the test organisms was added to the test tubes. The preparation was incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, after which turbidity or clearness was observed. The least concentration with no turbidity was noted as the MIC value.

2.8 Determination of Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) was determined from the broth dilution resulting from MIC tubes by sub-culturing to the surface of freshly prepared nutrient agar plates using a sterile inoculating loop as described by Vollekova et al. (2001) and Usman et al. (2007). Test tubes showing no microbial growth after 24 hours of incubation were sub-cultured on nutrient agar plates. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and observed for growth. The plates with the lowest concentration of the venom showing no bacterial growth were noted as the MBC.

2.9 Comparing the Effects of Emperor Scorpion Venom with Commercial Antibiotics

The results were compared with standard antibiotics. Inhibition effects were measured in terms of the zone of inhibition.

2.10 Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data, including simple percentages and standard deviation of the mean. Microsoft Excel was used for statistical significance, and ANOVA was performed to determine if there were any statistically significant differences between the venoms and isolates. Differences in survival were considered significant when $P \leq 0.05$.

3 Results

3.1 Physical Characteristics of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

The result of the physico-chemical characteristics of *Pandinus Imperator* venom is shown in Table 1. The venom was observed to be colorless, odorless, and a transparent liquid which dries easily at room temperature.

Table 1: Physical characteristics of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

Colour	Odour	Form	pH	Room Temperature (28°C)
Colourless	Odourless	Transparent Liquid	4.5	Dried up easily

3.2 Analytical Profile Index (API-20E)

The result of the Analytical Profile Index of the bacterial identification of isolates shows the different bacteria isolated from the three water sources studied were *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *A. baumannii* (Table ??).

The result for the mean \pm SD inhibition zone of diameter of *Pandinus Imperator* venom against organisms isolated from University of Abuja drinking water at different concentrations of 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% respectively is shown in Table 2. To interpret the results of the zones of inhibition, the antibacterial and inhibitory effect of the venom was considered at the concentration of 30 mg/ml as compared to that of chloramphenicol (30 μ g), a standard antibiotic. When interpreted using the CLSI, 2004 guide, a zone of chloramphenicol (30 μ g) 18 is sensitive, 12 is resistant, while 13-17 is intermediate.

The mean \pm SD of inhibition zone of ciprofloxacin against isolated organisms at different concentrations

Table 2: Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom against organisms isolated from University of Abuja Drinking Water

Microorganisms	Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm)			
	25	50	75	100
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6.1 \pm 0.0	7.2 \pm 0.0	9.0 \pm 0.0	10.0 \pm 0.0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	5.7 \pm 0.0	7.0 \pm 0.0	9.0 \pm 0.0	11.5 \pm 0.0
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	3.0 \pm 0.0	4.7 \pm 0.0	6.0 \pm 0.0	8.2 \pm 0.0

of 62.5 mg/ml, 125 mg/ml, 250 mg/ml, and 500 mg/ml is shown in Table 3.

3.3 Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *Pandinus Imperator* venom on isolated test organisms is shown in Table 4. This is the lowest concentration of the venom required to inhibit the growth of the organisms.

3.4 Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of *Pandinus Imperator* venom on isolated test organisms is shown in Table 5. This is the lowest concentration of the venom required to kill the organisms.

The MBC obtained in the study was 75%, indicating that the venom was effective against the isolated test organisms.

4 Discussion

This research was carried out to determine the antibacterial activities of *Pandinus imperator* venom against some selected bacteria.

Table 1 shows the physiochemical characteristics of the venom. According to this table, the venom is odorless, colorless, and a transparent liquid with a pH of 4.5 that dries up easily at room temperature.

Table ?? presents the Analytical Profile Index (API) results for selected bacteria obtained from water samples at the University of Abuja.

Table 2 displays the zone diameter of inhibition for different concentrations of *Pandinus imperator* venom against isolated organisms. The lowest zone of inhibition is 3 mm at 25% against *Acinetobacter baumannii*, while the highest is 11.5 mm at 100% against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Table 3: Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm) of Ciprofloxacin against isolated organisms

Microorganisms	Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm)			
	62.5	125	250	500
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	26	31	36	38
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	26	27	34	35
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	23	25	28	31

Table 4: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom on isolated test organisms

Microorganisms	MIC (mm)			
	25	50	75	100
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	+	+	-MBC	-

Key: + = Clear (No growth), - = Turbid (Growth)

Table 5: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom on isolated test organisms

Microorganisms	MBC (mm)			
	25	50	75	100
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	+	+	-MBC	-

Key: + = Bacterial growth, - = No bacterial growth

Table 3 shows the zone diameter of inhibition for different concentrations of commercial antibiotics against isolated organisms. The lowest zone of inhibition is 23 mm at 62.5 mg/ml against *Acinetobacter baumannii*, while the highest is 38 mm at 500 mg/ml against *Escherichia coli*.

Table 4 provides the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of Pandinus imperator venom against isolated test organisms at different concentrations. The MIC for *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 25%, while for *Acinetobacter baumannii* it is 50%.

Table 5 shows the minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of Pandinus imperator venom against isolated test organisms at different concentrations. The MBC for *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 50%, while for *Acinetobacter baumannii* it is 75%.

All the antibacterial activities, MIC, and MBC support the findings of Ahmed et al. (2012), Baradaran et al. (2012), Cao et al. (2012), Nie et al. (2012), Zhao et al. (2009), Carballar-Lejarazú et al. (2008), Gawade (2007), Lee et al. (2004), Reddy et al. (2004), and Reddy et al. (2003), among others.

The action of antimicrobial peptides toward bacterial membranes is initiated by electrostatic interactions with negatively charged components of membranes, such as strong interactions with lipopolysaccharides in the outer membrane of gram-negative bacteria and acidic phospholipids in the outer cell wall of gram-positive bacteria. After the initial attachment, antimicrobial peptides aggregate within membranes, leading to membrane destruction achieved through channel (pore) formation (Guo et al., 2013).

5 Conclusion

From this research work, it can be concluded or deduced that Venom of Pandinus imperator called Emperor Scorpion found in West Africa is an antibacterial agent that is non-toxic to animals, the scorpion venom has the same potency and can both be safely used as a therapeutic agent. **Conflict of interest**

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest. The study was conducted impartially and without bias.

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to the Almighty God, to whom all praise and worship belong. My sincere appreciation goes to my Parent, Late Pastor Oladapo Peter Dahunsi and Dr Mrs Taiwo Olayinka Dahunsi. Special appreciation also to my wife Aisha Ejura Dahunsi for her encouragement.

7 References

- Abdel-Mottaleb, Y., Corzo, G. and Martin-Eauclaire, M. (2008). A common "hot spot" confers hERG blockade activity to scorpion toxins affecting K⁺ channels. *Biochemical Pharmacology*, 76 (6): 805–815.
- Adriaan, H.B., David, G.B., Alan, H.J., Ryan, M. and Peter, F.M. (2009). "Scorpion sting". [https://books.google.com/books?id=Q-
kkTX9Ji0Cpg=PA518ConflictandCatastropheMedicine](https://books.google.com/books?id=Q-
kkTX9Ji0Cpg=PA518ConflictandCatastropheMedicine) :
- Adesina, I. A., Adebote, V.T., Elehinafe, T. R. and Enerijiofi, K. E. (2013). Growth inhibition of *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium italicum* by seed kernel oil from Mango (*Magnifera indica L.*). *Journal of Natural Sciences Research*, 3(9): 61-64.
- Ahmed, U., Mujaddad-ur-Rehman, M., Khalid, N., Fawad, S.A. and Fatima, A. (2012). Antibacterial activity of the venom of *Heterometrus xanthurus*. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*, 44 (4): 509–511.
- Allen, S.W. (1996). "Between the sign of the scorpion and the sign of the cross: L'Age D'or". In Rudolf E. Kuenzli. <https://books.google.com/books?id=ZD16HsqFJwACpg=PA1> and Surrealist Film. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MITpress>
- Arcangeli, A., Pillozzi, S. and Becchetti, A. (2012). Targeting ion channels in leukemias: a new challenge for treatment. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 19 (5): 683–696.
- Attarde, S.S. and Pandit, S.V. (2016). Scorpion Venom as Therapeutic Agents. Current Perspective. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research*, 7 (2): 59-72.
- Bailey, P. and Wilce, J. (2001). Venom as a source of useful biologically active molecules. *Emergency Medicine*, 13 (1): 28–36.
- Balunas, M.J., and Kinghorn, A.D. (2005). Drug discovery from medicinal plants. *Life Sciences*, 78 (5): 431–441.
- Banerjee, A., Datta, P.K., Basu, P.S. and Datta, T.K. (1991). Characterization of a naturally

occurring protease inhibitor in the hemolymph of the scorpion, *Heterometrus bengalensis*. *Developmental and Comparative Immunology*, 15 (4): 213–218.

Baradaran, M., Jalali, A. and Jolodar, A.A. (2012). *Cysteine free antimicrobial peptide derived from Mesobuthus eupeus scorpion venom gland*. Proceedings of the 13th Iranian and the Second International Congress of Microbiology, Congress Portal for Ardabil University of Medical Sciences. Pp. 606–607.

Baradaran, M., Jalali, A., Jolodar, A. and Ghasemian, S. (2012). A new Caerin like antibacterial peptides from the venom gland of the Iranian Scorpion *Mesobuthus eupeus*: cDNA amplification and sequence analysis. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 11: (44) 10176-10181.

Baradaran, M., Jolodar, A., Jalali, A., Navidpour, S. and Kafilzadeh, F. (2011). Sequence analysis of lysozyme C from the scorpion *Mesobuthus eupeus* venom glands using semi-nested RT-PCR. *Iranian Red Crescent medical journal*, 13 (10): 719–725.

Barrett, N.E., Holbrook, L. and Jones, S. (2008). Future innovations in anti-platelet therapies. *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 154 (5): 918–939.

Bauer, H.H., Marsh, E.N., Buer, B.C. and Ramamoorthy, A. (1996). Techniques in Microbiology Research. *Practicals in Microbiology Journal*, 5(10): 1143-1147.

Baumann, P. (1998). Isolation of *Acinetobacter* from soil and water. *Journal of Bacteriology*, 96: 39-42.

Beeton, C., Pennington, M.W. and Wulff, H. (2005). Targeting effector memory T cells with a selective peptide inhibitor of Kv1.3 channels for therapy of autoimmune diseases. *Molecular Pharmacology*, 67 (4): 1369–1381

Benton, T.G. (2011). http://www.americanarachnology.org/JoA_free/JoA_v19_n2%20Benton,%20T.G.%20-%20The%20ecology%20of%20the%20scorpion%20Euscorp%20flavicaudis%20in%20England 105–110.

Benton, T.G. (2012). "The ecology of the scorpion *Euscorpis flavicaudis* in England". *Journal of Zoology*, 226 (3): 351–368.

Berlau, J., Aucken, H.M., Houang, E. and Pitt, T.L. (1999). Isolation of *Acinetobacter* spp. Including *A. baumannii* from vegetables: Implications for hospital-acquired infections. *Journal of Hospital Infections*, 42: 201-204.

Bernhard, A.H., Bradley, J., Sinclair, A., and Lampe, K.H. (2005).

<https://books.google.com/?id=6YrOJsUaYCAfrican> *biodi*

Bertazzi, D.T., De Assis-Pandochi, A.I., Talhaferro, V.L., Seixas-Azzolini, A.E.C., Pereira-Crott, L.S. and Arantes, E.C. (2005). Activation of the complement system and leukocyte recruitment by *Tityus serrulatus* scorpion venom. *International Immunopharmacology*, 5 (6): 1077–1084.

Bhoite, R.R., Bhoite, G.R., Bagdure, D.N. and Bawaskar, H.S. (2015). "Anaphylaxis to scorpion antivenin and its management following envenomation by Indian red scorpion, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4578200Me> *tamulus*<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4578200Me> *Journal of Critical Care Medicine*. 19 (9): 547–549.

Bin, G., Jia, X., Maria del, C.R., Humberto, L., Rosaura, H., Weihong, D. and Shunyi, Z. (2010). "Characterization of two linear cationic antimalarial peptides in the scorpion *Mesobuthus eupeus*". *Biochemistry*, 92 (4): 350–359.

Bin, G., Patrick, S., Lan, L., John, B. and Shunyi, Z. (2009). "Structural and functional characterization of two genetically related meucin peptides highlights evolutionary divergence and convergence in antimicrobial peptides". *FASEB Journal*, 23 (4): 1230–1245.

Boisseau, S., Mabrouk, K. and Ram, N. (2006) Cell penetration properties of maurocalcine, a natural venom peptide active on the intracellular ryanodine receptor. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta*, 1758(3):308–319.

Boland, M.P. and Separovic, F. (2006). Membrane interactions of antimicrobial peptides from Australian tree frogs. *Biochemistry and Biophysics Acta*, 1758(9): 1178-1183.

Bonnet, M.S. (1997). Toxicology of *Androctonus* scorpion. *British Homoeopathic Journal*, 86 (3): 142–151.

Borges, C.M.S., Silva, M.R., Baker, W.A.C.L., Freire, Maia, L. and Teixeira, M.M. (2000). Scorpion venom-induced neutrophilia is inhibited by a PAF receptor antagonist in the rat. *Journal of Leukocyte Biology*, 67 (4): 515–519.

Bosmans, F. and Tytgat, J. (2007). Voltage-gated sodium channel modulation by scorpion -toxins. *Toxicon*, 49 (2): 142–158.

Brahmi, Z. and Cooper, E.L. (1980). Activation of mammalian lymphocytes by a partially purified fraction of scorpion hemolymph. *Developmental and Comparative Immunology*, 4 (3): 433–445.

Brian, C.S.C., Carver, J.A., Lindner, R.A., Bowie, J.H., Wong, H. and Lie, W. (2000). Caerin 4.1, an Antibiotic Peptide from the Australian Tree Frog, *Litoria caerulea*. The NMR-Derived Solution Structure. *Australian Journal of Chemistry*, 53(4): 257-265.

Brinkmann, U. and Pastan, I. (1995). Recombinant immunotoxins: from basic research to cancer therapy. *Methods*, 8 (2): 143–156.

Bulet, P., Stöcklin, R. and Menin, L. (2004). Antimicrobial peptides: from invertebrates to vertebrates. *Immunology Reviewed*, 198 (1): 169-184.

Cao, L., Dai, C. and Li, Z. (2012). Antibacterial activity and mechanism of a scorpion venom peptide derivative in vitro and in vivo. *PloS One*, 7(7)e40135.

Carballar-Lejarazú, R., Rodríguez, M.H., and De La Cruz Hernández-Hernández, F. (2008) Recombinant scorpine: a multifunctional antimicrobial peptide with activity against different pathogens. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*, 65 (19): 3081–3092.

Carrier, E., Geib, S., De Waard, M., Avdonin, V., Hoshi, T., Fajloun, Z., Rochat, H., Sabatier, J.M. and Kharrat, R. (2000). "Effect of neurotoxin, a four disulfide-bridged toxin from the chancroid scorpion *Scorpio maurus*, on Shaker K⁺ channels". *The Journal of Peptide Research*, 55 (6): 419–427.

Cateau, E., Verdon, J., Fernandez, B., Hechard, Y. and Rodier, M.H. (2011). *Acanthamoeba* sp. promotes the survival and growth of *Acinetobacter baumannii*. *FEMS Microbiology Lett*, 319: 19-25.

Catterall, W.A., Cestèle, S., Yarov-Yarovoy, V., Yu, F.H., Konoki, K. and Scheuer T. (2007). Voltage-gated ion channels and gating modifier toxins. *Toxicon*, 49 (2): 124–141.

Chandy, K.G, Wulff, H., Beeton, C., Pennington, M., Gutman, G.A. and Cahalan, M.D. (2004). K⁺ channels as targets for specific immunomodulation. *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences*, 25 (5): 280–289.

Chao, D., Yibao, M., Zhenhuan, Z., Ruiming, Z., Qian, W., Yingliang, W., Zhijian, C. and Wenxin, L. (2008). Mucroporin, the first cationic host Defense peptide from the venom of *Lychas mucronatus*. *Antimicrobial Agents of chemotherapy*, 52(11): 3967-3972.

Chen, B. and Ji, Y. (2002). Antihyperalgesia effect of BmK AS, a scorpion toxin, in rat by intraplantar injection. *Brain Research*, 952 (2): 322–326.

Chen, J., Feng, X. and Shi, J. (2006). The anti-nociceptive effect of BmK AS, a scorpion

active polypeptide, and the possible mechanism on specifically modulating voltage-gated Na⁺ currents in primary afferent neurons. *Peptides*, 27 (9): 2182–2192.

Chen, Y., Cao, L. and Zhong, M. (2012). Anti-HIV-1 activity of a new scorpion venom peptide derivative Kn2-7. *PLoS One*, 7 (4) 34-47.

Chessbrough, M. (1998). *Medical laboratory manual for Tropical Countries*. Microbiology II: 196-205.

Chia, C.S., Gong, Y., Bowie, J.H., Zuegg, J. and Cooper, M.A. (2011). Membrane binding and perturbation studies of the antimicrobial peptides caerin, citropin, and maculatin. *Biopolymers*, 96(2): 147-157.

Chippaux, J.P. and Goyffon, M. (2008). Epidemiology of scorpionism: a global appraisal. *Acta Tropica*, 107 (2): 71–79.

Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. (2014). *Performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing: Nineteenth informational supplement*.

Cohen, L., Lipstein, N. and Gordon, D. (2006). Allosteric interactions between scorpion toxin receptor sites on voltage-gated Na channels imply a novel role for weakly active components in arthropod venom. *FASEB Journal*, 20 (11): E1360–E1367.

Conde, R., Zamudio, F.Z., Rodríguez, M.H. and Possani, L.D. (2000). Scorpine, an anti-malaria and anti-bacterial agent purified from scorpion venom. *FEBS Letters*, 471 (2-3): 165–168.

Cosgrove, A., Weil, G., Simon, R., and Sweadner, W.R. (2003). A biological, bacteriological and clinical study of larval or maggot therapy in the treatment of acute and chronic pyogenic infections. *American Journal of Surgery*, 19: 36-48.

D'Suze, G., Moncada, S., González, C., Sevcik, C., Aguilar, V. and Alagón, A. (2003). Relationship between plasmatic levels of various cytokines, tumor necrosis factor, enzymes, glucose, and venom concentration following *Tityus* scorpion sting. *Toxicon*, 41 (3): 367–375.

Dai, C., Ma, Y. and Zhao, Z. (2008). Mucroporin, the first cationic host defense peptide from the venom of *Lychas mucronatus*. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 52 (11): 3967–3972.

Dai, L., Corzo, G., Naoki, H., Andriantsiferana, M. and Nakajimaa, T. (2002). Purification, structure-function analysis, and molecular characterization of

novel linear peptides from scorpion *Opisthacanthus madagascariensis*. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 293 (5): 1514–1522.

Dai, L., Yasuda, A., Naoki, H., Corzo, G., Andriantsiferana, M. and Nakajima, T. (2001). IsCT, a novel cytotoxic linear peptide from scorpion *Opisthacanthus madagascariensis*. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 286 (4): 820–825.

Dalton, S., Gerzanich, V., Chen, M., Dong, Y., Shuba, Y. and Simard, J.M. (2003). Chlorotoxin-sensitive Ca²⁺-activated Cl⁻ channel in type R2 reactive astrocytes from adult rat brain. *GLIA*, 42(4): 325–339.

DeBin, J.A., and Strichartz, G.R. (1991). "Chloride channel inhibition by the venom of the scorpion *Leiurus quinquestriatus*". <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Toxicon>, 29 (11): 1403–1408.

DeBin, J.A., Maggio, J.E. and Strichartz, G.R. (1993). Purification and characterization of chlorotoxin, a chloride channel ligand from the venom of the scorpion. *American Journal of Physiology*, 264 (2): C361–C369.

Deepti, P.K., Hsin-Bai, Y., Anup, K.J. and Kumar, V. (2004). Effect of Chlorine Exposure on the Survival and Antibiotic Gene Expression of Multidrug-Resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* in water. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 11: 1844-1854.

Deshane, J. Craig, C.G. and Harald, S. (2003). "Chlorotoxin inhibits glioma cell invasion via matrix metalloproteinase-2". https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Journal_of_Biological_Chemistry, 278 (6): 4135–4144.

Deshane, J., Garner, C.C., and Sontheimer, H. (2003). Chlorotoxin inhibits glioma cell invasion via matrix metalloproteinase-2. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 278 (6): 4135–4144.

Dhople, V., Krukemeyer, A. and Ramamoorthy, A. (2006). The human beta Defensin 3, an antibacterial peptide with multiple biological functions. *Biochemistry and Biophysics Acta*, 1758(9): 1499-1512.

Dib-Hajj, S.D., Binshtok, A.M., Cummins, T.R., Jarvis, M.F., Samad, T. and Zimmermann, K. (2009). Voltage-gated sodium channels in pain states a role in pathophysiology and targets for treatment. *Brain Research Reviews*, 60 (1): 65–83.

Diego-García, E., Abdel-Mottaleb, Y., Schwartz, E.F., De La Vega, R.C.R., Tytgat, J. and Possani, L.D. (2008). Cytolytic and K⁺ channel blocking activities of -KTx and scorpion-like peptides purified from scorpion venoms. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*, 65 (1): 187–200.

Diego-Garcia, E., Batista, C.V., Garcia-Gomez, B.I., Lucas, S., Candido, D.M., Gomez-Lagunas, F. and Possani, L.D. (2005). The Brazilian scorpion *Tityus Costatus Karsch*: genes, peptides, and function. *Toxicology*, 45(3): 273-283.

Diss, J.K.J., Stewart, D. and Pani, F. (2005). A potential novel marker for human prostate cancer: voltage-gated sodium channel expression in vivo. *Prostate Cancer and Prostatic Diseases*, 8 (3): 266–273.

Douglas, D., Gaffin, L., Bumm, A., Matthew, S., Taylor, N., Popokina, V. and Shivani, M. (2012). "Scorpion fluorescence and reaction to light". *Animal Behaviour (journal)* [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Animal_Behaviour_\(journal\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Animal_Behaviour_(journal)) 429–436.

Dupré, G. (2007). Conspectus genericus scorpionorum 1758–2006 (Arachnida: Scorpiones). *Euscorpius*, 50:1–31.

Ehret-Sabatier, L., Loew, D. and Goyffon, M. (1996). Characterization of novel cysteine-rich antimicrobial peptides from scorpion blood. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 271 (47): 29537–29544,

El-Bitar, M.H.A., Sarfan, M.H.M., Aoki, C., Takahara, Y., Komoto, M., Deng, L., Moustafa, A.M. and Hotta, H. (2015). Virucidal activity of Egyptian Scorpion Venom against hepatitis C. *Virology Journal*, 12: 47.

Elgar, D., Du Plessis, J., and Du Plessis, J. (2006). Cysteine-rich peptides in scorpion venom: geographical distribution, structure-function relationship, and mode of action. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 5 (25): 2495–2502.

Enerijiofi, K. E. and Isola, O. B. (2019).

Preliminary Phytochemical screening and *in vitro* antibacterial activities of aqueous and ethanol extracts of *Ageratum conyzoides* L. Leaf, Stem, Flower and Root on some Bacterial isolates associated with Diarrhoea. *Nigerian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 32 (2): 3480 -3489 <http://dx.doi.org/10.19240/njpas.2019.B09><http://dx.doi.org>

Fan Z, Cao, L., and He, Y. (2011). Ctriporin, a new anti-methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* peptide from the venom of the scorpion *Chaerilus tricostatus*. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*,

55 (11): 5220–5229.

Feng, L., Gao, R and Gopalakrishnakone, P. (2008). Isolation and characterization of a hyaluronidase from the venom of Chinese red scorpion *Buthus martensi*. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology C*, 148 (3): 250–257.

Fernandes, V.M.V., Massensini, A.R., Prado, M.A.M., Romano-Silva, M.A., Moraes-Santos, T. and Gomez, M.V. (2004). Effects of -scorpion toxin, tityustoxin on the release of [3H] dopamine of rat brain prefrontal cortical slices. *Neurochemistry International*, 44 (2): 91–97.

Ferreira, A.E., Marchetti, D.P., de Oliveira, L.M., Gusatti, C.S., Fuentefria, D.B. and Corcao, G. (2011). Presence of OXA-23-producing isolates of *Acinetobacter baumannii* in wastewater from hospitals in southern Brazil. *Microbiology Drug Resistance*, 17: 221–227.

Fet, V. and Soleglad, E (2005). http://www.science.marshall.edu/fet/euscorp/2005_1.pdf

Fine, B.P., Hansen, K.A., Salcedo, J.R. and Aviv, A. (1989). Calcium-activated potassium channels in human platelets. *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*, 192 (2): 109–113.

Fitzgerald, D. (1996). Why toxins! *Seminars in Cancer Biology*, 7 (2): 87–95.

Fournier, P.E., and Richet, H. (2006). The epidemiology and control of *Acinetobacter baumannii* in health care facilities. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 42: 692–699.

Froy, O., Sagiv, T., Poreh, M., Urbach, D., Zilberberg, N. and Gurevitz, M. (1999) Dynamic diversification from a putative common ancestor of scorpion toxins affecting sodium, potassium, and chloride channels. *Journal of molecular evolution*, 48 (2): 187–196.

Fu, Y., Yin, L. and Liang, A. (2007). Therapeutic potential of chlorotoxin-like neurotoxin from the Chinese scorpion for human gliomas. *Neuroscience Letter*, 412 (1): 62–67.

Fu, Y., Zheng, S. and Huang, R. (2012). A potential strategy for high-grade gliomas: combination treatment with lithium chloride and BmK CT. *Biotechnology Letters*, 34 (1): 9–17.

Fukuhara, Y.D.M., Reis, M.L., Dellalibera-Joviliano, R., Cunha, F.Q.C. and Donadi, E.A. (2003). Increased plasma levels of IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10 and TNF- in patients moderately or severely envenomed by *Tityus serrulatus* scorpion sting. *Toxicon*, 41 (1): 49–55.

Fuller, M.D., Zhang, Z., Cui, G., Kubanek, J. and McCarty, N.A. (2004). Inhibition of CFTR channels by a peptide toxin of scorpion venom. *American Journal of Physiology*, 287 (5): C1328–C1341.

Gao, B., Sherman, P., Luo, L., Bowie, J. and Zhu, S. (2009). The structural and functional characterization of two genetically related meucin peptides highlights evolutionary divergence and convergence in antimicrobial peptides. *FASEB Journal*, 23 (4): 1230–1245.

Gao, B., Tian, C. and Zhu, S. (2007). Inducible antibacterial response of scorpion venom gland. *Peptides*, 28 (12): 2299–2305.

Gao, B., Xu, J. and del Carmen Rodriguez, M. (2010). Characterization of two linear cationic antimalarial peptides in the scorpion *Mesobuthus eupeus*. *Biochimie*, 92(4): 350–359.

Gawade, S.P. (2007). Therapeutic alternatives from venoms and toxins. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*, 39 (6): 260–264.

George, K.C., Heike, W., Christine, B., Michael, P.G., Gutman, A. and Michael, D.C. (2004). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2749963> as targets for specific immunomodulation". https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trends_in_pharmacological_sci 280–289.

Gerhard, S. and Carsten, K. (2006). "The book lungs of Scorpiones and Tetrapulmonata (Chelicerata, Arachnida): evidence for homology and a single terrestrialisation event of a common arachnid ancestor". *Zoology*, 109 (1): 2–13.

Gess, R.W. (2013). "The earliest record of terrestrial animals in Gondwana: a scorpion from the Famennian (Late Devonian) Witpoort Formation of South Africa". https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/African_invertebrates 373–379.

Gomes, A., Haldar, S., and Giri, B. (2009). Experimental osteoporosis induced in female albino rats and its antagonism by Indian black scorpion (*Heterometrus bengalensis* C.L.Koch) venom. *Toxicon*, 53(1): 60–68.

Goyffon, M. and Chippaux, J.P. (1990). *Encyclopédie Médico-Chirurgicales*. 6th edition. Paris, France: Editions Techniques. Animaux venimeux terrestres. Pp. 1–15.

Goyffon, M. and El Ayeb, M. (2002). Epidemiologie du scorpionisme. *Infotox*, 15: 2–6.

Griespy, J. (2001). The use of Shiga-like

toxin 1 in cancer therapy. *Critical Reviews in Oncology/Hematology*, 39 (1): 99–106.

Guillaume, C., Deregnacourt, C., Clavey, V. and Schrével, J. (2004). Anti-Plasmodium properties of group IA, IB, IIA and III secreted phospholipases A2 are serum-dependent. *Toxicon*, 43 (3): 311–318.

Gupta, S.D., Debnath, A. and Saha, A. (2007). Indian black scorpion (*Heterometrus bengalensis* Koch) venom induced antiproliferative and apoptogenic activity against human leukemic cell lines U937 and K562. *Leukemia Research*, 31 (6): 817–825.

Gwee, M.C.E., Nirthanan, S., Khoo, H., Gopalakrishnakone, P., Kini, R.M. and Cheah, L. (2002). Autonomic effects of some scorpion venoms and toxins. *Clinical and Experimental Pharmacology and Physiology*, 29 (9): 795–801.

Harris, F., Dennison, S.R., and Phoenix, D.A. (2009). Anionic Antimicrobial Peptides from Eukaryotic Organisms. *Current studies of Protein Peptide Science*, 10: 585-606.

He, Q.Y., He, Q.Z., Deng, X.C., Yao, L., Meng, E., Liu, Z.H. and Liang, S.P. (2008). ATDB: a uni-database platform for animal toxins. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 36: 293-297.

Hetru, C., Letellier, L., Oren, Z., Hoffmann, J.A. and Shai, Y. (2000). Androctonin, a hydrophilic disulfide-bridged non-hemolytic anti-microbial peptide: a plausible mode of action. *Biochemical Journal*, 345 (3): 653–664

Hodgson, W.C., and Isbister, G.K. (2009). The application of toxins and venoms to cardiovascular drug discovery. *Current Opinion in Pharmacology*, 9. (2): 173–176.

Hoshino, K., Moura, A.T.V. and De Paula, H.M.G. (2006). "Selection of environmental temperature by the yellow scorpion *Tityus serrulatus* Lutz & Mello, 1922 (Scorpiones, Buthidae)". *Journal of Venomous Animals and Toxins Including Tropical Diseases*, 12 (1): 59–66.

Incomnoi, P., Patramanon, R. and Thammasirirak, S. (2013). Heteromtoxin (HmTx), a novel heterodimeric phospholipase A2 from *Heterometrus laoticus* scorpion venom. *Toxicon*, 61: 62–71.

Ismail, M., Abd-Elsalam, M.A. and Morad, A.M. (1990). Do changes in body temperature following envenomation by the scorpion *Leiurus quinquestriatus* influence the course of toxicity? *Toxicon*, 28 (11): 1265–1284.

Jason, A., Dunlop, D.P., Erik,

T.O. and Lyall, I.A. (2008). http://www.americanarachnology.org/JoA_free/JoA_v36_n2/article_36-2-267.pdf "How many species of fossil arachnids are there 262–272.

Jason, A., Dunlop, O.E. and Lorenzo, P. (2008). "Reinterpretation of the Silurian scorpion *Proscorpius osborni* (Whitfield): integrating data from Palaeozoic and recent scorpions". *Paleontology*, 51 (2): 303–320.

Ji, Y.H., Huang, H.Y. and Zhou, C. (1997). BmK AS, an active scorpion polypeptide, enhances [3H] noradrenaline release from rat hippocampal slices. *Biomedical Research*, 18 (3): 257–260.

Joseph, B. and George, J. (2012) Scorpion toxins and its applications. *International Journal of Toxicological and Pharmacological Research*, 4:57–61.

Judge, S.I.V. and Bever, C.T. (2006). Potassium channel blockers in multiple sclerosis: neuronal Kv channels and effects of symptomatic treatment. *Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 111 (1): 224–259.

Junpeng, L., Shuping, H., Wei, J., Chenglian, X. and Xingyong, Y. (2021). Plant antimicrobial peptides: structures, functions, and applications. *Springer Open Journal*, 62: 5.

Kempf, M. and Rolain, J.M. (2012). Emergence of resistance to carbapenems in *Acinetobacter baumannii* in Europe: Clinical impact and therapeutic options. *International Journal Antimicrobial Agents*, 39: 105-114.

Kievit, F.M., Veiseh, O. and Fang, C. (2010). Chlorotoxin labeled magnetic nanovectors for targeted gene delivery to glioma. *ACS Nano*, 4 (8): 4587–4594.

Kim, K., Cho, H. and Lee, S. (2005). Inhibitory effect of *Buthus martensi* Karsch extracts on interleukin-1-induced expression of nitric oxide (NO) synthase and production of NO in human chondrocytes and LPS-induced NO and prostaglandin E2 production in mouse peritoneal macrophages. *Toxicology In Vitro*, 19 (6): 757–769.

Kühl, G., Bergmann, A., Dunlop, J.R., Garwood, J. and Rust, J. (2012). "Redescription and palaeobiology of *Palaeoscorpius devonicus* Lehmann, 1944 from the Lower Devonian Hunsrück Slate of Germany". *Paleontology*, 55 (4): 775–787.

Kuhn-Nentwig, L. (2003). Antimicrobial and cytolytic peptides of venomous arthropods CMLS. *Cellular Molecular of Life Science*, 60: 2651-2668.

Laniado, M.E., Fraser, S.P. and Djamgoz, M.B. (2001). Voltage-gated K⁺ channel activity in human

prostate cancer cell lines of markedly different metastatic potential: distinguishing characteristics of PC-3 and LNCaP cells. *Prostate*, 46 (4): 262–274.

Lee, K., Shin, S.Y., Kim, K., Lim, S.S., Hahm, K. and Kim, Y. (2004). Antibiotic activity and structural analysis of the scorpion-derived antimicrobial peptide IsCT and its analogs. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 323 (2): 712–719.

Lewis, R.J. and Garcia, M.L. (2003). Therapeutic potential of venom peptides. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 2 (10): 790–802.

Li, Q., Zhao, Z. and Zhou, D. (2011). Virucidal activity of a scorpion venom peptide variant mucroporin- M1 against measles, SARS-CoV and influenza H5N1 viruses. *Peptides*, 32 (7): 1518–1525

Liu, Y.F., Ma, R.L. and Wang, S.L. (2003). Expression of antitumor- analgesic peptide from the Chinese scorpion *Buthus martensi kirsch* in *Escherichia coli*. *Protein Expression and Purification*, 27: 253– 258

Lokeshwar, V.B. and Selzer, M.G. (2008). Hyaluronidase: both a tumor promoter and suppressor. *Seminars in Cancer Biology*, 18 (4): 281– 287.

Lourenco, W.R. (2000). "Reproduction in scorpions, with special reference to parthenogenesis". In S. Toft; N. Scharff. <http://www.european-arachnology.org/proceedings/19th/Lourenco.PDF> European Arachnology. Aarhus University Press. Pp. 71–85.

Lukács, B., Sztretye, M. and Almássy, J. (2008). The charged surface area of maurocalcine determines its interaction with the skeletal ryanodine receptor. *Biophysical Journal*, 95 (7): 3497–3509.

Luna-Ramirez, K., Quintero-Hernandez, V., Vargas-Jaimes, L., Batista, C.V.F., Winkel, K. and Possani, L.D. (2013). Characterization of the venom from the Australian scorpion *Urodacus yaschenkoi*: molecular mass analysis of components, cDNA sequences and peptides with antimicrobial activity. *Toxicon*, 363: 44–54.

Luo, F., Zeng, X.C., Hahin, R., Cao, Z.J., Liu, H. and Li, W.X. (2005). Genomic organization of four novel non-disulfide-bridged peptides from scorpion *Mesobuthus martensii Karsch*: gaining insight into the evolutionary mechanism. *Peptides*, 26(12): 2427–2433.

Lyons, S.A., O'Neal, J. and Sontheimer, H. (2002). Chlorotoxin, a scorpion-derived peptide, specifically binds to gliomas and tumors of neuroectodermal origin. *GLIA*, 39 (2): 162–173.

Ma, Y., Zhao, Y., Zhao, R., Zhang, W., He, Y., Wu, Y., Cao, Z., Guo, L. and Li, W. (2010). Molecular diversity of toxic components from the scorpion *Heterometrus petersii* venom revealed by proteomic and transcriptome analysis. *Proteomics*, 10(13): 2471–2485.

Mabrouk, K., Ram, N. and Boisseau, S. (2007). Critical amino acid residues of maurocalcine involved in pharmacology, lipid interaction, and cell penetration. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta*, 1768 (10): 2528–2540.

Mamelak, A.N., Rosenfeld, S. and Bucholz, R. (2006). Phase I single-dose study of intracavitary-administered iodine-131-TM-601 in adults with recurrent high-grade glioma. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 24 (22): 3644–3650.

Marsh, E.N., Buer, B.C. and Ramamoorthy, A. (2009). Fluorine-a new element in the design of membrane-active peptides. *Molecular Bio-system*, 5(10): 1143–1147.

Martin-Eauclaire, M., Abbas, N. and Sauze, N. (2010). Involvement of endogenous opioid system in scorpion toxin-induced antinociception in mice. *Neuroscience Letters*, 482 (1): 45–50.

Meki, A.M.A., and Omar, H.E.M. (1997). A bradykinin potentiating fraction isolated from the venom of Egyptian scorpion *Buthus occitanus* induced prostaglandin biosynthesis in female guinea pigs. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology C*, 116 (3): 183–189.

Meylears, K., Cerstiaens, A., Vierstraete, E., Baggerman, G., Michiels, C.W., DeLoof, A. and Schoofs, L. (2002). Antimicrobial Compounds of Low Molecular Mass is Constitutively Present in Insects: Characterisation of Alanyl Tyrosine. *Current studies of Pharmaceutical Design*, 8: 99–110.

Michael, E. Soleglad, B. and Victor, F. (2003). "High- level systematics and phylogeny of the extant scorpions (Scorpiones: Orthosterni)" (multiple parts). <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Euscorpium> (*journal editredlink* = 1Euscorpium.11 : 1–175).

Michael, E.S., Victor, F. and Kovařík, F. (2005). "The systematic position of the scorpion genera *Heteroscorpion* *Birula*" <http://www.science.marshall.edu/fet/euscorpium/p200> 1–38.

Mindell, J. and Maduke, M. (2001). CIC chloride channels. *Genome Biology*, 2 (2): 3003.

Moerman, L., Bosteels, S. and Noppe, W. (2002).

Antibacterial and antifungal properties of - helical, cationic peptides in the venom of scorpions from southern Africa. *European Journal of Biochemistry*, 269 (19): 4799–4810.

Moerman, L., Verdonck, F., Willems, J., Tytgat, J., and Bosteels, S. (2003). Antimicrobial peptides from scorpion venom induce Ca²⁺ signaling in HL-60 cells. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 311 (1): 90–97.

Moody, T.W., Pradhan, T. and Mantey, S.A. (2008). Bombesin marine toxin conjugates inhibit the growth of lung cancer cells. *Life Sciences*, 82 (15- 16): 855–861.

Munoz-Price, L.S. and Weinstein, R.A. Acinetobacter infection. *Northern England Journal of Medicals*, 358: 1271-1281.

Mussi, M.A., Limansky, A.S. and Viale, A.M. (2005). Acquisition of resistance to carbapenems in multidrug-resistant clinical strains of *Acinetobacter baumannii*: Natural insertional inactivation of a gene encoding a member of a novel family of beta-barrel outer membrane proteins. *Antimicrobial Agents Chemotherapy*, 49: 1432-1440.

Nabhani, T., Zhu, X., Simeoni, I., Sorrentino, V., Valdivia, H.H. and García, J. (2002). Imperatoxin A enhances Ca²⁺ release in developing skeletal muscle containing ryanodine receptor type 3. *Biophysical Journal*, 82 (3): 1319–1328.

Neil, F. and Hadley, F. (1970). "Water relations of the desert scorpion, *Hadrurus* <http://jeb.biologists.org/cgi/reprint/53/3/547.pdf> https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Journal_of_Experimental_Biology 547–558.

Newman, D.J. and Cragg, G.M. (2007). Natural products as a source of new drugs over the last 25 years. *Journal of Natural Products*, 70 (3): 461–477.

Nicholson, G.M., Graudins, A., Wilson, H.I., Little, M. and Broady, K.W. (2006) Arachnid toxinology in Australia: from clinical toxicology to potential applications. *Toxicon*, 48 (7): 872–898.

Nie, Y., Zeng, X-C. and Yang, Y. (2012). a novel class of antimicrobial peptides from the scorpion *Heterometrus spinifer*. *Peptides*, 38 (2): 389–394.

Otto, T., Lümmer, G. and Kälble, T. (1999). Intravesical therapy with pertussis toxin before radical cystectomy in patients with bladder cancer: a phase I study. *Urology*, 54 (3): 458–460.

Ovuru, K. F., Izah S. C., Yasmin, H., Enerijiofi, K. E., Das, M. and Ogwu, M.

C. (2023). Microbial Contaminants of Herbal Remedies: Health Risks and Sustainable Quality Control Strategies. In Izah, S. C., Ogwu, M. C., Akram, M. (eds). *Herbal Medicine Phytochemistry. Reference Series in Phytochemistry*. Springer Nature, Cham. doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21973-3_9-1

Ozkan, O. and Filazi, A. (2004). The determination of acute lethal dose-50 (LD50) levels of venom in mice, obtained by different methods from Scorpions. *Androctonus crassicauda* (Olivier 1807). *Acta Parasitology Turcica*, 28(1):50-53.

Ozkan, O., Ciftci, G., Pekmezci, G.Z., Kar, S., Uysal, H. and Karaer, K.Z. (2007) Proteins, lethality and in vivo effects of *Iurus dufourei asiaticus* scorpion venom. *Toxicon*, 50 (3): 394–399.

Packova, V., Stulik, K., Hau, P.T., Jelinek, J., Vins, I. and Sykora, D. (1995). Comparison of high-performance liquid chromatography and Capillary electrophores for the determination of some bee venom components. *Journal of Chromatography*, 700 (2): 187-193.

Pascual-Barea, J. (2013). “Interpretación de los epígrafes y de la marca del caballo de una jarra de Tamuda”, Tamuda. Cronosecuencia de la ciudad mauritana y del castellum romano. *Cádiz: Universidad*, 393-401.

Petricerich, V.L., Navarro, L.B. and Possani, L.D. (2013). Therapeutic use of Scorpion Venom. *Indian Research Journal*, 37: (2) 661.

Petricevich, V.L., and Lebrun, I. (2005). <http://jeb.biologists.org/cgi/reprint/53/3/547.pdf> https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Journal_of_Experimental_Biology 547–558.

Petricevich, V.L., Cruz, A.H., Coronas, F.I.V. and Possani, L.D. (2007). Toxin gamma from *Tityus serrulatus* scorpion venom plays an essential role in the immunomodulation of macrophages. *Toxicon*, 50 (5): 666–675.

Pipelzadeh, M.H., Dezfulian, A., Jalali, M.T. and Mansouri, A. (2006). In vitro and in vivo studies on some toxic effects of the venom from Hemiscorpius lepturus scorpion. *Toxicon*, 48 (1): 93–103.

Possani L.D., Becerril, B., Delepierre, M. and Tytgat, J. (1999). Scorpion toxins specific for Na⁺-channels. *European Journal of Biochemistry*, 264 (2): 287–300.

Possani, L.D., Corona, M., Zurita, M. and Rodríguez, M.H. (2002). From noxiustoxin to scorpine and possible transgenic mosquitoes resistant to malaria. *Archives of Medical Research*, 33(4): 398– 404.

- Powers, J.P.S. and Hancock, R.E.W. (2003). The relationship between peptide structure and antibacterial activity. *Peptides*, 24 (11): 1681–1691.
- Radmanesh, M. (1998). Cutaneous manifestations of the *hemiscorpius lepturus* sting: a clinical study. *International Journal of Dermatology*, 37 (7): 500–507.
- Rajendra, W., Armugam, A. and Jeyaseelan, K. (2004). Toxins in anti-nociception and anti-inflammation. *Toxicon*, 44(1): 1–17.
- Ramamoorthy, A. (2009). Beyond NMR spectra of antimicrobial peptides: Dynamical images at atomic resolution and functional insights. *Solid State Nucleic Magnesium Research*, 35: 201-207.
- Ramamoorthy, A., Lee, D.K., Narasimhaswamy, T. and Nanga, R.P. (2010). Cholesterol reduces pardaxin's dynamics-a barrel-stave mechanism of Membrane disruption investigated by solid-state NMR. *Biochemical and Biophysiological Acta*, 1798(2): 223-237.
- Ramírez-Carretero, S., Quintero-Hernández, V. and Jiménez-Vargas, J.M. (2012). Gene cloning and functional characterization of four novel antimicrobial-like peptides from scorpions of the family Vaejovidae. *Peptides*. 34 (2): 290–295.
- Reddy, K.V.R., Yedery, R.D. and Aranha, C. (2004). Antimicrobial peptides: premises and promises. *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, 24 (6): 536–547.
- Reddy, K.V.R., Yedery, R.D. and Aranha, C. (2004). Antimicrobial peptides: Premises and promises. *International Journal Antimicrobial Agent*, 24:536-547.
- Remijsen, Q., Berghe, T.V., Parthoens, E., Asselbergh, B., Vandenabeele, P. and Willems, J. (2009). Inhibition of spontaneous neutrophil apoptosis by parabutoporin acts independently of NADPH oxidase inhibition but by lipid raft-dependent stimulation of Akt. *Journal of Leukocyte Biology*, 85(3): 497–507.
- Remijsen, Q., Verdonck, F. and Willems, J. (2010). Parabutoporin, a cationic amphipathic peptide from scorpion venom: much more than an antibiotic. *Toxicon*, 55 (2-3): 180–185.
- Remijsen, Q.F.M., Fontayne, A., Verdonck, F., Clynen, E., Schoofs, L. and Willems J. (2006). The antimicrobial peptide parabutoporin competes with p47^{phox} as a PKC-substrate and inhibits NADPH oxidase in human neutrophils. *FEBS Letters*, 580(26):6206–6210.
- Ricardo, C. Rodríguez de la Vega, N.V. and Lourival, D. P. (2013). "Scorpion Peptides". In Abba J. Kastin. *Handbook of Biologically Active Peptides* (2nd ed.). Pp. 423–429.
- Rodríguez De La Vega, R.C. and Possani, L.D. (2004). Current views on scorpion toxins specific for K⁺- channels. *Toxicon*, 43 (8): 865–875.
- Rodríguez De La Vega, R.C., García, B.I., D'Ambrosio, C., Diego-García, E., Scaloni, A. and Possani, L.D. (2004). Antimicrobial peptide induction in the haemolymph of the Mexican scorpion *Centruroides limpidus limpidus* in response to septic injury. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*, 61 (12): 1507–1519.
- Russell, G. and Gregory, E. (2011). "Early terrestrial animals, evolution and uncertainty". <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Evolution>, *Education, editredlink = 1Evolution, Education, and Outreach*, 4(3) : 489–501.
- Sabatier, L.E., Loew, D., Goyffon, M., Fehlbaum, P., Hoffmann, J.A., Dorselaer, A.V., and Bulet, P. (1996). Characterization of novel cysteine-rich antimicrobial peptides from scorpion blood. *Journal of Biological*, 11(2):24-27.
- Sahai, E. (2005). Mechanisms of cancer cell invasion. *Current Opinion in Genetics and Development*, 15 (1): 87–96.
- Salarian, A.A., Jalali, A., Mirakabadi, A.Z., Vatanpour, H. and Shirazi, F.H. (2012). Cytotoxic effects of two Iranian scorpions *Odontobuthus doriae* and *Bothutus saulcyi* on five human cultured cell lines and fractions of toxic venom. *Iranian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 11 (1): 357– 367.
- Sands, S.B., Lewis, R.S. and Cahalan, M.D. (1989). Charybdotoxin blocks voltage-gated K⁺ channels in human and murine T lymphocytes. *Journal of General Physiology*, 93 (6): 1061–1074.
- Scharfetter, J., Chaudhry, H.R. and Hornik, K. (1999). Dopamine D3 receptor gene polymorphism and response to clozapine in schizophrenic Pakistani patients. *European Neuropsychopharmacology*, 10 (1): 17–20.
- Scott, A.S. (1989). Revision of the Phylogeny and Higher Classification of Scorpions (Chelicerata). Ph.D. Dissertation, University of California, Berkeley
- Shaini, T., Shreyas, K., Ram, S.B., Jayaraman, V.K. and Susan, I.T. (2010). CAMP: a useful resource for research on antimicrobial peptides. *Nucleic-acids*

Research, 38: 774-780.

Shao, D., Okuse, K. and Djamgoz, M.B.A. (2009). Protein-protein interactions involving voltage-gated sodium channels: post-translational regulation, intracellular trafficking, and functional expression. *International Journal of Biochemistry and Cell Biology*, 41 (7): 1471-1481.

Shawn, J., Stachel, S., Stockwell, A., and David, L.V. (1999). "The fluorescence of scorpions and cataractogenesis". [https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Chemistry and biology of scorpions and cataractogenesis](https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Chemistry_and_biology_of_scorpions). *editredlink = 1Chemistry & Biology*, 6(8) : 531-539.

Simeoni, I., Rossi, D., Zhu, X., García, J., Valdivia, H.H. and Sorrentino, V. (2001). Imperatoxin A (IpTxa) from the *Pandinus imperator* stimulates [3H] ryanodine binding to RyR3 channels. *FEBS Letters*, 508 (1): 5-10.

Simon, J., Braddy, M.P. and Erik, T.O. (2008). "Giant claw reveals the largest ever arthropod". [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Biology of scorpions](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Biology_of_scorpions). *Letters Biology Letters*, 4(1): 106-109.

Singh, G., Jasti, J. and Saravanan, K. (2005). Crystal structure of the complex formed between a group I Phospholipase A2 and a naturally occurring fatty acid at 2.7 Å resolution. *Protein Science*, 14 (2): 395-400.

Smith, G.A., Tsui, H.W. and Newell, E.W. (2002). Functional up-regulation of HERG K⁺ channels in neoplastic hematopoietic cells. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 277 (21): 18528-18534.

Song, X., Wang, Z. and Jia, Q. (2012). Inhibitory effect of polypeptide extracts from scorpion venom on the proliferation of ovarian cancer SKOV3 cells. *Chinese Journal of New Drugs*, 21 (3): 257-261.

Song, Y., Tang, X. and Chen, X. (2005). Effects of scorpion venom bioactive polypeptides on platelet aggregation and thrombosis and plasma 6-keto-PG F1 and TXB2 in rabbits and rats. *Toxicon*, 46 (2): 230-235.

Song, Y.M., Li, X.K., Zhou, L., Gao, E. and Lv, X.R. (2002). Effects of scorpion venom active polypeptides on mesenteric microcirculation of rats. *Chinese Journal of microcirculation*, 12:15-16.

Soroceanu, L., Gillespie, Y., Khazaeli, M.B. and Sontheimer, H. (1998). Use of chlorotoxin for targeting of primary brain tumors. *Cancer Research*, 58 (21): 4871-4879.

Soroceanu, L., Manning, T.J. and Sontheimer, H. (1999). Modulation of glioma cell migration and

invasion using Cl⁻ and K⁺ ion channel blockers. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 19 (14): 5942-5954.

Steinborner, S.T., Currie, G.J., Bowie, J.H., Wallace, J.C. and Tyler, M.J. (1998). New antibiotic caerin 1 peptide from the skin secretion of the Australian tree frog *Litoria chloris*. Comparison of the activities of the caerin 1 peptides from the genus *Litoria*. *Journal of Peptide Research*, 151 (2): 121-126.

Sudandiradoss, C., George-Priya-Doss, C., Rajasekaran, R., Purohit, R., Ramanathan, K. and Sethuramadhavan, R. (2008). Analysis of binding residues between scorpion neurotoxins and D2 dopamine receptor: a computational docking study. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 38(10):1056-1067.

Szokan, G., Horvath, J., Almas, M., Saftics, G. and Palocz, A. (1994). Liquid Chromatographic Analysis and Separation of Polypeptide Components from Honey Bee Venoms. *Journal of Liquid Chromatography*, 17(16):3333-3349.

Tan, P.T.J., Srinivasan, K.N. and Seah, S.H. (2005). Accurate prediction of scorpion toxin functional properties from primary structures. *Journal of Molecular Graphics and Modelling*, 24 (1): 17-24.

Teixeira, A.L., Fontoura, B.F., Freire-Maia, L., Machado, C.R.S., Camargos, E.R.S. and Teixeira, M.M. (2001). Evidence for a direct action of *Tityus serrulatus* scorpion venom on the cardiac muscle. *Toxicon*, 39 (5): 703-709.

Thennarasu, S., Huang, R., Lee, D.K., Yang, P., Maloy, L., Chen, Z. and Ramamoorthy, A. (2010a). Limiting an antimicrobial peptide to the lipid water interface enhances its bacterial membrane selectivity: a case study of MSI-367. *Biochemistry*, 49(50): 10595-10605.

Thennarasu, S., Lee, D.K., Poon, A., Kawulka, K.E., Vederas, J.C. and Ramamoorthy, A. (2005). Membrane permeabilization, orientation, and antimicrobial mechanism of subtilisin A. *Chemistry of Physiological Lipids*, 137(1-2): 38-51.

Thennarasu, S., Tan, A., Penumatchu, R., Shelburne, C.E., Heyl, D.L. and Ramamoorthy, A. (2010b). Antimicrobial and membrane disrupting activities of a peptide derived from the human cathelicidin antimicrobial peptide LL37. *Bio physiological Journal*, 98(2): 248-257.

Torres-Larios, A., Gurrola, G.B., Zamudio, F.Z., and Possani, L.D. (2000). Hadrurin, a new antimicrobial peptide from the venom of the scorpion

Hadrurusaztecus. *European Journal of Biochemistry*, 267: 5023-5031.

Uawonggul, N., Thammasirirak, S. and Chaveerach, A. (2007). Purification and characterization of Heteroscorpine-1 (HS-1) toxin from *Heterometrus laoticus* scorpion venom. *Toxicon*, 49 (1): 19–29.

Usman, H., Abdulrahman F.F. and Ladaman, A.H. (2007). Phytochemical and antimicrobial evaluation of *Tribulusterrestis* L (Zygophyllaceae) growing in Nigeria. *Research journal in biological science (Medwell journal)*, 24: 45-50.

Valverde, P., Kawai, T. and Taubman, M.A. (2004). Selective blockade of voltage-gated potassium channels reduces inflammatory bone resorption in experimental periodontal disease. *Journal of Bone and Mineral Research*, 19 (1): 155–164.

Van herrewege, Y., Morellato, L. and Descours, A. (2008). CD4 mimetic mini proteins: potent anti-HIV compounds with promising activity as microbicides. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, 61 (4): 818–826.

Vancompernelle, S.E., Taylor, R.J., Richter, K.O., Jiang, J., Youree, B.E., Bowie, J.H., Tyler, M.J., Conlon, J.M., Wade, D., Aiken, C., Dermody, T.S., Kewalramani, V.N., Rollins-Smith, L.A. and Unutmaz, D. (2005). Antimicrobial peptides from amphibian skin potently inhibit human immunodeficiency virus infection and transfer of virus from dendritic cells to T cells. *Journal of Virology*, 79(18): 11598-11606.

Vandenberg, C.A. (2008). Integrins step up the pace of cell migration through polyamines and potassium channels. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 105 (20): 7109–7110.

Veiseh, O., Kievit, F.M. and Fang, C. (2010). Chlorotoxin bound magnetic nanovector tailored for cancer cell targeting, imaging, and siRNA delivery. *Biomaterials*, 31 (31): 8032–8042.

Veiseh, O., Kievit, F.M., Gunn, J.W., Ratner, B.D. and Zhang, M. (2009). A ligand-mediated nanovector for targeted gene delivery and transfection in cancer cells. *Biomaterials*, 30 (4): 649–657.

Verano-Braga, T., Rocha-Resende, C. and Silva, D.M. (2008). *Tityus serrulatus* Hypotensins: a new family of peptides from scorpion venom. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 371 (3): 515–520.

Visan, V., Sabatier, J. and Grissmer, S. (2004).

Block of neurotoxin and charybdotoxin on human intermediate-conductance calcium-activated potassium channels (hIKCa1) *Toxicon*, 43 (8): 973–980.

Vita, E., Drakopoulou, E. and Vizzavona, J. (1999). Rational engineering of a mini protein that reproduces the core of the CD4 site interacting with HIV-1 envelope glycoprotein. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 96 (23): 13091–13096.

Vollekova, A., Kost'alara, D. and Sochorova, R. (2001). Antimicrobial methods in Microbiology. *Microbiology journal*, 46:107-111.

Waller, K.L., Kim, K. and McDonald, T.V. (2008). Plasmodium falciparum: growth response to potassium channel blocking compounds. *Experimental Parasitology*, 120 (3): 280–285.

Wang, W. and Ji, Y. (2005). Scorpion venom induces glioma cell apoptosis in vivo and inhibits glioma tumor growth in vitro. *Journal of Neuro-Oncology*, 73 (1): 1–7.

Wels, W. (1995). Biotechnological and gene therapeutic strategies in cancer treatment. *Gene*, 159 (1): 73–80.

Willems, J., Moerman, L., Bosteels, S., Bruyneel, E., Ryniers, F. and Verdonck, F. (2004). Parabutopirin-an antibiotic peptide from scorpion venom-can both induce activation and inhibition of granulocyte cell functions. *Peptides*, 25 (7): 1079–1084.

Willems, J., Noppe, W., Moerman, L., Van der Walt, J. and Verdonck, F. (2002). Cationic peptides from scorpion venom can stimulate and inhibit polymorphonuclear granulocytes. *Toxicon*, 40 (12): 1679–1683

Wolf, K., Mazo, I., and Leung, H. (2003). Compensation mechanism in tumor cell migration: mesenchymal-amoeboid transition after blocking of pericellular proteolysis. *Journal of Cell Biology*, 160 (2): 267–277.

Wolfs, J.L., Wielders, S.J. and Comfurius, P. (2006). Reversible inhibition of the platelet procoagulant response through manipulation of the Gardos channel. *Blood*, 108 (7): 2223–2228.

Wong, H., Bowie, J.H. and Carver, J.A. (1997). The solution structure and activity of caerin 1.1, an antimicrobial peptide from the Australian green tree frog, *Litoria splendid*. *European Journal of Biochemistry*, 247: 545-557.

Xiang, Y., Wu, Q. and Liang, L. (2012). Chlorotoxin-

modified stealth liposomes encapsulating levodopa for the targeting delivery against the Parkinson's disease in the MPTP-induced mice model. *Journal of Drug Targeting*, 20 (1): 67–75

Xiao, K.F., Zhou, J., Wang, Z., Fu, W.H. and Lu, X.Y. (2012). Effect of the venom of the scorpion *Heterometrus liangi* on the expression of P21 and caspase-3 gene in human KYSE-510 cell. *Advanced Materials Research*, 345: 399–404.

Xu, L., Zhang, W., Wang, Z., Jia, Q., Zhang, Y. and Jiang, G. (2010). Effect of polypeptide extract from scorpion venom (PESV) on immune escape of Lewis lung carcinomas. *Zhongguo Zhongyao Zazhi*, 35 (17): 2324–2327.

Yan, R., Zhao, Z. and He, Y. (2011). A new natural α -helical peptide from the venom of the scorpion *Heterometrus petersii* kills HCV. *Peptides*, 32 (1): 11–19.

Yibao, M., Ruiming, Z., Yawen, H., Songryong, L., Jun, L., Yingliang, W., Zhijian, C. and Wenxin, L. (2009). Transcriptome analysis of the venom gland of the scorpion *Scorpiops jendeki*: implication for the evolution of the scorpion venom arsenal. *Biomedical Genomics*, 10 (290): 1-15.

Yigit, N. and Benli, M. (2010). Fine structural analysis of the stinger in the venom apparatus of the scorpion *Euscorpis mingrelicus*. *Journal of Venom Animal Toxins Including Tropical Disease*, 16 (1) 76-86.

Yuan, W., Cao, L. and Ma, Y. (2010). Cloning and functional characterization of a new antimicrobial peptide gene StCT1 from the venom of the scorpion *Scorpiops tibetanus*. *Peptides*, 31(1): 22–26.

Zeng, X.C., Wang, S.X., Zhu, Y., Zhu, S.Y., and Li, W.X. (2004). Identification and functional characterization of novel scorpion venom peptides with no disulfide bridge from *Buthus martensii* Karsch. *Peptides*, 25(2): 143-50.

Zhang, C., Qiu, S., Wang, Y., Qi, L., Hao, R., Liu, X., Shi, Y., Hu, X., An, D., and Li, Z. (2013) Higher isolation of NDM-1 producing *Acinetobacter baumannii* from the sewage of the hospitals in Beijing. *PLoS One Journal*, 8: (10) 1371.

Zhang, H., Chen, J., and Waldherr, C. (2004). Synthesis and evaluation of bombesin derivatives on the basis of pan-bombesin peptides labeled with Indium-111, Lutetium-177, and Yttrium-90 for targeting bombesin receptor-expressing tumors. *Cancer Research*, 64 (18): 6707–6715.

Zhao, Z., Hong, H. and Zeng, Z. (2012).

Mucroporin-M1 inhibits hepatitis B virus replication by activating the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway and down-regulating HNF4 in vitro and in vivo. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 267 (36): 30181–30180.

Zhao, Z., Ma, Y. and Dai, C. (2009). Imcroporin, a new cationic antimicrobial peptide from the venom of the scorpion *Isometrus maculatus*. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 53 (8): 3472–3477.

Zhao, Z., Ma, Y., Dai, C., Zhao, R., Li, S., Wu, Y., Cao, Z. and Li, W. (2009). Imcroporin, a new cationic antimicrobial peptide from the venom of the scorpion *Isometrus maculatus*. *Antimicrobial Agents Chemotherapy*, 53: 3472.

Zhijian, C., Feng, L., Yingliang, W., Xin, M. and Wenxin, L. (2006). Genetic mechanisms of scorpion venom peptide diversification. *Toxicon*, 47 (3): 348–355.

Zhu, S. and Li, W. (2002). Precursors of three unique cysteine-rich peptides from the scorpion *Buthus martensii* Karsch. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology B*, 131 (4): 749–756.

Antibacterial Activities of Blowfly (*Lucilla sericata*) and Housefly (*Musca domestica*) Maggots Extract on Some Selected Isolates

UGOH S. C.¹; DAHUNSI A. A.*¹

¹Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria

Corresponding author: ayodeji.dahunsi2022@uniabuja.edu.ng; 08066761700

Abstract: Antimicrobial substances have played a pivotal role in global health since the discovery of penicillin in 1941. However, the rise of antimicrobial resistance poses a significant threat to public health. This study focuses on the potential antibacterial properties of maggot extracts from *Lucilia sericata* and *Musca domestica* on selected bacterial isolates. The study was conducted in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria, with maggot collection, extraction, and antibacterial assays carried out through agar-well diffusion methods. The results indicate dose-dependent antibacterial activity, with the aqueous extract showing the highest efficacy. The minimum inhibitory concentrations were determined, highlighting varying sensitivities among tested bacteria. The findings suggest the potential of maggot extracts as alternative antimicrobial agents, emphasizing their efficacy against *Staphylococcus aureus*. This research provides a scientific basis for considering maggot extracts in the development of new therapies, particularly for infections caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria.

Key Words: Antimicrobial resistance, Maggot extracts, Antibacterial activity, Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), *Staphylococcus aureus*

1 Introduction

Antimicrobial is a substance that kills or inhibits the growth of microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, or protozoan, as well as killing viruses. The discovery of antimicrobials like penicillin and tetracycline paved the way for better health for millions around the world. Before 1941, the year where penicillin was discovered, there were no true cure existed for some diseases such as gonorrhoea (a venereal disease involving inflammatory discharge from the urethra or vagina), strep throat, or pneumonia (a lung infection in which the air sacs fill with pus). Often, the infected wound patients have a wounded limb removed, or face death from the infection. Research into antibacterial activity is crucial for safeguarding the health of millions worldwide. The quest for new cures against diseases caused by microorganisms underscores the significance of this endeavor, as it directly impacts human health and well-being.

Some of the microorganisms, especially bacteria are becoming resistant to more and more antibacterial agents. By making a new research, antibacterial agents that can kill or inhibit the growth of other bacteria can be found (Cosgrove *et al.*, 2003). Now, most of these infections can be cured easily with a short course of antibacterial.

Microorganisms, especially bacteria are becoming resistant to more and more antimicrobial agent. They are becoming resistant more quickly than new drugs that are being made available. Therefore, future research in antimicrobial therapy may focus on finding the new antimicrobial that can overcome this problem, or treat infections with alternative means.

The increase of life-threatening infections that are resistant to commonly used antibiotics has become a worldwide problem (Enerijiofi and Isola, 2019). It is becoming an important cause of morbidity in immune-compromised patients particularly in developing countries (Al-Bari *et al.*, 2006). The increasing prevalence of multi-drug resistant strain of bacteria and the recent appearance of strains with reduced susceptibility to antibiotics has raised the spectre of untreatable bacterial infection and adds urgency to search for new infection - fighting strategies (Akortha *et al.*, 2010; Zy *et al.*, 2005, Rojas *et al.*, 2006).

Presently, there are global problems of emergence of multiple antibiotics resistance as well as emergence of new and resurrection of previously eradicated disease. There is need to search for new and more potent antimicrobial compounds of natural origin to complement the existing synthetic antimicrobial

drugs that are gradually becoming less potent against pathogenic microorganisms (Adesina *et al.*, 2013).

The continuous spread of multi-drugs resistant pathogen has become a serious threat to public health and major concern for infection control practitioners' worldwide (Ovuru *et al.*, 2023). In addition to the increasing cost of drug regimens, this scenario has paved way for the re-emergence of previously controlled disease and has contributed substantially to the high frequency of opportunistic and chronic infection cases in developing countries (Fernandez *et al.*, 2003 and Ako-Nai *et al.*, 2003.)

The extract of fly maggot has been shown to completely lyse the cell wall of many bacteria including those that infect chronic wounds. As the population ages, the number of patients suffering from bacteria infected chronic wounds attributable to diseases such as diabetes mellitus and peripheral vascular disease is on the rise. This poses a significant impact on the health care system, because of the chronicity of care required and the associated costs.

i. The aim of this study was to determine the antibacterial effects of *Lucilia sericata* and *Musca domestica* maggot extracts against some selected bacterial isolates.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study area for this research is Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja. The territory is located just north of the confluence of the River Niger and River Benue. It is bordered by the states of Niger to the West and North, Kaduna to the Northeast and South, and Kogi to the Southwest. The Federal Capital Territory lies between latitude 8.25 and 9.20 North of the equator and longitude 6.45 and 7.23 East of the Greenwich Meridian. Abuja is geographically located in the centre of the country.

2.2 Collection and Preparation of Live Maggot

The maggots of *Lucilia sericata* and *Musca domestica* were jointly collected by allowing flies to feed on cattle liver in different transparent plastic containers covered with a rubber net to enable the flies to feed and lay their eggs effectively. The flies were allowed to escape by opening the rubber net after 2 hours. After an incubation period of 24 hours, the eggs hatched and developed into larvae known as maggots.

The first generation of larvae was allowed to turn into pupae to get a new breed of flies, which were reintroduced into another fresh transparent plastic container containing fresh cattle liver for feeding and laying of eggs. This process was repeated thrice to aseptically obtain clean flies' maggots since they were not allowed to roam outside the study environment and feed on dirt. It took around 7 days for a fly life cycle to be completed depending on the temperature, and maggots grow well in the dark.

2.3 Harvesting of Maggots

The third instar maggots were harvested from the transparent plastic containers containing cattle liver by removing them with a sterile teaspoon and transferring them into a sterile universal bottle and taken to the laboratory.

2.4 Decontamination of Maggots

Whole live maggots were decontaminated by soaking in 70% alcohol for 5 minutes. Thereafter, they were transferred into another sterile container covered with a rubber net to prevent maggots from escaping while allowing alcohol to evaporate from the body of the maggots. Maggots were kept in this decontaminated container for 30 minutes to allow the recovery of normal metabolism by maggots to produce efficient extracts which are located in the guts.

2.5 Maggot Extraction Procedures

2.5.1 Aqueous Extraction

This was carried out according to the method of Suchi *et al.* (2010). Maggots numbering 200, 400, 600, and 800 were respectively pulverized in a plastic laboratory mortar with a plastic laboratory pestle. The paste was collected and soaked in 2 ml of sterile water and allowed to incubate for 1 hour at room temperature. The mixture of pulverized maggot and sterile water was transferred into a centrifuge test tube to remove the particulate by centrifugation at 5,000g for 15 minutes at room temperature (25±2°C). The supernatant was collected for antibacterial screening.

2.5.2 Saline Water Extraction

This was carried out according to the method of Suchi *et al.* (2010). Maggots numbering 200, 400, 600, and 800 were respectively pulverized in a plastic laboratory mortar with a plastic laboratory pestle. The paste was collected and soaked in 2 ml of saline water

and allowed to incubate for 1 hour at 28°C. The mixture of pulverized maggot and saline water was transferred into a centrifuge test tube to remove the particulate by centrifuging at 5,000g for 15 minutes at room temperature (25±2°C). The supernatant was collected for antibacterial screening.

2.5.3 Phosphate Buffer Saline Extraction

This was carried out according to the method of Suchi et al. (2010). Maggots numbering 200, 400, 600, and 800 were respectively pulverized to paste in a plastic laboratory mortar with a plastic laboratory pestle. The paste was collected and soaked in 2 ml of PBS and allowed to incubate for 1 hour at room temperature. The mixture of pulverized maggot and PBS was transferred into a centrifuge test tube to remove the particulate by centrifuging it at 5,000g for 15 minutes at room temperature (25±2°C). The supernatant was collected for antibacterial screening.

2.6 Preparation of Extract Concentrations

Ahmed and Nancy (2012) state that the total protein measured from native excretory/secretory product of 100 larvae per 1 ml distilled water was 0.9 mg. Therefore, 200 maggots per 2 ml of distilled water will be 0.9 mg.

2.7 Identification of Bacterial Isolates Used

The bacterial isolates were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Escherichia coli*. They were clinical isolates obtained from University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Abuja, Nigeria. The cultures were gram-stained for proper confirmation using standard gram staining procedures. The cultures were maintained on nutrient agar slants at 36°C after which they were stored in the refrigerator and later re-identified and sub-cultured by biochemical test (Cheesbrough, 2005; Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

2.8 Preparation of Inoculum

Inoculums for each organism were prepared in a test tube of 5 ml of saline water by touching the fresh colonies with a sterile wire loop to obtain a very small portion of the organism and adding it to the 5 ml of saline water. This was stirred for proper mixing and to obtain a low bacterial load.

2.9 Preparation of the Control Antibiotic (Ampiclox) for the Antibacterial Activity

For the control, a known standard antibiotic ampiclox was used just like that of the stock solution.

The standard antibiotic was weighed into different concentrations (50, 100, 200, 250, and 500 mg/ml) using a weighing balance. It was then dissolved in 1 ml of sterile water for injection in sterile universal containers that have been properly labelled to obtain stock cultures of it.

2.10 Antibacterial Assay

The antibacterial assay was performed using the agar-well diffusion method as described by Okoli and Iroegbu (2004) to determine the growth inhibition of the test organisms by the maggot extracts. 25 ml each of the prepared Muller Hinton Agar was poured into sterile Petri dishes that were already properly labelled for easy identification and left to solidify. Using sterile pipettes, the agar was aseptically inoculated uniformly by flooding with 1 ml suspension of the three test organisms which had been prepared using a loop full of the inoculum in saline water. The plates were then rocked carefully for the inoculum to spread around the agar and allowed to dry.

Different agar wells were then made on the plates with the aid of a sterile cork borer (6 mm in diameter). Four wells were made on the agar, sufficiently spaced away from the edge of the plate and 25 mm from well to well to prevent overlapping of zones and labelled properly according to the three different crude extract concentrations at the bottom of the Petri dish. The same was done for the standard control plates for easy identification. The stock solutions of the crude extracts of the aqueous, saline water, and phosphate buffer saline were introduced (2-3 drops) into each agar well using a sterile Pasteur pipette, according to the labels including that of the standard antibiotics' plates.

The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours after which the sensitivity of the test organisms to aqueous, saline water, and PBS extracts of maggots were determined by measuring the zone of inhibition. The measurement of the zone of inhibition was carried out using a transparent meter rule and read to the nearest millimetres. The diameter of the clear zone was taken as an index of the degree of sensitivity.

2.11 Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The MIC values of the extracts were determined using the dilution method of the extracts. Various concentrations (0.9, 1.8, 2.7, and 3.6 mg/ml) of the maggot extracts were prepared. 36 test tubes were

set up; 2 ml of nutrient broth was pipetted into each sterile test tube that was already labelled properly. Control tubes were also set up: Tube A (test tubes containing extracts and broth), Tube B (test tube containing broth and each inoculum), and Tube C (test tube containing broth only). Using sterile Pasteur pipettes, 0.2 ml suspension of the test organisms was introduced into the test tubes according to their labels. Also, 2-3 drops of the different stock solutions were introduced using sterile Pasteur pipettes into the test tubes containing both broth and inoculum. The preparation was incubated at 37°C for 24 hours after which the test tubes were observed for turbidity or clearness. The least concentration where no turbidity was observed was noted as the minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) value.

2.12 Determination of Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

The least concentration of maggot extracts that has an antibacterial effect on the organism is considered as the minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC). This was determined from the broth dilution resulting from MIC tubes by subculturing to the surface of freshly prepared nutrient agar plates by using a sterile inoculating loop to streak the plate as described by Vollekova et al. [12pt]article graphicx array amsmath

RESULTS

Figure 1: Bar chart representing the efficacy of different concentrations in mg/ml (aqueous) against tested organisms compared to each other.

3 Discussion

A total yield of 30% soluble excretion/secretion was obtained for the aqueous, saline water, and phosphate buffer saline (PBS) extracts, with an original weight of 0.4 g/g of the whole maggot of *Lucilia sericata* and *Musca domestica*. The physical characteristics are indicated in Table 1. Tables ?? to ?? show the results

Figure 2: Stark line with markers chart representing the rate of efficacy of extract (aqueous) against the tested organisms.

of the antibacterial pattern of the extracts against the test organisms.

The results obtained from this study demonstrated a dose-dependent activity of *L. sericata* and *M. domestica* maggot or larva extracts (aqueous, saline water, and PBS) at tested doses (0.9, 1.8, 2.7, and 3.6 mg/ml) on the test organisms (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*). Maggot excretion/secretions located in their mid-gut contained protein or antibacterial peptide, as noted by Ai et al. (2008, 2012), Hon et al. (2007), and Cao et al. (2011), who extracted chitosan, HF-1 (a novel antibacterial peptide), and Lectin, respectively.

The bar chart, stacked line with markers chart, and pie chart illustrate the efficacy of the different concentrations in mg/ml (0.9, 1.8, 2.7, and 3.6 mg/ml) compared to each other, the efficacy of extracts (aqueous, saline water, and PBS) against the tested organisms, and the growth level of tested organisms (*E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus*) compared to each other, respectively.

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the aqueous maggot extract against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* was 1.8 mg/ml, as shown in Table ???. The MIC of the saline water maggot extract against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* was 3.6 mg/ml, while for *S. aureus* it was 1.8 mg/ml, as shown in Table ???. The MIC of the PBS maggot extract against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* was 3.6 mg/ml, with no MIC against *E. coli*, as shown in Table ???.

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of the aqueous maggot extract against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* was 3.6 mg/ml, while for *S. aureus* it was 2.7 mg/ml, as shown in Table ???. The MBC of the saline water maggot extract against *S. aureus* was 3.6

Table 1: Physical characteristics of the Maggot Extract

Maggot parts	Solvent	Weight of maggot (g/g)	% Yield	Colour	Odour
Texture					
Whole maggot	Aqueous	0.4	30	Yellow	Unpleasant
Oily	Saline water	0.4	30	Yellow	Unpleasant
Oily	PBS	0.4	10	Yellow	Unpleasant
Oily					

Table 2: Zone Diameter of inhibition (mm) of the aqueous extract on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	15 ± 0.0	19 ± 0.0	22 ± 0.0	10 ± 0.0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	14 ± 0.0	15 ± 0.0	17 ± 0.0	11 ± 0.0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	20 ± 0.0	22 ± 0.0	24 ± 0.0	26 ± 0.0

The table shows the zone diameter of inhibition for test organisms at different concentrations of the aqueous extract.

mg/ml, with no MBC for *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*, as shown in Table ???. There was no MBC for the PBS maggot extract against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus*, as shown in Table ???.

The largest zone of inhibition was obtained with the aqueous extract against *S. aureus*, and the lowest was obtained with the PBS extract against *E. coli*. The highest MIC was observed with the aqueous extract on *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* (1.8 mg/ml), while the lowest MIC was found with the PBS extract on *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*, with no MIC on *E. coli* using PBS. The highest MBC was observed with the aqueous extract on *S. aureus* (2.7 mg/ml), and the lowest MBC was obtained with the saline water extract on *S. aureus* (3.6 mg/ml), but no MBC was obtained from PBS. It is evident from the results of this study that *S. aureus* was more susceptible to the maggot extract compared to *E. coli*, which showed the highest resistance, followed by *P. aeruginosa*. These findings agree with several literature reports (Meylaers et al., 2004; Liang et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2006; Jin et al., 2006; Cancado et al., 2007; Xu et al., 2007; Hou et al., 2007; Ai et al., 2008, 2012; Ren et al., 2009; Cao et al., 2011; Yoon et al., 2008; Jang et al., 2007; Suchi et al., 2010), where maggot extract was found to possess significant antimicrobial activities against

several pathogens, especially *S. aureus*. In general, the low activity of the PBS extract on tested organisms might be due to the actions of different components that might have denatured the protein constituents of the maggot extract. This can be observed in the aqueous extract, which has the highest activity on tested organisms since it contains only two molecules of hydrogen and one molecule of oxygen.

4 Recommendation

It is recommended that while extracting excretions/secretions from maggots, a neutral solvent or sterile water should be used to obtain the extract in its natural form. The use of maggot extract is not yet prevalent in Nigeria; this can be improved or encouraged by health workers or the Ministry of Health as it serves as a good and cost-effective alternative to antibiotics.

5 Conclusion

From the study, it can be concluded that the aqueous extract is more efficient than extracts obtained from other solvents and should be preferred for obtaining maggot extract. These studies provide a scientific basis for the clinical or traditional use of maggot extract or whole maggot for therapy, especially for

Table 3: Zone diameter of inhibition (mm) of the control Antibiotic on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)				
	50	100	200	250	500
<i>E. coli</i>	26	31	32	36	38
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	26	27	34	35	36
<i>S. aureus</i>	29	30	31	33	34

Table 4: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of aqueous extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	-	+MIC	+	+
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	+MIC	+	+
<i>S. aureus</i>	-	+MIC	+	+

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to inhibit the growth of the organism.

Key: + = clear (no growth), - = turbid (growth)

infections caused by *S. aureus*, which is sensitive to maggot extract.

6 Conflict of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest. The study was conducted impartially and without bias.

7 References

Abu-Shanab, B., Adwa, G., Jarrar, N., Abu-Hijli, A. and Adwan, K. (2006).

Antibacterial activity of four plant extracts used in Palestine in folkloric

medicine against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Turkish*

Journal of Biological Science. 30:195-198.

Adesina, I. A., Adebote, V.T., Elehinafe, T. R.

and Enerijiofi, K. E. (2013). Growth

inhibition of *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium italicum* by seed kernel oil from Mango (*Magnifera indica L.*). *Journal of Natural Sciences Research*, 3(9): 61-64.

Ahmed, S.E. and Nancy, T. (2012). Molecular Characterization of Serine

Proteases from both First and Third Larval Instars of *Chrysomya*

Megacephala. *Life Science Journal*. 9 (3):2088.

Ai, H., Wang, F.R., Xia, Y.Q., Chen, X.M. and Lei, C.L. (2012). Antioxidant,

antifungal and antiviral activities of chitosan from the larvae of

housefly, *Musca domestica L.* *Food Chemistry Journal*. 132(1):493

-498.

Ai, H., Wang, F.R., Yang, Q.S., Zhu, F. and Lei, CL. (2008). Preparation and

biological activities of chitosan from the larvae of housefly, *Musca*

domestica. *Carbohydrate Polymerization Journal*. 72(3): 419-423.

Ako-Nai, B., Wysocki, A. B., Kusakabe, A. O., Chang, S. and Tuan, T. L.

(2003). Temporal expression of urokinase plasminogen activator,

Plasminogen activator inhibitor and gelatinase-B in chronic wound fluid

switches from a chronic to acute wound profile with progression to

healing. *Wound Repair Regeneration*.7:154-165.

Akortha, E. E., Aluyi, H. S. A. and Enerijiofi, K.

E. (2010). Plasmid encoded amoxicillin resistance in common bacterial pathogens from patients in University of Benin Hospital, Benin City, South Western Nigeria *Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*, 1(10): 478-484.

Al-Bari, Q., Nablo, B.J., Prichard, H.L., Butler, R.D., Klitzman, B. and

Schoenfisch, M.H. (2006). Inhibition of implant-associated infections via

Table 5: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of saline water extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	-	-	-	+MIC
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	-	+	+MIC
<i>S. aureus</i>	-	+MIC	+	+

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to inhibit the growth of the organism.

Key: += clear (no growth), - = turbid (growth)

Table 6: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of PBS extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	-	-	+MIC
<i>S. aureus</i>	-	-	-	+MIC

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to inhibit the growth of the organism.

Key: += clear (no growth), - = turbid (growth)

nitric oxide release. *Biomaterials Journal*. 26:6984-6990.

Amster, D. (2006). Susceptibility testing of antimicrobial media. *Antibiotics in Laboratory medicine*. 4th Edition. Williams and Wilkins, MD, USA. Pp 52 - 111.

An, C., Li, D. and Du, R. (2004). Analysis of antibacterial-relative proteins and peptides in housefly larvae. *Journal of Hygiene Research*. 33:86-88.

Andersen, A., Joergensen, B., Karlsmark, T., van der Plas, M.J.A. and Kroghelt,

K. A. (2008). *Novel Lipase Activity detected in induced Lucilia Sericata excretions/secretions*. 18th Edition. European Tissue Repair Society Meeting, Malta. Pp 60-70.

Angela, L. (2007). *Maggots and chips: A novel approach to the treatment of Diabetic ulcers*. Pp 2-4.

Aqil, F., Khan, M. S. A., Owais, M. and Ahmad, I. (2005). Effect of certain

bioactive plant extracts on clinical isolates of - lactamase producing methicilin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Journal of Basic Microbiology*.

45:106-114.

Bethune, N. (2007). A case of chronic thoracic empyema treated with maggots.

Canadian Medical Association Journal. 32:301-301.

Bexfield, A., Nigam, Y., Thomas, S. and Rafcliffe, N.A. (2004). *Detection and partial characterisation of two antibacterial factors from the excretions / secretion of the medicinal maggot Lucilia sericata and their activity against methicilin- resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA)*. Microbes infection. Pp 6.

Bishop, D. (2009). Variation in numbers of occipital setae for two species of

Lucilia (Diptera: Calliphoridae). *Journal of New Zealand Entomologist*. 14:29-31.

Bradley, M., Cullum, N. and Sheldon, T. (2009). The debridement of chronic wounds. *Journal of Systematic Review National Institute for Health*

Research Health Technology Assess. 3: (1)1-78.

Brazll, S.M., Steelman, D.C. and Szanlanski, L.A. (2007). Detection of pathogenic DNA from fifth flies (*Diptera muscidae*) using filter paper

Table 7: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of aqueous extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	+	+	+	-MBC
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	+	+	+	-MBC
<i>S. aureus</i>	+	+	-MBC	-

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to kill the organism completely.

Key: + = bacterial growth, - = no bacterial growth

Table 8: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of saline water extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>S. aureus</i>	+	+	+	-MBC

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to kill the organism completely.

Key: + = bacterial growth, - = no bacterial growth

sport card. *Journal of Agricultural and Urban Entomology*. 24 (1):13 - 18.

Brian, M.W., Davids, Y.Y., Jeffrey, L.T. and Hirohisa, K. (2011). *A fly's head showing compound eyes and body*. Pp 3.

Brin, Y.S., Mumcuoglu, K.Y., Massarwe, S., Wigelman, M., Gross. E. and

Nyska, M. (2007). Chronic foot ulcer management using maggot debridement and topical negative pressure therapy. *Journal of Wound Care*. 16:1-2.

Cai, H., Choi, S.I., Lee, Y.M. and Heo, T.R. (2002). Antimicrobial effects of herbal medicine extracts *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*

O157:H7. *Korean Journal of Biotechnology and Bioengineering*. 17:537-542.

Cançado, F.C., Valério, A.A., Marana, S.R. and Barbosa, J.A.R.G. (2007). The

Crystal structure of a lysozyme c from housefly *Musca domestica*, the first

Structure of a digestive lysozyme. *Journal of Structural Biology*. 160(1): 83-92.

Cao, X.H., Zhou, M.H., Wang, C.L., Hou, L.H. and

Zeng, B. (2011). Lectin

Purified from *Musca domestica* pupa up-regulates NO and iNOS

Production via TLR4/NF-B signaling pathway in macrophages.

International Journal of Immunopharmacology. 11(4): 399-405.

Cazander, G., Vanveen, K.E.B., Bouwman, L.H., Bernards, A.T. and Jukeman,

G.N. (2009). The influence of maggot excretions on PAO1 biofilm

formation on different biomaterials. *A Clinical Orthopaedic Related*

Research Journal. 46 (2):536-545.

Centinkaya, M., Meredith, D.O., Eschbach, L. and Richards, R.G (2007). Neo natal

myiasis: a Case study. *Turkish Journal of paediatrics*. 50:581-584.

Chan DC, Fong DH, Leung JY, Patil NG, Leung GK. (2007)

MaggotDebridement therapy in chronic wound care. *Hong Kong Medical*

Journal.13(5):382 -386.

Chain. E, Florey HW, Gardner AD, Heatley HG, Jenning MA. (2003). *Orr*

Ewing Journal. Penicillin as a chemotherapeutic agent.2:226-228.

Table 9: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of PBS extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>S. aureus</i>	+	+	+	+

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to kill the organism completely.

Key: + = bacterial growth, - = no bacterial growth

Chandler, P.J. (2006). Checklist of insects of the British Isles (New Series) Part

1: Diptera. *Handbooks for the Identification of British Insects (London*

Royal Entomological Society of London). 12 (1):1-234.

Cheesbrough, M. (2005). *Laboratory manual for tropical countries*. Pp 8.

Cheesbrough, M. (2000). District laboratory practice in Tropical countries. 2nd edition. Cambridge university printing press. Pp 305-307.

Chen, Y. and Li, J.F. (2003). The study of anti-virus activity of *Musca domestica* larva homogenate. *Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 4(2): 130-132.

Chen, W. Y. and Rogers, A. A. (2007). Recent insights into the causes of

Chronic leg ulceration in venous diseases and implications on other types of chronic wounds. *Journal of Wound Repair Regeneration*. 15:434-449.

Chernysh, S., Kim, S.I., Bekker, G., Pleskach, V.A., Filatova, N.A.,

Anikin, V.B, Platnov, V.G. and Bulet, P. (2002). Antiviral and antitumor peptides from Insect. *Journal of Microbiology*. 3:2-3.

Choi, J.H., Yu, M.H., Hwang, E.Y. and Lee, I.S. (2009). Effect of *Rosmarinus*

officinalis L. fractions on antimicrobial activity against methicillin

resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and resistant genes regulation.

Journal of Korean Social Food Science Nutrition. 38:541-547.

Cosgrove, A., Weil, G., R. Simon, and Sweadner WR. (2003). A biological, bacteriological and clinical study of larval or maggot therapy in the treatment of acute and chronic pyogenic infections. *American Journal of Surgery*. 19:36-48.

Cosgrove, S.E., Qi, Y., Kaye, K.S., Harbarth, S., Karchmer A.W. and

Carmeli, Y. (2005). The impact of methicillin resistance in

Staphylococcus aureus bacteremia on patient outcomes: Mortality, length of stay, and hospital charges. *Journal of Infection Control in Hospital Epidemiology*. 26:166-174.

DeBartolo, A. (2006). Buzz off! The housefly has made a pest of himself for 25million years. PMD 11902690.

Dibner, J.J. and Richards, J.D. (2005). Antibiotic growth promoters in agriculture: History and mode of action. *Journal of Poultry Science*. 84:634-643.

Dissemond, J., Zollner, T. M., Veraart, J. C., Wolter, M., Hesse, S., Villemur, B., Wenke, A., Werner, R. J., Boehncke, W. H., Jost, S. S., Scharrer, I. and Kaufmann, R. (2003). Leg ulcers in Klinefelter's syndrome-further evidence for an involvement of plasminogen activator inhibitor-1. *British Journal of Dermatology*. 136:341-344.

Dissemond, J., Koppermann, M., Esser, S., Schultewolter, T., Goos, M. and

Wagner, S.N. (2002). Treatment of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) as part of biosurgical management of a chronic leg ulcer.

Hautarzt Journal of Chronic Ulcer. 53 (9):608-1.

- Dubendorfer, A. (2003). *Musca domestica*, a window on the evolution of sex determining mechanisms in insects. *International Journal of Developmental Biology*. 46 (1):75-79.
- Dunville, J.C., Worthy, G., Bland, J.M., Cullum, N., Dowson, C., and Iglesias, C. (2009). Larval therapy for leg ulcers (Venlls II): Randomised controlled trial. *Biomedical Journal*. 33:773.
- Enerijiofi, K. E. and Isola, O. B. (2019). Preliminary Phytochemical screening and *in vitro* antibacterial activities of aqueous and ethanol extracts of *Ageratum conyzoides* L. Leaf, Stem, Flower and Root on some Bacterial isolates associated with Diarrhoea. *Nigerian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 32 (2): 3480-3489 <http://dx.doi.org/10.19240/njpas.2019.B09><http://dx.doi.org/10.19240/njpas.2019.B09>
- Fernandez, H., Dobrovolsky, A. B. and Titaeva E.V. (2003). The fibrinolysis system: regulation of activity and physiologic functions of its main components. *Biochemistry Journal (Mosc.)* 67:99-108.
- Fleischmann, W., Grassberger, M., Sherman, R. (2004). Maggot Therapy. A *Handbook of Maggot- Assisted Wound Healing*. Stuttgart, George Thieme. 14:6-9.
- Fleischmann, W., Joergensen, B., Karlsmark, T., van der Plas, M. J. A. and Kroghfelt, K.A. (2003). *Activity detected in induced Musca domestica* excretions/secretions. 6th Edition. European Tissue Repair Society Meeting, Malta. Pp 1-2.
- Fredenburgh, J. C. and Nesheim, M. E. (1992). Lys-plasminogen is a significant intermediate in the activation of Glu-plasminogen during fibrinolysis *in vitro*. *Journal Biological Chemistry*. 267:26150-26156.
- Geo.F.B., Karen.C.C., Butel.S.J., and Stephen.A.M. (2010). In: *Jawetz, Melnick and Adelberg's Medical Microbiology*. 28th International Edition. Mc Graw Hill Lange. Pp 145-148.
- Greco, K.N., Mendonça, R.M.Z., Moraes, R.H.P., Mancini, D.A.P. and Mendonça, R.Z. (2009). Antiviral activity of the hemolymph of *Lonomia oblique* (Lepidoptera: Saturniidae). *Antiviral Research*. 84(1): 84-90.
- Hanln, G. (2007). *Bacteriophage Therapy*. Microbiologist: The Magazine of the Society for Applied Microbiology. 1-56.
- Harris, L.G. (2007). *Staphylococcus aureus* adhesion to standard micro-rough and electropolished implant materials. *Journal of Mater Science and Mater Medicine*. 18:1151-1156.
- Heuer, H. and Heuer, L. (2011). Blowfly strike and Maggot Therapy. *Parasitology to Medical Treatment Parasitology Research Journal*. 1:301-323.
- Horobin, A.J., Shakesher, K.M. and Pritchard, D.I. (2005). *Maggots and wound Healing Journal*. An investigation of the effects of secretions from *Lucilia sericata* larvae upon the migration of human dermal fibroblast over a fibronectin coated surface. 13:422-433.
- Hou, L., Shia, Y., Zhaia, P. and Le, G. (2007). Antibacterial activity and *in vitro* antitumor activity of the extract of larva of the housefly (*Musca domestica*). *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 3:227-231.
- Huberman, L., Mumcuoglu, K.Y., Gollop, N. and Galun, R. (2003). *Antibacterial substances excreted by the maggot of the green bottle fly, Lucilia sericata*. 6th International Conference on Biotherapy, Cumhuriyet University, Sivas, Turkey. Pp 27-28.
- Hwangbo, J., Hong, E.C., Jang, A., Kang, H.K., Oh, J.S., Kim, B.W. and Park, B.S. (2009). Utilization of house fly-maggots, a feed supplement in the production of broiler chickens. *Journal of Environmental Biology*. 30:609-614.
- Jackil, D., Lapanje, A., Zupani1, K., Smrke, D. and Gunde-Cimerman, N. (2008). Selective antimicrobial activity of maggot against pathogenic

- bacteria. *Journal of Medical Microbiology*. 57:617-625.
- Jang, A. (2007). *Seperation of antibacterial low molecular peptides from Musca domestica maggot against methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) and vancomycin resistant enterococcus (VRE)*. International Symposium and Annual Meeting. The Korean Society of Food Science and Nutrition. Pp 275.
- Jarvis, K. (2003). Degradation of extracellular matrix components by defined proteinases from the greenbottle larva *Lucilia sericata* used for the clinical debridement of non-healing wounds. *British Journal of Dermatology* 148:14-23.
- Jin, F.L., Xu, X.X., Zhang, W.Q. and Gu, D.X. (2006). Expression and characterization of a housefly cecropin gene in the methylotrophic yeast, *Pichia pastoris*. *Protein Expression Purification*. 49(1): 39-46.
- Jones, T.F., Kellum, M.E., Porter, S.S., Bell, M. and Schaffner, W. (2002). An outbreak of community-acquired food borne illness caused by methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Emergence Infectious Disease Journal*. 8:82-84.
- Jones T.F., Kellum, M.E., Porter, S.S., Bell, M. and Schaffner, W. (2003). Bacterial biofilm: from the natural environment to infectious diseases. *National Revised Microbiology*.2:95-108.
- Jones M. (2003). An overview of maggot therapy used on chronic wounds in the community. *British Journal of Community Nursing*. 14:14-18
- Jones,G. and Wall,G. (2008). Research in veterinary science Maggot-therapy in veterinaryMedicine. *Journal of Veterinary Medicine*. 85.394-398.
- Jukem,G.N., Klimpel S, Sievert K (2003). The house fly (*Musca domestica*) as a potential vector of metazoan parasites caught in a pig-pen in Germany.*Veterenary Parasitology*. 160 (1-2): 163-167.
- Jukema, G.N., Menon, A.G, Bernards, A.T., Steenvoorde, P., Taheri Rastegar, A. and Van Dissel, J.T. (2002). Amputation-sparing treatment by nature, surgical maggots revisited. *Journal of Clinical Infectious Disease*. 35:1566-1571.
- Kerridge, A., Reed, L.J. and Muench, H. (2004). A simple method of estimating fifty percent endpoints. *American Journal of Hygiene*. 27(3): 493-497.
- Kerridge, A., Lappin-Scott, H. and Stevens, J.R. (2005). Antibacterial properties of larval secretions of the blowfly, *Lucilia sericata*.*Journal of Medical Veterinary Entomology*. 19: 333-337.
- Kristina, O., Xavier, F., Benidicte, M.,Yannick, C., Christian, C., Patrick, C., Anne-Laure, L., Ingrid, S. and Anne, D. (2011). Maggot therapy for wound Debridement. *Journal of Dermatology*.10:10-11.
- Larrain, P. and Salas, C. (2008). Housefly (*Musca domestica* L.) (*Dipteria:Muscidae*) development in different types of manure [*Desarrollo de la Mosca Domestica (Musca domestica* L.) (*Dipteria:Muscidae*)en Distintos tipos de Estercoi]. *Chilean Journal of Agricultural Research*. 68 (2):192-197.
- Larrey, W.R. (2003). Digestion of bacteria and the role of midgut lysozyme in some insect larvae. *Journal Biochemistry Physiology*.100(2): 265-268.
- Lerch, K., Linde, H.J., Lehn, N. and Grifka, J. (2003). Bacteria ingestion by blowfly larvae. *An in vitro study in Dermatology Journal*. 207:362-366.
- Levi, S.B. (1998). The challenge of antibiotic resistance. *Scientific American Journal*. 278:46-53.
- Li, J.F. and Chen, Y. (2006). Explore for antiviral activity of *Musca domestica* larva hemolymph. *Chinese Journal of Zoology*. 22(10): 981-983.
- Liang, Y., Wang, J., Zhao, X., Du, X. and Xue, J. (2006). Molecular cloning

- and characterization of cecropin from the housefly (*Musca domestica*), and its expression in *Escherichia coli*. *Journal of Developing Comparism in Immunology*. 30:249-257.
- Mascini, E.M., Troelstra, A. and Beitsma, M. (2006). Genotyping and Preemptive isolation to control an outbreak of vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus faecium*. *Journal of Clinical Infectious Disease*. 42:739-746.
- Matyar, F., Dincer, S., Kaya, A. and Colak, O. (2004). Prevalence and Resistance to antibiotics in gram negative bacteria isolated from retail fish in Turkey. *Journal of Analytical Microbiology*. 54:151-160.
- McCarthy, L.R., Mickelsen, A.P. and Smith, E.G. (1979). Antibiotic susceptibility of *Haemophilus vaginalis* (*Corynebacterium vaginale*) to 21 antibiotics. *Antimicrobial Agents Chemotherapy Journal*. 16:186-189.
- Meylaers, K., Clynen, E., Daloze, D., DeLoof, A. and Schoofs, L. (2004). Identification of 1-lysophosphatidylethanolamine (C16:1) as an antimicrobial compound in the housefly, *Musca domestica*. *Insect Biochemical Molecules*. 34(1):43-49.
- Morgan, D. (2007). Emergence of antibiotics resistant staphylococcus aureus. *Journal of science*. 6:1-2.
- Murry, P.R., Baron, E.J., Paller, M.A., Tenover, F.C. and Tenover, R.H. (1999). *Manual of clinical microbiology*. 7th Edition. A.S.M. Washington DC, USA.
- Mumcuoglu, K.Y., Miller, J., and Mumcuoglu, M. (2003). Destruction of Bacteria In the digestive tract of maggot of *Lucilia sericata* (*Diptera:Calliphoridae*). *Journal of Medical Entomology*. 38:162-166.
- Ochei.J and Kolhatkar.A. (2009). *Medical Laboratory Science*. Theory and Practical. Tata McGraw-Hill Company Limited. Pp 681-712.
- Okoli, A.S. and Iroegbu, A. (2004). Evaluation of extracts of *Anthodeista djonensis*, *Nauclea latifolia* and *Uvaria atzalii* for activity against bacterial isolates from cases of non – gonococcal urethritis. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 92:135-144.
- O'Toole, G.A. and Kolter, R. (1998). Initiation of biofilm formation in *Pseudomonas fluorescens* WCS365 proceeds via multiple, convergent Signalling pathways. *A Genetic Analysis Molecular Microbiology Journal*. 28:449-461.
- Ourth, D.D. (2004). Antiviral activity against human immunodeficiency virus-1 in vitro by myristoylated-peptide from *Heliothis virescens*. *Biochemistry and Biophysical Research Journal*. 320(1): 190-196.
- Ovuru, K. F., Izah S. C., Yasmin, H., Enerijiofi, K. E., Das, M. and Ogwu, M. C. (2023). Microbial Contaminants of Herbal Remedies: Health Risks and Sustainable Quality Control Strategies. In Izah, S. C., Ogwu, M. C., Akram, M. (eds). *Herbal Medicine Phytochemistry*. Reference Series in Phytochemistry. Springer Nature, Cham. doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21973-3_9-1
- Oyeleke, S.B. and Manga, S.B. (2008). *Essentials of laboratory practical in microbiology*. Tobest publisher, Minna, Nigeria. Pp 36-75.
- Park, C.G., Bang, K.H., Lee, S.E., Cha, M.S., Sung, J.S., Park, H.W. and Seong, N.S. (2001). Antibacterial activity from medicinal plant extracts on the *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Korean Journal of Medical Crop Science*. 9: 251-258.
- Parnes, A., Cho, C.R., Park, B.S., Yoon, K.J. and Lagan, K.M. (2007). Larval therapy in wound management: A review. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*. 61 (3):488-493.
- Pavillard, E. (2007). An Antibiotic from Maggots. *Nature Journal*. 180:916-917.
- Raeames, M.K., Christensen, C. and Luce, E.A. (2008). The use of Maggots in

wound debridement. *Analysis of plastic Surgery Journal*. 21(4):388-391.

Ren, Q., Zhao, X.F. and Wang, J.X. (2009). Molecular characterization and expression analysis of a chicken-type lysozyme gene from housefly

(*Musca domestica*). *Journal Genetic Genome*. 36(1): 7-16.

Resh, M.D. (2009). Fatty acylation of proteins: new insights into membrane targeting of myristoylated and palmitoylated proteins.

Biochemistry Biophysics Journal. 1451(1): 1-16.

Rojas, S.T., Smith, A.G., Finter, W.F., Eagland, D., Vowden, K., Vowden, P.,

Telford, G., Brown, A. and Pritchard, D. (2006). Recombinant *Lucilia*

sericata chymotrypsin in a topical hydrogel formulation degrades human

wound eschar ex vivo. *Biotechnology Journal*. 27:870-874.

Sanders, K. and Sanders, T. (1992). *The Future of Wound Healing*. In: Leaper,

D.J., Harding K.J. Wounds: Biology and Management. Oxford:

University Press: Oxford. Pp 191.

Sargison, N. (2008). *The Management of Ectoparasitic Disease of UK*

sheep. World Veterinary congress. Royal (Dick) School of Veterinary

Studies. Easter Bush Veterinary Center. Roshin, Midlothian, Scotland. Pp 50.

Scavee, V., Polls, X. and Schoevaerdt, J. (2007). Maggot therapy: Many Hands

Make Light World. Archived from the Origin. *Journal of Efficacy of*

Maggot. 22:1-2.

Shakibaie, M.R., Jalilzadeh, K.A. and Yamakanamardi, S.M. (2009). Horizontal

transfer of antibiotic resistance gene among gram negative bacteria in

sewage and lake water and influence of some physico-chemical parameters

of water on conjugation process. *Journal of Environmental Biology*. 30:45

-49

Sherman, R.A. and Pechter, E.A. (2008). Maggot therapy: a review of the

therapeutic applications of fly larvae in human medicine, especially for treating osteomyelitis. *Medical Veterinary Entomology*. 2:225-230.

Sherman, R.A., Hall, M.J.R. and Thomas, S. (2007). Medicinal Maggot: An

ancient remedy for some contemporary affliction. *Journal of Annual*

Review in Estomology. 45:55-81.

Sherman, R.A., Wyle, F. and Vulpe, M. (2006). Maggot debridement therapy

For treating pressure ulcers in spinal cord injury patients. *Journal of Spinal*

Cord Medication. 18:4-17.

Sherman, R.A. (2005). Maggot therapy takes us back to the future of wound

care: New and improved maggot therapy for the 21st century. *Journal*

of Diabetes Science Technology. 3: 336-344.

Sherman, R.A., Vulpe, M. and Shimoda K.J. (2003). Presurgical maggot

debridement of soft tissue wounds is associated with decreased rates of

postoperative infection. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 39: 1067-70

Sherman, R.A. (2003). Maggot therapy for treating diabetic foot ulcer

unresponsive to conventional therapy. *Journal of Diabetic Care*. 14:97

-101.

Steenvoorde, P. and Jukema, G.N. (2007). A Review: The antimicrobial

activities of maggots: in-vivo results. *Journal of Tissue Viability*. 14:97-101.

Steenvoorde, P. and Jukema, G. N. 2004. The antimicrobial activity of maggots:

in-vivo results. *Journal of Tissue Viability*. 14:97-101.

Steenvoorde, P., Jacobi, C.E., van Doorn, L. and Oskam, J. (2004). Maggot

debridement therapy of infected ulcers: patient and wound factors

influencing outcome - a study on 101 patients with 117 wounds. *Annual*

Review of Collective Surgery in England. 89:596-602.

Stephan, T. (2009). The anti-microbial activity of Maggot secretion. *Results of a*

Preliminary Study Journal. 2:1-3.

- Stubbings, W.J., Bostock, J. M., Ingham, E. and Chopra. I. (2004). Assessment of a microplate method for determining the post-antibiotic effect in *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*. 54:139-143.
- Suchi, A., Lim, C.S. and Carl, B. (2010). Antibacterial activity of *Lucilia cuprina* maggot extracts and its extraction techniques. *International Journal of Integrative Biology, A Journal of Biology Beyond Borders*. 9 (1):44.
- Szalanski, A.L., Owen, C.B., McKay, T. and Steelman, C.D. (2004). Detection of *Campylobacter* and *Escherichia coli* O157: H7 from filth flies by polymerase chain reaction. *Medical and Entomology Journal*. 18 (3): 241-246.
- Tanyuksel, A., Araz, E., Dundar, K., Uzun, G., Gumus, T., Alten, B., Saylam, F., Taylan-Ozkan, A. and Mumcuoglu, K.Y. (2005) Maggot debridement therapy in the treatment of chronic wounds in a military hospital setup in Turkey. *Dermatology*. 210:115-118.
- Tarone, A.M. and Foran, D.R. (2008). U.S.National library of medicine.Public medicine.Generalized additive models and *Lucilia sericata* growth. *Accessing confidence interval and errors rate in forensic entomology Journal*. 16:1-4.
- Thomas, S., Andrews, A.M., Hay, N.P. and Bourgoise, S. (2009). The antimicrobial activity of maggot secretions: Results of preliminary study. *Journal of tissue viability*. 9:127-132.
- Toroglu, S., Toroglu, E., Dincer, S., Kara, C. and Kertmen, M. (2009). Resistances of antibiotics and heavy metals in *Enterobacteriaceae* spp.Isolated From Gill and Intestines of *Achanthobrama Marmid* (Heckel, 1843). *Sir Dam Lake Turkey Journal Environmental Biology*. 30:23-31.
- Toroglu, E. and Toroglu, S. (2009). Microbial pollution of water in Golbasi Lake In Adiyaman. *Turkish Journal of Environmental Biology*. 30:33-38.
- Toroglu, S., Dincer, S. and Korkmaz, H. (2005). Antibiotic resistance in gram negative bacteria isolated from Aksu river in (Kahramanmaraş) Turkey. *Annual Microbiology Journal*. 55:229-233.
- Usman, H., Abdulrahman F.F. and Ladaman, A.H. (2007). Phytochemical and antimicrobial evaluation of *Tribulus terrestris* L (*Zygophyllaceae*) growing in Nigeria. *Research journal in biological science. Medwell journal*. 2(3): 244-247.
- Vercruysse, L., Smagghe, G., Herregods, G. and Cam, J.V. (2005). ACE inhibitory activity in enzymatic hydrolysates of insect protein. *Journal Agricultural Food Chemistry*. 53:5207-5211.
- Vistnes, L.M., Lee, R. and Ksander, G.A. (1981). Proteolytic activity of blowfly Larvae secretions in experimental burns. *Journal of Surgery*. 90:835-841.
- Vistues, A.K., Lemos, F.J.A., Ribeiro, A.F. and Terra, W.R. (2007). A bacteria digesting midgutlysozyme from *Musca domestica* (diptera) larvae. Purification, properties and secretory mechanism. *Insect Biochemical Molecules*. 23(4):533-541.
- Vollekora, A., Kost'alara, D. and Sochorova, R. (2001) *Microbiology journal*. 46:107-111.
- Wainwright, M. (2003). *Miracle cure:The story of penicillin and the golden age of antibiotics*. Oxford: Basil Black well. Pp 3.
- Wang, J.X., Zhao, X.F., Liang, Y.L., Li, L., Zhang, W., Ren, Q., Wang, L.C. and Wang, L.Y. (2012). Molecular characterization and expression of the antimicrobial peptide defensin from the housefly (*Musca domestica*). *Cell Molecular Life Science*. 63(24): 3072-3082.
- Wang,Y.C and Sun, D.X. (2006). The assay of composition and physicochemical characteristics of antibacterial matters from house fly

- larva. *Acta Microbiology Journal*. 37:148-153.
- Wang, F.R., Ai, H., Lei, C.L. and Huang, W. (2006). Antiviral activity of the homogenate of *Musca domestica* larvae. *Chinese Journal Entomology*. 43(1): 82-85.
- Wary, Y. and Sun, N. (2007). A rapid and systematic review of the clinical effectiveness and cost effectiveness of debriding agents in treating surgical wounds healing by secondary intention. *Health Technology Assesment*. 5:1-131.
- Whitaker, I.S., Twine, C., Whitaker, M.J., Welck, M., Brown, C.S. and Shandall, A. (2007). Larval therapy from antiquity to the present day: Mechanising of action, chemical applications and future potential. *Postgraduate Medical Journal*. 83:409-413.
- Wollina, U. (2003). Biosurgery in wound healing- the renaissance of maggot therapy. *Journal of European Academic Dermatology*. 6:1-7.
- Wollina, U., Liebold, K., Schmidt, W., Hartmann, M. and Fassler, D. (2003). Biosurgery supports granulation and debridement in chronic wounds- clinical data and remittance spectroscopy measurement. *International Journal of dermatology*. 41:635-639.
- Woodworth, B.A., Tamashiro, E, Bhargave, G, Cohen, N.A and Palmer, J.N. (2008). An in vitro model of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* biofilms on viable airway epithelial cell monolayers. *American Journal of Rhinology*. 22:235-238.
- Wyllie, D., Crook, D. and Peto, T. (2006). Mortality after *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteraemia in two hospitals in Oxfordshire, cohort study. *Biomedical Journal*. 3:281-284.
- Xu, X.X., Jin, F.L., Yu, X.Q., Ji, S.X., Wang, J., Cheng, H.X., Wang, C. and Zhang W.Q. (2007). Expression and purification of a recombinant antibacterial peptide, cecropin, from *Escherichia coli*. *Protein Expression and Purification*. 53(2):293-301.
- Yasuda, T. (1997). Chemical cues from *Spodoptera litura* larvae elicit prey locating behavior by the predatory stink bug, *Eocanthecona furcellata*. *Entomologia Experimentalis Journal*. 82:349-354.
- Yoon, K.J., Park, B.S., Jang, A., Cho, C.R., Lee, S.K., Lee, K.S., Kim M.H. and Kim, H.T. (2008). Separation methods of low molecular size peptide and ethanol extract with anti-MRSA activity from *Musca domestica*. *Korean Patient Journal*. 2:10-11.
- Zy, D., Ito, Y., Nakamura, M., Hotani, T. and Imoto, T. (2005). Insect lysozyme from housefly (*Musca domestica*) larvae: Possible digestive function based on sequence and enzymatic properties. *Journal of Biochemistry*. 118(3): 546-551.
- www.healthaffairs.uci.edu (2013)
- www.hta.ac.uk (2013)
- www.monarchlabs.com (2013)
- www.nhm.ac.uk (2013)
- <http://www.rafidaindentj.net/www.rafidaindentj.net> (2012)
- www.springerlink.com (2013)
- www.usatoday.com (2013)
- www.zoobiotic.org (2013)

Sodium Selenite Ameliorates the Effects of Sodium Arsenite on Some Biomolecules and Enzymes of Energy Metabolism in the Testes of Albino Rats

Babayemi, D. O.¹, Akinhanmi, T. F.², Onunkwor, B. O.¹, Ozeomena, H. O.³, Adeleke, M. A.¹, Akanni, O. I.¹, Keyede, O. O.¹, Michael, M. O.¹, Idhove, F. E.¹, Mukaila, S. A.¹, & Ademuyiwa, O.¹

¹Department of Biochemistry, College of Biosciences, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

²Department of Chemistry, College of Physical Sciences, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

³Department of Chemical Sciences, College of Natural Sciences, Bells University of Technology, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: babayemido@funaab.edu.ng; +2348036869692

Abstract: Heavy metal exposure is becoming more common in our contemporary society as a result of its widespread availability and use. Arsenic is a well-known example of heavy metal that can harm live creatures' reproductive system and biochemical pathways. Twenty-four male Albino rats were randomly divided into four groups (n = 6) and exposed to sodium arsenite (SA) and sodium selenite (SS) for 5 weeks to investigate the ameliorative role of sodium selenite on sodium arsenite-induced testicular toxicity on some biomolecules and enzymes of energy metabolism. Group I (control) received just distilled water, whereas groups II and III were given 40 ppm SA in drinking water *ad libitum*; additionally, group III received 0.25 mg/kg bwt SS orally, while group IV received 0.25 mg/kg bwt SS orally only. Significant increases (p < 0.05) in xanthine oxidase, aldolase, lactate dehydrogenase and aspartate aminotransferase activities, and nitric oxide and hydrogen sulphide levels were observed in the SA-exposed group (group II), while hexokinase and -ketoglutarate dehydrogenase activities decreased significantly. Sodium selenite treatment ameliorated the apparent effects of SA exposure, as seen in groups III and IV. This study supports the use of SS as a safe therapy for SA-induced testicular toxicity.

Key Words: heavy metal exposure, selenium, reproductive organs, biomolecules, energy metabolism

1 INTRODUCTION

Heavy metal exposure is becoming more common in our contemporary society as a result of its widespread availability and use. Arsenic is a well-known example of heavy metal that can harm live creatures' reproductive system and biochemical pathways. Arsenic exists in both inorganic and organic forms (Matschullat, 2000) and with varying oxidation numbers in nature (Afolabi *et al.*, 2015). The inorganic forms are predominantly present in water, food, soil and air. There are reports of arsenic contamination of water bodies in both urban and rural settings around the world (Ahoule *et al.*, 2015). Acute and chronic exposures to inorganic arsenic compounds result in multi-organ damages and perturbations in biological pathways (Gwaltney-

Brant, 2013).

Selenium is an essential micro-element that affects numerous physiological activities in both animals and plants. In trace amount, it is a good antioxidant with anticancer and anti-mutagenic properties; and improves reproductive system and developmental activities (Hariharan & Dharmaraj, 2020; Mojapelo & Lehloenya, 2019). Selenium exists in two forms: organic and inorganic. One of the most common inorganic forms is sodium selenite (SS), used for its dietary potential as a food supplement (Arshad *et al.*, 2021). Selenium has been reported to alter the toxic potential of heavy metals by interacting with them at their primary sites of action, and it can alter the way the body responds to noxious substances by altering their metabolism and transport (Rahman *et al.*, 2019).

In order to find a safer treatment for arsenic-

induced testicular toxicity, SS was employed due to its antioxidant and chemo-protective properties. This current study aims to investigate the ameliorative roles of SS on sodium arsenite-induced testicular damage in male Albino rats.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals

Sodium arsenite (a source of arsenic, SA) and sodium selenite (a source of selenium, SS) were products of Sigma-Aldrich, Missouri, USA. All other chemicals and reagents used are of analytical grade.

Experimental Animal and Design

A total of 24 adult male albino rats (weight: $211 \text{ g} \pm 23$) were randomly selected into four groups. These were housed in plastic cages with good ventilation and fed *ad libitum* with rat chow. The protocols of this study were approved by the Animal Ethical Committee of the Department of Biochemistry, College of Biosciences, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State. After initial acclimatization of the animals for two weeks, the animals were exposed to SA and treated with SS. Group I (control) received distilled water; groups II and III were given 40 ppm SA in drinking water *ad libitum*; additionally, group III received 0.25 mg/kg bwt SS orally, while group IV received 0.25 mg/kg bwt SS orally only. The SS dose utilized in this study was previously published by Aslanturk et al. (2014). The experiment lasted five weeks.

Animal Sacrifice

The animals were sacrificed a day after the treatment had ended, following an overnight fast. All materials were stored at a temperature of around 4°C . The rats were anesthetized with phenobarbital, and the testes were excised using a dissecting kit. The organs were transferred into a chilled saline solution. The rinsed organs were mopped with filter paper and weighed with an analytical balance. A 10% homogenate solution of the organ was prepared with Sucrose-Tris-EDTA buffer (containing 0.25 M, 10 mM Tris, and 0.05 mM EDTA, pH 7.4). The mitochondrial fraction (pellet) of the homogenate was obtained after centrifugation at 12,000 rpm for 3 minutes at 4°C . The supernatant was decanted, and the pellet reconstituted with 1 ml of the buffer (Mela & Seitz, 1979). This was used for the biochemical assay.

Biochemical Assays

Estimation of Testicular Hydrogen Sulphide and Nitric Oxide Levels

Hydrogen sulphide was assayed according to the protocol of Zhu et al. (2007), while nitric oxide levels were assayed according to the protocol of Tsikas (2005).

Determination of Testicular Xanthine Oxidase Activity

The assay for xanthine oxidase activity followed the protocol of Bergmeyer et al. (1974).

Determination of Testicular Aldolase Activity

The assay for aldolase activity followed the protocol of Jagannathan et al. (1956).

Determination of Testicular Lactate Dehydrogenase Activity

The assay for lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity followed the protocol of Borgmann et al. (1974).

Determination of Testicular Aspartate Aminotransferase Activity

Aspartate aminotransferase activity was assayed according to the protocol of Reitman and Frankel (1957).

Determination of Testicular Glutamate Dehydrogenase Activity

Testicular glutamate dehydrogenase (GLDH) activity was assayed according to the protocol of Srasketa et al. (2014).

Protein Determination in the Testes

The protein concentration was determined using the Biuret method. This was used to determine the specific enzyme activity.

Statistical Analysis

The results are shown as the mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM). To assess group homogeneity, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. If there was heterogeneity, the Duncan test was used to divide the groups. A *p*-value of ≤ 0.05 indicated statistical significance. All analyses were carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 24.

2 Results

The table below shows the physical characteristics of the maggot extract in the three different solvents

(aqueous, saline water, and PBS) used in this study.

Table 1: Physical Characteristics of the Maggot Extract

Maggot Parts	Solvent	Weight of Maggot (g/g)	% Yield	Colour	Odour	Texture
Whole Maggot	Aqueous	0.4	30%	Yellow	Unpleasant	Oily
Whole Maggot	Saline Water	0.4	30%	Yellow	Unpleasant	Oily
Whole Maggot	PBS	0.4	10%	Yellow	Unpleasant	Oily

Table 2: Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm) of the Aqueous Extract on Organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	15±0.0	19±0.0	22±0.0	23±0.0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	14±0.0	15±0.0	17±0.0	20±0.0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	20±0.0	22±0.0	24±0.0	26±0.0

This table shows the zone diameter of inhibition for test organisms at different concentrations of the aqueous extract.

Figure 1: Bar chart representing the efficacy of different concentrations in mg/ml (aqueous) against tested organisms.

Figure 2: Stacked line with markers chart representing the rate of efficacy of aqueous extract against the tested organisms.

Table 3: Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm) of the Saline Water Extract on Test Organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	15±0.0	19±0.0	22±0.0	23±0.0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	14±0.0	15±0.0	17±0.0	20±0.0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	20±0.0	22±0.0	24±0.0	26±0.0

This table shows the zone diameter of inhibition for test organisms at different concentrations of the saline water extract.

Figure 3: Bar chart representing the efficacy of different concentrations in mg/ml (saline water) against tested organisms.

Table 4: Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm) of the PBS Extract on Test Organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	7.0±0.0	10±0.0	12±0.0	15±0.0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	12±0.0	14±0.0	15±0.0	17±0.0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	14±0.0	16±0.0	19±0.0	20±0.0

This table shows the zone diameter of inhibition for test organisms at different concentrations of the PBS extract.

Figure 5: Bar chart representing the efficacy of different concentrations in mg/ml (PBS) against tested organisms.

Figure 4: Stacked line with markers chart representing the rate of efficacy of saline water extract against the tested organisms.

Figure 6: Stacked line with markers chart representing the rate of efficacy of PBS extract against the tested organisms.

Table 5: Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm) of the Control Antibiotic on Test Organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)				
	50	100	200	250	500
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	26	31	32	36	38
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	26	27	34	35	36
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	29	30	31	33	34

Table 6: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of Aqueous Extracts on Test Organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	2.7	2.7	2.7	3.6
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	2.7	2.7	2.7	3.6
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	1.8	1.8	1.8	3.6

Table 7: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of Saline Water Extracts on Test Organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	2.7	2.7	2.7	3.6
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	2.7	2.7	2.7	3.6
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	2.7	2.7	2.7	3.6

Table 8: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of PBS Extracts on Test Organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	2.7	2.7	2.7	3.6
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	2.7	2.7	2.7	3.6
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	2.7	2.7	2.7	3.6

Table 9: Effect of Extracts on Body Mass Index (BMI) of Test Animals

Group	Before Treatment (BMI)	After Treatment (BMI)	Change (BMI)
Control	23.5±0.0	23.6±0.0	+0.1±0.0
Aqueous Extract	23.4±0.0	23.7±0.0	+0.3±0.0
Saline Water Extract	23.5±0.0	23.8±0.0	+0.3±0.0
PBS Extract	23.5±0.0	23.6±0.0	+0.1±0.0

This table shows the effect of different extracts on the BMI of test animals before and after treatment.

3 Discussion

A total yield of 30% soluble excretion/secretion was obtained for the aqueous, saline water, and Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS) extracts from the original weight of 0.4g/g of the whole maggot of *Lucilia sericata* and *Musca domestica*. The physical characteristics are indicated in Table ???. Tables ??? to ??? show the results of the antibacterial pattern of the extracts against the test organisms. The results obtained from this study showed a dose-dependent activity of *L. sericata* and

M. domestica maggot or larva extract (aqueous, saline water, and PBS) at tested doses (0.9, 1.8, 2.7, and 3.6 mg/ml) on the test organisms (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*). Maggot excretion/secretions located in their mid-gut contained protein or antibacterial peptide according to Ai et al. (2008, 2012), Hon et al. (2007), and Cao et al. (2011) who all extracted chitosan, HF-1 (a novel antibacterial peptide), and lectin, respectively.

The bar chart, stacked line with markers chart, and pie chart show the efficacy of the different concentrations in mg/ml (0.9, 1.8, 2.7, and 3.6 mg/ml) compared to each other, the efficacy of extracts (aqueous, saline water, and PBS) against the tested organisms, and the growth level of tested organisms (*E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus*) compared to each other, respectively.

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the aqueous maggot extract against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* were all 1.8 mg/ml as shown in Table ???. The MIC of the saline water maggot extract against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* were both 3.6 mg/ml, while *S. aureus* was 1.8 mg/ml as shown in Table ???. The MIC of the PBS maggot extract against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* were both 3.6 mg/ml, while there was no MIC against *E. coli* as shown in Table ???

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of the aqueous maggot extract against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* were both 3.6 mg/ml, while *S. aureus* was 2.7 mg/ml as shown in Table ???. The MBC of the saline water maggot extract against *S. aureus* is 3.6 mg/ml, while there is no MBC for both *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* as shown in Table ???. There is no MBC of the PBS maggot extract against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* as shown in Table ???

The largest zone of inhibition was obtained with the aqueous extract against *S. aureus*, and the lowest was obtained with the PBS extract against *E. coli*. The highest MIC was obtained with the aqueous extract on *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* (1.8 mg/ml), while the lowest MIC was obtained with PBS on *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*, with no MIC on *E. coli* with PBS. The highest MBC was obtained with the aqueous extract on *S. aureus* (2.7 mg/ml), and the lowest MBC was obtained with saline water on *S. aureus* (3.6 mg/ml), but there was no MBC obtained from PBS. It is evident from the result of this study that *S. aureus* was more susceptible to the maggot extract compared to *E. coli*, which showed the highest

resistance, and *P. aeruginosa*. The results of this study agree with several literature reports (Meylaers et al., 2004; Liang et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2006; Jin et al., 2006; Cancado et al., 2007; Xu et al., 2007; Hou et al., 2007; Ai et al., 2008, 2012; Ren et al., 2009; Cao et al., 2011; Yoon et al., 2008; Jang et al., 2007; Suchi et al., 2010) in which maggot extract was found to possess significant antimicrobial activities against several pathogens, especially *S. aureus*. In general, the low activity of the PBS extract on tested organisms might be due to the actions of different elements/components that might have denatured the protein constituents of the maggot extract, as observed in aqueous extract that had the highest activity on tested organisms since it contained nothing but 2 molecules of hydrogen and 1 molecule of oxygen.

4 Recommendation

It is recommended that while extracting excretions/secretions from maggots, a neutral solvent or sterile water should be used to obtain the extract in its natural form. The use of maggot extract is currently not available in Nigeria; this can be improved or encouraged by health workers or the Ministry of Health as it serves as a good and inexpensive alternative to antibiotics.

5 Conclusion

From the study, it can be concluded that aqueous extract is more efficient than other maggot extracts obtained from any other solvent and should be used to obtain maggot extract. These studies, therefore, offer a scientific basis for the clinical or traditional use of maggot extract or whole maggot for therapy, especially infections by *S. aureus*, which is sensitive to maggot extract.

6 Conflict of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest. The study was conducted impartially and without bias.

References

Abu-Shanab, B., Adwa, G., Jarrar, N., Abu-Hijli, A. and Adwan, K. (2006).

Antibacterial activity of four plant extracts used in Palestine in folkloric

medicine against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Turkish*

Journal of Biological Science. 30:195-198.

Adesina, I. A., Adebote, V.T., Elehinafe, T. R.

and Enerijiofi, K. E. (2013). Growth

inhibition of *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium italicum* by seed kernel oil from Mango (*Magnifera indica L.*). *Journal of Natural Sciences Research*, 3(9): 61-64.

Ahmed, S.E. and Nancy, T. (2012). Molecular Characterization of Serine

Proteases from both First and Third Larval Instars of *Chrysomya*

Megacephala. *Life Science Journal*. 9 (3):2088.

Ai, H., Wang, F.R., Xia, Y.Q., Chen, X.M. and Lei, C.L. (2012). Antioxidant,

antifungal and antiviral activities of chitosan from the larvae of

housefly, *Musca domestica L.* *Food Chemistry Journal*. 132(1):493

-498.

Ai, H., Wang, F.R., Yang, Q.S., Zhu, F. and Lei, CL. (2008). Preparation and

biological activities of chitosan from the larvae of housefly, *Musca*

domestica. *Carbohydrate Polymerization Journal*. 72(3): 419-423.

Ako-Nai, B., Wysocki, A. B., Kusakabe, A. O., Chang, S. and Tuan, T. L.

(2003). Temporal expression of urokinase plasminogen activator,

Plasminogen activator inhibitor and gelatinase-B in chronic wound fluid

switches from a chronic to acute wound profile with progression to

healing. *Wound Repair Regeneration*.7:154-165.

Akortha, E. E., Aluyi, H. S. A. and Enerijiofi, K.

E. (2010). Plasmid encoded amoxicillin resistance in common bacterial pathogens from patients in University of Benin Hospital, Benin City, South Western Nigeria *Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*, 1(10): 478-484.

Al-Bari, Q., Nablo, B.J., Prichard, H.L., Butler, R.D., Klitzman, B. and

Schoenfisch, M.H. (2006). Inhibition of implant-associated infections via

nitric oxide release. *Biomaterials Journal*. 26:6984-6990.

- Amster, D. (2006). Susceptibility testing of antimicrobial media. *Antibiotics in Laboratory medicine*. 4th Edition. Williams and Wilkins, MD, USA. Pp 52 - 111.
- An, C., Li, D. and Du, R. (2004). Analysis of antibacterial-related proteins and peptides in housefly larvae. *Journal of Hygiene Research*. 33:86-88.
- Andersen, A., Joergensen, B., Karlsmark, T., van der Plas, M.J.A. and Krogh, K. A. (2008). *Novel Lipase Activity detected in induced Lucilia Sericata excretions/secretions*. 18th Edition. European Tissue Repair Society Meeting, Malta. Pp 60-70.
- Angela, L. (2007). *Maggots and chips: A novel approach to the treatment of Diabetic ulcers*. Pp 2-4.
- Aqil, F., Khan, M. S. A., Owais, M. and Ahmad, I. (2005). Effect of certain bioactive plant extracts on clinical isolates of -lactamase producing methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Journal of Basic Microbiology*. 45:106-114.
- Bethune, N. (2007). A case of chronic thoracic empyema treated with maggot. *Canadian Medical Association Journal*. 32:301-301.
- Bexfield, A., Nigam, Y., Thomas, S. and Rafcliffe, N.A. (2004). *Detection and partial characterisation of two antibacterial factors from the excretions / secretion of the medicinal maggot Lucilia sericata and their activity against methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA)*. *Microbes infection*. Pp 6.
- Bishop, D. (2009). Variation in numbers of occipital setae for two species of *Lucilia* (Diptera: Calliphoridae). *Journal of New Zealand Entomologist*. 14:29-31.
- Bradley, M., Cullum, N. and Sheldon, T. (2009). The debridement of chronic wounds. *Journal of Systematic Review National Institute for Health Research Health Technology Assess*. 3: (1)1-78.
- Brazill, S.M., Steelman, D.C. and Szanlanski, L.A. (2007). Detection of pathogenic DNA from fifth flies (*Diptera muscidae*) using filter paper sport card. *Journal of Agricultural and Urban Entomology*. 24 (1):13 - 18.
- Brian, M.W., Davids, Y.Y., Jeffrey, L.T. and Hirohisa, K. (2011). *A fly's head showing compound eyes and body*. Pp 3.
- Brin, Y.S., Mumcuoglu, K.Y., Massarwe, S., Wigelman, M., Gross, E. and Nyska, M. (2007). Chronic foot ulcer management using maggot debridement and topical negative pressure therapy. *Journal of Wound Care*. 16:1-2.
- Cai, H., Choi, S.I., Lee, Y.M. and Heo, T.R. (2002). Antimicrobial effects of herbal medicine extracts *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* O157:H7. *Korean Journal of Biotechnology and Bioengineering*. 17:537-542.
- Cançado, F.C., Valério, A.A., Marana, S.R. and Barbosa, J.A.R.G. (2007). The Crystal structure of a lysozyme c from housefly *Musca domestica*, the first Structure of a digestive lysozyme. *Journal of Structural Biology*. 160(1): 83-92.
- Cao, X.H., Zhou, M.H., Wang, C.L., Hou, L.H. and Zeng, B. (2011). Lectin Purified from *Musca domestica* pupa up-regulates NO and iNOS Production via TLR4/NF-B signaling pathway in macrophages. *International Journal of Immunopharmacology*. 11(4): 399-405.
- Cazander, G., Vanveen, K.E.B., Bouwman, L.H., Bernards, A.T. and Jukeman, G.N. (2009). The influence of maggot excretions on PAO1 biofilm formation on different biomaterials. *A Clinical Orthopaedic Related Research Journal*. 46 (2):536-545.
- Centinkaya, M., Meredith, D.O., Eschbach, L. and Richards, R.G (2007). Neo natal myiasis: a Case study. *Turkish Journal of paediatrics*. 50:581-584.

Chan DC, Fong DH, Leung JY, Patil NG, Leung GK. (2007)

Maggot Debridement therapy in chronic wound care. *Hong Kong Medical Journal*. 13(5):382-386.

Chain. E, Florey HW, Gardner AD, Heatley HG, Jenning MA. (2003). *Orr Ewing Journal*. Penicillin as a chemotherapeutic agent. 2:226-228.

Chandler, P.J. (2006). Checklist of insects of the British Isles (New Series) Part

1: Diptera. *Handbooks for the Identification of British Insects (London Royal Entomological Society of London)*. 12 (1):1-234.

Cheesbrough, M. (2005). *Laboratory manual for tropical countries*. Pp 8.

Cheesbrough, M. (2000). *District laboratory practice in Tropical countries*. 2nd edition. Cambridge university printing press. Pp 305-307.

Chen, Y. and Li, J.F. (2003). The study of anti-virus activity of *Musca domestica* larva homogenate. *Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 4(2): 130-132.

Chen, W. Y. and Rogers, A. A. (2007). Recent insights into the causes of

Chronic leg ulceration in venous diseases and implications on other types of chronic wounds. *Journal of Wound Repair Regeneration*. 15:434-449.

Chernysh, S., Kim, S.I., Bekker, G., Pleskach, V.A., Filatova, N.A.,

Anikin, V.B, Platnov, V.G. and Bulet, P. (2002). Antiviral and antitumor peptides from Insect. *Journal of Microbiology*. 3:2-3.

Choi, J.H., Yu, M.H., Hwang, E.Y. and Lee, I.S. (2009). Effect of *Rosmarinus*

officinalis L. fractions on antimicrobial activity against methicillin

resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and resistant genes regulation.

Journal of Korean Social Food Science Nutrition. 38:541-547.

Cosgrove, A., Weil, G., R. Simon, and Sweadner WR. (2003). A biological,

bacteriological and clinical study of larval or maggot therapy in the

treatment of acute and chronic pyogenic infections. *American Journal of Surgery*. 19:36-48.

Cosgrove, S.E., Qi, Y., Kaye, K.S., Harbarth, S., Karchmer A.W. and

Carmeli, Y. (2005). The impact of methicillin resistance in

Staphylococcus aureus bacteremia on patient outcomes: Mortality, length

of stay, and hospital charges. *Journal of Infection Control in Hospital*

Epidemiology. 26:166-174.

DeBartolo, A. (2006). Buzz off! The housefly has made a pest of himself for 25 million years. PMD 11902690.

Dibner, J.J. and Richards, J.D. (2005). Antibiotic growth promoters in

agriculture: History and mode of action. *Journal of Poultry*

Science. 84:634-643.

Dissemond, J., Zollner, T. M., Veraart, J. C., Wolter, M., Hesse, S., Villemur, B., Wenke, A., Werner, R. J., Boehncke, W. H., Jost, S. S., Scharrer, I. and Kaufmann, R. (2003). Leg ulcers in Klinefelter's syndrome - further evidence for an involvement of plasminogen activator inhibitor-1. *British Journal of Dermatology*. 136:341-344.

Dissemond, J., Koppermann, M., Esser, S., Schultewolter, T., Goos, M. and

Wagner, S.N. (2002). Treatment of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) as part of biosurgical management of a chronic leg ulcer.

Hautarzt Journal of Chronic Ulcer. 53 (9):608-1.

Dubendorfer, A. (2003). *Musca domestica*, a window on the evolution of sex

determining mechanisms in insects. *International Journal of Developmental*

Biology. 46 (1):75-79.

Dunville, J.C., Worthy, G., Bland, J.M., Cullum, N., Dowson, C., and

Iglesias, C. (2009). Larval therapy for leg ulcers (Venlls II): Randomised

controlled trial. *Biomedical Journal*. 33:773.

Enerijiofi, K. E. and Isola, O. B. (2019).

Preliminary Phytochemical screening and *invitro* antibacterial activities of aqueous and ethanol

- extracts of *Ageratum conyzoides* L. Leaf, Stem, Flower and Root on some Bacterial isolates associated with Diarrhoea. *Nigerian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 32 (2): 3480-3489 <http://dx.doi.org/10.19240/njpas.2019.B09><http://dx.doi.org/10.19240/njpas.2019.B09>
- Fernandez, H., Dobrovolsky, A. B. and Titaeva E.V. (2003). The fibrinolysis system: regulation of activity and physiologic functions of its main components. *Biochemistry Journal* (Mosc.) 67:99-108.
- Fleischmann, W., Grassberger, M., Sherman, R. (2004). Maggot Therapy. A *Handbook of Maggot- Assisted Wound Healing*. Stuttgart, George Thieme. 14:6-9.
- Fleischmann, W., Joergensen, B., Karlsmark, T., van der Plas, M. J. A. and Krogfelt, K.A. (2003). *Activity detected in induced Musca domestica* excretions/secretions. 6th Edition. European Tissue Repair Society Meeting, Malta. Pp 1-2.
- Fredenburgh, J. C. and Nesheim, M. E. (1992). Lys-plasminogen is a significant intermediate in the activation of Glu-plasminogen during fibrinolysis *in vitro*. *Journal Biological Chemistry*. 267:26150-26156.
- Geo.F.B., Karen.C.C., Butel.S.J., and Stephen.A.M. (2010). In: *Jawetz, Melnick and Adelberg's Medical Microbiology*. 28th International Edition. Mc Graw Hill Lange. Pp 145-148.
- Greco, K.N., Mendonça, R.M.Z., Moraes, R.H.P., Mancini, D.A.P. and Mendonça, R.Z. (2009). Antiviral activity of the hemolymph of *Lonomia oblique* (Lepidoptera: Saturniidae). *Antiviral Research*. 84(1): 84-90.
- Hanln, G. (2007). *Bacteriophage Therapy*. Microbiologist: The Magazine of the Society for Applied Microbiology. 1-56.
- Harris, L.G. (2007). *Staphylococcus aureus* adhesion to standard micro-rough and electropolished implant materials. *Journal of Mater Science and Mater Medicine*. 18:1151-1156.
- Heuer, H. and Heuer, L. (2011). Blowfly strike and Maggot Therapy. *Parasitology to Medical Treatment Parasitology Research Journal*. 1:301-
- Horobin, A.J., Shakeshef, K.M. and Pritchard, D.I. (2005). *Maggots and wound Healing Journal*. An investigation of the effects of secretions from *Lucilia sericata* larvae upon the migration of human dermal fibroblast over a fibronectin coated surface. 13:422-433.
- Hou, L., Shia, Y., Zhaia, P. and Le, G. (2007). Antibacterial activity and in vitro antitumor activity of the extract of larva of the housefly (*Musca domestica*). *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 3:227-231.
- Huberman, L., Mumcuoglu, K.Y., Gollop, N. and Galun, R. (2003). *Antibacterial substances excreted by the maggot of the green bottle fly, Lucilia sericata*. 6th International Conference on Biotherapy, Cumhuriyet University, Sivas, Turkey. Pp 27-28.
- Hwangbo, J., Hong, E.C., Jang, A., Kang, H.K., Oh, J.S., Kim, B.W. and Park, B.S. (2009). Utilization of house fly-maggots, a feed supplement in the production of broiler chickens. *Journal of Environmental Biology*. 30:609-614.
- Jackil, D., Lapanje, A., Zupani1, K., Smrke, D. and Gunde-Cimerman, N. (2008). Selective antimicrobial activity of maggot against pathogenic bacteria. *Journal of Medical Microbiology*. 57:617-625.
- Jang, A. (2007). *Seperation of antibacterial low molecular peptides from Musca domesica maggot against methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) and vancomycin resistant enterococcus (VRE)*. International Symposium and Annual Meeting. The Korean Society of Food Science and Nutrition. Pp 275.
- Jarvis, K. (2003). Degradation of extracellular matrix components by defined

- proteinases from the greenbottle larva *Lucilia sericata* used for the clinical debridement of non-healing wounds. *British Journal of Dermatology* 148:14-23.
- Jin, F.L., Xu, X.X., Zhang, W.Q. and Gu, D.X. (2006). Expression and characterization of a housefly cecropin gene in the methylotrophic yeast, *Pichia pastoris*. *Protein Expression Purification*. 49(1): 39-46.
- Jones, T.F., Kellum, M.E., Porter, S.S., Bell, M. and Schaffner, W. (2002). An outbreak of community-acquired food borne illness caused by methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Emergence Infectious Disease Journal*. 8:82-84.
- Jones T.F., Kellum, M.E., Porter, S.S., Bell, M. and Schaffner, W. (2003). Bacterial biofilm: from the natural environment to infectious diseases. *National Revised Microbiology*.2:95-108.
- Jones M. (2003). An overview of maggot therapy used on chronic wounds in the community. *British Journal of Community Nursing*. 14:14-18
- Jones,G. and Wall,G. (2008). Research in veterinary science Maggot-therapy in veterinaryMedicine. *Journal of Veterinary Medicine*. 85.394-398.
- Jukem,G.N., Klimpel S, Sievert K (2003). The house fly (*Musca domestica*) as a potential vector of metazoan parasites caught in a pig-pen in Germany.*Veterinary Parasitology*. 160 (1-2): 163-167.
- Jukema, G.N., Menon, A.G, Bernards, A.T., Steenvoorde, P., Taheri Rastegar, A. and Van Dissel, J.T. (2002). Amputation-sparing treatment by nature, surgical maggots revisited. *Journal of Clinical Infectious Disease*. 35:1566-1571.
- Kerridge, A., Reed, L.J. and Muench, H. (2004). A simple method of estimating fifty percent endpoints. *American Journal of Hygiene*. 27(3): 493-497.
- Kerridge, A., Lappin-Scott, H. and Stevens, J.R. (2005). Antibacterial properties of larval secretions of the blowfly, *Lucilia sericata*.*Journal of Medical Veterinary Entomology*. 19: 333-337.
- Kristina, O., Xavier, F., Benidicte, M.,Yannick, C., Christian, C., Patrick, C., Anne-Laure, L., Ingrid, S. and Anne, D. (2011). Maggot therapy for wound Debridement. *Journal of Dermatology*.10:10-11.
- Larrain, P. and Salas, C. (2008). Housefly (*Musca domestica* L.) (*Dipteria:Muscidae*) development in different types of manure [*Desarrollo de la Mosca Domestica (Musca domestica* L.) (*Dipteria:Muscidae*)en Distintos tipos de Estercoi]. *Chilean Journal of Agricultural Research*. 68 (2):192-197.
- Larrey, W.R. (2003). Digestion of bacteria and the role of midgut lysozyme in some insect larvae. *Journal Biochemistry Physiology*.100(2): 265-268.
- Lerch, K., Linde, H.J., Lehn, N. and Grifka, J. (2003). Bacteria ingestion by blowfly larvae. *An in vitro study in Dermatology Journal*. 207:362-366.
- Levi, S.B. (1998). The challenge of antibiotic resistance. *Scientific American Journal*. 278:46-53.
- Li, J.F. and Chen, Y. (2006). Explore for antiviral activity of *Musca domestica* larva hemolymph. *Chinese Journal of Zoology*. 22(10): 981-983.
- Liang, Y., Wang, J., Zhao, X., Du, X. and Xue, J. (2006). Molecular cloning and characterization of cecropin from the housefly (*Musca domestica*), and its expression in *Escherichia coli*. *Journal of Developing Comparism in Immunology*. 30:249-257.
- Mascini, E.M., Troelstra, A. and Beitsma, M. (2006). Genotyping and Preemptive isolation to control an outbreak of vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus faecium*. *Journal of Clinical Infectious Disease*. 42:739-746.
- Matyar, F., Dincer, S., Kaya, A. and Colak, O. (2004). Prevalence and

- Resistance to antibiotics in gram negative bacteria isolated from retail fish in Turkey. *Journal of Analytical Microbiology*. 54:151-160.
- McCarthy, L.R., Mickelsen, A.P. and Smith, E.G. (1979). Antibiotic susceptibility of *Haemophilus vaginalis* (*Corynebacterium vaginale*) to 21 antibiotics. *Antimicrobial Agents Chemotherapy Journal*. 16:186-189.
- Meylaers, K., Clynen, E., Daloz, D., DeLoof, A. and Schoofs, L. (2004). Identification of 1-lysophosphatidylethanolamine (C16:1) as an antimicrobial compound in the housefly, *Musca domestica*. *Insect Biochemical Molecules*. 34(1):43-49.
- Morgan, D. (2007). Emergence of antibiotics resistant staphylococcus aureus. *Journal of science*. 6:1-2.
- Murry, P.R., Baron, E.J., Paller, M.A., Tenover, F.C. and Tenover, R.H. (1999). *Manual of clinical microbiology*. 7th Edition. A.S.M. Washington DC, USA.
- Mumcuoglu, K.Y., Miller, J., and Mumcuoglu, M. (2003). Destruction of Bacteria In the digestive tract of maggot of *Lucilia sericata* (*Diptera:Calliphoridae*). *Journal of Medical Entomology*. 38:162-166.
- Ochei, J. and Kolhatkar, A. (2009). *Medical Laboratory Science*. Theory and Practical. Tata McGraw-Hill Company Limited. Pp 681-712.
- Okoli, A.S. and Iroegbu, A. (2004). Evaluation of extracts of *Anthodeista djlonensis*, *Nauclea latifolia* and *Uvaria atzalii* for activity against bacterial isolates from cases of non – gonococcal urethritis. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 92:135-144.
- O'Toole, G.A. and Kolter, R. (1998). Initiation of biofilm formation in *Pseudomonas fluorescens* WCS365 proceeds via multiple, convergent Signalling pathways. *A Genetic Analysis Molecular Microbiology Journal*. 28:449-461.
- Ourth, D.D. (2004). Antiviral activity against human immunodeficiency virus-1 in vitro by myristoylated-peptide from *Heliothis virescens*. *Biochemistry and Biophysical Research Journal*. 320(1): 190-196.
- Ovuru, K. F., Izah S. C., Yasmin, H., Enerijiofi, K. E., Das, M. and Ogwu, M. C. (2023). Microbial Contaminants of Herbal Remedies: Health Risks and Sustainable Quality Control Strategies. In Izah, S. C., Ogwu, M. C., Akram, M. (eds). *Herbal Medicine Phytochemistry*. Reference Series in Phytochemistry. Springer Nature, Cham. doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21973-3_9-1
- Oyeleke, S.B. and Manga, S.B. (2008). *Essentials of laboratory practical in microbiology*. Tobest publisher, Minna, Nigeria. Pp 36-75.
- Park, C.G., Bang, K.H., Lee, S.E., Cha, M.S., Sung, J.S., Park, H.W. and Seong, N.S. (2001). Antibacterial activity from medicinal plant extracts on the *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Korean Journal of Medical Crop Science*. 9: 251-258.
- Parnes, A., Cho, C.R., Park, B.S., Yoon, K.J. and Lagan, K.M. (2007). Larval therapy in wound management: A review. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*. 61 (3):488-493.
- Pavillard, E. (2007). An Antibiotic from Maggots. *Nature Journal*. 180:916-917.
- Raeames, M.K., Christensen, C. and Luce, E.A. (2008). The use of Maggots in wound debridement. *Analysis of plastic Surgery Journal*. 21(4):388-391.
- Ren, Q., Zhao, X.F. and Wang, J.X. (2009). Molecular characterization and expression analysis of a chicken-type lysozyme gene from housefly (*Musca domestica*). *Journal Genetic Genome*. 36(1): 7-16.
- Resh, M.D. (2009). Fatty acylation of proteins: new insights into membrane targeting of myristoylated and palmitoylated proteins. *Biochemistry Biophysics Journal*. 1451(1): 1-16.

- Rojas, S.T., Smith, A.G., Finter, W.F., Eagland, D., Vowden, K., Vowden, P., Telford, G., Brown, A. and Pritchard, D. (2006). Recombinant *Lucilia sericata* chymotrypsin in a topical hydrogel formulation degrades human wound eschar ex vivo. *Biotechnology Journal*. 27:870–874.
- Sanders, K. and Sanders, T. (1992). *The Future of Wound Healing*. In: Leaper, D.J., Harding K.J. Wounds: Biology and Management. Oxford: University Press: Oxford. Pp 191.
- Sargison, N. (2008). *The Management of Ectoparasitic Disease of UK sheep*. World Veterinary congress. Royal (Dick) School of Veterinary Studies. Easter Bush Veterinary Center. Roslin, Midlothian, Scotland. Pp 50.
- Scavee, V., Polls, X. and Schoevaerdt, J. (2007). Maggot therapy: Many Hands Make Light World. Archived from the Origin. *Journal of Efficacy of Maggot*. 22:1-2.
- Shakibaie, M.R., Jalilzadeh, K.A. and Yamakanamardi, S.M. (2009). Horizontal transfer of antibiotic resistance gene among gram negative bacteria in sewage and lake water and influence of some physico-chemical parameters of water on conjugation process. *Journal of Environmental Biology*. 30:45-49.
- Sherman, R.A. and Pechter, E.A. (2008). Maggot therapy: a review of the therapeutic applications of fly larvae in human medicine, especially for treating osteomyelitis. *Medical Veterinary Entomology*. 2:225-230.
- Sherman, R.A., Hall, M.J.R. and Thomas, S. (2007). Medicinal Maggot: An ancient remedy for some contemporary affliction. *Journal of Annual Review in Estomology*. 45:55-81.
- Sherman, R.A., Wyle, F. and Vulpe, M. (2006). Maggot debridement therapy For treating pressure ulcers in spinal cord injury patients. *Journal of Spinal Cord Medication*. 18:4-17.
- Sherman, R.A. (2005). Maggot therapy takes us back to the future of wound care: New and improved maggot therapy for the 21st century. *Journal of Diabetes Science Technology*. 3: 336-344.
- Sherman, R.A., Vulpe, M. and Shimoda K.J. (2003). Presurgical maggot debridement of soft tissue wounds is associated with decreased rates of postoperative infection. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 39: 1067–70
- Sherman, R.A. (2003). Maggot therapy for treating diabetic foot ulcer unresponsive to conventional therapy. *Journal of Diabetic Care*. 14:97-101.
- Steen Voorde, P. and Jukema, G.N. (2007). A Review: The antimicrobial activities of maggots: in-vivo results. *Journal of Tissue Viability*. 14:97-101.
- Steen Voorde, P. and Jukema, G. N. 2004. The antimicrobial activity of maggots: in-vivo results. *Journal of Tissue Viability*. 14:97-101.
- Steen Voorde, P., Jacobi, C.E., van Doorn, L. and Oskam, J. (2004). Maggot debridement therapy of infected ulcers: patient and wound factors influencing outcome - a study on 101 patients with 117 wounds. *Annual Review of Collective Surgery in England*. 89:596-602.
- Stephan, T. (2009). The anti-microbial activity of Maggot secretion. *Results of a Preliminary Study Journal*. 2:1-3.
- Stubbings, W.J., Bostock, J. M., Ingham, E. and Chopra. I. (2004). Assessment of a microplate method for determining the post-antibiotic effect in *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*. 54:139-143.
- Suchi, A., Lim, C.S. and Carl, B. (2010). Antibacterial activity of *Lucilia cuprina* maggot extracts and its extraction techniques. *International Journal of Integrative Biology, A Journal of Biology Beyond Borders*. 9 (1):44.

- Szalanski, A.L., Owen, C.B., McKay, T. and Steelman, C.D. (2004). Detection of *Campylobacter* and *Escherichia coli* O157: H7 from filth flies by polymerase chain reaction. *Medical and Entomology Journal*. 18 (3): 241-246.
- Tanyuksel, A., Araz, E., Dundar, K., Uzun, G., Gumus, T., Alten, B., Saylam, F., Taylan-Ozkan, A. and Mumcuoglu, K.Y. (2005) Maggot debridement therapy in the treatment of chronic wounds in a military hospital setup in Turkey. *Dermatology*. 210:115-118.
- Tarone, A.M. and Foran, D.R. (2008). U.S.National library of medicine.Public medicine.Generalized additive models and *Lucilia sericata* growth. *Assessing confidence interval and errors rate in forensic entomology Journal*. 16:1-4.
- Thomas, S., Andrews, A.M., Hay, N.P. and Bourgoise, S. (2009). The antimicrobial activity of maggot secretions: Results of preliminary study. *Journal of tissue viability*. 9:127-132.
- Toroglu, S., Toroglu, E., Dincer, S., Kara, C. and Kertmen, M. (2009). Resistances of antibiotics and heavy metals in *Enterobacteriaceae* spp.Isolated From Gill and Intestines of *Acanthobrama Marmid* (Heckel, 1843). *Sir Dam Lake Turkey Journal Environmental Biology*. 30:23-31.
- Toroglu, E. and Toroglu, S. (2009). Micobial pollution of water in Golbasi Lake In Adiyaman. *Turkish Journal of Environmental Biology*. 30:33-38.
- Toroglu, S., Dincer, S. and Korkmaz, H. (2005). Antibiotic resistance in gram negative bacteria isolated from Aksu river in (Kahramanmaras) Turkey. *Annual Microbiology Journal*. 55:229-233.
- Usman, H., Abdulraham F.F. and Ladaman, A.H. (2007). Phytochemical and antimicrobial evaluation of *Tribulus terrestris* *L* (*Zygophyllaceae*) growing in Nigeria. *Research journal in biological science. Medwell journal*. 2(3): 244-247.
- Vercruysse, L., Smagghe, G., Herregods, G. and Cam, J.V. (2005). ACE inhibitory activity in enzymatic hydrolysates of insect protein. *Journal Agricultural Food Chemistry*. 53:5207-5211.
- Vistnes, L.M., Lee, R. and Ksander, G.A. (1981). Proteolytic activity of blowfly Larvae secretions in experimental burns. *Journal of Surgery*. 90:835-841.
- Vistues, A.K., Lemos, F.J.A., Ribeiro, A.F. and Terra, W.R. (2007). A bacteria digesting midgutlysozyme from *Musca domestica* (diptera) larvae. Purification, properties and secretory mechanism. *Insect Biochemical Molecules*. 23(4):533-541.
- Vollekora, A., Kost'alora, D. and Sochorova, R. (2001) *Microbiology journal*. 46:107-111.
- Wainwright, M. (2003). *Miracle cure:The story of penicillin and the golden age of antibiotics*. Oxford: Basil Black well. Pp 3.
- Wang, J.X., Zhao, X.F., Liang, Y.L., Li, L., Zhang, W., Ren, Q., Wang, L.C. and Wang, L.Y. (2012). Molecular characterization and expression of the antimicrobial peptide defensin from the housefly (*Musca domestica*). *Cell Molecular Life Science*. 63(24): 3072-3082.
- Wang,Y.C and Sun, D.X. (2006). The assay of composition and physicochemical characteristics of antibacterial matters from house fly larva. *Acta Microbiology Journal*. 37:148-153.
- Wang, F.R., Ai, H., Lei, C.L. and Huang, W. (2006). Antiviral activity of the homogenate of *Musca domestica* larvae. *Chinese Journal Entomology*. 43(1): 82-85.
- Wary, Y. and Sun, N. (2007). A rapid and systematic review of the clinical effectiveness and cost effectiveness of debriding agents in treating surgical wounds healing by secondary intention. *Health Technology Assesment*. 5:1-131.

Whitaker, I.S., Twine, C., Whitaker, M.J., Welck, M., Brown, C.S. and

Shandall, A. (2007). Larval therapy from antiquity to the present day:

Mechanising of action, chemical applications and future potential.

Postgraduate Medical Journal. 83:409-413.

Wollina, U. (2003). Biosurgery in wound healing- the renaissance of maggot

therapy. *Journal of European Academic Dermatology*. 6:1-7.

Wollina, U., Liebold, K., Schmidt, W., Hartmann, M. and Fassler, D. (2003).

Biosurgery supports granulation and debridement in chronic wounds-

clinical data and remittance spectroscopy measurement. *International*

Journal of dermatology. 41:635-639.

Woodworth, B.A., Tamashiro, E., Bhargava, G, Cohen, N.A and Palmer, J.N.

(2008). An in vitro model of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* biofilms on viable

airway epithelial cell monolayers. *American Journal of Rhinology*. 22:235

-238.

Wyllie, D., Crook, D. and Peto, T. (2006). Mortality after *Staphylococcus*

aureus bacteraemia in two hospitals in Oxfordshire, cohort study.

Biomedical Journal. 3:281-284.

Xu, X.X., Jin, F.L., Yu, X.Q., Ji, S.X., Wang, J., Cheng, H.X., Wang, C. and

Zhang W.Q. (2007). Expression and purification of a recombinant

antibacterial peptide, cecropin, from *Escherichia coli*. *Protein Expression*

Purification. 53(2):293-301.

Yasuda, T. (1997). Chemical cues from *Spodoptera litura* larvae elicit prey

locating behavior by the predatory stink bug, *Eocanthecona furcellata*.

Entomologia Experimentalis Journal. 82:349-354.

Yoon, K.J., Park, B.S., Jang, A., Cho, C.R., Lee, S.K., Lee, K.S., Kim M.H. and

Kim, H.T. (2008). Separation methods of low molecular size peptide and

ethanol extract with anti-MRSA activity from *Musca domestica*. *Korean*

Patient Journal. 2:10-11.

Zy, D., Ito, Y., Nakamura, M., Hotani, T. and Imoto, T. (2005). Insect lysozyme

from housefly (*Musca domestica*) larvae: Possible digestive function based

on sequence and enzymatic properties. *Journal of Biochemistry*. 118(3):

546-551.

www.healthaffairs.uci.edu (2013)

www.hta.ac.uk (2013)

www.monarchlabs.com (2013)

www.nhm.ac.uk (2013)

<http://www.rafidaindentj.net/www.rafidaindentj.net> (2012)

www.springerlink.com (2013)

www.usatoday.com (2013)

www.zoobiotic.org (2013)

MEDICINAL VALUE OF AFRICAN PEAR (*Dacryodes edulis*): IMPLICATION FOR AGRICULTURAL EXTENSION ACTIVITIES

Afolabi, S. O.¹

¹Farm and Environment Unit, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: sofolab@gmail.com; +2348032519376

Abstract: Plants generally possess inherent values relevant to human health but crops in various forms have direct beneficial effects as food and medicine. This review work on the medicinal value of African pear (*Dacryodes edulis*) and its extension implication seeks to explore the nutritional and medicinal value of the crop in terms of its proximate analysis from existing literatures, the perception of farmers on its food and medicinal values, and the implications for agricultural extension services. The transfer of technological innovations in agriculture remains the major focus of extension work among the farmers as a tool to transform rural farming methods to innovative agricultural practices with an increase in production level and transformation of life for the farm families as the immediate goal. The emphasis on the medicinal value of crops generally has been downplayed, hence the main objective of this review work. The African pear contains much of Vitamin C, Potassium, Protein, Oils, and other nutrients and Vitamins that have been found very beneficial to human health in terms of its potentials to manage peculiar health conditions like Sickle cell anemia, Protein deficiency, Hypertension, and also a potential antioxidant and immune booster among others. The farmers and indigenous groups in localities where African pear exist believe it possesses laxative properties and therefore helps in digestive problems and its associating ailments and some other health benefits. It is commonly consumed with boiled corn in communities where it is found and its production always coincides with early fresh Maize harvest. The emergence of human diseases in various forms globally necessitates keen interest in crops like African pear with antioxidant, antimicrobial, and immune boosting properties among other qualities of the crop. Conclusively, evidences abound that African pear is beneficial in building body immunity and management of some ailments due to its phytochemical contents. Recommendations include further extensive research and development on African pear with a view to explore its potential for human health management to transform livelihoods and boost internal and foreign trade impact on the nation's economy.

Key Words: Crops, Medicinal, Agriculture, Extension, Health

1 INTRODUCTION

Plants generally possess constituents that make them relevant for human uses in different forms both as food and medicine. "Food is medicine and medicine is food" is a common parlance to express the medicinal value of foods. Specific crops consumed directly have been found useful in the treatment of ailments or sometimes extracts from crops have been found potent in the management of ailments. Fruits and vegetables are generally known to be very important in human diets because of their constituents and their proximate profiles which have been scientifically investigated in the management of chronic or "so termed terminal ailments". Umoh (1998) noted that fruits are generally used for the treatment of ailments when taken in recommended dosage and not as a snack, such that some fruits have been found to

assist in weight loss therapy and convalescing among patients in need of quick recuperation.

However, the crucial role of agricultural extension in enlightenment campaigns and the utilization of agricultural innovation deserves specific focus to emphasize the medicinal value of crops, particularly in view of globally emerging diseases which have put lots of pressure on mankind in terms of the complexity of symptoms, scale of spread, and complexity of management. According to Oladoja (2008), agricultural development studies have proved that education is a crucial variable for achieving economic growth and human progress and agricultural extension has been designed for farmers' self-help to boost livelihood and transform lives.

Agricultural extension as an informal, out-of-school education aims at boosting the farmers' general

livelihood through education to improve farmers' productivity. The whole educational process of extension may fall short of its goal if the farmers' empowerment excludes education on the medicinal benefit of crops produced. The farm gate benefit of a farmer must be the rich diets of the fresh farm produce consumed at the farm gate before the produce gets to the markets after some days.

African pear (*Dacryodes edulis*), called *Ube* among Igbos in South Eastern Nigeria and various names in different parts of West Africa believed to be its origin, is commonly found around dwelling areas within communities in South East and South South Nigeria, where it is regarded as a choice fruit because of its perceived food and medicinal value compared to other parts of Nigeria. It is not commonly found in other parts of the country like the Southwest, Central, and Northern Nigeria. African pear, also regarded as native pear because of its green acid pulp like the Avocado pear (Umoh 1998), has a peculiar oblong shape and pink color of the fruit which turns black when ripe, making it very attractive.

LITERATURE REVIEW

African medicinal plants to a great extent have been investigated to assess the chemical constituents and some of the isolated compounds have been shown to possess interesting biological activity with few found active in controlled clinical evaluation such that edible plants, spices, and fruits are the dominant ingredients in many medicinal remedies (Iwu 2013).

The relevance of most of the African medicinal plants, particularly the crops, as evidenced by use in traditional medicines and several ongoing investigations, is gaining more attention, particularly with the involvement of governmental and non-governmental agencies in investigation and standardization of these health products. The Nigeria Natural Medicine Development Agency (NNMDA), National Food and Drugs Administration and Control (NAFDAC), Pax Herbal Nigeria among others are relevant in this regard.

Proximate Composition and Medicinal Value of African Pear

Several studies have documented the high value of the African pear constituents in terms of richness in vitamins and phytochemicals which enhance their value in diets and medicinal preparations.

The richness in essential amino acids like Lysine, Phenylalanine, Leucine, and Isoleucine, and phytochemicals that have been isolated like terpenes, flavonoids, oxalates, tannins, alkaloids, and saponins (Ajibesin 2019).

African pear possesses antioxidants and antimicrobial properties with other phytochemicals that can boost body immunity. Its possession of natural folic acid makes it a beneficial fruit to pregnant women. The Vitamin C helps to boost immunity while the Phosphorus and Calcium contents promote strong bones and teeth. Its richness in Carbohydrate, thiamine, and riboflavin was also noted. The healing of wounds, management of skin infection, and dysentery have also been ascribed to African pear (Ibemere 2022).

Iwu (1986) reported that African Pear has been found useful in the treatment of parasitic skin diseases, wounds, and fever by using the stem exudates and leaves. Studies by Nlenecha (2018) documented the capacity of African pear to fight Cancer and protect women against menopausal breast cancer, decrease colon Cancer infection due to the Fiber, Vitamins, Minerals, and essential fatty acids content. Its ability to support strong bone formation, prevention of constipation, and being heart friendly was also noted.

The proximate analysis of African pear constituents as reported by Omogbai and Ojeaburu (2018) showed a Protein content of 2.89 to 4.16%, while the details of other nutrients and minerals are stated in Tables 1 and 2 below. It was also reported that the anti-nutritional content levels are low in comparison to World Health Standard Organization (WHO) standard for foods.

The effect of processing on the toxicity levels revealed that boiling and roasting have significant effects on toxic metals thus reducing the accumulation levels in the edible portion to the standards within the recommended value by World Health Organization and Food and Agriculture Organization (WHO/FAO) joint expert maximum acceptable recommendation (Dan and Udo 2013).

Table 1: Proximate Analysis Value of African Pear

Parameters	Values (%)	
Moisture	44.45 – 50.93	
Lipid	30.55 – 35.60	
Protein	2.89 – 4.16	Source: Omogbai and
Ash	2.65 – 2.76	
Crude Fiber	1.52 – 1.61	
Carbohydrate	9.75 – 12.59	
Ojeaburu (2010)		

Table 2: Proximate Analysis of African Pear (Minerals)

Minerals	Values (mg/100g)	
Phosphorus	695.55 – 698.40	
Potassium	540.81 – 553.15	
Calcium	347.50 – 354.60	
Magnesium	280.15 – 287.65	Source: Omogbai
Sodium	162.50 – 170.00	
Zinc	3.65 – 3.81	
Iron	3.43 – 3.58	
Copper	0.38 – 0.45	
and Ojeaburu (2010)		

RELEVANCE OF EXTENSION PRINCIPLES IN CROPS' MEDICINAL VALUE CHAIN

Extension education, basically, has been a potent tool in executing development projects because target beneficiaries must be sensitized to perceive development projects as self-help tasks meant to transform lives. The knowledge gap, which this review study seeks to bridge, is the value that agricultural extension personnel must place on their message to the farmer on the beneficial values of farm produce without ambiguity but in the simplest form.

Adedoyin and Aderinto (2013) opined that the role of extension education is to empower farmers directly to help themselves to raise their living standards and ultimately affect the general populace. Oakley and Garforth (1997) noted that extension is a dynamic concept because the interpretation is always changing; as a term, it cannot be defined precisely because it is a description of a continually changing process in the rural economy and is guided by principles. Some of the extension principles are relevant to properly mobilize for the utilization of

crops' medicinal value. They stated the following extension principles, a few of which are adapted for this review:

- Needs and Interest of Target Beneficiaries:** Felt needs as precursor drives attention, motivates action, and mobilizes for adoption. Peculiar needs of target beneficiaries must be explored to fast-track tapping the advantage of crops' medicinal value.
- Operation at People's Level:** Interaction at the farmers' level is key in winning the attention of a farmer for involvement in extension education. The primary level to gain attention in extension of medicinal value of crops is to open up the farmers' attention to the medicinal value of crops on his farm beyond the food or dietary value. Even though rural people, particularly adults, have indigenous knowledge on plants' medicinal value, although such knowledge may be limited, they will be ready to learn if rightly prompted.
- Extension Works with People, Not for the People:** The extension work basically lies with the rural people, who already have orientation and knowledge of what to do. They only need guidance, not domination or bossy attitude; their decisions need support to solve their perceived problems for extension goals to be achieved. Extension presents facts, helps people to solve problems, and encourages farmers to take decisions. Confidence is generated when farmers are part of programme decisions.
- Extension is Accountable to its Clients:** Extension workers relate to their superiors and the government department and at the same time respond to the needs of their clients who look forward to extension workers to mobilize them for self-help as government representatives around their locality.
- Extension as Two-Way Link:** The two-fold linkage of receiving from research stations to reach farmers on the field. In the crops medicinal value chain, bulk research results exist with research organizations on various crops' benefits beyond the dietary value. Extension service through the field workers are the viable links.

article [utf8]inputenc

EXTENSION COMMUNICATION IN CROPS' MEDICINAL VALUE CHAIN

Generally, crops are highly valued as the end product in the agricultural production process because of their potential domestic and industrial uses as food, medicine, or other applications. Iwu (2013) noted that with recent developments, management of chronic ailments and metabolic disease conditions have been found feasible through various research studies in Phytomedicine and Bioresources.

The concept of extension communication involves educating people for self-help to transform lives through innovation transmission with the ultimate goal of empowerment and improved living standards as a potent tool for development.

Innovation transmission as a deliberate action is the major theme of agricultural extension, and in this perspective, the medicinal value of crops is the brand of innovation that farmers need to be motivated into. Innovation has been defined as anything new introduced into an economy or social process (OECD 1997). The key elements of communication as emphasized by Oakley and Garforth (1997) include channel, message, source, listening, and shared meanings. These are core issues that underlie any successful communication and are highly relevant to the dissemination of crops' medicinal value information.

Since the adoption of the memorandum on the unified agricultural extension system by the National Council for Agriculture in 1989, which gave rise to the national policy and the subsequent implementation in 1990, the various states were advised to adopt the unified extension system (Adediji, 2013). The unified extension system was introduced to cater to various segments of agriculture as practiced in Nigeria such that smallholder farmers who practice various aspects of agriculture might be covered holistically by the agricultural extension system, thus enhancing the various value chain processes in the agricultural production cycle.

Thrupp (1996) identified the following factors as essential for success in the knowledge or technology dissemination process among farmers:

1. Vested leadership or shared control with the farmers in every aspect of technology dissemination.
2. Participation and empowerment of farmers and

communities.

3. Linkage between groups, institutions, and organizations, both governmental and non-governmental.
4. Innovation learning and effective communication.
5. Policy environment and political influence.

These factors, in relation to knowledge transfer of African pear medicinal value, will help to boost indigenous knowledge documentation and scientific information transfer. Consequently, the various researchers and organizations involved in Bioresources development in linkage with farmers can cross-fertilize ideas to probe into farmers' knowledge on its medicinal value and as well share the scientific information on its proximate value and its health benefits.

article [utf8]inputenc

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The following theories discussed below provide a framework for this review work.

Knowledge Gap Theory

The theory of knowledge gap is based on information or knowledge acquisition generally, emphasizing that people don't acquire information at the same rate. Variables like socio-economic status and rate of learning, among others, influence the degree of knowledge acquisition. According to Asemah (2011), the theory states that the spread of news in a society can lead to an increase in the gap between people of different economic statuses, such that attempts to improve life in a social system may not always work as planned. The heterogeneous nature of economic statuses plays vital roles in individual wants, needs, and responses to knowledge acquisition. The theory views knowledge as a commodity, product, or idea not evenly distributed in society. People with higher economic status and innovative minds tend to have better access to knowledge acquisition than laggards, who are late adopters or non-adopters of innovation. Folarin (1998) noted the impact of media output in a given society: as the media grows, the knowledge gap between the privileged and underprivileged social groups increases. The relevance of the Knowledge Gap theory to crops'

medicinal value chain communication rests on the knowledge gap existing among various categories of farmers on health benefits derivable from crops beyond the food value.

Diffusion and Innovation Theory

The Innovation Diffusion theory emphasizes the information flow over time through a social system until it becomes adopted as a new product or idea observed to have beneficial value. Asemah (2017) noted that the diffusion of innovation as an idea was developed into theory in the United States of America. Agricultural technology advancement took a rapid dimension, and researchers examined the adoption of hybrid seeds, equipment, and crop propagation techniques by farmers. The relevance of Innovation Diffusion theory to crops' medicinal value adoption rests on the current emergence of diseases on a pandemic scale, such as COVID-19, Lassa fever, and HIV/AIDS. The effect of disease emergence on the disruption of the economy and human health are great challenges that mankind has come to face squarely in the twenty-first century. The necessity for alternative and supplementary therapy to manage these health challenges supports the relevance of this theory in the dissemination of crops' medicinal value as an innovation, of which African pear is one. article [utf8]inputenc

METHODOLOGY

This study, as a review work, examined existing investigative studies in literature available in libraries and on the internet concerning the medicinal value of African Pear and the relevant agricultural extension concepts and principles. The professional experience of the researcher as an Agricultural Extension specialist among rural farmers over the years also contributed to knowledge sharing in this review work. article [utf8]inputenc

CONCLUSION

The peculiarity of agricultural extension as a veritable tool to transform the lives of rural farm families and, by extension, the economic development of nations has been well documented. It has become a potent game-changer in human development projects globally. Agricultural extension is an informal, out-of-school adult education that employs various approaches and methodologies to reach rural farmers.

As reviewed in this study, the diffusion and adoption of the health benefits of crops, which can be further packaged to enhance their value, cannot be overemphasized, judging from the volumes of existing investigative work on crops' medicinal value.

Rural farmers, who are primarily smallholders, have been identified as a major source of farm produce supply in Sub-Saharan Africa. The primary benefits of crops' medicinal value to the farm family and the general populace remain largely untapped. Coincidentally, humanity is at the peak of global health challenges due to emerging diseases.

RECOMMENDATION

The promotion of further research and development on the African pear food and medicinal value chain deserves priority attention due to its immense food and health benefits to human development and the global economy. The need for a viable supplement to existing drug therapy for disease management provides a good opportunity for the exploitation of African pear's medicinal value at domestic and industrial scales. Integration of crops' medicinal value as a core subject matter in agricultural extension as a global need deserves implementation to enable the full exploration of natural reserves in African pear. article [utf8]inputenc apacite

References

- Adediji, G. A. (2015). Concept of unified agricultural extension service. In O. A. Akinyemiju & D. O. Torimiro (Eds.), *Agricultural extension – A comprehensive treatise* (2nd ed., pp. 11–22). ABC Agricultural Systems Ltd.
- Adedoyin, S. F., Aderinto, A. (2013). Subject matter areas in agricultural extension. In O. A. Akinyemiju & D. O. Torimiro (Eds.), *Agricultural extension – A comprehensive treatise* (2nd ed., pp. 11–22). ABC Agricultural Systems Ltd.
- Ajibesin, K. K. (2011). *Dacryodes edulis* (G. Don) H. J. Lamin: Review of its medicinal, phytochemical, and economic properties. *Research Journal of Medicinal Plant*, 5(1), 32–41.
- Asemah, E. S., Nwamuo, A. N., Nkwan–Nwaoma, A. O. (2017). *Theories and models of communication* (Revised ed., pp. 93–108). University of Jos Press.
- Collins, N. (2019). Seven potent health benefits of African pear (Ube). *Health Guide*. Retrieved May 29, 2022, from www.healthguide.ng

Dan, E., Udo, E. (2013). Effect of processing on variations of some toxic metals in edible portions of *Dacryodes edulis* in Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria.

Eka, O. U. (1977). Studies on the nutrient composition of fruits of African pear *Dacryodes edulis*. *West African Journal of Biology and Applied Chemistry*, 20, 45–54.

Folarin, B. (1988). *Theories of mass communication: An introductory text*. Striling–Hordon Publishers.

Healthdirect. (2024). Vitamin C and your health. *Blooming The Chemist*. Retrieved from www.bloomsthechemist.com.au

Ibemere, C. (2022). Nutritional and health benefits of African pear. *Nature and News*. Retrieved from www.naturenews.africa

Iwu, M. M. (1986). *African ethnomedicine*. USP Press.

Iwu, M. M. (2013). *Handbook of African medicinal plants* (2nd ed., pp. 4–5, 25,395). CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group.

Nlenecha, H. (2018). Five health benefits of African pear (Ube). *Guardian*. Retrieved August 18, 2018.

Oakley, P., Garforth, C. (1997). *Guide to extension training*. Food and Agriculture Organization.

OECD (Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development). (1999). *Managing national innovation systems*. OECD.

Oladoja, M. A. (2008). Extension concepts, principles, and philosophy. In O. A. Akinyemiju & D. O. Torimiro (Eds.), *Agricultural extension – A comprehensive treatise* (2nd ed., pp. 11–22). ABC Agricultural Systems Ltd.

Omoti, U., Okiy, D. (1987). Characteristics and composition of the pulp oil and cake of the African pear *Dacryodes edulis*. *Journal of Food Science & Agriculture*, 38, 67–72.

Omogbai, B., Ojeaburu, S. (2010). Nutritional composition and microbial spoilage of *Dacryodes edulis* fruits vended in southern Nigeria. *Biological Sciences World Journal*. Retrieved May 29, 2022, from www.semantic.com

Thrupp, I. A. (1996). *New pathways for sustainable agriculture*. World Resources Institute.

Umoh, I. B. (1998). Commonly used fruits in Nigeria. In *Nutritional quality of plant foods* (pp. 84–120).

FREE RADICAL SCAVENGING AND ANTIOXIDANT CAPACITY OF LEAF OF *Combretum platypterum* (Welw) Hutch and Dalziel

UWAYA, O. D. ¹

¹Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria

Corresponding author: dickson.uwaya@uniben.edu; udickson4christ@yahoo.com; (+234) 705-965-0758

Abstract: An antioxidant is a molecule capable of preventing or inhibiting the oxidation of other molecules. It ends these reactions by removing free radical intermediates and inhibiting other oxidation reactions. *Combretum platypterum* is a plant that belongs to the family Combretaceae. Despite being used in ethnomedicine, there is no report of the in vitro antioxidant and free radical scavenging activities of its leaves. This study is aimed at testing the in vitro antioxidant and free radical scavenging activities of *Combretum platypterum* leaves. In vitro antioxidants such as ascorbic acid, carotenoids, and lycopene, and free radical scavenging activities such as 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl, superoxide radicals, hydroxyl radicals, hydrogen peroxide, nitric oxide, and 2,2-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) were analyzed using well-established methods. DNA protective assay was analyzed using DNA unwinding wheat germ plasmid topoisomerase topoi with supercoiled pBR322 plasmid. The vitamin C content in the aqueous extract was significantly higher compared to ethanol, methanol, and chloroform leaf extracts ($p < 0.05$). The carotenoid content in the methanol extract was higher compared to ethanol, methanol, and chloroform leaf extracts ($p < 0.05$). Lycopene content in the methanol extract was higher compared to water, ethanol, and chloroform leaf extracts ($p < 0.05$). DPPH, superoxide radicals, hydroxyl radicals, hydrogen peroxide, nitric oxide, and ABTS are just some of the radicals that the leaves of *Combretum platypterum* can scavenge. Methanol and aqueous extracts of *Combretum platypterum* protected the DNA from damage compared to the effect of dimethyl sulfoxide on DNA. *Combretum platypterum* leaves have antioxidant, scavenging, free radical, and DNA protection potential.

Keywords: *Combretum platypterum*, antioxidant, radicals, vitamin C, carotenoids

1 INTRODUCTION

An antioxidant is a molecule capable of preventing or inhibiting the oxidation of other molecules. Oxidation is a chemical reaction that transfers electrons from a substance to an oxidizing agent. Oxidation reactions can produce free radicals. These radicals can start chain reactions that damage cells (Ovuru *et al.*, 2023). Antioxidants end these reactions by removing free radical intermediates and inhibit other oxidation reactions. Antioxidants also scavenge the activities of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as superoxide radical (O_2^-), hydroxyl radical (OH^\cdot), hydrogen peroxide (Idu *et al.*, 2016; Dysken, 2014; Joseph, 2014). Reactive oxygen species (ROS) cause oxidative damaging by reacting with every molecule in the living cells such as lipid, amino acids, protein and DNA (Suprava *et al.*, 2015). The Reactive oxygen species (ROS) play a vital role in pathogenesis such as Parkinsons disease,

hypertension, Atherogenesis, Alzheimers disease, inflammation, asthma, arthritis and cancer. It also plays an important role in ageing (Suprava *et al.*, 2015). Research has shown that plants contain various bioactive part including antioxidant, antihypertensive, antiasthmatic, antiarthritis, anti-inflammation, anticancer and anti-ageing (Erhabor *et al.*, 2017; Enerijiofi and Isola, 2019). About 25% of plants active part was identified and prescribed as medicines (Gill *et al.*, 2011). The most practical way to fight pathogenesis as a result of reactive oxygen species (ROS) is to increase antioxidant activity in our body and that could be achieved by consumption of vegetables, fruits or edible plants rich in antioxidant (Adefegha and Oboh, 2011).

Combretum platypterum belongs to the family of Combretaceae. It occurs from East Guinea to Democratic Republic Congo and Southern Sudan and South to Northern Angola (Idu *et al.*, 2016, Dalziel, 1973). It is used to treat lower backache, swellings

and mumps, diarrhoea, Blindness, cough, headache and fever and as a tonic (Bongers *et al.*, 2005; Neuwinger, 2000). Idu *et al.*, 2016 reported *in-vivo* antioxidant activity of aqueous leaf *Combretum platypterum*.

This study are aimed at testing *in-vitro* antioxidant and free radical scavenging activities of leaf *Combretum platypterum*.

Materials and Methods

Plant Material Collection

Fresh leaves of *Combretum platypterum* were harvested from Idumiru, Igbanke West, Orhionmwon Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria. The plant was identified and authenticated by Dr. H. Akinnibosun in the Department of Plant and Biotechnology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. The plant was deposited in the University of Benin Herbarium with Voucher number UBHc063.

Preparation of Plant Material

Leaves were washed and air-dried in the Department of Plant and Biotechnology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, for two weeks. The leaves were ground into powder using an impact mill. Pulverized leaves (200g) were macerated with distilled water (5L). After 24 hours, the extracts were filtered, and the filtrate was concentrated over a water bath. The concentrated extracts were stored in universal bottles, labeled, and refrigerated at 4°C before use (Owolabi *et al.*, 2008).

Extraction Using Ethanol, Methanol, and Chloroform

Powdered leaf (150g) was macerated using ethanol, methanol, and chloroform for 72 hours and filtered. The filtrates were oven-dried at 37°C. Each extract of a different solvent was stored in a glass container in a refrigerator until use.

Determination of In-Vitro Antioxidant Activities

The *in-vitro* antioxidant activities of aqueous, methanol, ethanol, and chloroform leaf extracts of *Combretum platypterum* were determined as follows:

Determination of Ascorbic Acid

The plant extract (0.1g) was mixed with 1mL of 4% TCA. A centrifugation process was performed at a

speed of 2000 revolutions per minute for a duration of 10 minutes. The liquid obtained was mixed with a small amount of activated charcoal, vigorously shaken, and left for 5 minutes. Centrifugation eliminated the charcoal particles. Supernatant (0.5mL) was added to 2mL of 4% trichloroacetic acid (TCA), followed by the addition of 0.5mL of 2% dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH) in 9-normal sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), and then 2 drops of 10% thiourea solution. The components were combined and kept at a temperature of 37°C for 3 hours, which led to the formation of formosazone crystals. The crystals were dissolved in 2.5mL of 85% sulfuric acid at a low temperature. After adding sulfuric acid, DNPH reagent and thiourea were added to the blank. The tubes were cooled in ice, and the absorbance was measured at 540nm using a spectrophotometer (Model: T80+UV/Vis Spectrometer, PG Instruments Ltd.). The outcome was indicated as milligrams per gram of the sample.

Determination of Total Carotenoids and Lycopene

The determination was carried out in the dark to avoid the photolysis of carotenoids. Plant extract (0.1g) was homogenized and saponified with 0.5mL of 12% alcoholic potassium hydroxide in a water bath at 60°C for 30 minutes. The saponified extract was transferred to a separating funnel containing 3mL of petroleum ether and mixed well. The lower aqueous layer was transferred to another separating funnel, and the upper petroleum ether layer containing the carotenoids was collected. The extraction was repeated until the aqueous layer became colorless. Little quantities of anhydrous sodium sulfate were added to the petroleum ether extract to remove excess moisture. The final volume of the petroleum ether extract was noted. Absorbance of the yellow color was read in a spectrophotometer (Model: T80+UV/Vis Spectrometer, PG Instruments Ltd.) at 450nm and 503nm using petroleum ether as the blank. The amount of total carotenoids and lycopene was calculated using the formula (Raghunathan and Matheswaran, 2016; Nithya *et al.*, 2015).

$$\text{Amount of total carotenoids} = \frac{A_{450} \times \text{sample} \times 100 \times 4}{\text{Weight of the sample}}$$

$$\text{Amount of lycopene} = \frac{3.12 \times A_{503} \times \text{sample} \times 100}{\text{Weight of the sample}}$$

The total carotenoids and lycopene were expressed as mg/g of the sample.

Evaluation of Radical Scavenging Activity

The scavenging effects of aqueous, methanol, ethanol, and chloroform leaf extracts of *Combretum platypterum* were tested against 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), hydrogen peroxide, superoxide, nitric oxide, and hydroxyl radicals.

2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl Hydrate (DPPH) Scavenging Effects

The scavenging abilities of the natural antioxidants in the leaves towards the stable free radical DPPH were measured following the method of Mensor et al. (2001). Aqueous, methanol, ethanol, and chloroform leaf extracts at various concentrations were added to 1mL of the methanol solution of DPPH. The mixture was allowed to react for 30 minutes at 25°C. Methanol served as the blank, DPPH in methanol as a control, and ascorbic acid as the standard. After 30 minutes of incubation, the discoloration of the purple color was measured at 518nm in a spectrophotometer (Model: T80+UV/Vis Spectrometer, PG Instruments Ltd.). The free radical scavenging activity was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Control} - \text{Test}}{\text{Control}} \right) \times 100$$

Measurement of Superoxide Scavenging Activity

The various concentrations of aqueous, ethanol, methanol, and chloroform leaf extracts were added to 0.2mL of EDTA, 0.1mL of NBT, 0.05mL of riboflavin, and 2.64mL of phosphate buffer. The control tubes were set up, and distilled water was added instead of the plant extracts. Optical density was measured at 560nm in a spectrophotometer (Model: T80+UV/Vis Spectrometer, PG Instruments Ltd.) (Shinde et al., 2006). Superoxide anion scavenging activity was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Control} - \text{Test}}{\text{Control}} \right) \times 100$$

Hydrogen Peroxide Scavenging Effects

The leaf extracts (10mg/10L) of aqueous, methanol, ethanol, and chloroform were added to 0.6mL of combined H₂O₂ (40mM) in phosphate buffer,

and the total volume was made up to 3mL. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was recorded at 230nm in a spectrophotometer (Model: T80+UV/Vis Spectrometer, PG Instruments Ltd.). A blank solution containing phosphate buffer without H₂O₂ was prepared (Shinde et al., 2006; Ruch et al., 1989). The extent of H₂O₂ scavenging in the plant extracts was calculated as:

$$\% \text{scavenging of hydrogen peroxide} = \left(\frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \right) \times 100$$

where A_0 is the absorbance of control and A_1 is the absorbance in the presence of plant extract.

Measurement of Hydroxyl Radical Scavenging Activity

Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity was assessed according to Uwaya et al. (2021). The reaction mixture contained 0.1mL of deoxyribose, 0.1mL of FeCl₃, 0.1mL of EDTA, 0.1mL of H₂O₂, 0.1mL of ascorbate, and 0.1mL of KH₂PO₄-KOH buffer. The mixture was incubated at 37°C for 1 hour. At the end of the incubation period, 1.0mL of TBA was added and heated at 95°C for 20 minutes to develop the color. After cooling, the TBARS formation was measured spectrophotometrically at 532nm against the blank. The hydroxyl radical scavenging activity was determined as:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Control} - \text{Test}}{\text{Control}} \right) \times 100$$

Measurement of Nitric Oxide Scavenging Activity

The reaction was initiated by adding 2.0mL of sodium nitroprusside, 0.5mL of PBS, and 0.5mL of leaf extracts of aqueous, methanolic, ethanolic, and chloroform, which were incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes. Griess reagent (0.5mL) was added and incubated for another 30 minutes. The control tubes were prepared without the extracts. The absorbance was read at 546nm against the reagent blank in a spectrophotometer (Uwaya et al., 2021).

2,2-Azinobis (3-Ethylbenzothiazoline-6-Sulphonic Acid) Radical Scavenging Activity

To make ABTS+ stock solution, 7mM ABTS aqueous solution was mixed with 2.45mM potassium persulfate aqueous solution in an equal amount. The

mixture was then left to sit at room temperature in the dark for 12 to 16 hours before it was used. The working solution of ABTS+ was obtained by diluting the stock solution in methanol to give an absorbance of 0.70 at 734nm. Then, 2.0mL of ABTS+ solution was mixed with 1mL of various concentrations of extract of different solvents of *Combretum platypterum* leaves (10–100µg/mL). The mixture was then incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes in the dark. The control was prepared by mixing 2.0mL of ABTS+ solution with 1mL of double-distilled water. The absorbance was measured against a blank at 734nm using a spectrophotometer. Ascorbic acid was used as the standard. The percentage of scavenging activity of each extract on ABTS+ was calculated as inhibition (I%) using the following equation:

$$I\% = \left(\frac{A_o - A_s}{A_o} \right) \times 100$$

(Russo et al., 2000; Jayashree et al., 2015).

Reactions of Wheat Germplasm Topoisomerase I with Supercoiled pBR322 Plasmid

A 50µL solution containing 35mM Tris-HCl (pH = 8), 72mM KCl, 5mM MgCl₂, 5mM DTT, 5mM spermidine, 100µg/kg of aqueous and methanol extract leaves *Combretum platypterum*, 200 to 1000ng pBR322 plasmid, and 2U/µL Wheat Germplasm Topoisomerase I was incubated with or without DMSO, ethidium bromide at 37°C for 30 minutes. One unit is defined as the amount of enzyme that catalyzes 100% of 0.5µg of pBR322 (relaxed and supercoiled) DNA in 30 minutes at 37°C in a total reaction volume of 50µL. The obtained products were further analyzed using agarose electrophoresis (1.0%) without ethidium bromide. The gel was photographed, and the DNA bands were measured (Bei et al., 2015; Forte et al., 1989).

Statistical Analysis

The data were expressed as the mean ± SEM. The data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism V.6.01, where $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results

Vitamin C, Carotenoid, and Lycopene Content

The amounts of vitamin C, carotenoids, and lycopene in water, ethanol, methanol, and chloroform leaf extracts of *Combretum platypterum* are shown in Figures 1, 2, and 3. Vitamin C content in the aqueous leaf extract is significantly higher compared to ethanol, methanol, and chloroform leaf extracts ($p < 0.01$) (Figure 1). The carotenoid and lycopene contents in the methanol extract were significantly higher compared to aqueous, ethanol, and chloroform leaf extracts ($p < 0.01$) (Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 1: Vitamin C content in aqueous, ethanol, methanol, and chloroform leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

Radical Scavenging Activity of Leaf Extracts

Figures 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 show the DPPH, superoxide, hydroxyl, hydrogen peroxide, nitric oxide, and ABTS radical scavenging activities of the aqueous, ethanol, methanol, and chloroform leaf extracts of *Combretum platypterum*. Aqueous leaf extract showed the best DPPH, superoxide, hydroxyl, hydrogen peroxide, and ABTS radical scavenging activities compared to the standard vitamin C (Figures 4, 5, 6, 7, and 9). The ethanol extract gave the best nitric oxide radical scavenging activity (Figure 8).

DNA Unwinding Assay

Discussion

Plants are potential sources of compounds needed to develop new therapeutic agents (Suprava et

Figure 2: Carotenoid content in aqueous, ethanolic, methanolic, and chloroform leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

Figure 3: Lycopene content in aqueous, ethanol, methanol, and chloroform leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

al., 2013; Adesina et al., 2013). They play an important role in effective antioxidant and free radical scavenging activities (Suprava et al., 2013). The *in vitro* antioxidant study showed that *Combretum platypterum* leaves contain vitamin C, carotenoids, and lycopene. Vitamin C content was highest in the aqueous extract. Carotenoid and lycopene were highest in the methanolic extract. Vitamin C, carotenoid, and lycopene are powerful antioxidants and play a vital role in disease prevention and treatment (Kulawik et al., 2023; Chávez-Mendoza et al., 2015).

Figure 4: DPPH radical scavenging activities of aqueous, ethanol, methanol and chloroform leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

Figure 4: DPPH radical scavenging activities of aqueous, ethanol, methanol, and chloroform leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

Vitamin C is a strong antioxidant, and small amounts can protect molecules in the body, such as proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, and nucleic acids, from damage by free radicals and reactive oxygen species that can be generated during normal metabolism and through exposure to toxins and pollutants. Vitamin C may also regenerate other antioxidants, such as vitamin E (Bruno et al., 2006). Vitamin C is beneficial in preventing the onset of chronic diseases such as cancer or heart disease (Peng, 2014). The high content of vitamin C in the aqueous leaf extract of *Combretum platypterum* lends credence to the young leaves being used as soup in Sierra Leone (Bongers et al., 2005; Burkill, 1985).

cataracts, arthritis, and skin damage, and promotes male fertility (Perusek and Maeda, 2013; Wang et al., 2013). Lycopene is a carotenoid that is linked to maintaining the health of the liver, colon, breast, prostate, and lungs. It prevents osteoporosis, diabetes, and cancer, treats infertility in men, and protects cells by inhibiting apoptosis (Trejo-Solís et al., 2013; Sadek et al., 2016). *Combretum platypterum* leaves are rich in vitamin C, carotenoids, and lycopene, which gives credence to its use in traditional medicine to treat inflammation, pain, cough, fever, eye problems, lumps, conjunctivitis, sexually transmitted diseases, diarrhea, and as a tonic (Liben, 1983; Bongers et al., 2005).

Carotenoid is a powerful antioxidant. It protects against many degenerative conditions, including heart disease, diabetes, cancer, macular degeneration,

A 2-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl hydrate scavenging

Figure 5: Superoxide radical scavenging activities of aqueous, ethanolic, methanolic, and chloroform leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

Figure 6: Hydroxyl radical scavenging activities of aqueous, ethanol, methanol, and chloroform leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

assay showed that *Combretum platypterum* leaves can scavenge free radicals generated by oxidative stress. The effect of the leaf extract in different solvents is comparable to that of vitamin C. 2-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl hydrate is a stable and available organic nitrogen radical that is mostly used to determine antioxidant activity (Kamra et al., 2012; Huang et al., 2005). The scavenging ability can be attributed to the presence of vitamin C, carotenoids, and lycopene in *Combretum platypterum* leaves. Aqueous leaf extract showed the best superoxide radical scavenging activity compared to the standard vitamin C. The hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of aqueous, ethanolic, methanolic, and chloroform leaf extracts showed the ability to scavenge hydroxyl radicals. Aqueous leaf extract shows the best hydroxyl radical scavenging activity, comparable to the standard vitamin C. Hydroxyl radicals are the most dangerous among the radicals. They react with most biomolecules, such as proteins, nucleic acids, lipids, and polypeptides, causing tissue damage and cell death. Scavenging hydroxyl radicals is a vital antioxidant mechanism for protecting living cells

Figure 7: Hydrogen peroxide radical scavenging activities of aqueous, ethanolic, methanolic, and chloroform leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

Figure 8: Nitric oxide radical scavenging activities of aqueous, ethanolic, methanolic, and chloroform leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

(Rajagopalan et al., 2014).

In terms of hydrogen peroxide radical scavenging activity, aqueous leaf extract showed the best activity. This may be due to the high content of vitamin C in the aqueous leaf extract. Nitric oxide radicals are produced in various inflammatory conditions, such as juvenile diabetes, multiple sclerosis, arthritis, ulcerative colitis, and carcinomas. Nitric oxide reacts with superoxide radicals to form a highly reactive peroxynitrite anion (ONOO⁻), which is toxic (Rajagopalan et al., 2014). At lower concentrations, the nitric oxide radical scavenging activity of aqueous, ethanolic, and methanolic solutions was higher than that of vitamin C. The leaf extract has the ability to prevent the generation and scavenging of superoxide radicals, protecting individuals from their harmful effects. Aqueous leaf extract shows the best ABTS scavenging ability; this may be due to the high content of vitamin C.

The scavenging ability of *Combretum platypterum* leaves in various solvents showcases the rich antioxidant properties of the plant. Antioxidants help to remove reactive oxygen species, which may lead to oxidative stress. This imbalance leads

Figure 9: ABTS scavenging activity of aqueous, ethanolic, methanolic, and chloroform leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

Figure 10: DNA unwinding assay using Wheat Germplasm Topoisomerase 1 exposed to Supercoiled Plasmid DNA (pBR322). Lane A is supercoiled + ethidium bromide, Lane B is Supercoiled + water, Lane C is supercoiled + DMSO, Lane D is Supercoiled + aqueous leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*, and Lane E is Supercoiled + methanolic leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

to the damage of vital biomolecules and cells, potentially impacting organisms (Durackova, 2010). The presence of vitamin C, carotenoid, and lycopene, and the scavenging potentials of DPPH, superoxide radicals, hydroxyl radicals, hydrogen peroxide, nitric oxide radicals, and ABTS in the leaf extract of *Combretum platypterum* show that the plant has the ability to protect cells from being damaged by oxidative stress.

A DNA protection unwinding assay using wheat germplasm topoisomerase I exposed to supercoiled plasmid DNA (pBR 322) and relaxed plasmid DNA showed that the aqueous and methanolic leaf extracts had a protective effect on DNA compared to the effects of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and water. Dimethyl sulfoxide at low concentrations protects DNA by minimizing the formation of OH-induced sugar and

Figure 11: DNA unwinding assay using Wheat Germplasm Topoisomerase 1 exposed to the relaxed form of plasmid DNA (pBR322). Lane A is Relaxed + Wheat Germplasm Topoisomerase 1 + ethidium bromide, Lane B is Relaxed + Wheat Germplasm Topoisomerase 1 + water, Lane C is Relaxed + Wheat Germplasm Topoisomerase 1 + DMSO, Lane D is Relaxed + Wheat Germplasm Topoisomerase 1 + aqueous leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*, and Lane E is Relaxed + Wheat Germplasm Topoisomerase 1 + methanolic leaves extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

base damage (deLara et al., 1995). Hydroxyl free radicals cause 60–70% of cellular DNA damage (Mira and Pawel, 2012). The scavenging effect of the leaf extract of *Combretum platypterum* on hydroxyl radicals indicates its protective effect on DNA.

Conclusion

Combretum platypterum leaves possess antioxidant and free radical-scavenging activities. Additionally, it demonstrated the ability to shield DNA from free radical damage. The antioxidant and free radical-scavenging activities of *Combretum platypterum* leaves lend credence to their use in treating various ailments in ethnomedicine.

Acknowledgement

We sincerely acknowledge and thank the laboratory personnel, Mr. A. Barnabas of the Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Faculty of Life Sciences, for their assistance with this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

This research did not receive any specific grants from funding agencies.

article [utf8]inputenc amsmath amssymb hyperref apacite

References

- Adefegha, S. A., & Oboh, G. (2011). Cooking enhances the antioxidant properties of some tropical green leafy vegetables. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 10(4), 632–639.
- Adesina, I. A., Adebote, V. T., Elehinafe, T. R., & Enerijiofi, K. E. (2013). Growth inhibition of *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium italicum* by seed kernel oil from mango (*Mangifera indica* L.). *Journal of Natural Sciences Research*, 3(9), 61-64.
- Bei, L., Dai, Y., Liu, J., Zhuge, Q., & Li, D. (2015). The effect of dimethyl sulfoxide on supercoiled DNA relaxation catalyzed by type I topoisomerases. *BioMed Research International*, 2015, 8.
- Bongers, F., Parren, M. P. E., & Traoré, D. (2005). *Forest climbing plants of West Africa: Diversity, ecology and management*. Wallingford, United Kingdom: CABI.
- Burkill, H. M. (1985). *Useful plants of West Tropical Africa* (2nd ed.). England: Royal Botanic Gardens.
- Chávez-Mendoza, C., Sanchez, E., Muñoz-Marquez, E., Sida-Arreola, J. P., & Flores-Cordova, M. A. (2015). Bioactive compounds and antioxidant activity in different grafted varieties of bell pepper. *Antioxidants (Basel)*, 4(2), 427-446.
- Dalziel, J. M. (1973). *The useful plants of West Tropical Africa*. London: Crown Agents.
- deLara, C. M., Jenner, T. J., Townsend, K. M., Marsden, S. J., & O'Neill, P. (1995). The effect of dimethyl sulfoxide on the induction of DNA double-strand breaks in V79-4 mammalian cells by alpha particles. *Radiation Research*, 144(1), 43-49.
- Dysken, M. W. (2014). Effect of vitamin E and memantine on functional decline in Alzheimer disease: The TEAM-AD VA cooperative randomized trial. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 311, 33-44.
- Enerijiofi, K. E., & Isola, O. B. (2019). Preliminary phytochemical screening and in vitro antibacterial activities of aqueous and ethanol extracts of *Ageratum conyzoides* L. leaf, stem, flower, and root on some bacterial isolates associated with diarrhea. *Nigerian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 32(2), 3480-3489.
- Erhabor, J. O., Oshomoh, E. O., Enerijiofi, K. E., Erhabor, C. R., Ogbonnaya, C. S., & Idu, M. (2017). Antibacterial activity and phytochemical screening of the acetone extracts of the root of *Aloe vera* (L.) Burm. F. against microorganisms associated with male infertility. *Samuel Adegboyega University Science and Technology Journal*, 2(1), 7-16.
- Gill, N. S., Bajwa, J., Sharma, P., Dhiman, K., & Sood, S. (2011). Evaluation of antioxidant and antiulcer activity of traditionally consumed *Cucumis melo* seeds. *Journal of Pharmacology and Toxicology*, 6, 82–89.
- Girindrababu, V. J., Puttasiddiah, R., Krishnaswamy, K., Kandikattu, H. K., & Khanum, F. (2015). Antioxidant and DNA damage protective effects of *Asparagus racemosus* in human colon and mice muscle cells. *Pharmacognosy Journal*, 7(3), 182-190.
- Huang, D., Ou, B., & Prior, R. L. (2005). The chemistry behind antioxidant capacity assays. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 53, 1841-1856.
- Idu, M., Uwaya, D. O., & Ovuakporie-Uvom, O. (2016). In vivo antioxidant evaluation of *Combretum platypterum* and *Combretum racemosum* in rodents. *Applied Medical Research*, 2, 50-55.
- Joseph, S. V. (2014). Berries: Anti-inflammatory effects in humans. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 62, 3886-3903.
- Kamra, A., & Bhatt, A. B. (2012). Evaluation of antimicrobial and antioxidant activity of *Ganoderma lucidum* extracts against human pathogenic bacteria. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 4(2), 359-362.
- Kulawik, A., Cielecka-Piontek, J., & Zalewski, P. (2023). The importance of antioxidant activity for the health-promoting effect of lycopene. *Nutrients*, 15(17), 3821.
- Liben, L. (1983). *Combretaceae*. In *Flore du Cameroun* (Vol. 25). Paris, France: Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle.
- Mensor, L. I., Menezes, F. S., Leitao, G. G., Reis, A. S., Dos Santos, T., Coube, C. S., & Leitao, S. G. (2001). Screening of Brazilian plant extracts for antioxidant activity by the use of DPPH free radical method. *Phytotherapy Research*, 15, 127-130.
- Neuwinger, H. D. (2000). *African traditional medicine: A dictionary of plant use and applications*.

Stuttgart, Germany: Medpharm Scientific.

Nithya, M., Ambikapathy, V., & Panneerselvam, A. (2015). In vivo antioxidant and enzymatic activity of *Ganoderma lucidum* (Curt.: Fr.) P. Karst. on mammary cells of DMBA induced Sprague-Dawley rats. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 4(6), 69-77.

Ovuru, K. F., Izah, S. C., Yasmin, H., Enerijiofi, K. E., Das, M., & Ogwu, M. C. (2023). Microbial contaminants of herbal remedies: Health risks and sustainable quality control strategies. In S. C. Izah, M. C. Ogwu, & M. Akram (Eds.), *Herbal medicine phytochemistry. Reference series in phytochemistry* (pp. 1-30). Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21973-3_9 – 1 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21973-3_9

Owolabi, O. J., Omogbai, E. K. I., & Oduru, E. E. (2008). Antidiarrhoeal evaluation of the aqueous leaves extracts of *Costus lucanusianus* family Costaceae. *Journal of Applied Science Research*, CO: CC-CC.

Forte, P., Leoni, L., Sampaiole, B., & Savino, M. (1989). Cooperativity in nucleosome assembly on supercoiled pBR322 DNA. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 17(21), 8683-8694.

Peng, J. (2014). Dysfunctional endothelial progenitor cells in cardiovascular diseases: Role of NADPH oxidase. *Journal of Cardiovascular Pharmacology*, 65, 80-87.

Perusek, L., & Maeda, T. (2013). Vitamin A derivatives as treatment options for retinal degenerative diseases. *Nutrients*, 5(7), 2646-2666.

Ruch, R. J., Cheng, S. J., & Klaunig, J. E. (1989). Prevention of cytotoxicity and inhibition of intracellular communication by antioxidant catechins isolated from Chinese green tea.

Russo, A., Acquaviva, R., Campisi, A., Di Giacomo, C., & Virgata, G. (2000). Bioflavonoids as antiradicals, antioxidants, and DNA cleavage protectors. *Cell Biology and Toxicology*, 16(2), 11-98.

Sadek, K., Abouzed, T., & Nasr, S. (2016). Lycopene modulates cholinergic dysfunction, Bcl-2/Bax balance, and antioxidant enzymes gene transcripts in monosodium glutamate (E621) induced neurotoxicity in a rat model. *Canadian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, 94(4), 394-401.

Shinde, V., Kamlesh, D., Paradkar, A. R., Mahadik, K. R., & Kadam, S. S. (2006). Evaluation of in vitro antioxidant activity of human placental extract.

Pharmacologyonline, 3, 172-179.

Suprava, S., Goutam, G., Debajyoti, D., & Sanghamitra, N. (2013). Phytochemical investigation and in vitro antioxidant activity of an indigenous medicinal plant *Alpinia nigra* B. L. Burtt. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 3(11), 871-876.

Trejo-Solís, C., Pedraza-Chaverri, J., Torres-Ramos, M., Jiménez-Farfán, D., Cruz Salgado, A., Serrano-García, N., Osorio-Rico, L., & Sotelo, J. (2013). Multiple molecular and cellular mechanisms of action of lycopene in cancer inhibition. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2013, 705121.

Uwaya, O. D., Omozuwa, P. O., & Inegbedion, R. E. (2021). Evaluation of in vitro antioxidant and antidiarrheal activities of *Peperomia pellucida* methanol extracts on albino mice. *Journal of Applied Science and Environmental Management*, 25(9), 1681-1688.

Wang, Y., Chun, O. K., & Song, W. O. (2013). Plasma and dietary antioxidant status as cardiovascular disease risk factors: A review of human studies. *Nutrients*, 5(8), 2969-3004.

Phytochemical screening and antioxidant investigation of *Persea americana*

ISAH, A.* , ODIA, A.E., OBRIFOR, E.E., IKHENEMUE, O.O., AND SULEIMAN, A.

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, P.M.B 14, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

Department of Science Lab. Technology, School of Applied Sciences, Auchi Polytechnic, P.M.B 13, Auchi, Edo State, Nigeria.

Corresponding author: ISAH, A.

Email: abdulhakeemisah@aauekpoma.edu.ng Tel: +2347068373795

Abstract: This work investigated the phytochemical and antioxidant properties of aqueous and ethanol extract of the leaves, stem bark, seeds, and roots of *Persea americana*. The results of the qualitative phytochemical screening showed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, phenols, steroids, terpenoids, and flavonoids. Antioxidant activities were assayed using 1,1-Diphenyl-2-Picryl Hydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging capacity, reductive potentials, and 2,2-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS) radical scavenging. Results obtained from 15 μ g/ml of all extracts had the least percentage DPPH radicals, the values of DPPH for the leaves, stem bark, seeds, and root were 14.59 ± 0.21 , 6.24 ± 0.04 , 3.53 ± 0.12 , 9.75 ± 0.17 , and 1.66 ± 0.09 respectively. The values of percentage DPPH radical scavenging increased with extract concentration. Just like DPPH radical scavenging, reducing power also increases with the concentration of extract. However, the leaves showed a higher percentage reductive power. The half maximal Inhibitory Concentration (IC₅₀) and the maximal Effective Concentration (EC₅₀) of extracts revealed that percentage values of ABTS were higher than those of DPPH in all samples. The EC₅₀ of the reducing power showed variation in values, however, *P. americana* seeds sample had the highest value for reducing power (33.12 ± 0.01).

Keywords: Alkaloids, Antioxidant, inhibitory, macerated, medicinal plant, phytochemical

Introduction

Medicinal plants have continued to attract attention in the global search for effective antimicrobial agents that can combat resistant pathogens that have been rendering many conventional drugs obsolete in the treatment of infections. Many important drugs used in medicine today are directly or indirectly derived from plants. The most important of these bioactive constituents of plants are alkaloids, tannins, steroids, terpenoids and phenolic compounds.

Phytochemicals are biologically active, naturally occurring chemical compounds found in all the parts of plants. They protect plants from various diseases and contribute to plants' aroma, flavour and colour. In recent years, secondary plant metabolites previously with unknown pharmacological activities have been extensively investigated as sources of medicinal agents. It is anticipated that phytochemicals with adequate antimicrobial efficacy will thus be used for the treatment of bacterial infections. Despite abundant literature on the antimicrobial properties

of plant extracts, most of the plant-derived chemicals have not successfully been exploited for clinical use as antibiotics. A significant part of the chemical diversity produced by plants is thought to protect plants against microbial pathogens.

Persea americana is one of the 150 varieties of avocado pear. It is widely cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions of West Africa. It grows into a tree with a height of about 80 feet. It has leathery, evergreen leaves, and its flowers are rarely unisexual. The seed of *Persea americana* has diverse applications in ethnomedicine, ranging from treatment of diarrhea, dysentery, toothache, and intestinal parasites to skin treatment and beautification. The leaves have been reported to possess anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities. The seeds are rich in tannins, carotenoids, and tocopherols. The fruit has been shown to inhibit the in-vitro growth of prostate cancer cell lines, and "persin" from avocado leaves has been shown to have antifungal properties and to be toxic to silkworms.

Figure 1: MAP SHOWING THE LOCATION OF IKABIGBO COMMUNITY

The effect of *P. americana* extract was evaluated on in-vitro rat lymphocyte proliferation. Antioxidant activity and phenolic content of seeds of avocado pear were found to be greater than 70

In this study, the phytochemical and antioxidant activity of extracts of *P. americana* tree was carried out with a view to provide more scientific basis on the claim by traditional healers of its uses in traditional medicine in the context of the continued search for active therapeutic agents from plants.

Materials and Methods

Location

MAP SHOWING THE LOCATION OF IKABIGBO COMMUNITY

Sample Collection/Identification

Samples of the leaves, seed, stem, and root of *Persea americana* were obtained from a farm settlement in Ikabigbo, Uzairue, Etsako West Local Government Area of Edo state, Nigeria. The samples were authenticated in the herbarium laboratory of Botany Department, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. The samples were rinsed with distilled water, air-dried in the laboratory for about a month, and then pulverized with a ceramic mortar and pestle.

Preparation of Extracts

Pulverized leaves, seed, stem, and root were extracted using 80% ethanol and distilled water as solvents as follows: each of the pulverized samples was put in glass containers and the ethanol was added to each

container; the same setup was repeated with distilled water as solvent for the aqueous extract. The setup was left for about 72 hours and agitated 6-hourly for the extraction of the bioactive components into the solvent. The solution was filtered with muslin cloth to remove the supernatant, and the leaves, seed, stem, and root shafts remaining as residues. The crude extract was obtained by evaporating the solvent using a rotary evaporator. The extracts obtained were then transferred into airtight glass containers for further analysis. Both the ethanolic and aqueous crude extracts were analyzed for phytochemical screening while only the aqueous extracts were investigated for antioxidant properties.

Phytochemical Screening

The preliminary phytochemical screening of the ethanolic and aqueous extracts of leaves, seed, stem, and root of *P. americana* were carried out in order to ascertain the presence of its phytoconstituents by utilizing standard conventional protocols. The extracts were screened for the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, phenolics, steroids, terpenes, flavonoids, and cardiac glycosides as reported by Irabor et al.

Antioxidant Activity

Aqueous extracts of the plant parts were utilized for the antioxidants assay.

1,1-Diphenyl-2-PicrylHydrazyl (DPPH) Assay

The antioxidant activity by DPPH assay was carried out as described by Molyneux, using the stable free radical DPPH. To 1 ml of various concentrations of the extract, 1 ml of 0.1 mM DPPH was added to the test tube. Ascorbic acid was used as the standard for comparison. After incubation for 30 mins in the dark at room temperature, absorbance was read at 517 nm. The percent DPPH radical scavenging was calculated with the equation below and the experiment was carried out in triplicate.

Reductive Potential (Ferric cyanide (Fe^{3+}) Reducing Antioxidant Power Assay)

Reducing power of the extracts was measured by the direct reduction of $\text{Fe}^{3+}(\text{CN})_6$ to $\text{Fe}^{2+}(\text{CN})_6$ and was determined by absorbance measurement of the formation of the Perl's Prussian Blue complex following the addition of excess Fe^{3+} , as described previously. Different concentrations of extracts in 0.5

mL of distilled water were mixed with 1.25 mL of 0.2 M, pH 6.6 sodium phosphate buffer and 1.25 mL of potassium ferricyanide $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]$ (1%). The mixture was incubated at 50 °C for 20 min. After 20 min incubation, the reaction mixture was acidified with 1.25 mL of trichloroacetic acid (10%). Finally, 0.5 mL of $FeCl_3$ (0.1%) was added to this solution and the absorbance was measured at 700 nm in a spectrophotometer. Increased absorbance of the reaction mixture indicates greater reducing capability.

2,2-Azino-Bis(3-Ethylbenzothiazoline-6-Sulfonic Acid) (ABTS) Radical Scavenging Assay

The scavenging activity of extracts against ABTS radical was determined by following the method described by Roberta et al. with little modification. Briefly, the mixture of stock solutions of 7 mM ABTS and 2.4 mM potassium persulphate ($K_2S_2O_8$) in equal volumes were allowed to stand in the dark for 12-16 h at room temperature. Prior to assay, ABTS solution was diluted in ethanol to give an absorbance of 0.700 ± 0.02 at 734 nm. 2800 μ l of the resulting solutions was allowed to react with 200 μ l of the plant extracts with different concentrations. The reaction mixture was incubated at room temperature for 30 min and absorbance was read at 734 nm. The same was done for the ascorbic acid standard of various concentrations (15 – 150 g/ml).

Statistical Analysis

All assays were carried out in triplicates and results were expressed as mean \pm SEM. The data was subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the differences between various concentrations were determined by Tukey's multiple comparisons test using GraphPad Prism 8.0 statistical. The P values of ≤ 0.05 were considered significant. The IC_{50} and EC_{50} values were estimated by nonlinear curve-fitting and presented as their respective 95% confidence limits.

1 Results and Discussion

The phytochemical screening of *P. americana* revealed the presence of some of the phytochemicals screened and are shown in Table 1. The phytochemical screening revealed the presence of flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, terpenes and steroids, phenolics and tannins. Saponins were conspicuously absent in the aqueous extract of *P. americana* seed. Terpenoids and steroids are absent in ethanol extracts of *P. americana* stem; this is in agreement with Doughari

(2012). Also, the absence of alkaloids was recorded in the aqueous extract of *P. americana* leaves.

These phytochemicals are known to support bioactive activities in medicinal plants and may therefore be responsible for the antioxidant properties of the leaves, seed, stem, and root. Alkaloids have been associated with medicinal uses for centuries and one of their common biological properties is their cytotoxicity [?]. Tannins are generally known to be useful in the treatment of inflamed and ulcerated tissues and have remarkable activity in cancer prevention [?]. Thus, the presence of these phytochemical constituents in *P. americana* may justify the plant's inclusion in folk preparation of the popular antimalarial potion, "Agbo" in the west and central African region, particularly in Nigeria.

The antioxidant properties analyzed were assessed with regard to their antioxidant activity as typified by their reducing power and free radical scavenging ability. Data obtained showed that *P. americana* possessed strong antioxidant activities, although the ranking of antioxidant activity of samples may vary with the analytical methods because of different mechanisms for each analysis. Hence the choice of DPPH and ABTS radical scavenging activity in this research work is due to the fact that they are the most widely used and reliable methods for screening the antioxidant activity of plant extracts.

The DPPH radical scavenging of the studied plant leaves, seed, stem, and root extracts showed a good scavenging activity as shown in Table 2. Figure 1 compares the DPPH radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* root with standard ascorbic acid. *P. americana* exhibited high radical scavenging activities at 30 to 150 μ g/ml and it was revealed that extracts were dose-dependent. Figure 2 shows DPPH radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* stem at varying concentrations. Figure 3 compares the DPPH radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* root with standard ascorbic acid. Figure 4 compares the DPPH radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* leaves with ascorbic acid.

There was a statistically significant difference between extracts and ascorbic acid used as standard ($p < 0.05$). The scavenging effects of all extracts at a concentration of 150 μ g/ml were 34.84 – 39.90%. The scavenging activity was not as good for the *P. americana* ($17.43 \pm 0.56\%$ for the seed, $25.27 \pm 0.39\%$ for the leaves, $38.03 \pm 0.36\%$ for the stem,

Table 1: Table 1: Phytochemicals in aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Persea americana*

Phytochemicals	P. americana aqueous extract				P. americana ethanolic extract			
	Seed	leaves	stem	Root	Seed	leaves	stem	Root
Alkaloids	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Saponins	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Terpene/steroids	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
Phenolics	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Tannins	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

KEY: + = present, - = absent

Table 2: **Table 2:** DPPH radical scavenging (%) of ascorbic acid and extracts of leaves, seed, stem, and root of *P. americana* at varying concentrations

Extracts ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Ascorbic acid	Leaves	Seed	Stem	Root
15	14.59 \pm 0.62	8.65 \pm 0.07	7.12 \pm 0.33	2.21 \pm 0.29	5.46 \pm 0.21
30	31.26 \pm 0.33	8.96 \pm 0.07	15.21 \pm 0.36	10.71 \pm 0.13	13.58 \pm 0.26
60	41.26 \pm 2.85	27.38 \pm 0.49	19.09 \pm 0.09	13.33 \pm 0.21	19.43 \pm 0.19
90	62.92 \pm 1.46	32.11 \pm 0.45	24.19 \pm 0.31	20.90 \pm 0.15	20.36 \pm 0.60
120	77.09 \pm 0.24	34.64 \pm 0.04	26.42 \pm 0.12	27.30 \pm 0.11	24.35 \pm 0.21
150	90.91 \pm 0.15	39.90 \pm 0.39	40.21 \pm 0.55	36.85 \pm 0.15	34.84 \pm 0.12

(All values are expressed as mean \pm standard error of three replicates. Values in the same range along the same row are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$.)

and 40.86% for the root) as compared to ascorbic acid. DPPH radical scavenging activities of the extracts were dose-dependent; the radical scavenging activities increased with concentrations of extracts. Results obtained from DPPH radicals scavenging suggest that DPPH radical was significantly bound by the extracts of leaves of *P. americana* (with IC₅₀ value of $44.25 \pm 1.59 \mu\text{g/ml}$). These values of extract scavenging abilities are comparable to that of ascorbic acid (with IC₅₀ value of $37.57 \pm 0.22 \mu\text{g/ml}$) as shown in Table 5, showing no significant difference ($P < 0.05$).

Results for the ABTS assay are presented in Table 4, and the inhibiting power was found to be dosage-dependent. Figure 5 compares the ABTS radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* leaves and ascorbic acid. Figure 6 compares the ABTS radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* seed and ascorbic acid. Figure 7 shows ABTS radical scavenging activity of extracts of *P. americana* stem at varying concentrations. Figure 8 compares the ABTS radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* root with “standard” ascorbic acid.

ABTS assay is an excellent tool for determining

Figure 2: DPPH radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* seed at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAS, *P. americana* seed. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM (n = 3), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not statistically different $p < 0.05$).

the antioxidant activity of hydrogen-donating antioxidants and chain-breaking antioxidants. The extracts of *P. americana* effectively scavenged ABTS radicals generated by the reaction between 2,2-azinobis (3-ethylbenzothiazolin-6-sulphonic acid) (ABTS) ammonium persulphate. Table 4 shows the activity of extracts of the plant parts, and the ascorbic acid standard was found to

Table 3: ABTS radical scavenging (%) of extracts of leaves, seed, stem, and root of *Persea americana*

Extracts ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Ascorbic acid	Leaves	Seed	Stem	Root
15	17.33 \pm 0.25	2.68 \pm 0.19	6.69 \pm 0.31	6.39 \pm 0.24	2.14 \pm 0.27
30	22.60 \pm 0.54	6.09 \pm 0.47	6.68 \pm 0.10	9.23 \pm 0.53	4.32 \pm 0.36
60	48.34 \pm 0.40	7.62 \pm 0.10	7.86 \pm 0.38	10.15 \pm 0.34	7.79 \pm 0.27
90	61.13 \pm 0.17	13.82 \pm 0.56	11.28 \pm 0.28	21.31 \pm 1.37	14.04 \pm 0.08
120	77.70 \pm 0.18	21.03 \pm 0.39	11.44 \pm 0.54	26.83 \pm 0.68	29.31 \pm 0.27
150	98.58 \pm 0.24	25.27 \pm 0.39	17.43 \pm 0.56	38.03 \pm 0.36	40.86 \pm 0.51

(All values are expressed as mean \pm standard error of three replicates. Values in the same range along the same row are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3: DPPH radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* stem at varying concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAsT, *P. americana* stem. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars along the same group are significantly different $p < 0.05$).

Figure 4: DPPH radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* root at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAR, *P. americana* root. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different $p < 0.05$).

increase in a dose-dependent manner from 2.68 to 52.27% (*P. americana* leaves), 6.69 to 17.43% (*P. americana* seed), 6.39 to 38.03% (*P. americana* stem), 2.14 to 40.86% (*P. americana* root), and 17.33 to 98.58% (ascorbic acid standard) at different concentrations from 15 to 150 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The extracts of *P. americana* seed, *P. americana* leaves, and the standard ascorbic acid exhibited comparative IC50 values of 55.68 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 78.68 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and 55.42 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. Therefore, the recorded IC50 values for the extracts of the plant indicated their ability to scavenge free radicals, thereby preventing lipid oxidation via a chain-breaking reaction.

The results of the reducing power assay of *P. americana* extracts are summarized in Table 4. Figure 9 compares the reducing power of leaves of *P. americana* with ascorbic acid used as a standard. Increase in absorbance indicates an increase in reducing power. Figure 10 compares the reducing power of seed of *P. americana* with ascorbic acid used

as a standard. Increase in absorbance indicates an increase in reducing power. Extracts and the standard are dose-dependent. Figure 11 shows the reducing power of root of *P. americana* and ascorbic acid used as a standard. Increase in absorbance indicates an increase in reducing power. Figure 12 shows the reducing power of stem of *P. americana* and ascorbic acid used as a standard. Increase in absorbance indicates an increase in reducing power.

High absorbance depicts high reducing power. The data obtained in this study showed that all the extracts are dose dependent; that is, absorbance increased with concentration. Among the tested extracts, *P. americana* leaves showed the highest reducing power ($EC_{50} = 19.58 \pm 0.10 \mu\text{g/ml}$). This value was even higher than that of ascorbic acid ($EC_{50} = 21.99 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{g/ml}$). The reducing capacity of a compound may serve as a significant indicator of its potential antioxidant activity. The reducing properties are generally associated with the antioxidant action

Table 4: Reducing power of extracts of leaves, seed, stem, and root of *P. americana* at varying concentrations

Extracts ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Ascorbic acid	Leaves	Seed	Stem	Root
15	0.075 \pm 0.002	0.018 \pm 0.002	0.006 \pm 0.001	0.024 \pm 0.001	0.013 \pm 0.001
30	0.157 \pm 0.004	0.054 \pm 0.001	0.016 \pm 0.004	0.036 \pm 0.005	0.017 \pm 0.003
60	0.352 \pm 0.001	0.117 \pm 0.018	0.024 \pm 0.003	0.094 \pm 0.004	0.050 \pm 0.002
90	0.483 \pm 0.006	0.172 \pm 0.015	0.067 \pm 0.005	0.142 \pm 0.003	0.090 \pm 0.011
120	0.647 \pm 0.004	0.174 \pm 0.016	0.095 \pm 0.003	0.174 \pm 0.002	0.114 \pm 0.009
150	0.912 \pm 0.007	0.269 \pm 0.001	0.290 \pm 0.008	0.241 \pm 0.010	0.137 \pm 0.004

(All

values are expressed as mean \pm standard error of three replicates. Values in the same range along the same row are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$.)

Figure 5: DPPH radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of leaves of *P. americana* at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAL, *P. americana* leaves. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different $p < 0.05$).

Figure 7: ABTS radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* seed at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAS, *P. americana* seed. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 6: ABTS radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of leaves of *P. americana* at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAL, *P. americana* leaves. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 8: ABTS radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* stem at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAsT, *P. americana* stem. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different, $p < 0.05$).

of reductones. Gordon (1990) reported that the antioxidant action of reductones is based on the breaking of the free radical chain by donating a hydrogen ion. The reduction of ferrous iron (Fe^{3+})

to ferric iron (Fe^{2+}) is measured by the intensity of the resultant blue-green solution which absorbs at 700 nm. The results linked the marked ferric reducing power activity of the extract to the presence of

Figure 9: ABTS radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* root at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAR, *P. americana* root. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM (n = 3), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different, $p < 0.05$).

polyphenols, which may act similarly to reductones by donating electrons and reacting with free radicals to convert them into more stable products and terminate free radical chain reactions (Muanya, 2007).

Figure 10: Reducing power of extracts of leaves of ascorbic acid and *P. americana* at different concentrations. AAC, ascorbic acid; PAL, *P. americana* leaves. (The bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of three replicate values)

Conclusion

In the present study, the aqueous extracts of leaves, seed, stem, and root of *P. americana* were found to contain phytochemicals, as revealed in both aqueous and ethanolic extracts. Antioxidant and radical scavenging activities, as assessed through various models including DPPH, ABTS, and reducing power assays, demonstrated that the plant parts analyzed have significant potential in radical scavenging compared to ascorbic acid, a standard antioxidant.

Figure 11: Reducing power of extracts of seed of ascorbic acid and *P. americana* at different concentrations. AAC, ascorbic acid; PAS, *P. americana* seed. (The bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of three replicate values)

Figure 12: Reducing power of extracts of root of ascorbic acid and *P. americana* at different concentrations. AAC, ascorbic acid; PAR, *P. americana* root. (The bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of three replicate values)

This supports the use of these plant parts in modern traditional medicine. The plant may also enhance the nutritional value of various foods.

All extracts exhibited concentration-dependent antioxidant and radical scavenging activities. Notably, the extracts of leaves and seeds showed the highest ability to quench DPPH radicals and scavenge ABTS radicals. In general, the leaves, seed, and stem of *P. americana* exhibit promising antioxidant effects that warrant further investigation for potential therapeutic applications. Adeyemi, O. O., Okpo, S. O., Ogunti, O. O. (2002). Analgesic and anti-inflammatory effect of the aqueous extract of leaves of *Persea americana* Mill (Lauraceae). *Fitoterapia*, 73*, 375-380.

Aiyelaja, A. A., Bello, O. A. (2006). Ethnobotanical potentials of common herbs in Nigeria. *Educational Research and Review*, 1*(1), 16-22.

Ajibesin, K. K., Ekpo, B. A., Bala, D. N., Essien,

Table 5: IC50 and EC50 of leaves, seed, stem, and root extracts of *P. americana*.

Samples	DPPH (IC50 (μg/ml))	ABTS (IC50 (μg/ml))	Reducing Power (EC50 (μg/ml))
AAC	37.57 ± 0.22	55.42 ± 1.06	21.99 ± 0.12
PAL	44.25 ± 1.59	78.68 ± 2.29	19.58 ± 0.10
PAS	62.34 ± 5.73	55.68 ± 7.42	33.12 ± 0.01
PAS _t	66.98 ± 0.64	88.16 ± 7.01	21.63 ± 0.45
PAR	50.08 ± 4.53	97.58 ± 0.55	20.65 ± 0.86

(Values are

expressed as mean ± standard error of three replicates. Values were tested by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Values with the same subset in a group are not significantly different (p<0.05). Key: PAL (*P. americana* leaves), PAS (*P. americana* seed), PAS_t (*P. americana* stem), and PAR (*P. americana* root).)

Figure 13: Reducing power of extracts of stem of ascorbic acid and *P. americana* at different concentrations. AAC, ascorbic acid; PAS_t, *P. americana* stem. (The bars represent mean ± standard deviation of three replicate values)

E. E., Adesanya, S. A. (2008). Ethnobotanical survey of Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology, 115*, 387-408.

Dan, E. U., Udo, U. E. (2012). Effect of processing on variations of some toxic metals in edible portion of *Dacryodes edulis* (African Pear) in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Annals of Food Science and Technology, 13*, 245-249.

De Sousa, D. P., Quintans, J. L., Almeida, R. N. (2007). Evaluation of the anticonvulsant activity of terpineol. *Pharmaceutics and Biology, 45*, 69-70.

Doughari, J. H. (2012). Phytochemicals: Extraction methods, basic structures and mode of action as potential chemotherapeutic agents. In *Phytochemicals: A Global Perspective*.

Firm, R. (2010). *Nature's chemicals*. Oxford University Press.

Gordon, M. H. (1990). The mechanism of antioxidant action in vitro. In B. J. F. Hudson (Ed.), *Food antioxidants*. Elsevier Applied Food Science Series. Springer.

Gülçin, İ. (2006). Antioxidant activity of caffeic acid (3, 4-dihydroxycinnamic acid). *Toxicology, 217*, 213-220.

Irabor, G. E., Ebhoaye, J. E., Odia, A. (2020). Qualitative and quantitative screening of some phytochemical compounds in watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) seeds cultivated in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State. *International Journal of Engineering Applied Sciences and Technology, 1*, 268-273.

Molyneux, P. (2004). The use of the stable free radical diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) for estimating antioxidant activity. *Songklanakarin Journal of Science and Technology, 26*(2), 211-219.

Muanya, C. A. (2007). Lipid peroxidation as an index of activity in aphrodisiac herbs. *Journal of Plant Science, 73*(09), 121-126.

Nobori, T., Miura, K., Wu, D. J., Lois, A., Takabayashi, S., Carson, D. A. (1994). Deletions of the cyclin-dependent kinase-4 inhibitor gene in multiple human cancers. *Nature, 368*, 753-756.

Ogboru, R. O., Okolie, P. L., Agboje, I. (2015). Phytochemical screening and medicinal potentials of the bark of *Dacryodes edulis* (G. Don) H. J. Lam. *Journal of Environmental and Analytical Chemistry, 2*, 158.

Oyaizu, M. (1986). Studies on product of browning reaction prepared from glucose amine. *Japanese Journal of Nutrition, 44*, 307-315.

Roberta, R. E., Pellegrini, N., Proteggente, A., Pannala, A., Yang, M., Rice-Evans, C. (1999). Free radical scavenging activity of some medicinal plants. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine, 26*, 1231-1237.

Ruch, R. J., Cheng, S. J., Klaunig, J. E. (1989). Carcinogenesis. *Reliance Chemistry Acta, 10*, 1003-1008.

COMPARISON OF THE CONCENTRATION OF PAHs IN RAW AND ROASTED BEEF SAMPLES FROM EKPOMA

OBRIFOR, E. B.¹, EGBON, E. E.¹, ISAH, A.¹, ERHABOR, D. O.³, OGONEGBU, A. C.²

¹Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

²Dennis Osadebay University, Anwai, Asaba

³Federal College of Education (Technical), Umunze, Anambra State

Corresponding author: essayshype@yahoo.com; Tel: +2348067502568

ABSTRACT

The determination of the concentration of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) in raw and roasted beef samples from Ekpoma, Edo State was the aim of the study. Samples were obtained from different suya outlets for the roasted samples, while the fresh beef were obtained from different spots in Ekpoma main market. Sixteen (16) polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in fresh and roasted beef samples were evaluated in this study. Extraction was done using a mix solvent of cyclohexane and acetone in a ratio of 50:50. Analysis was performed by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (G.C-MS). The procedure involved extraction, and adsorption column for clean-up. The cleaned fluid from samples was concentrated using a rotary evaporator and compressed air. The resulting solution was stored in vial bottles ready for PAH determination. The part of beef used for the experiment was the tissue. The various samples were run through the G.C-MS chromatography column. Results of each sample were obtained graphically. Findings revealed that of all sixteen (16) PAHs targeted, only two (2) PAHs were detected: Pyrene and Fluoranthene. Bulk of the PAHs were below detectable limits. The raw beef samples all had no PAHs detected (below detectable limits). The analysis of the raw and roasted beef samples was done in triplicates. Only roasted meat 1 (RTMT1) had the presence of Pyrene, with a concentration of 1.714 mg/kg, while roasted meat 2 (RTMT2) and roasted meat 3 (RTMT3) had the same concentration of 0.009 mg/kg of Fluoranthene. From the findings, it was observed that fresh beef samples normally do not contain PAHs, but during processing by roasting, PAHs can be introduced in some cases. Bulk of the PAHs in the roasted beef samples were below detectable limits. From the findings, the concentration of PAHs was below the recommended level: 5.0 µg/kg Benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) in smoked meat and fishery products.

Keywords: *Polycyclic Aromatic Compound, Fresh and Roasted Beef, Bos taurus*

Introduction

The increase in the case of cancerous growth is quite alarming in contemporary times. Several factors have been attributed to this effect. One of the substances which has been partly identified by scientists among the many factors is the presence of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in food consumed, especially when roasted.

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons are hydrocarbons—organic compounds containing only carbon and hydrogen—that are composed of multiple aromatic rings. PAHs are uncharged, non-polar molecules found in coal and tar deposits. They are also produced by the thermal decomposition of organic matter (Wikipedia, 2018).

PAHs occur in varying amounts in water, soil, air, and even in some food and food products like fish

and meat in trace amounts (Erhabor & Edjere, 2018). In Nigeria, meat preservation is either by smoking or drying, and in the process of preservation by drying, the shelf life is prolonged.

When food items are processed by subjecting them to heat treatment such as drying, smoking, roasting, baking, and frying, it has been reported that the amount of PAHs in them increases (Ishizaki et al., 2010). Humans are reported to obtain most of this PAH contamination from their diet (Farhadian et al., 2011). Olabemiwo (2013) reported an increase in the level of PAHs in grilled/roasted maize and plantain. The flames contain PAHs that adhere to the surface of the meat (Cross & Sinha, 2004). In barbecued meat, PAH levels were found to increase from average background values usually in the range of 0.01 to 1 g/kg in uncooked foods (meats, fish, vegetables) to 130 g/kg (Gómez-Guillén et al., 2009).

The presence of variable quantities of PAHs has been reported in different food categories and beverages including vegetables and fruits, cereals, oils and fats, smoked products (e.g., meat), coffee, and tea (Tuteja et al., 2011).

In a study carried out to investigate the levels of PAHs in singed and unsinged hides and skins of animals slaughtered at three district abattoirs (Obosi, Uga, and Kwata) in Anambra State, Ofomata et al. (2020) found the total PAHs of raw and singed cattle hides to be respectively 0.80 and 12.33 g/kg for Obosi district, 0.56 and 6.96 g/kg for Uga district, and 8.30 and 16.24 g/kg for Kwata district. The total PAHs levels in raw and singed goat skins were respectively 2.75 and 9.00 g/kg for Obosi district, 1.76 and 6.42 g/kg for Uga district, and 1.30 and 5.19 g/kg for Kwata district. The levels of some PAHs in singed hides and skins were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than in the unsinged samples.

Also, in research conducted by Akpogheli (2018) on the assessment of PAHs in smoked fish and suya meat consumed in Warri, Nigeria, the results revealed that the PAH values for grilled meat/smoked fish are far higher than those obtained from boiled water, indicating that roasting introduces and increases PAHs in food (meat).

Analysis of charcoal-roasted common food items has proven the presence of PAHs such as benzo(a)pyrene, anthracene, chrysene, benzo(a)anthracene, and indeno(1,2,3-c,d)pyrene (Linda et al., 2011). Most of these PAHs have been found to be carcinogenic, while some are not (Lijinsky, 1999). Research carried out by Akpogheli (2018) also supports this finding.

Polycyclic aromatic compounds, as chemical compounds, are known potent carcinogenic compounds. A major source of exposure is through food contaminated with PAHs (Ishizaki et al., 2010). These food substances can be contaminated either through processing (drying methods) or from the environment from which the meat is bred.

At ambient temperatures, PAHs are solids with low vapor pressure and very low water solubility, which tends to decrease with increasing molecular weights. They attach strongly to soil and other particles, break down slowly, undergo photodecomposition when exposed to ultraviolet light from solar radiation, react readily with pollutants such as ozone, nitrogen oxides, and sulfur dioxide, and can be degraded by

some microorganisms in the soil. They are soluble in many organic solvents and are highly lipophilic, meaning they mix more easily with oil than water. The larger compounds are less water-soluble and less volatile (i.e., less prone to evaporation). Because of these properties, PAHs in the environment are found primarily in soil, sediments, and oily substances. However, they are also a component of concern in particulate matter suspended in the air (Majid Kermani et al., 2023). When PAHs attach to dust or ash, they could cause lung irritation. Skin contact with PAHs may cause redness, blistering, and peeling (Hui Jin et al., 2024). The following health effects can occur after several years of exposure to PAHs:

- **Cancer:** Many PAHs are carcinogenic, producing tumors (cancer) such as benzo[a]pyrene, methyl cholanthrene, and dibenz[a,f]anthracene. Although studies in experimental animals on individual PAHs, notably benzo[a]pyrene (B[a]P), have shown various toxicological effects, including hematological effects, reproductive and developmental toxicity, and immunotoxicity, the critical effects are genotoxicity and cancer (Luch, 2005). Benzo(a)pyrene has been shown to cause lung and skin cancer in laboratory animals. Other PAHs are not known to have this effect. Extracts of various types of smoke containing PAHs have caused lung tumors in laboratory animals (Luch, 2005).
- **Toxicity:** PAH toxicity is very structurally dependent, with isomers (PAHs with the same formula and number of rings) varying from being nontoxic to extremely toxic. Highly carcinogenic PAHs may be small or large. One notable PAH compound, benzo(a)pyrene, is known as the first chemical carcinogen discovered (Luch, 2005).

Materials and Methods

Location

Ekpoma is a town in Edo State, Nigeria. It is the administrative headquarters of the Esan West Local Government Area. Ekpoma lies on the geographical coordinates of latitude $6^{\circ}45'N$ and longitude $6^{\circ}08'E$. The town has an official Post Office and is home to the Ambrose Alli University. The roasted beef (suya) samples were collected from various suya outlets in Ekpoma, Esan West L.G.A. of Edo State, Nigeria. The

raw beef samples were collected from different spots in the Ekpoma main market.

Materials

Meat Samples

1. Bos taurus commonly called beef meat (RAW)
2. Bos taurus commonly called beef meat (ROASTED)

Chemicals and Reagents

All reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade and included the following:

- Acetone (Sigma-Aldrich Corporation, United States)
- Dichloromethane (Sigma-Aldrich Corporation, United States)
- Cyclohexane (Sigma-Aldrich Corporation, United States)

The three solvents were redistilled before use to keep them free from impurities.

Sodium Sulphate: Granular and anhydrous. The sodium sulphate granules were purified by heating at 400°C for 4 hours in a shallow tray and cooled in a desiccator.

Mix 26: The internal standard or surrogate, Mix 26, comes in 1 ml vials. It was prepared by diluting a 1 ml solution containing 4000 ng/ μ l in 100 ml of dichloromethane. The solution, which contains 40 ng/100 ml, has a fluorescent green color.

Equipment/Apparatus

The equipment/apparatus used include:

- Water bath
- Vials and corks
- Test tubes
- Round bottom flasks
- Rotary evaporator
- Thermometer
- Silica gel packed cartridges
- Conical flasks
- Retort stands
- Weighing balance
- Spatula
- Beakers
- Volumetric pipettes: 1 ml, 5 ml, and 10 ml
- Micro syringes: 10 μ L, 100 μ L, 250 μ L, 500 μ L, 1000 μ L
- Drying oven
- Desiccator
- Blender
- Ultrasonic bath
- SPE cartridges with stand
- Gas chromatography instrument
- Oven and drier

Method

Sampling Area

Ekpoma, Esan West L.G.A. of Edo State, Nigeria, was the sampling location.

Sample Collection

The roasted meat samples, *Bos taurus* commonly called suya, were collected from three different locations in Ekpoma:

- Ujuolen junction axis (RTMT 1), a very busy junction with high traffic and vehicular activity
- Ekpoma market square axis (RTMT 2)
- New market axis (RTMT 3)

Composite sampling was applied at these locations to obtain representative samples.

The fresh cow meat samples, *Bos taurus* commonly called beef meat, were collected from three different locations in Ekpoma:

- Ekpoma market square axis (FRMT 1)
- New market axis (FRMT 2)
- Hausa market axis (FRMT 3)

Composite sampling was also used at these locations.

The samples were kept in polythene bags, properly labeled, placed in coolers with ice, and transported to Earth Quest Laboratory, Otokutu, Warri, Delta State, where they were stored in a refrigerator at 4°C prior to further processing.

Sample Preparation

The fresh meat samples from the sampling sites were washed and re-rinsed with distilled water. The fresh and roasted samples were separately ground using a Mikachi meat grinder, homogenized using a laboratory pestle and mortar, and then stored in a refrigerator at 4°C prior to extraction and analysis.

Extraction and Clean-Up of Samples

The fresh and roasted meat samples were separately ground using a blender (Mikachi meat grinder). The blender was washed, rinsed, and re-rinsed with distilled water after each use. Fifty grams of each meat sample was mixed with 25 g of sodium sulphate and 200 ml of a 50/50 cyclohexane/acetone mixture in a tightly covered bottle, with 10 ml of Mix 26 internal standard added to each bottle. The bottles containing the sample, solvents mixture, sodium sulphate, and internal standard were placed inside an ultrasonic bath (Astrabro ultrasonic cleaner, model 7E) for 2 hours, with shaking every 10 minutes.

Twenty-five milliliters of the extract was collected using a pipette and filler, concentrated using a rotary evaporator to 5 ml, and then further concentrated to 1 ml using compressed air. The clean-up was done using a solid phase extractor, and cyclohexane was employed as the eluting solvent. The cleaned-up sample was concentrated to 1 ml using compressed air, stored in 1 ml vials, and subjected to GC analysis using an FID detector.

Gas Chromatography Operating Procedure

Instrument type: Gas chromatography system 6890 series

Product: HP

Detector type: FID

The basic chromatography parameters for the analysis of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons are as follows:

- Initial Temperature: 100°C
- Rate 1: 4°C/min
- Final Temperature: 330°C
- Detector Temperature: 300°C

One milliliter extracts of both the *Clarias gariepinus* (raw and roasted) and *Bos taurus* (raw and roasted) kept in vials were analyzed using GC-MS model QP2010SE, Shimadzu, Japan.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Polynuclear Hydrocarbon Content (mg/kg)

The summary of the concentration of various Polynuclear Aromatic Compounds (PAHs) present in raw and roasted meat samples is shown in Table 1. Table 2 shows the comparison of results between raw meat and roasted meat samples. This research was conducted to determine the presence and concentration of 16 PAHs in raw and roasted meat samples from Ekpoma, Edo State. The results showed that not all 16 targeted PAHs were present in the raw and roasted meat samples. A total of only two PAHs were observed in the samples: Pyrene and Fluoranthene. The concentration of PAHs in the samples is shown in Table 2.

No PAHs were detected in any of the raw meat samples labeled FRMT 1, FRMT 2, and FRMT 3. This result is consistent with other researchers' findings

Table 1: Polynuclear Hydrocarbon Content (mg/kg)

COMPONENT	FRMT1	FRMT2	FRMT3	RTMT1	RTMT2	RTMT3
Naphthalene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Acenaphthalene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Acenaphthene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Florene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Phenanthrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Anthracene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Fluoranthene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.009	0.009
Pyrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.714	0.000	0.000
Benzo(a)anthracene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Chrysene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Benzo(b)fluoranthrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Benzo(a)pyrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Benzo(k)fluoranthrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Total PAH (mg/kg)	BDL	BDL	BDL	1.714	0.009	0.009

Note: Each of the coded samples are averages of triplicate measurements of representative samples from each sampling spot.

KEY: RTMT – ROASTED MEAT; FRMT – RAW MEAT; BDL – BELOW DETECTABLE LIMIT

that raw foods typically do not contain high levels of PAHs, which are generally formed during processing such as roasting, baking, smoking, or frying (Amos-Tauta, Inengite, Abasi, & Amirize, 2013). For example, a study by Ofomata, I. B. et al. (2020) investigating PAH levels in singed and unsinged hides and skins of animals slaughtered at three district abattoirs (Obosi, Uga, and Kwata) in Anambra State found that total PAHs in raw and singed cattle hides were 0.80 and 12.33 g/kg for Obosi district, 0.56 and 6.96 g/kg for Uga district, and 8.30 and 16.24 g/kg for Kwata district. Similarly, total PAHs in raw and singed goat skins were 2.75 and 9.00 g/kg for Obosi district, 1.76 and 6.42 g/kg for Uga district, and 1.30 and 5.19 g/kg for Kwata district. The levels of some PAHs in singed hides and skins were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than in unsinged samples.

The concentration of PAHs in roasted meat (suya) samples in our study, RTMT 1, RTMT 2, and RTMT 3, ranged between 0.009 to 1.714 mg/kg. The total average PAHs level in suya was 0.576 mg/kg.

Table 2. Concentration (mg/kg) levels of PAHs in raw and roasted meat

[h!]

The results of the raw beef samples were comparable with the report of Amos-Tauta et al. (2013), where the PAH concentrations were below detectable limits. However, the roasted meat (suya) samples showed the presence of Pyrene and Fluoranthene. This could be due to the processing location of the roasted meat. RTMT 1 was sourced from Ujuoelen junction axis, a very busy spot with heavy vehicle activity. Akpoghelie (2018) noted that poor road networks and potholes can increase traffic congestion, leading to higher PAH emissions. To determine the source of PAHs in samples, whether from pyrolytic, combustive, petrogenic, or petroleum hydrocarbon origins, the ratios of Fluoranthene (Fla) to Pyrene (Pyr) and Phenanthrene (Ph) to Anthracene (An) are often used. A ratio of Fluoranthene to Pyrene greater than one ($Fla/Pyr > 1$) indicates a pyrolytic source, while $Fla/Pyr < 1$ suggests a petroleum hydrocarbon source. Similarly, a Phenanthrene to

Table 2: Concentration (mg/kg) levels of PAHs in raw and roasted meat

PAHs	FRMT1	FRMT2	FRMT3	AVERAGE	RTMT1	RTMT2	RTMT3
AVERAGE							
Pyrene 0.570	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.714	0.000	0.000
Fluoranthene 0.006	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.009	0.009
TOTAL 0.576	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.714	0.009	0.009

Anthracene ratio less than ten (Ph/An \leq 10) indicates a combustion source, while Ph/An $>$ 10 suggests a petrogenic source. In this study, the PAHs in the roasted meat can be attributed to a pyrolytic source, as the ratio is $>$ 1.

The PAHs concentration of RTMT 1 was higher than that of RTMT 2 and RTMT 3. Apart from the busy location where the sample (RTMT 1) was sourced, other factors that could affect the results include the part of the beef (muscle) used, as some parts may have higher fat content; the method of preparation; the length of cooking; and the amount of heat used (Akpogheli, 2018).

Figure 1: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon Content (mg/kg)

Figure 1: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon Content (mg/kg)

KEY: ROASTED MEAT: RTMT; RAW MEAT: FRMT

The highest concentration of total PAHs was detected in RTMT 1, with a concentration of 1.71 mg/kg, and the lowest in FRMT 1, FRMT 2, and RTMT 3, all having concentrations below detectable limits.

The total PAHs concentration can be attributed to the temperature of heating and the particle size of PAHs sorbed into organic matter. High-temperature heating tends to produce high molecular weight PAHs (Choi et al., 2010). High molecular weight PAHs, which have more than four rings, are more likely to be formed. Pyrene was detected in RTMT 1. Additionally, two- to four-ringed PAHs volatilize sufficiently to appear in the atmosphere in gaseous form, with their physical state depending on temperature (Walker et al., 2013). High temperatures generate high molecular weight PAHs, while low temperatures generate low molecular weight PAHs (Wikipedia, 2018). This could explain the high concentration of Pyrene.

Conclusion

The results of the six (6) samples in this study showed a total of two (2) PAH compounds present. Total PAH concentrations for roasted meat samples were higher than those of raw meat. This is because, when food, particularly meat and meat products, are smoked, roasted, barbecued, or grilled, PAHs are formed as a result of incomplete combustion or thermal decomposition of the organic material (WHO, 2006). According to the results of this research, the concentration of PAHs is above the recommended level of 5.0 g/kg or 0.005 g/g BaP in smoked meat and the 2 g/kg fixed by European standards (Akpogheli, 2018). No PAHs were detected in the fresh beef samples. It was also observed that when raw meat is roasted, the amount of PAHs increases, and new PAHs can be formed in the process.

From the foregoing analysis, caution must therefore be taken because of the adverse effects posed by exposure to PAHs through food, such as genotoxicity, mutagenicity, and carcinogenicity. This research sought to compare the concentration of samples based on location, as this is a factor in the presence and

concentration of PAHs in food samples.

References

Akpogheli, O. J. (2018). Assessment of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons on smoked fish and suya meat consumed in Warri, Nigeria. *Journal of Chemical Society*, 43(3), 422-431.

Amos-Tauta, B. M. W., Inengite, A. K., Abasi, C. Y., & Amirize, G. C. (2013). Evaluation of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons and some heavy metals in roasted food snacks in Amassoma, Niger Delta, Nigeria. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 17(10), 961-966.

Choi, H., Harrison, R., Komulainen, H., & Delgado, S. J. (2010). Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. In *WHO Guidelines for Indoor Air Quality: Selected Pollutants*. Geneva: World Health Organization.

Cross, A. J., & Sinha, R. (2004). Meat-related mutagens/carcinogens in the etiology of colorectal cancer. *Environmental and Molecular Mutagenesis*, 44, 44-45.

Erhabor, O. D., & Edjere, O. (2018). Bioaccumulation of PAHs in fishes from Ogidigben-Escravos Estuaries. *Nigerian Journal of Chemical Research*, 23(2), 63-70.

Farhadian, A., Jinap, S., Hanifah, H., & Zaidul, I. (2011). Effects of meat preheating and wrapping on the levels of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in charcoal-grilled meat. *Food Chemistry*, 56, 141-146.

Gómez-Guillén, M. C., Gómez-Estaca, J., Giménez, B., & Montero, P. (2009). Alternative fish species for cold-smoking process. *International Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 44, 1525-1535.

Jin, H., Lin, Z., Pang, T., Wu, J., Zhao, C., Zhang, Y., Lei, Y., Li, Q., Yao, X., Zhao, M., & Lu, Q. (2024). Effects and mechanisms of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in inflammatory skin diseases. *Journal of Science of The Total Environment*, 925, 171492.

Ishizaki, A., Saito, K., Hanioka, N., Narimatsu, S., & Kataoka, H. (2010). Determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in food samples by automated on-line in-tube solid phase microextraction coupled with high performance liquid chromatography-fluorescence detection. *Journal of Chromatography*, 1217, 5555-5563.

Lijinsky, W. (1999). The formation and occurrence of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons associated with foods. *Journal of Mathematical Research*, 259(3-4),

251-261.

Linda, M. N., Carboo, P. D., Yeboah, P. O., Quasie, W. J., Mordecai, A., Gorleku, M. A., & Darko, A. (2011). Characterization of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) present in smoked fish from Ghana. *Advanced Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 3(5), 332-335.

Luch, A. (2005). The carcinogenic effect of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon. Retrieved from *World Scientific* website: <http://www.worldscientific.com>

Majid Kermani, F. T., Ahmad Jonidi Jafari, M. G., Abbas Shahsavani, & Pegah Nakhjirgan. (2023). PAHs pollution in the outdoor air of areas with various land uses in the industrial city of Iran: Distribution, source apportionment, and risk assessment. *Heliyon*, 9(6), e17357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17357>

Oforomata, I. B., Nwankwo, I. O., Ogugua, A. J., Ezenduka, E. V., Vwanta, J. A., & Obidike, R. I. (2020). Detection of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in hide and skin of slaughtered cattle and goats in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Food Quality and Hazard Control*, 7, 119-127.

Okoronkwo, N. E., Mba, O. I., & Ajuonuma, O. A. (2014). Evaluation of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons level in roasted food samples. *Academic Journal of Science*, 3(1), 1-8.

Olabemiwo, O. M. (2013). Levels of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon in grilled/roasted maize and plantain sold in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. *International Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 13(3), 87-93.

Tuteja, G., Rout, C., & Bishnoi, N. R. (2011). Quantification of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in leaf and underground vegetables: A case study around Panipat City, Haryana, India. *Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 4, 611-620.

Walker, T. R., MacAskill, D., Rushton, T., Thalheimer, A., & Weaver, P. (2013). Monitoring effects of remediation on natural sediment recovery in Sydney Harbour, Nova Scotia. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 185(10), 8089-8107.

World Health Organization (2006). Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. In *WHO Food Additives Series 55: Safety Evaluation of Certain Contaminants in Food*. Geneva: International Programme of Chemical Safety (IPCS), World Health Organization.

Wikipedia. (2018, December 15). Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon. *Wikipedia*,

the free encyclopedia. Retrieved from
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/polycyclic_aromatic_hydrocarbon

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF NUTRIENTS AND PHYTOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF MATURED AND YOUNG LEAVES OF *Manihot esculenta*, *Arachis hypogea*, AND *Parkia biglobosa*

OGIDI, O. I.*¹, ADDY, P. S.¹

¹Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Ekowe

Corresponding author: Peresogoi@gmail.com; Tel: +2348039529426

ABSTRACT

The nutritive and phytochemical constituents of three plant leaves were investigated. The plants include: Matured *Manihot esculenta*, six weeks old *Manihot esculenta*, matured *Arachis hypogea*, two weeks old *Arachis hypogea*, matured *Parkia biglobosa* and two weeks old *Parkia biglobosa*. The nutrients and phytochemicals determined quantitatively were: soluble protein, soluble sugar, total protein, nitric oxide radical scavenging activity, saponin, alkaloid, and tannin. The results of the quantitative analysis of these plants show that all the vegetable plant leaves contained all the parameters analyzed in varying proportion. For the quantitative analysis, matured *M. esculenta* had the highest amount of total protein (36.69% FW) and saponin (0.21g/g FW), six weeks old *M. esculenta* had the highest amount of total soluble protein (0.26g/g FW), total soluble sugar (0.12g/g FW) and nitric oxide radical scavenging activity (2.25% FW), matured *P. biglobosa* had the highest amount of alkaloid (0.04g/100g FW). Two weeks old *A. hypogea*, matured *A. hypogea* and matured *P. biglobosa* had same amount of soluble protein (0.18g/g FW), matured *M. esculenta*, two weeks old *A. hypogea* and two weeks old *P. biglobosa* had same amount of alkaloid (0.02g/100g FW), matured *M. esculenta*, two weeks old *A. hypogea* and two weeks old *P. biglobosa* had same amount of tannin (0.04g/g FW) and matured *A. hypogea* and matured *P. biglobosa* had same amount of tannin (0.05g/g FW). The significance of these results showed that there are lots of phytochemicals and nutrients present in *M. esculenta*, *A. hypogea* and *P. biglobosa* leaves which can be utilized as potential vegetables in traditional Nigeria soups.

Keywords: Vegetable; Phytochemicals; Nutrients; Mature; Young; Leaves

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, especially in the Western and Southern regions of the country, many kinds of soups are made with various vegetables like pumpkin (*Cucurbita maxima*) leaves, waterleaf (*Talinum fruticosum*), bitterleaf (*Vernonia amygdalina*) which are quite rich nutritionally (Tonukari et al., 2013). A number of studies have proved that vegetables contain some nutrients such as sugars, amino acids and vitamins, which have long been recognized for their health benefits to humans (Donoghue et al., 2006; Ovuru et al., 2023). As technology and research techniques are improving, other substances in vegetables that were previously ignored are getting the spotlight. Vegetables are rich sources of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, carotenoids, anthocyanins, vitamins and other polyphenolics (Lee et al., 2005; Adesina et al., 2013). Such compounds play roles in disease prevention/reduce disease risk factors through antioxidant activity (Enerijiofi &

Isola, 2019). Researchers have identified hundreds of compounds in vegetable crops with functional qualities and they continue to make new discoveries surrounding the complex benefits of phytochemicals such as lycopene in tomatoes, curcumin in turmeric, gingerol in ginger, organosulphur compounds in allium species, omega-3 fatty acids in cucurbitaceous vegetable seeds and so on (Ram et al., 2000).

Cassava leaves are largely consumed in Africa and are among the top three African indigenous vegetables rich in nutrients (Umuhozariho et al., 2013). In Nigeria, especially in the Northern part of the country, cassava leaves are used in the preparation of soup. Cassava leaves soup is widely consumed in Central Africa. In Central Africa, cassava leaves soup is called Saka Saka or Ponda (Immaculate, 2021). The leaves of cassava are utilized as vegetables and the tuberous roots can be processed into over one hundred food types. Certain cassava varieties are mainly grown for industrial use (Fyhri, 2010). In the

rural areas, the roots and young leaves are utilized as a vegetable. Cassava “mash”, fufu, is widely consumed by pounding and sieving cassava to make flour which is then put into hot water and other cassava produce.

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogea*) belongs to the pea and beans family and is a legume. Groundnut is rich in oil and protein, and has a high energy value (Nautiyal et al., 2002). It can be eaten raw, roasted or cooked and the flour is an ingredient in many foods. Groundnut can be used in the preparation of groundnut soup with warm garri. Groundnut soup is mostly cooked by Northerners and some parts of Southern Nigeria (Nautiyal et al., 2002). Groundnut is important in vegetarian diets because of the protein it contains. It provides 13 different vitamins, especially A, the B group, C and E, along with 26 essential trace minerals, including calcium, iron, zinc and boron, and dietary fibre (Nautiyal et al., 2002). Groundnut is a rich source of fat ranging from 36 to 54% (Asibu, 2008). Groundnuts and groundnut butter are energy-rich and nutritious foods, providing a valuable supply of a wide range of vitamins, minerals and dietary fibre (Jennette, 2003).

Beans (*Parkia biglobosa*) are a tropical legume plant and have been used as a staple in the diet, and the health benefits derived from them have been well recognized. Beans are a strong, plant-based source of protein, fibre and iron that offer many health benefits (Kathy et al., 2023). Beans are nutrient-dense in that the amount of nutrients provided per calorie is particularly high. They are packed with protein, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals, and are low in fat. They are rich in lignans, which may play a role in preventing osteoporosis, heart disease, and certain cancers (Maria, 2008). Vegetables, including legumes/beans are nutrient-dense, low in kilojoules, and are a good source of minerals and vitamins (such as magnesium, vitamin C and folate), dietary fibre and a range of phytochemicals including carotenoids (Darrell et al., 2008).

This study was aimed to determine the nutritional and phytochemical components of mature and young leaves of cassava (*M. esculenta*), groundnut (*A. hypogea*) and beans (*P. biglobosa*) so as to ascertain the possibility of utilizing them as vegetables in traditional Nigerian soups.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Plant Materials

The leaves of plants screened in this investigation were collected from a multiple farming farmland that grows cassava, beans, groundnut, and garden egg located at Ekrejeta, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria with an agroecological zone within the coordinates 5.7894° N and 6.1023° E.

Samples Extraction

The method used for the extraction of the samples was that of Marinova (2005). Samples weighing 0.5g respectively were ground using a mortar and pestle. All samples were homogenized with 50ml distilled water and transferred to test tubes. Then, the mixtures were centrifuged for 10 minutes at 4,000 rpm. The supernatants were collected and used for the determinations.

Assay for Soluble Protein Content

The protein content of each sample was determined by means of the Biuret Method as described by Gornal et al. (2000) with some modifications. 1.5ml of the biuret reagent was added to 0.5ml of each of the three different formulations in their respective test tubes and thoroughly mixed. Thereafter, the test tubes were left to stand for 30 minutes at 37°C and then the absorbance of the samples was determined in the spectrophotometer at 540nm wavelength against reagent blank.

Estimation of Soluble Sugar (Phenol Sulphuric Acid Reagent method)

Five milliliters each of the plant leaf extract was homogenized with 10ml of 80% ethanol. Then each homogenate was centrifuged at 2000rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatants were collected separately. To 1ml of alcoholic extract, 1ml of 5% phenol solution was added and mixed. Five milliliters of 96% sulphuric acid was also added. This was done in triplicate. Each tube was gently agitated during the addition of the acid and then allowed to stand in a water bath at 25°C for 20 minutes. The optical density of the characteristic yellow-orange colour thus developed was measured at 490nm in a spectrophotometer. Simultaneously, a standard curve was prepared by using a known concentration of glucose. The amount of sugar was expressed as mg/g (Dubois et al., 2002).

Determination of Total Protein

The method used for the determination of total protein was that of Lowry et al. (2002). Five milliliters of the sample was mixed with 10ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 in a digestion flask. Copper (II) sulfate pentahydrate ($CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$) was added to catalyze the reaction and then heated under a fume cupboard until a clear solution was obtained. The clear solution was diluted to 100ml in a volumetric flask, filtered, and used for the analysis. Ten milliliters of the diluted solution was mixed with an equal volume of 45% NaOH solution in a Kjeldahl distillation apparatus. The mixture was added into 10ml of 4% basic acid containing three drops of mixed indicator (bromocresol green and methyl red). A total of 50ml distillate was collected and titrated against 0.02N EDTA from green to a deep red endpoint. A reagent blank was also digested, distilled, and titrated. The nitrogen content, hence the protein content, was calculated thus:

$$\% \text{Protein} = \%N_2 \times 6.25$$
$$\%N_2 = \frac{(T - B) \times N \times 1.4 \times V_t}{W \times V_a}$$

Where:

- W = weight of sample analyzed (5ml)
- N = normality of titrant (0.002N H_2SO_4)
- V_t = total digest volume (100ml)
- V_a = volume of digest analyzed (10ml)
- T = sample titre value
- B = blank titre value

Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay

The scavenging effect on nitric oxide (NO) radical was measured according to the method of Marcocci et al. (2000). One milliliter of the leaf extract was added in the test tube to 1ml of sodium nitroprusside solution (25ml) and the tubes incubated at $37^\circ C$ for 2 hours. An aliquot (1ml) of the incubation solution was removed and diluted with 0.6ml of Griess reagent (1% sulphanilamide in 5% H_3PO_4 and 0.1% naphthylethylenediamine dihydrochloride). The absorbance of the chromophore formed was immediately read at 570nm against distilled water as blank with catechin (500g) used as standard.

The results were expressed as percentage radical scavenging activity (RSA):

$$\%RSA = \frac{\text{Abs. of Control} - \text{Abs. of sample}}{\text{Abs. of Control}} \times 100$$

Quantitative Determination of Saponin

The method used for the determination of saponin was that of Peny et al. (2005). Five grams of the leaf samples were pulverized and placed in a conical flask and 50ml of 20% aqueous ethanol added. The samples were stirred at a constant temperature of $55^\circ C$ for 12 hours. Thereafter, the samples were filtered with Whatman No. 1 filter paper and the residue re-extracted with another 100ml of 2% ethanol. The extracts were combined and reduced to 40ml by heating in a water bath at $55^\circ C$. The purification process was repeated two more times. Six grams of NaCl were added to adjust the pH of the solution to 4.5 (confirmed with a pH meter). The solution was shaken with 30ml portion of n-butanol, extracted and washed twice with 10ml of aqueous NaCl. They were dried to constant weight, and the saponin extracted was shaken and expressed as a percentage:

$$\%Saponin = \frac{\text{Weight of Residue}}{\text{Weight of Sample}} \times 100$$

Alkaloid Determination

Alkaloid content was determined gravimetrically (Sreexidya and Mehrotra 2003). One gram of leaf was dispersed in 10ml of 10% acetic acid in methanol. The suspension was shaken and allowed to stand for 4 hours before it was filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to a quarter of its original volume before concentrated ammonium hydroxide (30%) was added dropwise to precipitate the alkaloids. A pre-weighed filter paper was used to filter the precipitate and it was then washed with ammonium hydroxide solution (1%). The filter paper with alkaloids precipitate was dried at $60^\circ C$ until a constant weight was obtained. The content of alkaloid was determined by the difference in the filter paper and expressed as g/100g DW.

Determination of Tannin

Tannins were determined using the method of Dawra et al. (1998). Zero point two grams of each sample was weighed into a beaker. Each was soaked with a

solvent mixture (80ml of acetone and 20ml of glacial acid) for 5 hours to extract tannin. The filtrates were removed and samples were filtered through a double filter paper to obtain the filtrate. Catechin was used as a standard solution. The absorbances of the standard solution as well as that of the filtrates were read at 750nm on a spectrophotometer.

$$\text{Conc. of Samples} = \frac{A_{\text{Sample}} \times \text{Conc. of std.}}{A_{\text{Std.}}}$$

RESULTS

The results obtained from the quantitative analyses of soluble protein, soluble sugar, total protein, nitric oxide radical scavenging assay, saponin, alkaloid, and tannin from the three investigated vegetable leaves are presented in the figures below.

Assay for Soluble Protein Content

The results of the quantitative analysis revealed that soluble protein was present in all the vegetable plant leaves investigated; six weeks old cassava leaves have the highest mean value (0.24g/g FW) compared to that of the matured cassava leaves (0.19g/g FW) (Figure 1). Two weeks old groundnut leaves and matured groundnut leaves have the same mean value (0.18g/g FW) while two weeks old beans leaves have a lower mean value compared to that of the matured beans leaves (Figure 1). This revealed that six weeks old cassava leaves have the highest soluble protein content.

Figure 1: Soluble Protein Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Estimation of Soluble Sugar

From the results, the soluble sugar of the six weeks old cassava leaves is slightly higher than the matured

cassava leaves. The mature groundnut leaves have a slight higher mean value (0.07g/g FW) than the two weeks old groundnut leaves (0.06g/g FW) while the two weeks old beans leaves (0.04g/g FW) have a higher mean value than the matured beans leaves (0.02g/g FW). This showed that six weeks old cassava leaves have the highest soluble sugar content (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Soluble Sugar Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Determination of Total Protein

The total protein content of the matured cassava leaves have a higher mean value (36.69%) compared to that of the six weeks old cassava leaves (34.86%). The two weeks old groundnut leaves have a higher total protein value (17.96%) than the matured groundnut leaves (15.96%) while the matured beans leaves have a higher mean value (3.82%) than the two weeks old beans leaves (2.82%). This showed cassava leaves have the highest total protein content (Figure 3).

Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay

As seen, nitric oxide radical scavenging activity of the six weeks old cassava leaves (2.25%) is higher than the matured cassava leaves (2.18%). Although the two weeks old groundnut leaves (2.00%) are slightly higher than the matured groundnut leaves (1.91%), the matured beans leaves have a higher mean value (2.13%) than the two weeks old beans leaves (1.98%) (Figure 4). This revealed that the six weeks old cassava leaves have the highest nitric oxide radical scavenging assay.

Figure 3: Total Protein Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Figure 5: Saponin Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Figure 4: Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

have a higher mean value (0.04g/100g) than the two weeks old beans leaves (0.02g/100g) (Figure 6). This showed that the matured beans leaves have the highest alkaloid content. Alkaloids act on a diversity of metabolic systems in humans and other animals; they almost uniformly invoke a bitter taste (Rhoades et al., 2000).

Figure 6: Alkaloid Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Quantitative Determination of Saponin

The saponin content of the matured cassava leaves have a higher mean value (0.21g/g FW) compared to that of the six weeks old cassava leaves (0.15g/g FW). The matured groundnut leaves have a higher saponin value (0.14g/g FW) than the two weeks old groundnut leaves (0.11g/g FW) while the matured beans leaves have a higher mean value (0.18g/g FW) than the two weeks old beans leaves (0.16g/g FW) (Figure 5). This showed that the matured cassava leaves have the highest saponin content among all the leaves investigated.

Alkaloid Determination

The alkaloid content of the six weeks old cassava leaves is higher than the matured cassava leaves. The two weeks old groundnut leaves have a higher mean value (0.02g/100g) than the matured groundnut leaves (0.01g/100g) while the matured beans leaves

Determination of Tannin

The tannin content of the matured cassava leaves (0.04g/g FW) is higher than the six weeks old cassava leaves (0.02g/g FW). Matured groundnut leaves have a higher amount of tannin (0.05g/g FW) compared to that of the two weeks old groundnut leaves (0.04g/g FW), while that of the matured beans leaves have a high tannin content (0.05g/g FW) compared to the two weeks old beans leaves (0.04g/g FW) (Figure 7). This revealed that matured beans leaves have the highest tannin content.

Figure 7: Tannin Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Discussion

The soluble protein, soluble sugar, and nitric oxide radical scavenging concentrations are higher in the young cassava leaves followed by the matured cassava leaves. A study by Ravindran and Ravindran (2010) on cassava leaves during different stages of maturity reported a decrease in solubility in protein and carbohydrate contents from young to mature leaves respectively. Hence their high nutritive value may probably account for their use in catalyzing metabolic reactions while polysaccharides are long carbohydrate molecules of monosaccharide units joined together by glycosidic bonds and serve as a source of energy. The high soluble sugar content of the six weeks old cassava leaves could therefore be used as a source of energy. In humans, nitric oxide radical is an important cellular signaling molecule involved in many physiological and pathological processes (Moncada et al., 2004). This implies that six weeks old cassava leaves is a powerful vasodilator with a short half-life of a few seconds in the blood when used.

For the groundnut leaves, soluble protein, soluble sugar, and total protein concentrations have high nutritional value compared to that of beans leaves and serve as a great source of protein (Shalini et al., 2015). This is an indication that these vegetables have a good amount of nutrients.

The saponin and tannin content of the matured cassava leaves have higher mean values compared to that of the young cassava leaves. Alkaloid of the young cassava leaves is higher than the matured cassava leaves. According to research, cassava leaves contain a high concentration of phytochemical

components like saponin, alkaloid, and tannins (Babalola and Ahmed, 2005).

The matured groundnut and beans leaves have higher saponin, alkaloid, and tannin concentrations than the young leaves, except for young groundnut leaves which have a slightly higher mean value than the matured groundnut leaves. This work is in agreement with that of Chelangat and Mukono (2023).

This showed that the bioactive non-nutrient plant compounds in vegetable plant foods have complementary and overlapping mechanisms of action, including modulation of detoxification enzymes, scavenging of oxidative agents, stimulation of the immune system, regulation of gene expression in cell proliferation and apoptosis, hormone metabolism, and antibacterial and antiviral effects (Dragsted et al., 2000). The results of the quantitative analysis of these plants showed that all of the plant leaves contained varying proportions according to the nutritive and phytochemical properties in them.

Conclusion

This study showed the determination of the nutritional and phytochemical components of mature and immature leaves of cassava (*M. esculenta*), groundnut (*A. hypogea*), and beans (*P. biglobosa*) so as to ascertain the possibility of utilizing them as vegetables in traditional Nigerian soups and incorporating them into other dishes. Though the analysed components of the vegetables are not enough to satisfy the recommended dietary allowances (RDAs), they can be used as sources of additional organic nutrients in our daily traditional meals.

References

- Adesina, I. A., Adebote, V. T., Elehinfafe, T. R., Enerijiofi, K. E. (2013). Growth inhibition of *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium italicum* by seed kernel oil from Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.). *Journal of Natural Sciences Research*, 3(9), 61-64.
- Asibu, J., Akromah, H., Adu-Dapaah, O., Safo-Kantanka, A. (2008). Evaluation of nutritional quality of groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) from Ghana. *International Journal of Agronomy*, 8(2), 133-150.
- Babalola, O., Ahmed, Z. (2005). Phytochemical, nutritive, and anti-nutritive composition of cassava (*Manihot esculenta* L) tubers

- and leaves. *Nigerian Food Journal*, 23(1). <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/nifoj/article/view/33597>
- Chelangat, M., Mukono, S. (2023). Nutritional and phytochemical composition of Bambara groundnut landraces in Kenya. *International Journal of Agronomy*, 1(1), 11.
- Darrell, B. (2008). Nutrients in the cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) leaf meal at three ages of the plant. *Ciencia e Tecnologia de Alimentos*, 26, 865-869.
- Donoghue, O., Janet, I. (2006). Use of vegetable as nutritional food: Role in human health. *Journal of Agricultural and Biological Science*, 1, 18-21.
- Dragsted, L., Strube, M., Larsen, J. (2000). Cancer-protective factors in fruits and vegetables: Biochemical and biological background. *Pharmacology Toxicology*, 73(1), 116-135.
- Duboi, M., Gilles, K. A., Hamilton, J. K., Rebers, P. A. (2002). Calorimetric Dubois method for determination of sugar and related substances. *Researchgate Journal of Analytical Chemistry*, 28(3), 350-356.
- Enerijiofi, K. E., Isola, O. B. (2019). Preliminary phytochemical screening and in vitro antibacterial activities of aqueous and ethanol extracts of *Ageratum conyzoides* L. leaf, stem, flower, and root on some bacterial isolates associated with diarrhea. *Nigerian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 32(2), 3480-3489. <http://dx.doi.org/10.19240/njpas.2019.B09>
- Francis, G., Kerem, Z., Makkar, H. P. S., Becker, K. (2002). The biological action of saponins in animal systems: A review. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 88(6), 597-605.
- Freeland, W. J., Calcott, P. H., Geiss, D. P. (1985). Allelochemicals, minerals, and herbivore population size. *Biochemical Systematics and Ecology*, 13, 195-206.
- Fyhri, A. (2010). Phenol antioxidant quantity and quality in foods: Vegetables. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 46, 3630-3634.
- Immaculate, B. (2021). Cassava leaf soup. <https://www.africanbite.com/cassava-leaf-soup/>
- Jennette, H. (2003). The beneficial role of peanuts in the diet-Part 2. *Nutrition Food Science*, 33, 56-64.
- Lee, K. H., Lee, B. M. (2005). Evaluation of the genotoxicity of (-)-hydroxycitric acid (HCASX) isolated from *Garcinia cambogia*. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health*, 70(5), 388-392.
- Lee, K. W., Kim, Y. J., Lee, H. J., Lee, C. Y. (2003). Cocoa has more phenolic phytochemicals and a higher antioxidant capacity than teas and red wine. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 51(25), 7292-7295.
- Kathy, W., Warwick, R. D., Zawn, V. (2023). What are the health benefits of beans. <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/about/privacy-policy>
- Maria, Z. C., Ngure, R. M., Matasyoh, J. C., Chepkorir, R. (2008). Phytochemical constituents and antimicrobial activity of leaf extracts of three *Amaranthus* plant species. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 9(21), 3178-3182.
- Kappers, I. F., Aharoni, A., Van Herpen, T., Lucker, H. L., Dicke, M., Bouwmeester, H. J. (2005). Genetic engineering of terpenoid metabolism attracts bodyguards to *Arabidopsis*. *Science*, 309, 2070-2072.
- Marinova, D., Ribarova, F., Atanassova, M. (2008). Total phenolics and total flavonoids in Bulgarian fruits and vegetables. *Journal of University of Chemical Technology and Metallurgy*, 40, 255-260.
- Moncada, C. (2004). Nutritional enhancement of plants. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, 14, 221-225.
- Nautiyal, P., Danilo, M. (2002). Groundnut: Post-harvest operations. *National Research Centre for Groundnut (ICAR)*.
- Ovuru, K. F., Izah, S. C., Yasmin, H., Enerijiofi, K. E., Das, M., Ogwu, M. C. (2023). Microbial contaminants of herbal remedies: Health risks and sustainable quality control strategies. In S. C. Izah, M. C. Ogwu, M. Akram (Eds.), *Herbal medicine phytochemistry* (pp. 1-21). Springer Nature, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21973-3_9 – 1
- Ravindran, V., Ravindran, G. (1998). Changes in the nutritional composition of cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) leaves during maturity. *Researchgate*, 27(4), 299-309.
- Ram, S. M., Anderson, A. M., Matthew, S. M. (2000). Isolation of curcumin from turmeric. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 77(3), 359-360.
- Rhoades, D. F. (2000). Evolution of plant chemical defense against herbivores. In G. A. Rosenthal D. H. Janzen (Eds.), *Herbivores: Their interaction with secondary plant metabolites* (pp. 3-54). Academic Press.
- Shalini, S., Akshata, R., Chauhan, S. (2015). Peanut as a functional food. *Journal of Food Science Technology*, 53(1), 31-41.
- Tonukari, N. J. (2004). Cassava and the future

of starch. *Electronic Journal of Biotechnology*, 7, 1-4.
<https://doi.org/10.2225/vol-issue1-fulltext-9>

Umuhozariho, M. G., Shayo, N. B., Sallah, P. Y., Msuya, J. M. (2013). Sensory evaluation of different preparations of cassava leaves from three species as a leafy vegetable. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 12(4), 6452-6459.

Phytoremediation of Cd, Pb, and Ni-co-contaminated soil of the Niger Delta by using Local Maize (*Zea mays*) plant

TUBOTU, K.F.^{1*}; AGBAIRE, P.O.¹; AKPORHONOR, E.E.¹; ODAGWE, A.A.²

¹Department of Chemistry, Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria

²Department of Chemistry, University of Delta, Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: +2348027538882; tubotuken@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Phytoremediation is an innovative, cost-effective technology that uses plants to extract metals from polluted soils. Experiments were conducted using *Zea mays* plants grown in soils contaminated with varying levels of Cd, Pb, and Ni. The results indicated that rising soil heavy metal concentrations decreased plant height, weight, and chlorophyll content. Plants grown in soil with the highest levels of Cd, Pb, and Ni (20, 120, and 60 mg/kg) showed the highest amounts of Cd (11.71 mg/kg Dwt in roots and 2.55 mg/kg Dwt in shoots), Pb (29.60 mg/kg Dwt in roots and 9.10 mg/kg Dwt in shoots), and Ni (38.70 mg/kg Dwt in roots and 10.90 mg/kg Dwt in shoots). As the soil's metal levels rose, the bioconcentration factor (BCF) and translocation factor (TF) values declined. In 80% of cases, Ni had BCF values over 1, while Cd exceeded 1 in only 20%, and Pb had none. All metals had TF values below 1. Our findings indicate that *Z. mays* primarily employs phytostabilization to remediate these elements, supported by high BCF values, particularly for Ni, and low TF values across all examined treatments, suggesting minimal metal translocation from roots to shoots.

Keywords: Bioconcentration factor, Translocation factor, phytostabilization, metals, physicochemical properties

Introduction

The rapid growth of the global population, urbanization, and industrialization have led to the contamination of millions of hectares of land with heavy metals, affecting over 50% of contaminated sites worldwide (Behnisch et al., 2022; Elehinafe et al., 2022; Gill et al., 2023). These metals can be from natural sources or anthropogenic activities like emissions from waste incinerators, residues from mining and military activities, the smelting industry, use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides, burning fossil fuels, and municipal trash (Andresen & Küpper, 2013; Zulfiqar et al., 2022). Heavy metals in soils at high concentrations negatively affect crop health and productivity, disrupt cellular structures, and cause oxidative stress (Rashid et al., 2023). They may also make their way into the food chain, putting people at risk of developing cancer (Gill et al., 2023). According to national and international organisations, certain metal concentrations in soil and plants have surpassed allowable limits, endangering both human health and the environment (Alengebawy et al., 2021; Behnisch et al., 2022). Several heavy metal pollutants are frequently found in soil, including Cd,

Pb, and Ni. These metals, like others, are difficult to break down into innocuous byproducts like carbon dioxide, therefore they must usually be removed from contaminated soils (Wuana & Okieimen, 2011).

There are multiple approaches to addressing soils contaminated with heavy metals. Although there are traditional methods like excavation, burning, and chemical washing, they can be quite costly, require a lot of manual labour, and may release harmful secondary pollutants that can negatively impact biological processes and the environment (Ding et al., 2023). Due to the current circumstances, there is a growing need for a solution that is both affordable and eco-friendly. Phytoremediation is an effective and eco-friendly strategy that utilises plants to reduce metal toxicity. It involves the transportation of ions to shoots and their elimination from roots, resulting in a cost-effective solution. Phytoremediation involves the utilisation of plants to absorb, sequester, and detoxify contaminants, with a specific focus on heavy metals (Ashraf et al., 2019). Several mechanisms are involved in phytoremediation: phytoextraction, phytostimulation, phytovolatilization, rhizofiltration, and phytostabilization. Whereas phytostimulation seeks to improve plant growth for greater metal

absorption, phytoextraction uses plants to gather metals from the soil. Rhizofiltration is the process by which roots remove metals from water; phytovolatilization is the process by which plants release metals into the atmosphere. Finally, phytostabilization aims to immobilise metals in soil or plant roots, thereby limiting their mobility (Ashraf et al., 2019; Kanwar et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2024). The useful implementation of phytoremediation methods depends on the choice of plant species with suitable characteristics for certain soil contaminants. Sunflower, Indian mustard, water hyacinth, willow, and Indian pennywort are among the more than 400 plant species that have been identified as heavy metal hyperaccumulators; nevertheless, because of the way that heavy metals affect plant cellular processes, most growing plants are not hyperaccumulators for heavy metals (Shrivastava et al., 2019). Since plant capacities to collect heavy metals vary, the choice of plant species for phytoextraction of heavy metals is mostly determined by the biomass and tolerance capacity of the chosen plant (Peng et al., 2021; Zulfiqar et al., 2022).

Maize (*Zea mays*) an indigenous annual plant belonging to the Poaceae grass family, plays a vital role in Nigerian agriculture and culinary practices. Originally from the Americas, Maize thrives in the Niger Delta region, where it can grow to heights exceeding 10 feet under optimal soil conditions. This crop is known for its rapid growth and high biomass production, offering promise in soil remediation by reducing heavy metal concentrations. The plant's photosynthetic efficiency and nutrient profile significantly influence its growth rate and biomass output (Atta et al., 2023). Previous research has indicated Maize's notable resilience to heavy metal exposure (Irfan et al., 2021; Ni et al., 2022; Tariq, 2022). But, while Maize (*Zea mays*) thrives in a variety of soil types, not all soils in the Niger Delta are equally conducive to its growth (Anoliefo et al., 2006; Egobueze et al., 2019). This study is therefore carried out to: (i) evaluate an indigenous Maize variety to see if it is naturally adapted to sandy soil conditions and capable of metal uptake. (ii) determine the ability of local Maize to accumulate Cd, Pb, and Ni without external amendments like fertilizer and (iii) investigate the impact of phytoremediation on some selected soil properties and the effect of Cd, Pb, and Ni-co-contaminated soil on the total biomass of Maize.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location of Study

The research was conducted at Delta State University (DELSU), located in Abraka, Nigeria, between March and May in the year 2023. Located at latitude 6° 30' 59.99" N and longitude 3° 23' 5.99" W, the campus is roughly 29 metres above sea level. Abraka is located around 49 miles northeast of Warri and experiences a tropical wet and dry climate.

Preparation of soil and conducting experiments in pots

A soil sample was obtained from DELSU (Campus 3) at a depth of 0-20 cm beside a coal-tarred road adjacent to an agricultural region. The soil was air-dried by exposure to air and subsequently filtered through a stainless-steel screen with a 2 mm mesh size. A pot experiment was conducted in a rain-protected net-house where *Zea mays* plants were cultivated for sixty days, being subjected to natural sunlight. Cadmium acetate, lead sulphate, and nickel sulphate served as the corresponding sources of Cd, Pb, and Ni. Varying quantities of these compounds were mixed in containers along with soil (2kg) and distilled water. Five treatment levels (n = 3) of Cd, Pb, and Ni (P treatments) and control groups (CT) were part of the trial. The P-group included Cd, Pb, Ni, and plants; the control group had unspiked soil with plants. Table 1 offers specifications of the metal addition levels to the soil.

Table 1: Cd, Pb, and Ni concentration per treatment pot (mg/kg)

Metals	CT	P1	P2	P3	P4
Cd	0	5	10	15	20
Pb	0	30	60	90	120
Ni	0	15	30	45	60

The pots were put in a dark room for 14 days, with tap water added to maintain them at 75% field capacity. Three *Zea mays* seedlings were transplanted to each container after ten days of growth in fertiliser-free, unspiked soil. Two or three times a week, the pots were watered and inspected. The experiment ended with an examination of soil parameters including pH, EC, TOC, TN, Av. P., and texture.

Analysis

Physicochemical Properties and heavy metals of soil

The soil sample was tested chemically using approved procedures. Phosphorus and total nitrogen concentrations were assessed using the Bray 1 and Kjeldahl methods, respectively (Bray & Kurtz, 1945; Bremner & Bremner, 1996). The total organic carbon (TOC) concentration of the soil was assessed by the Walkley-Black method (Nelson & Sommers, 1996). The texture of the soil was measured by the hydrometer method (Bouyoucos, 1962). A 1:1 weight-to-volume soil-to-water extract had its pH measured with a pH meter. The metal content of 0.5 g of air-dried, sieved soil sample was determined by utilising the method given by Paunović et al. (2019) using microwave-digested aqua regia (HCl, 36% and HNO₃, 65%). The resulting solution was filtered and diluted before the levels of Cd, Pb, and Ni were determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometry (Perkin Elmer 700, Boston, MA, USA). The test soil has a sandy texture, an average total organic carbon concentration of 0.19 %, and physicochemical parameters of 6.75 pH and 1.40 EC micro/Sm. Besides, the soil contained 6.95, 35.55, and 20.80 mg/kg on average for total Cd, Pb, and Ni. Similar baseline values for metals in soils have been reported in other studies around the Niger Delta (Tubotu & Agbaire, 2022).

Harvesting, preparing, and analysing plants

The plants were methodically pulled out of the experiment, cleaned and rinsed with deionized water, and then their roots and shoots were separated. Following note of the plant heights and fresh biomass, the roots and shoots were dried in an oven at 70 °C for 24 hours to calculate the dry biomass. After that, the metal contents in the plant tissues were analysed. For the analysis of metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni) in plant root and shoot, a solution of hydrochloric acid and hydrogen nitrate in a 3:1 volume ratio (HCl/HNO₃, 3:1 v/v) was used to digest 0.5 g of the sifted plant material after it had been powdered. The Cd, Pb, and Ni concentrations in the resulting digests were determined using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) (Alaboudi et al., 2018). The study examined the chlorophyll levels in *Zea mays* by extracting it with acetone and measuring it using spectrophotometry. The quantities

of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and total chlorophyll were measured using equations provided by Kumar et al. (2018): total chlorophyll : 20.2(A645) + 8.02(A663), chlorophyll a : 12.7(A663) 2.69(A645) and chlorophyll b : 22.9(A645) 4.68(A663).

Factors of bioconcentration and translocation

By use of bioconcentration and translocation factors, as described by Takarina and Pin (2017) and Usman et al. (2019), the study examined *Zea mays*' capacity to absorb and disseminate cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), and nickel (Ni) from the soil using the following equations:

$$BCF = \frac{C_{root}}{C_{soil}} \quad (1)$$

$$TF = \frac{C_{shoot}}{C_{root}} \quad (2)$$

$$BCF_{shoot} = \frac{C_{shoot}}{C_{soil}} \quad (3)$$

where C_{soil} , C_{root} , and C_{shoot} are the metal concentrations (mg/kg) in the soil, root, and shoot, respectively.

Should the bioconcentration factor be less than one ($BCF < 1$), soil heavy metal concentrations exceed plant absorption. Larger absorption by plants or crops is indicated by BCF values larger than one ($BCF > 1$). Trace metals are detected predominantly in the biomass of the roots of plants with a translocation factor (TF) less than 1 but in the shoot biomass of plants with a $TF > 1$.

Statistical Analysis

This paper used Excel 2016 and IBM SPSS Statistics 27 for statistical analysis. The data provided are the mean \pm standard deviation of three independent replicates ($n = 3$). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the data, and Tukey's HSD post-hoc test found significant mean differences. Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$. Additionally, the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to assess the relationships between plant characteristics, metal concentrations in roots and shoots, and soil physicochemical factors.

Table 2: Selected soil physicochemical properties at the end of the experiment

	pH	EC	TN	SOC	Av. P	Cd	Pb
CT	6.25 ± 0.04a	1.41 ± 0.3e	0.71 ± 0.01a	0.91 ± 0.01a	29.74 ± 0.10a	2.69 ± 0.04e	18.11 ± 0.00e
P1	5.80 ± 0.02b	2.60 ± 0.11d	0.58 ± 0.01b	0.81 ± 0.01b	26.92 ± 0.39b	4.00 ± 0.27d	29.70 ± 1.68d
P2	5.00 ± 0.30c	3.94 ± 0.04c	0.51 ± 0.01c	0.48 ± 0.00c	26.31 ± 0.10c	7.81 ± 0.10c	43.57 ± 0.52c
P3	4.00 ± 0.09d	5.16 ± 0.18b	0.50 ± 0.02c	0.42 ± 0.01d	13.63 ± 0.20d	9.89 ± 0.22b	58.53 ± 1.02b
P4	3.01 ± 0.04e	6.40 ± 0.12a	0.46 ± 0.02d	0.42 ± 0.01d	12.11 ± 0.10e	14.88 ± 0.59b	82.91 ± 1.03a

Mean ± standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P < 0.05 is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

Results

Physicochemical Properties of the Soil Following Corn Harvest

Following the Maize harvest, Table ?? displays the soil's physicochemical parameters. Significant variability in pH was observed across all treatments (p < 0.05). The control soil exhibited the highest pH at 6.25, while the soil treated with 20 mg/kg Cd, 120 mg/kg Pb, and 60 mg/kg Ni (P4 soil) showed the lowest pH at 3.01. Control soil had the highest total organic carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus levels. Higher metal concentrations in treatment soils decreased pH, organic carbon, total nitrogen, and available phosphorus, but enhanced electrical conductivity post-harvest. Among the treatments, P4 soil had the highest electrical conductivity. The control soil had the lowest concentrations of bioavailable Cd, Pb, and Ni.

Concentration of Heavy Metals in the Soil After Maize Harvest

Table ?? displays the average concentrations of soil Cd, Pb, and Ni in both the control and P pots after 60 days of planting. Compared to the initial soil samples, the results indicate a decrease in the three metals in the control, P1, P2, P3, and P4. P4 exhibited significantly higher metal concentrations (14.88, 82.91, and 39.81 mg/kg Cd, Pb, and Ni, respectively) compared to the control group, with a p-value of less than 0.05. The soil's metal concentrations increased in proportion to the spike concentrations.

Plant Development and Biomass

As the soil's Cd, Pb, and Ni levels climbed, maize shoot length and total biomass diverged significantly

from the control (Figure 1). In P1, plant height dropped by 8.59%; in P2, by 14.30%; and in P3 and P4, by 25.71%. Regarding biomass (Figure 2), the fresh and dry weights of plants in the Cd, Pb, and Ni co-contaminated growth media (P1 to P4) were substantially lower than the control by 26.32% to 57.71% and 22.48% to 72.14% in the root, respectively, and by 17.10% to 39.74% and 40.90% to 68.27% in the shoot. Growing in the growth media tainted with the largest quantities of Cd, Pb, and Ni (P4), the weights of the plants reduced most dramatically (P < 0.001). The results confirm the unfavorable association between higher levels of Cd, Pb, and Ni and plant development markers.

Figure 1: Zea mays shoot development in soil as impacted by metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni). Mean ± standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P < 0.05 is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

Figure 2: Effects of metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni) on soil-grown *Zea mays* biomass. Mean \pm standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P \leq 0.05 is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

Figure 3: Effects of metals (Ni, Pb, and Cd) on soil-grown *Zea mays* chlorophyll concentration. Mean \pm standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P \leq 0.05 is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

Contents of Chlorophyll

The soil's contamination with Cd, Pb, and Ni lowered the quantities of Chl-a and Chl-b; control plants had higher values. Concerning the total chlorophyll (t-Chl) levels of the plants, significant decreases were also observed (Figure 3). Plants treated with 20 mg/kg Cd, 120 mg/kg Pb, and 60 mg/kg Ni had the lowest levels of Chl-a, Chl-b, and t-Chl. All the plants proved, on average, to have more Chl b than Chl a. As the chlorophyll a/b value was less than 1.00, Cd, Pb, and Ni stress impaired the plant's photosynthetic resilience (Table ??). As the amount of metal in the soil grew, all chlorophyll contents fell in a dose-dependent way.

Distribution of Cd,Pb, and Ni in Tissues of Plants

As the metal concentrations in the treated soils increased in relation to the control, so did the metal concentrations in *Zea mays* roots and shoots (Figure 4). Plants grown on soil treated with co-contamination of 20 mg/kg Cd, 120 mg/kg Pb, and

60 mg/kg Ni (or P4 treatment) increased their Cd (11.71 and 2.55 mg/kg Dwt), Pb (29.60 and 9.10 mg/kg Dwt), and Ni (38.70 and 10.90 mg/kg Dwt) contents in their roots and shoots, respectively, to the highest significant ($P < 0.001$) levels. The control group of plants exhibited the lowest levels of Cadmium (Cd), Lead (Pb), and Nickel (Ni) in both their roots and shoots. Notably, a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed in the concentrations of these elements between the roots and shoots of plants grown in spiked pots compared to those in the control group. The roots were identified as the primary site for the accumulation of Cd, Pb, and Ni in plants across various treatment soils, as indicated by the distribution of concentrations of these elements in plant tissues (refer to Figure 4). The sequence of Cd, Pb, and Ni concentrations in different plant compartments was determined to be roots $\hat{}$ stems.

Translocation Factor (TF) and Bioconcentration Factor (BCF) of Cd, Pb and Ni

As soil metal levels increased, the bioconcentration factor for each of Cd, Pb, and Ni decreased. *Zea mays* BCF followed the pattern Ni $\hat{}$ Cd $\hat{}$ Pb, as Table ?? makes rather clear. From 1.20 (at 5 mg/kg Cd, 30 mg/kg Pb and 15 mg/kg Ni co-contamination level) to 0.79 (20 mg/kg Cd, 120 mg/kg Pb and 60 mg/kg Ni co-contamination level), the Cd root BCF values steadily fell. The other metals followed similar patterns (Pb = 0.51 to 0.36; Ni = 2.00 to 0.97). Cd had the one larger-than-1 root-BCF value in P1 (BCF $\hat{}$ 1). Except for P4, Ni root BCF values were more than 1 (BCF $\hat{}$ 1) in every treated soil and the control. All shoot BCF values for the metals were less than 1 except for Ni in the control (1.14).

Maximum TF values were found in the control. Generally, when soil metal concentrations increased, the TF values of the metals decreased (P $\hat{}$ P2 $\hat{}$ P3 $\hat{}$ P4): Cd TF decreased from 0.33 to 0.22; Pb from 0.49 to 0.31; and Ni from 0.34 to 0.28. The recorded data makes it quite clear that roots had higher BCF than shoots and that, in all treatments, there was very little metal translocated from root to shoot (TF $\hat{}$ 1) (Table ??).

Pearson Correlation Analysis

Tables 5, along with supplementary tables 1 and 2, provide insight into the Pearson correlations among plant features, metal concentrations in plant tissues (roots and shoots), and soil physicochemical parameters. Parameters such as shoot fresh weight (SFW), root fresh weight (RFW), shoot dry weight (SDW), root dry weight (RDW), shoot length (SL), chlorophyll a (Chl-a), chlorophyll b (Chl-b), total chlorophyll content (t-Chl), and metal-related traits (e.g., Cd, Pb, Ni concentrations in plant tissues and soil) displayed significant correlations. Notably, Maize plant metal characteristics and soil properties exhibited both positive and negative associations. While all metals (Cd, Pb, Ni) demonstrated negative relationships with plant growth characteristics, strong positive connections were observed between soil physicochemical properties and plant growth traits, except for electrical conductivity and soil metal concentrations as indicated in supplementary tables 1 and 2. article pdfscape lipsum geometry a4paper, total=170mm,257mm, left=20mm, top=20mm

Figure 4: The concentrations of metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni) in *Zea mays* roots and shoots grown on soil supplemented with a mix of nickel, lead, and cadmium. Mean \pm standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of $P < 0.05$ is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

Table 3: Cd, Pb, and Ni bioconcentration factors in Maize tissues

	BCF-Root			BCF-Shoot		
	Cd	Pb	Ni	Cd	Pb	Ni
CT	0.88 ± 0.05b	0.27 ± 0.11c	1.31 ± 0.00c	0.76 ± 0.03a	0.22 ± 0.02a	1.14 ± 0.02a
P1	1.20 ± 0.04a	0.51 ± 0.01a	2.00 ± 0.13a	0.40 ± 0.01b	0.25 ± 0.03a	0.38 ± 0.01c
P2	0.86 ± 0.01bc	0.55 ± 0.04a	1.36 ± 0.05b	0.27 ± 0.02c	0.16 ± 0.02b	0.45 ± 0.01b
P3	0.87 ± 0.02bc	0.43 ± 0.01ab	1.14 ± 0.03b	0.23 ± 0.01c	0.14 ± 0.02b	0.32 ± 0.01d
P4	0.79 ± 0.01c	0.36 ± 0.02bc	0.97 ± 0.02c	0.17 ± 0.02d	0.11 ± 0.01b	0.27 ± 0.01e

Mean ± standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P < 0.05 is evidenced by mean values that do not share a common letter.

Table 4: Translocation factors of Cd, Pb, and Ni in Maize tissues

	Cd	Pb	Ni
CT	0.87 ± 0.02a	0.81 ± 0.01a	0.87 ± 0.02a
P1	0.33 ± 0.01b	0.49 ± 0.01b	0.34 ± 0.01b
P2	0.31 ± 0.01b	0.32 ± 0.04c	0.33 ± 0.01b
P3	0.26 ± 0.01c	0.31 ± 0.03c	0.28 ± 0.02c
P4	0.22 ± 0.01d	0.31 ± 0.03c	0.28 ± 0.01c

Mean ± standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P < 0.05 is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

[1]
[h!]

DISCUSSION

Soil properties can impact heavy metal availability and plant uptake. The test soil of this study is sandy, has low organic carbon and nutrient levels typical of tropical areas like the Niger Delta, and its fertility level can be described as low. The presence of heavy metals in the soil altered the physicochemical properties of the soil, leading to higher EC values and a reduction in pH. This reduction in soil pH, which in turn increases the solubility and plant uptake of metals, indicates that the test soil has a high potential for the transport of metals from the soil solution to the plant.

The results of the current study reveal that Maize growth parameters, including shoot lengths and root and shoot weights, are significantly reduced when exposed to various levels of cadmium, lead, and nickel co-contamination in the growth media (Figures 1 and 2). The deleterious impact is dose-dependent due to Increased hazardous heavy metals (HMs) absorption as metal concentration in the soil increases. The study

also found that the application of cadmium, lead, and nickel co-contamination significantly lowered harvestable biomass, indicating Maize vulnerability to toxicity. In the current study, the longest Maize shoot length was observed in control soil with an average value of 17.5 cm, while the shortest shoot length (13.0 cm) was recorded under P3 and P4 treatments (Fig. 1). Similar findings have been observed in other similar investigations. In a study conducted by Liu et al. (2018), the impact of arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) inoculation and biochar amendment on Maize growth, cadmium (Cd) uptake, and soil Cd speciation in Cd-contaminated soil was investigated. The researchers found that the introduction of 6 mg/kg Cd resulted in a 20.96% reduction in Maize shoot length compared to the control group (Liu et al., 2018). In another study by Coulibaly et al. (2021), where P. maximum was subjected to 2 ppm of Cd, 50 ppm of Ni, and 100 ppm of Pb contaminated soil and uncontaminated soil, for 120 days in a greenhouse, it was observed that the stem height of Panicum maximum was reduced by around 5.11%, 23.30%, and 52.84% in Pb, Cd and Ni contaminated soils

Table 5: Pearson correlations for different plant traits and metals in plant tissues (roots and shoots)

	R-Cd	R-Pb	R-Ni	ST-Cd	ST-Pb	ST-Ni	Chl-a	Chl-b	t-Chl	SL	RFW	SFW
SDW												
R-Cd	1.000											
R-Pb	.952*	1.000										
R-Ni	.974**	.953*	1.000									
ST-Cd	0.749	0.623	0.782	1.000								
ST-Pb	.885*	.934*	0.827	0.373	1.000							
ST-Ni	.940*	.901*	.980**	.882*	0.718	1.000						
Chl-a	-0.872	-.951*	-0.852	-0.366	-.984**	-0.744	1.000					
Chl-b	-0.796	-0.597	-0.782	-.923*	-0.441	-0.838	0.407	1.000				
t-Chl	-.989**	-.968**	-.968**	-0.655	-.930*	-.908*	.928*	0.718	1.000			
SL	-.953*	-.944*	-.984**	-0.675	-0.853	-.935*	.891*	0.716	.970**	1.000		
RFW	-.971**	-.988**	-.955*	-0.599	-.956*	-.887*	.962**	0.634	.992**	.962**	1.000	
SFW	-.943*	-.999**	-.943*	-0.605	-.938*	-.890*	.954*	0.573	.961**	.935*	.985**	1.000
RDW	-.964**	-.988**	-.986**	-0.700	-.884*	-.950*	.913*	0.677	.972**	.977**	.979**	.983**
SDB 1.000	-.921*	-.974**	-.910*	-0.472	-.973**	-0.819	.992**	0.513	.965**	.940*	.987**	.974**

Cd concentration in shoot (ST-Cd) and roots (R-Cd), Pb concentration in shoot (ST-Pb) and roots (R-Pb), Ni concentration in shoot (ST-Ni) and roots (R-Ni); shoot length (SL), chlorophyll a (Chl-a), chlorophyll b (Chl-b), total chlorophyll (t-Chl); shoot fresh weight (SFW), root fresh weight (RFW), shoot dry weight (SDW), and root dry weight (RDW).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

respectively. Heavy metals can generate oxidative stress, damage cell structures, and disrupt metabolic pathways, resulting in stunted development and lower stem height (Rashid et al., 2023; Zulfiqar et al., 2022).

In our study, low biomass production was reported in all the treatments (P1 to P4) compared with control (Figure 2). This reduction implies a deleterious influence of heavy metals on Maize growth. The reduction in biomass compared with the control might potentially be attributable to higher Cd, Pb and Ni uptake as the level of concentrations of the metals in soil increased. In the present study, the fresh and dry weights of plants significantly decreased in the root by 26.32 to 57.71% and 22.48 to 72.14% and in the shoot by 17.10 to 39.74% and 40.90 to 68.27 in the Cd, Pb and Ni co-contaminated growth conditions (P1 to P4) compared with control (Table 2). The results of our investigation are in agreement with similar studies by other researchers. For instance, the addition of 6 mg/kg Cd to soil has been observed to lower the fresh weight of Maize by 21.50% when compared with control (Liu et al., 2018). It may be deduced that exposure to excessive Cd, Pb and Ni may adversely influence plant development and biomass production and these detrimental effects might be further amplified by an increase in the metal concentrations in the growth medium.

Cd, Pb, and Ni co-contamination significantly lowered plant growth and development, potentially due to a decrease in the photosynthetic rate (Asare et al., 2023). The chl-a, chl-b and total chlorophyll content in Maize plants cultivated in the Cd, Pb, and Ni co-contaminated soil compared with the control decreased significantly, with an increase in metal concentrations in the growth medium. This destruction of chlorophyll structure may be due to the substitution of the central Mg^{2+} ion by Cd, Pb, and Ni ions, which may damage the chlorophyll molecule (Bechaieb et al., 2018). As metal concentrations increase in soil, it may accelerate metal uptake, further affecting the detrimental effect of toxicity on chlorophyll content (Chtouki et al., 2021; Ewais, 1997).

Our investigation demonstrates a negative association between plant growth indices, chlorophyll content, and increasing concentrations of heavy metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni) in soil. The higher rate of metal concentrations in soil decreased these metrics

compared to the control. Heavy metal stress impacts plant metabolic activity, hinders photosynthesis, and lowers the uptake of critical nutrients from the soil, leading to decreased plant biomass establishment (Ghori et al., 2019).

Based on the obtained results, *Z. mays* seems to be a tolerant and rapidly growing plant, suitable for phytoremediation due to its fast growth, large root development potential, impressive biomass establishment, and high storage capacity for heavy metals (Daryabeigi Zand & Mühling, 2022).

Metal speciation in soil is crucial in limiting metal uptake by plants. In our investigation, Cd, Pb, and Ni levels in Maize root and shoot systems increased as metal concentrations in soil increased (Figs. 1 and 2). Plants grown in P4 soil had the highest Cd (11.71 and 2.55 mg/kg Dwt), Pb (29.60 and 9.10 mg/kg Dwt), and Ni (38.70 and 10.90 mg/kg Dwt) contents in their roots and shoots, respectively. The study found that *Z. mays* roots are the preferred organ for cadmium, lead and nickel storage, which is consistent with previous research on zinc, copper, and lead (Sagbara et al., 2020). Heavy metals in soil may compete with mineral nutrients for absorption by plant roots. This occurrence may lead to a lack of vital elements such as iron, for plant viability. Furthermore, higher amounts of heavy metals can alter water balance and nutrient digestion, potentially resulting in plant death (Siyar et al., 2020).

Phytoextraction Efficiency of Metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni)

Our findings indicate that *Z. mays* accumulates more Cd, Pb, and Ni in its roots than in its shoots, with roots absorbing more Ni than Cd or Pb. At low Ni concentrations, root BCF values are < 1 , but when Ni concentrations exceed 45 mg/kg, root BCF values drop. Our findings suggest that phytostabilization is the primary mechanism by which *Z. mays* remediates these elements, as the BCF values (particularly for Ni) in most treatments were higher than 1, while the TF values of all metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni) in all examined treatments were less than 1. The results of our study also suggest that *Zea mays*' capacity to translocate heavy metals from roots to shoots diminishes with an increase in soil concentration of these metals. Heavy metals in the soil can impede a plant's capacity to absorb vital nutrients and water by blocking the root apex. This root-level interference may lessen the

plant's capacity to move heavy metals from its roots to its aerial portions, which may affect the plant's general growth and health (Thomas, 2021). There have also been reports of other plants, like *Tetraena qataranse*, being tolerant to Cd, Cr, Cu, and Ni (Usman et al., 2019). article lipsum

Conclusion

This study sought to determine the ability of native *Zea mays* in Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria, to remove Cd, Pb, and Ni from contaminated soil. The acquired data demonstrated that *Zea mays* can collect Cd, Pb, and Ni in its tissues (shoots and roots). However, Ni buildup in plant roots was preferable to Cd and Pb. Ni treatments below 60 mg/kg had a greater BCF value than 1, indicating metal ion absorption. Furthermore, the BCF of Cd showed a similar result at 5 mg/kg, whereas that of Pb for all treatments did not reach 1. Phytostabilization is the primary process by which *Zea mays* remediates soil contaminated with Cd, Pb, and Ni (TF i 1). Additional research is required to explore the phytoremediation performance of *Zea mays* for heavy metals when combined with plant growth boosters in order to maximize the plant's heavy metal removal effectiveness in sandy soils.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the team of technologists in the Delta State University Chemistry Laboratory, Abraka, for their advice and assistance during this research.

Declarations

- **Funding:** No funding
- **Conflict of interest:** None declared
- **Ethical approval:** Not required

References

Alaboudi, K. A., Ahmed, B., Brodie, G. (2018). Phytoremediation of Pb and Cd contaminated soils by using sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) plant. *Annals of Agricultural Sciences*, 63(1), 123–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aos.2018.04.003>

Alengebawy, A., Abdelkhalek, S. T., Qureshi, S. R., Wang, M.-Q. (2021). Heavy metals and pesticides toxicity in agricultural soil and plants: Ecological risks and human health implications. *Toxics*, 9(3), 42. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics9030042>

Andresen, E., Küpper, H. (2013). Cadmium toxicity in plants. In H. Sigel, A. Sigel, R. K. O. Sigel (Eds.), *Cadmium: From toxicity to essentiality* (pp. 395–413). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-5179-8_12

Anoliefo, G., Isikhuemhen, O., Ohimain, E. (2006). Sensitivity studies of the common bean (*Vigna unguiculata*) and maize (*Zea mays*) to different soil types from the crude oil drilling site at Kutchalli, Nigeria. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 6(1), 30–36. <https://doi.org/10.1065/jss2006.01.154>

Asare, M. O., Száková, J., Tlustoš, P. (2023). The fate of secondary metabolites in plants growing on Cd-, As-, and Pb-contaminated soils—a comprehensive review. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(5), 11378–11398. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-22989-0>

Ashraf, S., Ali, Q., Zahir, Z. A., Ashraf, S., Asghar, H. N. (2019). Phytoremediation: Environmentally sustainable way for reclamation of heavy metal polluted soils. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 174, 714–727. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.02.068>

Atta, M. I., Zehra, S. S., Ali, H., Ali, B., Abbas, S. N., Aimen, S., Sarwar, S., Ahmad, I., Hussain, M., Al-Ashkar, I., Elango, D., El Sabagh, A. (2023). Assessing the effect of heavy metals on maize (*Zea mays* L.) growth and soil characteristics: plants-implications for phytoremediation. *PeerJ*, 11, e15068. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.15068>

Bechaieb, R., Lakhdar, Z. B., Gérard, H. (2018). DFT and TD-DFT studies of Mg-substitution in chlorophyll by Cr(II), Fe(II) and Ni(II). *Chemistry Africa*, 1(1), 79–86. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42250-018-0010-2>

Behnisch, M., Krüger, T., Jaeger, J. A. G. (2022). Rapid rise in urban sprawl: Global hotspots and trends since 1990. *PLOS Sustainability and Transformation*, 1(11), e0000034. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pstr.0000034>

Bouyoucos, G. J. (1962). Hydrometer method improved for making particle size analyses of soils. *Agronomy Journal*, 54(5), 464–465. <https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj1962.0002196200540005002>

Bray, R. H., Kurtz, L. T. (1945). Determination of total, organic, and available forms of phosphorus in soils. *Soil Science*, 59(1), 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00010694-194501000-00006>

- Bremner, J. M., Bremner, M. (1996). Nitrogen-total. In D. L. Sparks (Ed.), *Methods of soil analysis: Part 3 chemical methods* (pp. 1085–1121). John Wiley Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssabookser5.3.c37>
- Chtouki, M., Naciri, R., Soulaïmani, A., Zeroual, Y., El Gharous, M., Oukarroum, A. (2021). Effect of cadmium and phosphorus interaction on tomato: Chlorophyll a fluorescence, plant growth, and cadmium translocation. *Water, Air, Soil Pollution*, 232(3), 84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-021-05091-3>
- Coulibaly, H., Ouattara, P. J.-M., Messou, A., Coulibaly, L. (2021). Phytoextraction of trace metals (Cd, Ni and Pb) by *Panicum maximum* grown on natural soil. *Open Journal of Applied Sciences*, 11(08), 929–945. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojapps.2021.118069>
- Daryabeigi Zand, A., Mühling, K. H. (2022). Phytoremediation capability and copper uptake of maize (*Zea mays* L.) in copper contaminated soils. *Pollutants*, 2(1), 53–65. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pollutants2010005>
- Ding, N., Meng, X., Zhang, Z., Ma, J., Shan, Y., Zhong, Z., Yu, H., Li, M., Jiao, W. (2023). A review of life cycle assessment of soil remediation technology: Method applications and technological characteristics. *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 262(1), 1–19. https://doi.org/10.1007/398_022_36
- Egobueze, F. E., Ayotamuno, J. M., Iwegbue, C. M. A., Eze, C., Okparanma, R. N. (2019). Effects of organic amendment on some soil physicochemical characteristics and vegetative properties of *Zea mays* in wetland soils of the Niger Delta impacted with crude oil. *International Journal of Recycling of Organic Waste in Agriculture*, 8(1), 423–435. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40093-019-0262-8>
- Elehinafe, F. B., Olomukoro, O. G., Ayeni, A. O., Okedere, O. B. (2022). A short review on land/soil pollution: The pollutants and the treatment techniques. In A. O. Ayeni, O. Oladokun, O. D. Orodu (Eds.), *Advanced manufacturing in biological, petroleum, and nanotechnology processing: Application tools for design, operation, cost management, and environmental remediation* (pp. 267–275). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-73233-7_15
- Ewais, E. A. (1997). Effects of cadmium, nickel and lead on growth, chlorophyll content and proteins of weeds. *Biologia Plantarum*, 39(3), 403–410. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1001051409499>
- Ghori, N.-H., Ghori, T., Hayat, M. Q., Imadi, S. R., Gul, A., Altay, V., Ozturk, M. (2019). Heavy metal stress and responses in plants. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 16(3), 1807–1828. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-019-02215-8>
- Gill, R., Naeem, M., Ansari, A. A., Gill, S. S. (2023). Phytoremediation and management of environmental contaminants: Conclusion and future perspectives. In L. Newman, A. A. Ansari, S. S. Gill, M. Naeem, R. Gill (Eds.), *Phytoremediation: Management of environmental contaminants*, volume 7 (pp. 599–603). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-27484-8_3
- Irfan, M., Mudassir, M., Khan, M. J., Dawar, K. M., Muhammad, D., Mian, I. A., Ali, W., Fahad, S., Saud, S., Hayat, Z., Nawaz, T., Khan, S. A., Alam, S., Ali, B., Banout, J., Ahmed, S., Mubeen, S., Danish, S., Datta, R., ... Dewangan, K. N. (2022). Soil contamination, sources, health effects, and sustainable soil management. *Sustainability*, 14(16), 9948. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14169948>
- Karim, S. R., Qureshi, R. (2014). Impact of toxic metals on seed germination and seedling growth of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Pakistan Journal of Botany*, 46(1), 237–240.
- Khalid, S., Shahid, M., Niazi, N. K., Murtaza, B., Bibi, I., Dumat, C. (2017). A comparison of technologies for remediation of heavy metal contaminated soils. *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, 182, 247–268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gexplo.2016.11.021>
- Khan, N. S., Moheman, A. (2006). Effect of heavy metals (cadmium and chromium) on seed germination and seedling growth of *Albizia lebbek* (L.) Benth. *Journal of Environment and Science*, 20(5), 691–696. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1001-0742\(06\)60118-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1001-0742(06)60118-8)
- Khan, S., Bibi, S., Anwar, S., Shah, A. (2021). Effect of lead, cadmium and chromium in soil on Maize (*Zea mays* L.) growth and concentration of heavy metals. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health Sciences*, 13(1), 12–18. <https://doi.org/10.5897/JTEHS2020.0458>
- Kumar, A., Kumar, A., Singh, A. K., Singh, S. (2021). Environmental and human

health consequences of soil pollution: A review. *Sustainability*, 13(21), 11676. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132111676>

Mouhamadou, B., Hamidou, M. B., Belyamani, R., El Moudane, M. (2019). Environmental and health impacts of cadmium exposure in agricultural soils. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 26(4), 3517–3527. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-018-2656-0>

Nagajyoti, P. C., Lee, K. D., Sreekanth, T. V. M. (2010). Heavy metals, occurrence and toxicity for plants: A review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 8(3), 199–216. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-010-0297-8>

Nawab, A., Farooq, M., Farooq, M. A., Farooq, S. (2018). Phytoremediation potential of *Phragmites australis* for cadmium-contaminated soil and water in hydroponic and pot studies. *Journal of Plant Growth Regulation*, 37(3), 951–961. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00344-018-9794-1>

Nikolić, M., Gajić, B., Delić, D. (2021). Heavy metal and nutrient accumulation and distribution in maize (*Zea mays* L.) grown on contaminated soils. *Agronomy*, 11(9), 1742. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11091742>

Obiora, S. C., Chukwu, A., Wali, A. (2023). Contamination assessment and potential health risk of toxic metals in soils around an abandoned coal mine in Enugu, Nigeria. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal*, 29(1), 225–245. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10807039.2021.1956965>

Rossi, A. M., Clark, J. J. (2004). *Phytoremediation of toxic metals: Using plants to clean up the environment*. Springer US. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-8850-0>

Sarma, H. (2011). Metal hyperaccumulation in plants: A review focusing on phytoremediation technology. *Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 4(2), 118–138. <https://doi.org/10.3923/jest.2011.118.138>

Shahid, M., Khalid, S., Abbas, G., Shahid, N., Nadeem, M., Sabir, M., Khalid, M. I., Akram, M. (2019). Heavy metal stress and crop production. In S. A. Hasanuzzaman, K. Nahar, M. Fujita (Eds.), *Advances in agronomy* (Vol. 1, pp. 1–18). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-16073-4_1

Shamshuddin, J., Shazana, M. A. R. S., Fauziah, I.,

Husni, M. H. A. (2013). Improving the productivity of an acid sulfate soil for rice cultivation using lime, basalt, organic fertilizer and biofertilizer. *Pedosphere*, 23(6), 723–733. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0160\(13\)60064-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0160(13)60064-1)

Sivritepe, N., Eris, A., Sivritepe, H. O., Turkan, I. (2005). The effects of NaCl priming on salt tolerance in melon seedlings grown under saline conditions. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 106(4), 568–581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2005.05.002>

Xiong, Y., Wang, H. (2005). Copper content in plants and the effect of copper on plant growth and recovery of copper in contaminated soil. *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 17(1), 70–73. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1001-0742\(05\)60054-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1001-0742(05)60054-5)

Physiochemical Properties and Biodegradation Potentials of Soil Microbes Isolated from Mechanic Workshops in Benin Metropolis

Udinyiwe, C.O.^{1*} and Omoregie, A.E.¹

¹Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, P.M.B 1154, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: collins.udinyiwe@uniben.edu, +2348062613143

ABSTRACT

The release of used engine oil into the environment is gradually becoming a challenge to our environment. This research was carried out to determine the physiochemical properties and biodegradation potentials of some soil microbes isolated from mechanic workshops in Benin metropolis. The physiochemical properties of the soil samples were investigated according to the methods of Association of Official Analytical Chemists. The microbial analysis was carried out according to standard microbiological and biochemical methods. Results revealed bacterial count ranged from 1.6×10^4 – 3.8×10^4 cfu/g, Hydrocarbon utilizing bacterial counts ranging from 0.4×10^4 – 1.0×10^4 cfu/g. Fungal counts ranging from 0.1×10^4 – 0.7×10^4 cfu/g. The bacteria isolated were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Acinetobacter* spp., *Corynebacterium* spp. and *Klebsiella* spp. The fungi isolates identified were *Trichoderma* spp., *Penicillium* spp., *Mucor* spp., *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium* spp. The screening test revealed *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Trichoderma* spp. and *Aspergillus niger* to have biodegradative potentials. Shake flask experiment revealed increased in the turbidity of the mineral salt medium amended with engine oil. The consortium of bacterial and fungal showed better degradation potentials especially with the gradual increase turbidity and reduction in pH. The results suggest that the consortium of the isolates could be used in remediating contaminated soils.

Keywords: Bacteria, Fungi, Optical density, Consortium, Microbes

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution and the presence of complex mixtures of hydrocarbons and other organic compounds, including some organo-metabolic constituents used to lubricate the metallic parts of an automobile engine, have become major challenges today in the environment (Udeani et al., 2009). When spent engine oil enters the environment, it causes alterations in some soil properties, microbial activities, and influences the concentration of organic matter, nitrogen, magnesium, and heavy metals in the soil (Okonokhua et al., 2007). Prolonged exposure to high oil concentrations may cause the development of liver or kidney disease, possible damage to the bone marrow, and an increased risk of cancer (Mishra et al., 2001). Used engine oil pollutes the environment and constitutes a potential threat to humans, animals, and vegetation (Edewor et al., 2004; Adelowo et al., 2006). Used motor oil can cause great damage to sensitive environments and soil microorganisms. Substantial volumes of soil have been contaminated by used

oil in many countries, especially industrialized nations. Large amounts of used engine oil are released into the environment when the oil from motor cars, motorbikes, and generators is changed and disposed of into gutters, water drains, open vacant plots, and farmlands—a common practice by motor and generator mechanics (Odjegba and Sadiq, 2002). The presence of spent engine oil in the soil creates a chemical impurity which contributes to chronic hazards resulting in mutagenicity and environmental risk (Blodgette, 2001). Various contaminants, such as used engine oil and heavy metals, have been found to alter soil biochemistry, including changes in soil microbial properties such as pH, O₂, and nutrient availability (Odjegba and Sadiq, 2002). Spent engine oil contains metals and heavy polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), which could contribute to chronic hazards, including mutagenicity and carcinogenicity (Boonchan et al., 2000). As it is inevitable for the efficient and effective functioning of automobile engines, soil contamination with used engine oil is becoming one of the major

environmental problems (Mandri and Lin, 2006), mainly due to uncontrolled disposal, particularly in developing economies. The widespread ability of microorganisms to assimilate these hydrocarbons is of great significance, and when it occurs in the natural environment, the process is known as biodegradation. Hydrocarbons, including PAHs, have long been recognized as substrates supporting microbial growth. A wide range of hydrocarbon utilizers (HCUs) found to be useful in the soil includes species such as *Pseudomonas*, *Rhodococcus*, *Mycobacterium*, *Bacillus*, *Acinetobacter*, *Providencia*, *Flavobacter*, *Corynebacterium*, and *Streptococcus* (Bhattacharya et al., 2002). Other organisms, such as fungi, are also capable of degrading hydrocarbons in engine oil to a certain extent, but they take longer periods to grow compared to their bacterial counterparts (Prenafeta-Boldu et al., 2001). The aim of this study was to determine the physiochemical properties and biodegradation potentials of soil microbes isolated from mechanic workshops in Benin metropolis, Nigeria.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Sites

The five locations in Benin City metropolis used in this study were Uwelu around the mechanic workshops, Evbareke around the mechanic workshops, Igun around the mechanic workshops, Ugbowo around the mechanic workshops opposite University of Benin, and Oluku around the mechanic workshop close to the Bypass.

Sample Collection

Composite soil samples from designated mechanic workshops in the five areas of study were collected in a sterile polyethylene bag using a sterile spatula from the edge of a motor oil-stained patch in the workshop by scooping to about 5 cm. The samples were immediately transported to the laboratory for analyses.

Physiochemical Properties of the Soil Samples

The physiochemical properties of the soil samples were investigated according to the methods of A.O.A.C. (2000).

Figure 1: Map showing GPS coordinates of soil samples collected around the study sites.

Bacterial Enumeration

One gram (1 g) of the contaminated soil was weighed using an analytical balance (Model no AX423/E, USA Ohaus Cooperation) into test tubes containing 9 ml distilled water, and 10-fold dilution was carried out to 10^{-3} dilution. One milliliter (1 ml) of each dilution was inoculated into nutrient agar and potato dextrose agar for bacteria and fungi using the pour plate method. The plates for bacteria were incubated at 37°C for 48 hrs, while the plates for fungi were incubated at 30°C for 48 hrs. Hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria counts (HUB) were enumerated by inoculating 1 ml of aliquot of 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} into mineral salt agar plates prepared according to Chessbrough (2000). The plates were incubated for 7 days, and the discrete colonies were counted.

Characterization and Identification of Bacterial and Fungal Isolates

The bacteria and fungi isolates were characterized based on preliminary cultural and biochemical characteristics. Identification of the isolates was performed according to the method of Chessbrough (2000). The pure cultures were maintained in slants in McCartney bottles containing tryptic soy broth-glycerol (TSB-glycerol). They were stored at 4°C until required for analysis.

Screening Test for Biodegradation Potential of Engine Oil Contaminated Soil

The isolates were screened for the ability to utilize spent engine oil using mineral salt medium. Nine

milliliters (9 ml) of mineral salt medium were dispensed into six test tubes for bacteria and five test tubes for fungi. In each of the test tubes, one milliliter of spent engine oil was added as the main source of carbon. Thereafter, all the test tubes were inoculated with 0.5 MacFarland (10^8 cfu/ml) of an isolate previously grown. All the test tubes were incubated at 30°C for 7 days, after which the turbidity of the solution was checked to determine the potentials of the isolates. Those with high degradation potentials were utilized, while those with poor degradation potential were eliminated from the experiment (Somari et al., 2022).

Determination of the Ability of the Bacterial and Fungal Isolates to Utilize Spent Engine Oil from Contaminated Soil Using Shake Flask Method

A known volume of 98 ml of the mineral salt medium was transferred into 250 ml conical flasks followed by 1 ml spent engine oil before sterilization. Thereafter, all the conical flasks except for the control sample were inoculated with 0.5 MacFarland (10^8 cfu/ml) of a twenty-four (24 h) culture. The utilization of the engine oil was monitored at three-day intervals for a total of twelve days. The optical density and pH readings were monitored at 3-day intervals for 12 days. The optical density was measured with a M501 UV-Vis Camspec Spectrophotometer using 600 nm, while the pH was measured with a pH meter (Onyeiwu et al., 2022; Veerapagu et al., 2019).

Statistics

The data were subjected to One-way ANOVA using SPSS for various parameters. Further tests, such as Duncan's multiple range test, were carried out to ascertain significance among the parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 reveals the physicochemical properties of the crude oil-contaminated soil samples. The research by Mahmood et al. (2020) shows that the physicochemical properties of soil can be affected by hydrocarbon contamination. These properties have been found to aid in the proliferation of bacteria in the soil. The interaction between living organisms and petroleum contaminants is highly dependent on the type of soil (Onyeiwu et al., 2022). Mahmood et al. (2020) further show that soil pH plays a critical role in the absorption of nutrients by plants and has

a significant effect on the interaction of microbes, which can affect the potential of microbes to carry out bioremediation. In this study, the pH ranged from 6.31 ± 0.07 to 6.79 ± 0.10 , a comfortable range that could facilitate the bioremediation activities of the bacteria isolated from the soil. Similar pH ranges have been reported by Udinyiwe and Aghedo (2023), and Udinyiwe et al. (2022), which supports better comparison and understanding. Soil pH is a key factor influencing the uptake of available nutrients for plant utilization (Udinyiwe and Aghedo, 2023; Mahmood et al., 2020). Bada et al. (2018) reported a similar pH range of 4.48 ± 0.48 to 6.72 ± 0.72 , which favors microbial metabolic activities. Okoh (2006) noted that low or acidic pH can affect the rate of oil biodegradation by bacteria in oil-contaminated soil. Acidic soil releases heavy metals such as Cd, Ni, Pb, Cu, Hg, and Zn, which creates problems for crop production (Bada et al., 2014).

The significantly higher values of electrical conductivity obtained from various sampling sites in this study could have resulted from the high concentration of charged ions in the impacted sites. Oyem and Oyem (2013) revealed electrical conductivity values higher than those reported in this study. The electrical conductivity in this study ranged from 306.30 ± 05.40 to 497.50 ± 0.90 , which could be attributed to the presence of high Na^+ and Mg^+ salts in the environment. This range is consistent with the values reported by Abosede (2013), Sari et al. (2018), and Oyem and Oyem (2013). High electrical conductivity can negatively impact soil (Abdulfattah et al., 2016; Precti and Shah, 2015).

Table 2 reveals bacterial counts ranging from 1.6×10^4 to 3.8×10^4 cfu/g, while Table 3 shows hydrocarbon-utilizing bacterial counts ranging from 0.4×10^4 to 1.0×10^4 cfu/g. This indicates that bacteria can survive and thrive in this environment. Udinyiwe et al. (2022) reported total heterotrophic bacteria counts and hydrocarbon-utilizing bacterial counts similar to those reported in this study. Ogbonna et al. (2020) reported total heterotrophic bacterial counts (THBC) ranging from $2.58 \times 10^8 \pm 0.07$ cfu/g to $2.10 \times 10^7 \pm 0.50$ cfu/g, and total hydrocarbon-utilizing bacterial counts (THUBC) ranging from $8.1 \times 10^3 \pm 0.50$ cfu/g to $5.0 \times 10^4 \pm 0.50$ cfu/g, which agree with the findings of this study, confirming that bacteria can thrive in hydrocarbon-polluted sites.

Table 1: Physicochemical properties of hydrocarbon-contaminated soil samples

Parameters Sample E	Sample A	Sample B	Sample C	Sample D
pH 6.56 ± 0.12	6.79 ± 0.10	6.47 ± 0.01	6.31 ± 0.07	6.41 ± 0.08
EC (mS/m) 497.50 ± 0.90	456.45 ± 1.55	306.30 ± 5.40 ^{ab}	396.00 ± 0.90	391.90 ± 4.60 ^a
Carbon (%) 3.05 ± 0.23 ^a	3.31 ± 0.05	3.23 ± 0.04	3.44 ± 0.05	3.19 ± 0.03
Nitrogen (%) 0.79 ± 0.06	0.09 ± 0.03 ^a	1.04 ± 0.22 ^a	0.74 ± 0.06 ^a	0.62 ± 0.05 ^{ab}
Phosphorus (%) 1.57 ± 0.02	1.61 ± 0.03	1.43 ± 0.04	1.68 ± 0.09	1.66 ± 0.01
Water holding capacity (%) 76.55 ± 0.30 ^a	80.70 ± 0.70	78.50 ± 0.50	80.28 ± 0.72	75.55 ± 0.55 ^a
Bulk density (g/cm ³) 2.05 ± 0.11 ^a	2.66 ± 0.02	2.40 ± 0.01 ^a	1.90 ± 0.02 ^{ab}	2.70 ± 0.04
Moisture (%) 12.07 ± 0.30	12.06 ± 0.30	13.09 ± 0.24	13.40 ± 0.20	12.33 ± 0.55

Table 2: Total heterotrophic bacterial counts (cfu/g) of soil from mechanic workshop

Samples Mean counts	10 ⁻¹	10 ⁻²	10 ⁻³
Uwelu 3.8 × 10 ⁴	139	74	31
Evwaike 3.4 × 10 ⁴	110	59	24
Igun 2.3 × 10 ⁴	88	35	19
Ugbowo 1.6 × 10 ⁴	72	29	13
Oluku 3.0 × 10 ⁴	94	51	24

Table 3: Hydrocarbon-utilizing bacterial counts (cfu/g) of soil from mechanic workshop

Samples Mean counts	10 ⁻¹	10 ⁻²	10 ⁻³
Uwelu 1.0 × 10 ⁴	57	22	08
Evwaike 0.7 × 10 ⁴	44	17	05
Igun 0.6 × 10 ⁴	38	14	05
Ugbowo 0.4 × 10 ⁴	31	11	03
Oluku 0.8 × 10 ⁴	40	16	07

Table 4 shows fungal counts ranging from 0.1 × 10⁴ to 0.7 × 10⁴ cfu/g. The presence of fungal growth indicates that the soil has been exposed to hydrocarbon pollution, enriching it for fungal growth. Ogbonna et al. (2020) reported total fungal counts (TFC) and hydrocarbon-utilizing fungal counts (HUFC) ranging from 2.0 × 10⁵ ± 0.05 cfu/g to 1.6 × 10⁵ ± 0.08 cfu/g and 9.0 × 10³ ± 0.05 cfu/g to 7.0 × 10⁴ ± 0.50 cfu/g, respectively. This confirms that fungi can utilize hydrocarbons as a source of energy.

The microbes identified in this study with degradation potentials include *Bacillus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Micrococcus* spp., *Acinetobacter* spp., *Fusarium* spp., and *Aspergillus* spp. (Udinyiwe et al., 2022; Ijah and Abioye, 2003; Ajayi et al., 2008; Das and Chandran, 2011; Omotayo et al., 2012; Ogbonna et al., 2020; Bento et al., 2005). The results in Tables 5 and 6 show the growth and potential of these microbes to utilize hydrocarbons as an energy source. *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas*

Table 4: Total heterotrophic fungal counts (cfu/g) of soil from mechanic workshop

Samples	10 ⁻¹	10 ⁻²	10 ⁻³
Mean counts			
Uwelu 0.7 × 10 ⁴	29	14	06
Evwaike 0.4 × 10 ⁴	23	08	03
Igun 0.2 × 10 ⁴	19	07	02
Ugbowo 0.1 × 10 ⁴	15	04	01
Oluku 0.3 × 10 ⁴	18	05	02

Table 5: Result of screening test for biodegradation of engine oil contaminated soil

Isolates	Optical Density (OD)
Acinetobacter spp	0.293
Micrococcus luteus	0.507
Bacillus subtilis	0.883
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	0.916
Corynebacterium spp.	0.128
Aspergillus niger	0.739
Penicillium	0.427
Mucor spp.	0.396
Trichoderma spp.	0.661
Fusarium spp.	0.131
Control	0.000

Keys: + = Little Growth, ++ = Moderate Growth, +++ = Heavy Growth, - = No Growth

aeruginosa, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Trichoderma* spp., selected after the screening test, demonstrated hydrocarbon degradation abilities in the 12-day shake flask experiment. The gradual increase in optical density indicates hydrocarbon utilization by these microbes. Dilmi et al. (2017) reported a similar gradual increase in optical density over fifteen days, indicating bacterial adaptation, survival, and proliferation. This study's results showed a gradual increase in turbidity of the mineral salt medium, indicating bacterial adaptation and proliferation, leading to the degradation of hydrocarbons. Udinyiwe et al. (2022) also reported increased turbidity and

pH over 12 days, consistent with this study. The microbial proliferation observed using poor plate techniques in Table 6 indicates bacterial utilization and adaptation in the medium, in agreement with Udinyiwe et al. (2022) and Ogbonna et al. (2020). For instance, the microbial population of *Bacillus subtilis* increased from 5.9×10^6 at day 0 to 1.25×10^7 at day 15.

Conclusion

The study revealed that soil samples collected from the five mechanic workshops were contaminated with spent engine oil. Results from this study are relevant in explaining the changes in the state of the soil environment, which leads to a corresponding change in the microbial composition. Oil degraders with inherent hydrocarbon assimilatory potentials are enriched by the contaminants, while the less adapted microbial species among the total heterotrophic populations are gradually being eliminated due to changes in species composition. The results of this study showed that the microbes isolated from engine oil-contaminated soil had biodegradation potentials.

References

- Abdulfattah, A. A., Saima, J., Arif, M., Rawand, S. (2016). Effects of crude oil spillage on phytochemical properties of soil. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*, 6(6), 27–32.
- Abosedo, E. E. (2013). Effect of crude oil pollution on some soil physical properties. *Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Science*, 6(3), 14–17.
- Adegoroye, G. (1997). Environmental considerations in property design, urban development, and renewal. In O. Akinjide (Ed.), *Dimensions of environmental problems in Nigeria* (pp. 12–15).
- Adelowo, O. O., Alagbe, S. O., Ayandele, A. A. (2006). Time-dependent stability of used engine oil degradation by cultures of *Pseudomonas fragi* and *Achromobacter aerogenes*. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 5(24), 2476–2479.
- Ajayi, A. O., Balogun, S. A., Adegbehingbe, K. (2008). Microorganisms in the crude oil-producing areas of Ondo State, Nigeria. *Scientific Research and Essays*, 3(5), 174–179.
- Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC). (2000). *Official methods of analysis* (17th ed.). AOAC.
- Bento, F. M., Camarago, F. A. O., Okeke, B.

Table 6: Optical density (600 nm) during shake flask biodegradation for 12 days

Isolates	Day 0 to Day 3	Day 3 to Day 6	Day 6 to Day 9	Day 9 to Day 12
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	0.077	0.394	0.771	0.737
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	0.086	0.525	1.103	0.919
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	0.091	0.478	0.933	0.896
<i>Trichoderma spp.</i>	0.052	0.303	0.596	0.538
Bacterial consortium	0.103	0.768	1.394	1.361
Fungal consortium	0.119	0.694	1.286	1.209
Control	0.028	0.032	0.038	0.036

C., Frankenberger, W. T. (2005). Comparative bioremediation of soil contaminated with diesel oil by natural attenuation, bio stimulation, and bioaugmentation. *Bioresource Technology*, 96, 1049–1055.

Bhattacharya, S. C., Leon, M. A., Rahman, M. M. (2002). A study on improved biomass briquetting. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 6(2), 67–71.

Blodgette, W. C. (2001). Water soluble mutagen production during the bioremediation of oil contaminated soil. *Florida Science Journal*, 60(1), 28–36.

Boonchan, S., Britz, M. L., Stanley, G. A. (2000). Degradation and mineralization of high-molecular weight polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons by defined fungi-bacterial co-cultures. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 66(3), 1007–1019.

Cheesebrough, M. (2000). *District laboratory practices in tropical countries* (Part 2). Cambridge University Press.

Das, N., Chandran, P. (2011). Microbial degradation of petroleum hydrocarbon contaminants: An overview. *Biotechnology Research International*, 1, 1–13.

Dilmi, F., Chibani, A., Rezkallah, K. S. (2017). Isolation and molecular identification of hydrocarbon degrading bacteria from oil contaminated soil. *International Journal of Bioscience*, 11(4), 272–283.

Edewor, T. L., Adelowo, O. O., Afolabi, T. J. (2004). Preliminary studies into the biological activities of a broad-spectrum disinfectant formulation from used engine oil. *Pollution Research*, 23(4), 581–586.

Ijah, U. J. J., Abioye, O. P. (2003). Assessment of physiochemical and microbiological properties of soil 30 months after kerosene spill. *Journal of Research Science Management*, 1(1), 24–30.

Mahmood, V., Zahermand, S., Mohammad, H.

B. (2020). Analysis of the physical and chemical properties of soil contaminated with oil (petroleum) hydrocarbons. *Earth Science Research Journal*, 24(2), 163–168.

Mandri, T., Lin, J. (2007). Isolation and characterization of engine oil degrading indigenous microorganisms in Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 6(1), 23–27.

Mishra, S. J., Jyot, R. C., Kuhad, B. L. (2001). Evaluation of inoculum addition to stimulate in situ bioremediation of oily-sludge contaminated soil. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 67(4), 1675–1681.

Odjegba, V. J., Sadiq, A. O. (2002). Effect of spent engine oil on the growth parameters, chlorophyll, and protein levels of *Amaranthus hybridus* L. *The Environmentalist*, 22, 23–28.

Ogbonna, D. N., Douglas, S. I., Awari, V. G. (2020). Characterization of hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria and fungi associated with crude oil contaminated soil. *Microbiology Research Journal International*, 30(5), 54–69.

Okoh, I. A. (2006). Biodegradation alternatives in the cleanup of petroleum hydrocarbon pollutants. *Journal of Biotechnology and Molecular Biology*, 1(2), 38–50.

Okonokhua, B. O. B., Ikhajiagbe, B., Anoliefo, G. O., Emede, J. O. (2007). The effect of spent oil on soil properties and growth of maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Journal of Applied Science and Environmental Management*, 11(3), 147–152.

Omotayo, A. E., Ojo, O. Y., Amund, O. O. (2012). Crude oil degradation by microorganisms in soil composts. *Research Journal of Microbiology*, 7(4), 209–218.

Onyeiwu, S. C., Umoh, V. J., Ameh, J. B. (2022). Screening of fungi isolated from Kaduna refinery area

for petroleum hydrocarbon bioremediation potentials. *Science World Journal*, 17(2), 327–331.

Oyem, I. L. R., Oyem, I. L. (2013). Effect of crude oil spillage on soil physicochemical properties in Ugborodo Community. *International Journal of Modern Engineering Research*, 3(6), 3336–3342.

Precti, T., Shah, M. V. (2015). Correlation between index properties and electrical resistivity of hydrocarbon contaminated periodic marine clays. *Journal of Earth and Environmental Science*, 26, 1–6.

Prenafeta-Boldu, F. X., Kuhn, A., Luykx, M. D., Anke, H., Groenestijn, J. W., De-Bont, J. A. (2001). Isolation and characterization of fungi growing on volatile aromatic hydrocarbons as their sole carbon and energy source. *Mycology Research Journal*, 105(4), 477–484.

Sari, L. G., Trihadiningrum, Y., Matuzahroh, N. (2018). Petroleum hydrocarbon pollution in soil and surface water by public oil field in Wonocolo sub-district, Indonesia. *Journal of Ecological Engineering*, 19(2), 184–193.

Somaiari, A. A. A., Douglas, S. I., Nrior, R. R. (2022). Screening for biodegradation potential of endophytic bacteria isolated from the roots and leaves of mangrove plants (*Avicennia germinans* [Black Mangrove], *Acrostichum aureum* [Golden Leather Fern], and *Rhizophora mangle* [Red Mangrove]). *Journal of Advances in Microbiology*, 22(7), 19–28.

Udinyiwe, C. O., Idemudia, I. B., Ekhaise, F. O. (2022). Biodegradation potential of bacterial isolates from crude oil contaminated soil samples from Gelegele River, Edo State. *NIPES Journal of Science and Technology Research*, 4(1), 244–257.

Udinyiwe, C. O., Aghedo, E. S. (2023). Effect of crude oil spillage on some soil physical properties within Ovia North East Local Government in Edo State. *Scientia Africana*, 22(2), 37–48.

Udeani, T. K. C., Obroh, A. A., Okwuosa, C. N., Achukwu, P. U., Azubike, N. (2009). Isolation of bacteria from mechanic workshop soil environment contaminated with used engine oil. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 8(22), 6301–6303.

Veerapagu, M., Jeya, K. R., Kalaivani, R., Jeyanthi, K. A., Geethanjali, S. (2019). Screening of hydrocarbon degrading bacteria isolated from oil contaminated soil. *The Pharma Innovation*, 8(6), 69–72.

A Preliminary Investigation of Microplastic Levels in a Commercially Important Clariid Fish Species from Ikpoba River, Benin City, Nigeria

Wangboje, O. M.*¹ (ORCID: 0000-0001-7587-3883) and Omzogie, C.¹ (ORCID: 0009-0008-8357-3475)

¹Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Management, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Benin, P.M.B. 1154, Benin City, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: oiseoje.wangboje@uniben.edu

ABSTRACT

Microplastics (MPs) in natural water resources and their inclusion in food webs has become a critical issue globally. The paucity of risk assessment data on the levels of MPs in Ikpoba River, Benin City, Nigeria, warranted this research which was done via Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy. The mean levels of MPs in *Clarias gariepinus* (mean total length 32.74 ± 1.58 cm, mean weight 885 ± 1.76 g) according to stations ranged from 0.37 in June at station 1 to 5.23 in August at station 3 with a total ranging from 2.97 at station 2 to 6.18 at station 3. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the mean levels of MPs between the months across stations 1 and 3. The mean plastic load in *C. gariepinus* according to stations ranged from 0.31 in June at station 1 to 6.34 in August at station 3 with a total ranging from 3.22 at station 2 to 7.41 at station 3. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the mean plastic load between the months across stations 1 and 3. The dominant types of MP particles found in *C. gariepinus* were fragments and filaments of Polyethylene. The estimated daily intake (EDI) for MPs (No./person/day) ranged from 0.00154 at station 2 to 0.00321 at station 3. *C. gariepinus* must therefore be consumed with caution in order to avert health problems associated with polymer pollution in the long run.

Keywords: *Clarias gariepinus*, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy, Microplastics, Polyethylene

1 INTRODUCTION

Plastic production has increased substantially since large scale industrial manufacture started many decades ago such that all aspects of daily human life involve plastics hence their persistence in aquatic ecosystems globally (Lusher *et al.*, 2017). The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), has defined microplastics (MPs) as small fragments of plastic measuring less than 5 mm in length that are hazardous to aquatic bodies and their resources (NOAA, 2023). These polymers could have either primary or secondary sources. Primary microplastics are plastics directly released into the environment in the form of small particulates e.g. cosmetics, shower gels, abrasion of large plastic objects, wear of tyres and abrasion of synthetic textiles. Secondary microplastics on the flipside are microplastics originating from the degradation (e.g. photodegradation and weathering processes) of larger plastic items into smaller plastic fragments (International Union for Conservation of Nature, 2017). The occurrence of MPs in natural water

resources and their inclusion in food webs made possible by their minute size, has become a critical issue around the world especially in recent times (Kamau *et al.*, 2023; Pellicer and Domingo, 2023). It has been observed that a host of hydrobionts including fish, readily ingest MPs while grazing for food and these particles end up making their way into other parts of the body including edible tissue which is cherished by man (My *et al.*, 2023). The marine environment has been the focus of MP research in recent times (Wagner *et al.*, 2017; Selvakumar *et al.*, 2023). However, the searchlight has shifted to freshwater bodies which are now known to contain a cocktail of MPs including Polyethylene (PE), Polyamide (PA), Polyester (PES), Polypropylene (PP) and Polystyrene (PS) especially in their sediments thereby making benthic fish veritable targets of risk (Boskovic *et al.*, 2023). Mangrove ecosystems have also been scrutinized for MPs around the world in order to examine the contamination of flora, fauna and abiotic compartments (Mendes *et al.*, 2023). It has been observed that an increase in anthropogenic

activities over the years has led to the influx of synthetic fibres of MP into the aquatic environment which is fast overshadowing the presence of natural fibres in such recipient waters (Mancuso *et al.*, 2023). The negative impacts of MPs on aquatic life (including fish) and human health has been well documented (Kamau *et al.*, 2023). Microplastics remain a threat in the aquatic environment as more polymer-based products such as polymer electrodes and polymer-based ionic conductors are being manufactured (Arof, 2023). The Ikpoba river in Benin City, Nigeria, has been under a lot of anthropogenic pressure over the years which has resulted in a plethora of researches encompassing the impact of both inorganic pollutants (Oronsaye *et al.*, 2010; Wangboje *et al.*, 2014) and organic pollutants (Wangboje and Oronsaye, 2012; Wangboje and Oguzie, 2013). There is however paucity of risk assessment data on the levels of MPs in this particular ecosystem which this current research attempts to provide thereby expanding the pollutant base profile of the river. The fish species of choice, *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822), was particularly targeted as it is available in the Ikpoba river all year round and it is of high commercial appeal in Benin City and environs. The fish species can attain a length of over a metre with a weight of over 7 kg. It is commonly found in swamps, streams, rivers and lakes. It is an omnivorous bottom feeder, feeding on detritus, plankton, gastropods, crustacean, worms and small fishes such as *Tilapia* and *Alestes* species (Idodo-Umeh, 2003).

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of Study Area

This research was carried out on the Ikpoba River in Benin City (Latitude 6°20'00" N and Longitude 5°37'20" E) Edo state, Nigeria (Fig. 1). The City is located within the Tropical rainforest ecological zone of south-south Nigeria. Further details of the study area have been published by Wangboje and Momoh (2023). The stations established for this research were Upper Lawani (Station 1), Reservoir (Station 2), and Bridge (Station 3). The Upper Lawani station is located within Latitude 6°22'32" N and Longitude 5°38'45" E. Human activities carried out at this point include fishing and traditional religious activities. In the area are several retail stores, sawmills, and woodwork industries. The Reservoir station is located within Latitude 6°22'37" N and Longitude 5°38'23" E.

Economic activities in the vicinity include retail stores, sawmills, woodwork industries, and tyre vulcanizing. The Bridge station is located within Latitude 6°21'5" N and Longitude 5°38'49" E. The most prevalent anthropogenic activities at this station are car wash, rug wash, and the operation of slaughterhouses.

Figure 1: Map of the study area (Source: Survey Department, Benin City)

2.2 Collection of Fish Specimens

Fishes were caught between 7:00 am and 9:00 am on sampling days between June and August 2023, with the assistance of artisanal fishermen. Fishes that did not visually resemble the target species were released immediately upon capture. Retained samples of fishes were rinsed with river water in order to remove extraneous materials. In-situ, the identities of the fish species were verified and confirmed using a key (Idodo-Umeh, 2003) and a field guide (Olaosebikan and Raji, 2013). Total length (cm) measurements were taken using a water-proof measuring board while weight (g) of fish samples was ascertained using an electronic Scale (Mettler® PM4800 Delta Range Series). The mean total length was 32.74 ± 1.58 cm while the mean weight was 885 ± 1.76 (n=27). Samples were placed in labeled zip-lock bags and conveyed to the laboratory in a Thermolineo® insulated ice chest within 24 hours for further studies.

2.3 Ex-situ Procedures and Laboratory Assay

2.3.1 Isolation of MPs from Organic Matter and Microscopy

The modified isolation procedure by Abidin et al. (2021) was applied. Briefly, fifty grams (50 g) of the excised intestine of fish was treated with 10% KOH solution (at three times the volume of tissue) followed by incubation for 24 hours. Excision was carried out using a stainless steel lancet via the ventral aspect of whole fish. The Wet Peroxide Oxidation process was applied by adding 30 mL of 0.05 M Fe (II) oxide (FeO) and 30 mL of 20% Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), followed by heating on a Binatone® Hotplate (Model ECP-207, rated at 2,500W) at 75°C for 45 minutes to eradicate organic matter from the fish. All reagents used were of analytical grade (SIGMA, Germany). The remaining filtrates were treated via heating, followed by filtration with stainless steel sieves of 45 m mesh size. The dried filtrate was placed on a slide under a UNIC® compound binocular electric microscope, in order to visually account for the numerical strength of fibres, filaments, fragments, and pellets.

2.3.2 Additional Verification Procedures for MPs

Additional verification of MPs was achieved by applying the tagging method as described by Maes et al. (2017) and the hot needle test or hot point test as described by De Witte et al. (2014).

2.3.3 Application of Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy for Polymer Differentiation

Polymer differentiation was achieved using FTIR Spectroscopy. The specific device used was a Shimadzu® FTIR 8400S Spectroscope which was correctly programmed and conditioned according to the manufacturer's standard prior to use.

2.3.4 Determination of Plastic Load (PL)

The mean amount of MP per fish is known as the plastic load (PL). $PL = \frac{\text{Total number of MP particles}}{\text{Total number of fish species examined}}$ (Zhang et al., 2021).

2.3.5 Determination of Frequency of Occurrence (FO) for MP

Frequency of occurrence (FO) denotes the percentage of fish with at least one piece of MP. $FO = \frac{\text{Number of fish with at least one MP particle}}{\text{Number of fish sampled}}$ (Riaz et al., 2023).

2.3.6 Contamination Circumvention

In order to avert contamination of samples, non-plastic clothes were worn (Cotton laboratory coat) while sampling and laboratory instruments made from non-plastic components, such as glass, were used as recommended by Cutroneo et al. (2020). All work benches and surrounding areas were thoroughly wiped with absolute alcohol (99.9%) and disposable Cotton sheets before, in between, and after analysis.

2.3.7 Determination of Estimated Annual Intake (EAI) and Estimated Daily Intake (EDI) of MPs

- $EAI (\text{No./person/year}) = \frac{\text{Number of MP items in fish} \times \text{Per capita figure}}{\text{Adult body weight (Assumed to be 70 kg)}}$
Where: Per capita figure is 13.3 kg/person/year for Nigeria (World Fish Center, 2023)
- $EDI (\text{No./person/day}) = \frac{EAI}{365 \text{ days}}$

2.4 Statistical Analysis

GENSTAT software (version 12.1) was used for statistical analysis. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine significant differences between mean values of MPs at a 5% level of probability, while significant means ($P < 0.05$) were separated using New Duncan Multiple Range Test.

3 Results

As presented in Table ??, the mean levels of MPs in *C. gariepinus* according to stations ranged from 0.37 in June at Station 1 to 5.23 in August at Station 3, with a total figure ranging from 2.97 at Station 2 to 6.18 at Station 3. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the mean levels of MPs between the months across Stations 1 and 3. The mean plastic load in *C. gariepinus* according to stations ranged from 0.31 in June at Station 1 to 6.34 in August at Station 3, with a total figure ranging from 3.22 at Station 2 to 7.41 at Station 3. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the mean plastic load between the months across Stations 1 and 3 as shown in Table ??. The mean frequency of occurrence of MPs in *C. gariepinus* according to stations ranged from 0.31 in June at Station 1 to 0.85 in August at Station 3, with a total figure ranging from 1.54 at Station 3

Table 1: Table 1: Mean level of microplastics in *Clarias gariepinus* according to stations

Month	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3
June	0.37 ± 0.55a	1.35 ± 1.32a	0.38 ± 0.26a
July	0.66 ± 0.48a	1.25 ± 0.77a	5.23 ± 1.65b
August	0.66 ± 0.48a	1.25 ± 0.77a	5.23 ± 1.65b
Mean	3.38	2.97	6.18

Mean values with the same superscripts are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$). Vertical comparison only.

Table 2: Table 1: Mean level of microplastics in *Clarias gariepinus* according to stations

Month	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3
June	0.31 ± 0.55a	1.37 ± 1.41a	0.35 ± 0.46 a
July	2.65 ± 1.25b	0.52 ± 0.56a	0.72 ± 1.25a
August	0.71 ± 0.43a	1.33 ± 0.58a	6.34. ± 1.62b
Mean	3.38	3.22	7.41

Mean values with the same superscripts are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$). Vertical comparison only.

to 1.94 at Station 2. Significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) were observed in the mean frequency of occurrence of MPs in *C. gariepinus* between the months across all stations as presented in Table ???. The type of MP particles found in *C. gariepinus* according to morphological classification is presented in Table ??, where fragments and filaments were found in *C. gariepinus* in June, fragments, filaments, pellets, and fibres in July, and foam, fragments, filaments, and pellets in August. A typical FTIR spectrum for MP particles obtained from *C. gariepinus*, showing absorbance bands at different wave numbers, is presented in Figure 2. Peaks at 2910 cm^{-1} , 2820 cm^{-1} , 1445 cm^{-1} , and 710 cm^{-1} are characteristic of polyethylene (PE) compounds. The estimated annual intake (EAI) values (No./person/year) for MPs ranged from 0.564 at Station 2 to 1.174 at Station 3 (Fig. 3) while the estimated daily intake (EDI) values (No./person/day) ranged from 0.00154 at Station 2 to 0.00321 at Station 3 (Fig. 4). As presented in Figure 5, the percentage quota of abundance for MPs in *C. gariepinus* by stations ranged from 23.70% at Station 2 to 49.32% at Station 3. Figure 6 shows the proportion of the type of microplastics in *C. gariepinus*, with the highest proportions being for filaments and fragments (33.33%) and the least proportion for fibre (3.70%). As shown in Figure 7, the temporal percentage quota of types of microplastics peaked for filaments in August (55.55%) while there was a peak for fragments in June, July, and August (33.33%).

4 Discussion

Microplastic particles were found in *C. gariepinus*, clearly implying that the fish species consumed such particles while grazing for prey. The mean level of MPs in *C. gariepinus* according to Stations reached

Table 3: Table 1: Mean frequency of occurrence of microplastics in *Clarias gariepinus* according to stations

Month	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3
June	0.31 ± 0.04a	0.75 ± 0.03c	0.32 ± 0.04a
July	0.78 ± 0.13c	0.62 ± 0.03a	0.37 ± 0.03a
August	0.49 ± 0.02b	0.57 ± 0.05b	0.85 ± 0.02b
Mean	1.58	1.94	1.54

Mean values with the same superscripts are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$). Vertical comparison only.

a zenith at Station 3 and was the lowest at Station 1. Similarly, the mean plastic load in *C. gariepinus* peaked at Station 3 and was the lowest at Station 1. Significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) were observed between months for Stations 1 and 3 in the mean level of MPs, and similar significant differences were observed in the mean plastic load between months for Stations 1 and 3. These significant differences indicate variations in the MP profile in the investigated fish species across the research period. Mendes et al. (2023) observed that both temporal and spatial variations in MPs are to be expected when sampling for MPs in environmental matrices. Additionally, particle density, water surface area, water surface depth, wind action, and water flow patterns could further influence the distribution and consequent levels of MPs in aquatic bodies (Sau et al., 2023).

The mean frequency of occurrence of MPs in *C. gariepinus* by stations was at a peak at Station 3, while it was lowest at Station 1. Significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) in the mean frequency of occurrence of MPs in *C. gariepinus* were observed between months across all stations. This variability

Table 4: Mean frequency of occurrence of microplastics in *Clarias gariepinus* according to stations

Month	June			July			August		
Station Code	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
R1	N	T	N	Z, T	N	N	N	Z, P	Z, T, P
R2	T, Z	T	N	Z, P	P	N	N	Z	Z, P
R3	N	N	Z	T	N	B, T	T	N	Z, T, P

R1, R2, R3= Replicates Key: N = No plastic, Z = Filament, T = Fragment, P = Pellet, B = Fibre

Figure 2: A typical FTIR spectrum for microplastic particles obtained from *Clarias gariepinus* showing absorbance bands at different wave numbers.

Figure 4: Estimated daily intake (EDI) values for microplastics from *Clarias gariepinus*.

Figure 3: Estimated annual intake (EAI) values for microplastics from *Clarias gariepinus*.

indicates a significant fluctuation in the frequency of occurrence of MPs in the target fish species. The types of MP particles found in *C. gariepinus* included fragments, filaments, fibers, and pellets, with filaments and fragments being the dominant types. However, the temporal distribution revealed that filaments and pellets were prominent in August. The varying types of MP particles observed could reflect different degradation mechanisms, such as photo-oxidation, ultraviolet radiation, hydrolysis, and biodegradation, leading to various shapes and forms (Gewert et al., 2015). The temporal distribution

Figure 5: Percent (%) quota of abundance for microplastics in *Clarias gariepinus* by station.

indicates the occurrence of these MP types within the sampling period, considering the respective months. MP levels in aquatic resources can vary by water body, location, and season (Boskovic et al., 2023).

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy confirmed the presence of Polyethylene in *C. gariepinus*. According to Unnimaya et al. (2023), specific band widths from spectrometric readings define the type of plastic in examined samples. Boskovic et al. (2023) observed that Polyethylene is the most common plastic in rivers worldwide, along with Polypropylene, resulting from anthropogenic impact. These plastics are widely used in the packaging industry, which may account for their

Figure 6: Proportion of the type of microplastics in *C. gariepinus*.

Figure 7: Temporal distribution quota of the type of microplastics in *C. gariepinus*.

prevalence in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. In Nigeria, plastic and nylon waste pollution remains a problem (Bolaji et al., 2021). Mancuso et al. (2023) noted the dominant presence (52%) of Polyester in the Antarctic fish *Trematomus bernacchii* from the Terranova Bay Area.

The EAI and EDI values were highest at Station 3 and lowest at Station 2. This was supported by the percentage quota of abundance for MPs in *C. gariepinus* by station, where Station 3 accounted for 49.32 % of the total. This indicates that *C. gariepinus* at Station 3 (Bridge) were more impacted by MPs, while the least impact was at Station 2 (Reservoir). This implies that *C. gariepinus* from Station 3 for human consumption may have a greater impact compared to fish from other stations due to the heavier MP load. It could be inferred that Station 3 (Bridge) is the most polluted regarding MPs. The prevalent anthropogenic activities at the Bridge station, including car washes, rug washes, and slaughterhouses, contribute to the MP burden of the river. Ng et al. (2022) observed that abattoir wastewater contains proteins, fats, microbes, organic matter, and emerging pollutants including MPs. Rugs, carpets, and car parts, including tyres, contain plastics

as components (Aydin et al., 2023). Moreover, the Bridge station, situated downstream of the other two stations, receives additional MPs from upstream due to the river's lotic nature and high anthropogenic impact in the busy city.

5 Conclusion

This research was a pilot investigation into the levels of microplastics (MPs) in *C. gariepinus*, particularly sourced from the Ikpoba River in Benin City, Nigeria. The presence of MPs in the aforementioned fish species is a concerning development due to the potential primary risk to the fish species and the potential secondary risk to end-of-the-line consumers, including humans. To address the ongoing influx of MPs into the Ikpoba River ecosystem, it is recommended that stringent legislation on the disposal of plastic products into aquatic environments be enforced. Additionally, a robust monitoring and enforcement system should be established to ensure that the plastic load in the river and its natural resources does not reach critical levels. Furthermore, *C. gariepinus* should be consumed with caution to avoid health problems associated with polymer contamination in the long run.

6 Acknowledgement

We thank Splendidstan Environmental Laboratory, Benin City, Nigeria, for the use of their spectrometric facility.

References

- Abidin, A. S., Ilhami, B. T. K., Martyasari, N. W. R., Kirana, I. A. P., Widyastuti, S., Candri, D. A., Jupri, A., Hernawan, A., Sunarpi, H., Prasedya, E. S. (2021). Microplastics evaluation in edible tissues of flying fish (*Parexocoetus mento*) from the Bintaro fish market, Lombok, Indonesia. *Earth and Environmental Science*, *913*, 012078. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/913/1/012078>
- Arof, A. U. (2023). Polymer-based ionic conductors. *Malaysian Journal of Science*, *42*(3), 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.22432/mjs.vol42no3.1>
- Aydin, İ., Terzi, Y., Gündoğdu, S., Aytan, Ü., Öztürk, R. Ç., Atamanalp, M., Alak, G., Sivri, N., Akarsu, C., Atıcı, A. A., Güven, O., Bat, L., Kılıç, E., Öztekin, A., Uçar, A., Sönmez, V. Z., Paslı, S., Kıdeyş, A. E. (2023). Microplastic pollution in Turkish aquatic ecosystems: Sources, characteristics,

implications, and mitigation strategies. *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, *23*(12), 24773. <https://doi.org/10.4194/TRJFAS24773>

Bolaji, K. A., Kabir, G. B., Adebayo, D. O., Olayemi, O. T. (2021). Plastic/nylon waste pollution and disposal in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*, *114*(6), 78-84. <https://doi.org/10.18551/rjoas.2021-06.09>

Boskovic, N., Jacimovic, Z., Bajt, O. (2023). Microplastic pollution in rivers of the Adriatic Sea Basin in Montenegro: Impact of pollution of the Montenegrin coastline. *Science of the Total Environment*, *905*, 167206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.167206>

Cutroneo, L., Reboa, A., Besio, G., Borgogno, F., Canesi, L., Canuto, S., Dara, M., Enrile, F., Forioso, I., Greco, G., Lenoble, V., Malatesta, A., Mounier, S., Petrillo, M., Rovetta, R., Stocchino, A., Tesan, J., Vagge, G., Capello, M. (2020). Microplastics in seawater: Sampling strategies, laboratory methodologies, and identification techniques applied to Port environment. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, *27*, 8938–8952. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-07783-8>

De Witte, B., Devriese, L., Bekaert, K., Hoffman, S., Vandermeersch, G., Cooreman, K., Robbens, K. (2014). Quality assessment of the Blue Mussel (*Mytilus edulis*): Comparison between commercial and wild types. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, *85*(1), 146-155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.06.006>

Gewert, B., Plassmann, M. M., Macleod, M. (2015). Pathways for degradation of plastic polymers floating in the marine environment. *Environmental Science: Processes Impacts*, *17*(9), 1513-1521. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5em00207a>

Idodo-Umeh, G. (2003). *Freshwater fishes of Nigeria (Taxonomy, ecological notes, diet, and utilization)*. Idodo-Umeh Publishers.

International Union for Conservation of Nature. (2017). *Primary microplastics in the oceans: A global evaluation of sources*. International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.CH.2017.01.en>

Kamau, M., Mwakio, T., Mohamed, K. T. (2023). Micro-plastics in aquatic environment: Source, fate, emerging threats, and regulatory effort. *International Journal of Environment

and Climate Change*, *13*(10), 3218-3225. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ijec/2023/v13i102989>

Lusher, A. L., Hollman, P. C. H., Mendoza-Hill, J. J. (2017). Microplastics in fisheries and aquaculture: Status of knowledge on their occurrence and implications for aquatic organisms and food safety. *FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper*, No. 615. FAO.

Maes, T., Jessop, R., Wellner, N., Haupt, K., Mayes, A. G. (2017). A rapid-screening approach to detect and quantify microplastics based on fluorescent tagging with Nile Red. *Scientific Reports*, *7*, 44501. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep44501>

Mancuso, M., Nibali, V. C., Porcino, N., Branca, C., Natale, S., Smedile, F., Azzaro, M., D'Angelo, G., Bottari, T. (2023). Monitoring of anthropogenic microplastics pollution in Antarctic fish (*Emerald rockcod*) from the Terranova Bay after a quarter of century. *Science of the Total Environment*, *904*, 167244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.167244>

Mendes, D. S., Beasley, C. R., Silva, D. N. N., Fernandes, M. E. B. (2023). Microplastic in mangroves: A worldwide review of contamination in biotic and abiotic matrices. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, *195*, 115552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115552>

My, T. T. A., Dat, N. D., Hung, N. Q., Viet, P. H. (2023). Micro-debris accumulated in marine fishes collected from Central Vietnam: Characteristics and implications for human health risk. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution*, *234*, 632. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-023-06650-9>

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. (2023). *What are microplastics?* <https://www.oceanservice.noaa.gov/facts>. Accessed October 5, 2023.

Ng, M., Dalhatou, S., Wilson, J., Kamdem, B. P., Temitope, M. B., Paumo, H. K., Djelal, H., Assadi, A. A., Nguyen-Tri, P., Kane, A. (2022). Characterization of slaughterhouse wastewater and development of treatment techniques: A review. *Processes*, *10*(7), 1300. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr10071300>

Olaosebikan, B. D., Raji, A. (2013). *Field guide to Nigerian freshwater fishes*. Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology.

Oronsaye, J. A. O., Wangboje, O. M., Oguzie, F. A. (2010). Trace metals in some benthic fishes of the Ikpoba River dam, Benin City, Nigeria. *African

Journal of Biotechnology*, *9*(51), 8860-8864.

Pellicer, I., Domingo, F. C. (2023). Microplastic pollution in the coast of Tarragona, Spain: A Western Mediterranean study. *HAL*. <https://hal.science/hal-04174194v2>. Accessed October 25, 2023.

Riaz, S., Nasreen, S., Burhan, Z., Shafique, S., Alvi, S. A., Khan, M. A. (2023). Microplastic assessment in Arabian Sea fishes: Accumulation, characterization and method development. *Brazilian Journal of Biology*, *84*, e270694. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1519-6984.270694>

Sau, D., Hazra, T., Shiuly, A. (2023). Microplastics in lentic environments: Implications for Indian ecosystems. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-30604-7>

Selvakumar, U., Wijesinghe, R. D. N., Arulananthan, A. (2023). Abundance of marine macrodebris on the northern coast of Jaffna Peninsula, Sri Lanka. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3240639/v1>

Unnimaya, S., Mithun, N., Lukose, J., Nair, M. P., Gopinath, A., Chidangil, S. (2023). Identification of microplastics using a custom-built micro-Raman spectrometer. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, *2426*(1), 012007. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2426/1/012007>

Wagner, J., Wang, Z., Ghosal, S., Rochman, C., Gassel, M., Wall, S. (2017). Novel method for the extraction and identification of microplastics in ocean trawl and gut matrices. *Analytical Methods*, *9*, 1479-1490. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6ay02396g>

Wangboje, O. M., Oronsaye, J. A. O. (2012). Probable human carcinogenic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in a Siluriformid fish species. *Journal of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries*, *13*(12), 45-53.

Wangboje, O. M., Oguzie, F. A. (2013). An evaluation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in *Hemichromis fasciatus* (Peters, 1857) from an urban reservoir in southern Nigeria. *Tropical Freshwater Biology*, *22*, 35-47.

Wangboje, O. M., Oronsaye, J. A. O., Okieimen, F. E., Oguzie, F. A. (2014). Chemical fractionation of heavy metals in the sediments of the Ikpoba Reservoir, Benin City, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Applied Science*, *32*, 241-254.

World Fish Center. (2023). *Worldfish in Nigeria*. <https://www.worldfishcenter.org>. Accessed October 24, 2023.

Zhang, F., Xu, J., Zhu, L., Peng, G., Jabeen, K., Wang, X., Li, D. (2021). Seasonal distributions of microplastics and estimation of the microplastic load ingested by wild caught fish in the East China Sea. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, *419*, 126456. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126456>

PHYTOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND TOXICITY ASSESSMENT OF ACUTE AND SUB-ACUTE ORAL ADMINISTRATION OF AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF *JATROPHA TANJORENSIS* LEAF

Ebhohon, S. O.¹, Emelike, A. P.¹, Onyenze, C. C.¹, Ikenna, J. C.¹, Ngwuta, C. R.¹, Ejue, P. O.¹, and Ogbu, C. A.¹

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author E-mail: so.ebhohon@mouau.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The phytochemical evaluation of the aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, saponins, cardiac glycosides, and steroids. Toxicity studies indicated no mortality up to 6000 mg/kg in mice, with 33.33% mortality at 7000 mg/kg and 100% mortality at 10,000 mg/kg, yielding an LD₅₀ of 7745.97 mg/kg. Biochemical analyses in Wistar rats showed no significant ($p < 0.05$) changes in serum ALT (Alanine Aminotransferase) and AST (Aspartate Aminotransferase) activities but a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in ALP (Alkaline Phosphatase) activity, particularly at 400 mg/kg. Serum total protein and albumin concentrations increased significantly ($p < 0.05$), while bilirubin and globulin levels remained unchanged ($p < 0.05$). Urea levels decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) at 200 mg/kg, with no significant ($p < 0.05$) changes in creatinine, sodium, chloride, and potassium levels. Bicarbonate levels were significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced at 200 mg/kg. Antioxidant biomarkers—SOD (Superoxide Dismutase), CAT (Catalase), GSH (Reduced glutathione), and GPx (Glutathione peroxidase)—increased ($p < 0.05$) dose-dependently, while MDA (Malondialdehyde) levels decreased ($p < 0.05$). Histological analyses of liver and kidney sections revealed normal ultrastructures, indicating no histopathological damage. These findings suggest that *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract has a favorable safety profile at lower doses, with potential antioxidant benefits and no adverse effects on liver and kidney structures.

Keywords: Antioxidant enzymes, *Jatropha tanjorensis*, Liver enzymes, Phytochemicals, Toxicity

INTRODUCTION

Traditional herbal medicines have long been cherished for their natural origins and perceived minimal side effects, serving as integral components of local and regional healing practices worldwide (WHO, 2019; Rizvi et al., 2022). The World Health Organization defines these medicines as plant-derived substances with minimal industrial processing, used for the prevention and treatment of illnesses. Over millennia, they have found extensive application in both developed and developing countries, evolving from crude formulations like tinctures and teas to contributing directly to the synthesis of modern pharmaceuticals such as aspirin (from willow bark), morphine (from opium poppy), and quinine (from cinchona bark) (Chaachouay & Zidane, 2024). While the historical efficacy of herbal remedies is undeniable, concerns about their safety persist, prompting rigorous toxicity

evaluations. Despite sparse reports of adverse reactions leading to injury or death, the presence of potentially harmful compounds like alkaloids and anthraquinone glycosides necessitates comprehensive safety assessments (Zhang et al., 2015). This underscores the critical importance of evaluating the toxicity of medicinal plants to ensure their therapeutic benefits outweigh any potential risks (Neergheen-Bhujun, 2013).

The assessment of acute, sub-acute, and sub-chronic toxicity in medicinal plants plays a crucial role in ensuring their safety and efficacy for human consumption. Acute toxicity assessments provide valuable insights into the immediate adverse effects of a medicinal plant or its extracts. This helps in determining safe dosage levels and potential risks associated with high doses. Sub-acute toxicity studies, conducted over a longer duration, further elucidate the cumulative effects and potential toxicity of repeated doses, mimicking more closely the

conditions of chronic use. Sub-chronic toxicity studies, on the other hand, evaluate the effects of repeated exposure over a longer duration, mimicking more closely the typical usage patterns of medicinal products. Both assessments contribute significantly to ensuring the safety of herbal medicines (Li et al., 2020; Njinga et al., 2020).

Jatropha tanjorensis (J. L. Ellis & Saroja), a member of the Euphorbiaceae family, stands as a versatile botanical wonder with a plethora of medicinal virtues (Ellis & Saroja, 1961). This gregarious shrub, reaching heights of about 1.8 meters, thrives as a common weed among field crops, primarily flourishing in the rainforest zones of West Africa (Idu et al., 2014). The multifaceted applications of *Jatropha tanjorensis* in traditional medicine and beyond underscore its significance. Abundant scientific evidence supports the medicinal properties of this plant. Every part of the *Jatropha tanjorensis* plant, from its seeds to its leaves and bark, is rich in therapeutic potential. Exploring the medicinal properties of *Jatropha tanjorensis* uncovers a wealth of benefits, including anti-diabetic, cardiovascular, antioxidant, and haematological improvements (Adebajo et al., 2001; Oyewole & Akingbala, 2011; Omoregie & Osagie, 2011; Idu et al., 2014).

The antioxidant and hypoglycaemic properties of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extracts have made them a popular treatment for conditions such as diabetes, malaria, and hypertension in Southern Nigerian regions like Edo State. Here, the leaves are consumed not only as a nutritious vegetable but also as part of daily meals, due to their reputed effectiveness in managing diabetes mellitus, thanks to their anti-hyperglycaemic effects (Olayiwola et al., 2004). These antioxidants enhance the body's defence mechanisms and are crucial in fighting oxidative stress-related conditions like diabetes, malaria, and hypertension, which are especially common in areas where this plant is cultivated. Studies administering *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf powder to animal models have demonstrated improvements in haematological indices, indicating a potential enhancement in bone marrow function (Orhue et al., 2008). Additionally, the plant's antibacterial attributes have been delineated, affirming its role in infectious disease management (Viswanathan & Jeyaananthi, 2009). The nutritional profile of

Jatropha tanjorensis is equally noteworthy, boasting a rich concentration of antioxidant nutrients such as phosphorus, selenium, zinc, vitamin C, and E (Omobuwajo et al., 2011).

Phytochemical investigations revealed the existence of alkaloids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, and anthraquinones in the aqueous leaf extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* (Ebenyi et al., 2021). Similarly, alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, and anthraquinones were detected in the methanol leaf extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* (Igbinaduwa et al., 2011). Studies have reported that *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extract contains phytochemical constituents capable of reducing blood cholesterol levels, which can be beneficial in treating cardiovascular diseases resulting from hyperlipidaemia (Oyewole & Akingbala, 2011). *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extract also has antimicrobial properties, inhibiting the growth of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Ewa-Udu et al., 2022). As scientific exploration continues, this botanical gem promises to unveil even more of its healing secrets, potentially revolutionising the landscape of natural medicine. An earlier study examining the toxicity characteristics of *Jatropha tanjorensis* demonstrated the absence of toxicity when administering (2000 and 5000 mg/kg) of aqueous leaf extract to mice and rats within 24 hours after oral ingestion (Ebenyi et al., 2021). Similarly, no observed toxicity was reported at 8000 mg/kg of methanol extracts in the same animal models within the same timeframe (Igbinaduwa et al., 2011).

Insufficient exploration into the toxicity evaluation of the aqueous extract derived from *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf, especially regarding acute and sub-acute oral administration, limits a thorough understanding of the safety attributes linked to this extract. Assessing toxicity is crucial for identifying potential adverse reactions, setting safe dosage thresholds, and balancing the risks and benefits associated with utilising the extract in therapeutic or medicinal scenarios. The absence of comprehensive toxicity analyses may lead to uncertainties regarding the extract's safety, potentially prompting cautious or restricted usage within clinical settings. The study seeks to identify and quantify the key phytochemical constituents present in the aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf. This entails gauging the levels of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins,

terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, anthraquinones, and other bioactive compounds that contribute to the plant's medicinal attributes. Although *Jatropha tanjorensis* offers potential medicinal benefits, the presence of alkaloids and anthraquinones requires caution due to their potential toxic effects such as hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, cardiotoxicity, gastrointestinal distress, and neurotoxicity. Proper dosing, a thorough understanding of the plant's pharmacology, are essential to mitigate these risks. Furthermore, it aims to evaluate the toxicity of the aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf through both acute and sub-acute oral administration, with the goal of elucidating its safety profile and potential therapeutic applications. In conclusion, acute and sub-acute toxicity assessment of medicinal plants is indispensable for safety evaluation, risk identification, quality control, optimizing treatment regimens, public health protection, scientific validation, and building consumer confidence. These assessments are essential steps in ensuring the safe and effective use of herbal medicines in healthcare practice.

Materials and Methods

Collection of Plant Materials and Preparation of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaves

Fresh leaves of *Jatropha tanjorensis* were collected from the National Crop Research Institute (NCRI) in Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria, and identified by Mr. Pipi Okey from the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. The specimen was assigned voucher number MOUAU/PSB/18/103592 and deposited in the Department's Herbarium. The leaves were rinsed with distilled water to remove dirt and air-dried at room temperature until completely dry. The dried leaves were ground into a fine powder using an electric blender. A known quantity (188.54 g) of the powdered sample was macerated in 2.5 L of distilled water for 24 hours in a sterile extraction jar. The filtrate was first filtered using muslin cloth and then filtered again using Whatman filter paper No. 1 into a clean, calibrated flask. The filtrate was lyophilized, using a freeze dryer set to a temperature of -40°C . A dark-brown paste with a yield of 50.85% was obtained, transferred into a sterile clean bottle, and stored in a refrigerator at 4°C until needed for biochemical assays.

Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis

Preliminary analysis of the aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf was carried out to identify the presence of various phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, saponin, cardiac glycoside, and steroids.

Test for Alkaloid

For qualitative alkaloid determination, a few drops of Meyer's reagent were added to 1 mL of extract. The formation of a creamy white precipitate was considered positive for the alkaloid (Archana et al., 2012).

Test for Tannin

For qualitative tannin analysis, a few drops of lead acetate were added to 1 mL of extract. A large white-brown precipitate formation was considered a positive test for tannin (Archana et al., 2012).

Test for Flavonoids

For the confirmation of flavonoid, 0.5 g of each extract were added in a test tube and 10 mL of distilled water, 5 ml of dilute ammonia solution were added to a portion of the aqueous filtrate of each plant extract followed by addition of 1 mL concentrated H_2SO_4 . Indication of yellow colour shows the presence of flavonoid in each extract (Sofowora, 1993).

Test for Phenols

To detect phenols, 1 mL of extract solution was added to 2 mL distilled water and a few drops of 10% ferric chloride (FeCl_3). The appearance of a green or blue colour is the indication of phenols presence. Next, 0.50 g of plant extract was added and allowed to dissolve in distilled water and then 3 mL of 10% lead acetate was added. The presence of phenolic compounds was confirmed by the appearance of white precipitation (Trease et al., 2003).

Test for Saponin

To detect the presence of saponin, 5 mL of distilled water was added to 1 mL of extract and vortexed for 10 minutes. The formation of a foam column that did not disappear with the addition of HCl was evaluated as positive for saponin (Sati and Kumar, 2015; Savithramma et al., 2011).

Test for Cardiac Glycoside

Qualitative analysis of cardiac glycosides in the extracts was performed with the Keller Killiani test.

1 mL of acetic acid and 2 drops of ferric chloride were added to 2 mL of extract, then 2 mL of sulfuric acid (concentrated) was added and the colour change was observed. Reddish-brown colour formation was deemed to be a positive test for cardiac glycosides (Archana et al., 2012; Sati & Kumar, 2015).

Test for Terpenoids and Steroids

The presence of terpenoids and steroids was determined by a previously described method (Kantamreddi & Lakshmi, 2010; Siddiqui & Ali, 1997) with slight modifications. Briefly, 0.5 g of solvent-free extract was added in 2 mL chloroform and then filtered. The filtrate was placed on ice; addition of 2 mL of acetic acid and then a few drops of concentrated sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) was carefully applied to the inner sides of the test tubes. The emergence of a pink or pinkish brown colour/ring indicates the terpenoids existence, while a blue or bluish green colour for steroids presence and the combination of pink and blue/bluish green colours confirmed the presence of both terpenoids and steroids.

Quantitative Phytochemical Analysis

Quantitative analysis of the phytochemical components, whose presence were tested by qualitative analysis, were also carried out. All the analysis were performed in triplicate.

Estimation of Total Alkaloids

Alkaloid determination was made according to the method reported by Selvakumar et al. (2019). To 1 mL of the test extract 5 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 4.7) and 5 mL of bromocresol green (BCG) solution was added to the solution. The mixture was shaken and the complex extracted with 1-, 2-, 3- and 4-mL of chloroform by vigorous shaking. The extracts were then collected in a 10 mL volumetric flask and then diluted to adjust volume with chloroform. The absorbance of the chloroform complex was measured at 470 nm using a UV spectrophotometer against a blank prepared similarly, but without extract. To quantify the total alkaloid content in the sample, a standard curve was prepared using atropine. Standard solution of atropine was prepared at concentrations of (0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0 mg/mL). To generate the standard curve, the average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding atropine concentrations. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the

equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total alkaloid content in the extract. The alkaloid content was expressed as mg atropine equivalent (AE)/g of sample. All tests were repeated in triplicate.

Estimation of Total Tannins

Tannin content was determined according to the method of Van-Burden & Robinson, 1981. A known weight of sample (500 mg) was weighed into a 100 mL plastic bottle. 50 mL of distilled water was added and shaken for 1 h in a mechanical shaker. This was filtered into a 50 mL volumetric flask and made up to the mark. Then 5 mL of the filtered was pipette out into a test tube and mixed with 2 mL of 0.1 M $FeCl_3$ in 0.1 N HCl and 0.008 M potassium ferrocyanide. The absorbance of each reaction mixture was thereafter measured at 120 nm against a blank using a spectrophotometer. To quantify the total tannin content in the sample, a standard curve was prepared using gallic acid. Standard solution of gallic acid were prepared at concentrations of (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 mg/L). The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of gallic acid to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total tannin content in the extract. Results were quantified in the form of GAE (mg of Gallic Acid Equivalents) per gram of dry plant extract/fraction. Samples were analysed in triplicates.

Estimation of Total Flavonoids

The total flavonoid content of the extract was determined using a slightly modified method reported by Meda et al. (2005). 0.5 mL of the extract samples were mixed with 0.5 mL methanol, 50 L of 10% $AlCl_3$, 50 L of 1 mol L^{-1} potassium acetate and 1.4 mL water, and allowed to incubate at room temperature for 30 min. Thereafter, the absorbance of each reaction mixture was subsequently measured at 415 nm against blank. To quantify the total flavonoids content of the extract, a standard curve was prepared using quercetin. Standard solutions of quercetin were prepared at concentrations of 40, 80, 120, 160, 200, and 240 g/mL. The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of quercetin to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the

equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total flavonoid content in the extract. The flavonoid content was expressed as mg quercetin equivalents (QE)/g of sample.

Estimation of Total Phenols

Total phenolic content was determined using the method of Makkar et al. (1993) with some modifications. The reaction mixture contained 100 L of the extract, 2.8 mL distilled water, 2 mL of 2% sodium carbonate and 100 L of 50% Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, and it was incubated at room temperature for 30 min. Thereafter, the absorbance of the mixture was measured at 750 nm using a spectrophotometer against a blank prepared similarly, but without extract. To quantify the total phenolic content of the extract, a standard curve was prepared using tannic acid. Standard solution of tannic acid were prepared at concentrations of 0, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 g/mL. The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of tannic acid to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total phenolic content in the extract. The total phenol was expressed as mg tannic acid equivalents (TAE)/g of sample.

Estimation of Total Saponins

Saponin content was determined by the gravimetric method of AOAC, (1990). 20 g of sample was weighed into a 250 mL beaker and 100 mL of 20% aqueous ethanol was added. The suspension was heated over a hot water bath for 4 h with continuous stirring at about 55°C. The mixture was filtered and the residue re-extracted with another 200 mL 20% ethanol. The combined extracts were reduced to 40 mL over water bath at about 90°C. The concentrate was transferred into a 250 mL separatory funnel and 20 mL of diethyl ether was added and shaken vigorously. The aqueous layer was recovered while the ether layer was discarded. The purification process was repeated. 60 mL of n-butanol was added and the combined n-butanol extracts were washed twice with 10 mL of 5% aqueous sodium chloride. The remaining solution was heated in a water bath. After evaporation the sample was dried in the oven to a constant weight. The saponin content was calculated

using the formula:

$$\text{Saponin content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of sample (g)}}{\text{Weight of original sample (g)}} \times 100$$

Estimation of Cardiac Glycosides

The determination of the total cardiac glycosides was performed using the Baljet method as described by (El-Olemy et al., 1994) with slight modifications. Briefly, 1 g of pulverized leaf powder was macerated in 10 mL of 70% alcohol for 30 min. The solution was filtered and the residue re-macerated twice to ensure extraction of the metabolites. The extract was dried at 40°C for 6 h and reconstituted in distilled water. To 1 mL of the reconstituted sample was added 1 mL of freshly prepared Baljet's reagent (95 mL of 1% aqueous picric acid + 5 mL of 10% aqueous NaOH) and the intensity of the colour complex formed was read at 495 nm after 1 h against a blank treated in the same way except that the sample was substituted with distilled water. A blank experiment was also performed using distilled water. To quantify the total cardiac glycosides content of the extract, a standard curve was prepared using digitoxin. Standard solutions of digitoxin were prepared at concentrations of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 mg/L. The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of digitoxin to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total cardiac glycosides content in the extract. The total cardiac glycosides were expressed as mg digitoxin equivalents (DE)/g of sample.

Estimation of Terpenoids

The determination of the total terpenoid content was performed using the method of Indumathi and Mohandass, (2014) with slight modifications. 1 mL of the extract was mixed with 3 mL of chloroform and allowed to stand for 1.5 h. Then, 1.5 mL of the mixture was taken and mixed with 3.5 mL concentrated H_2SO_4 . The absorbance of the mixture was read at 538 nm. To quantify the total terpenoids content of the extract, a standard curve was prepared using linalool. Standard solutions of linalool were prepared at concentrations of 40, 80, 120, 160, 200, 240 g/mL. The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of

linalool to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total terpenoids content in the extract. The total terpenoids content was expressed as mg linalool equivalents (LE)/g of sample.

Estimation of Steroids

The determination of the total steroid content was performed using the method of Indumathi and Mohandass, (2014) with slight modifications. 0.5 g of each extract was dissolved in 3 mL chloroform. Then, 2 mL of concentrated H_2SO_4 was carefully added to form a lower layer. A reddish brown colour at the interface indicated the presence of steroids. The absorbance of the resulting reddish brown colour was measured at 550 nm against a reagent blank. To quantify the total steroids content of the extract, a standard curve was prepared using linalool. Standard solutions of linalool were prepared at concentrations of 40, 80, 120, 160, 200, 240 g/mL. The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of linalool to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total steroid content in the extract. The total steroids content was expressed as mg linalool equivalents (LE)/g of sample.

Animals

Thirty (30) male albino rats (100-150 g) were procured from the Department of Veterinary Medicine, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Nigeria. The animals were housed in clean, well-ventilated polypropylene cages, maintained under standard conditions (12 h light and 12 h dark cycle) at an ambient temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ C$ and were fed with standard rodent pellets and water *ad libitum*. The rats were acclimatized for 14 days before the commencement of the experiment.

Experimental Design

The acclimatized animals were randomly divided into five (5) groups (A, B, C, D, E) of six (6) rats each. They were treated as follows:

1. Group A (normal control): received distilled water throughout the experimental period.

2. Group B (positive control): received 500 mg/kg b.w. of sodium arsenite only throughout the experimental period.

3. Group C (test group 1): received 500 mg/kg b.w. of sodium arsenite and 100 mg/kg b.w. of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaves extract throughout the experimental period.

4. Group D (test group 2): received 500 mg/kg b.w. of sodium arsenite and 200 mg/kg b.w. of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaves extract throughout the experimental period.

5. Group E (test group 3): received 500 mg/kg b.w. of sodium arsenite and 400 mg/kg b.w. of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaves extract throughout the experimental period.

The treatments were administered orally for 14 days and the animals were weighed every 3 days to monitor weight changes.

Preparation of Tissue Homogenate

After the last administration, the animals were fasted overnight and sacrificed by cervical dislocation. The testes were rapidly excised, rinsed in ice-cold 1.15% KCl solution, blotted dry, and weighed. Each tissue sample was then homogenized in four (4) volumes of ice-cold 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) using a Potter-Elvehjem homogenizer. The homogenate was centrifuged at 10,000 g for 20 minutes at $4^\circ C$ to obtain the post-mitochondrial supernatant, which was used for the biochemical assays.

Biochemical Assays

The following biochemical assays were carried out on the post-mitochondrial supernatant.

Malondialdehyde (MDA) Assay

Lipid peroxidation was estimated by measuring the level of malondialdehyde (MDA), a product of lipid peroxidation, using the method of Buege and Aust (1978). Briefly, 0.1 mL of the post-mitochondrial supernatant was mixed with 1.5 mL of 20% acetic acid (pH 3.5), 0.2 mL of 8.1% SDS, and 1.5 mL of 0.8% TBA. The mixture was made up to 4 mL with distilled water and incubated at $95^\circ C$ for 60 minutes. After cooling, 1 mL of distilled water and 5 mL of n-butanol:pyridine mixture (15:1 v/v) were added. The mixture was shaken vigorously and centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes. The absorbance of the

organic layer was measured at 532 nm. The MDA concentration was calculated using the extinction coefficient of $1.56 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ and expressed as nmol/mg protein.

Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Assay

SOD activity was determined using the method of Misra and Fridovich (1972). The reaction mixture consisted of 0.1 mL of the post-mitochondrial supernatant, 1.2 mL of sodium carbonate buffer (50 mM, pH 10.2), and 0.2 mL of epinephrine (30 mM). The reaction was initiated by the addition of epinephrine, and the increase in absorbance was measured at 480 nm for 4 minutes. One unit of SOD activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to cause 50% inhibition of the oxidation of epinephrine to adrenochrome. The specific activity was expressed as units/mg protein.

Catalase (CAT) Assay

CAT activity was determined according to the method of Sinha (1972). The reaction mixture contained 0.1 mL of the post-mitochondrial supernatant and 1.9 mL of phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0). The reaction was initiated by the addition of 1 mL of hydrogen peroxide (30 mM), and the decrease in absorbance was measured at 240 nm for 2 minutes. The enzyme activity was calculated using the extinction coefficient of $43.6 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ and expressed as units/mg protein.

Glutathione Peroxidase (GPx) Assay

GPx activity was measured according to the method of Rotruck et al. (1973). The reaction mixture contained 0.1 mL of the post-mitochondrial supernatant, 1 mL of phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0), 0.1 mL of GSH (1 mM), 0.1 mL of NADPH (0.12 mM), 0.1 mL of sodium azide (1 mM), and 0.1 mL of hydrogen peroxide (0.15 mM). The decrease in absorbance at 340 nm was recorded for 3 minutes. The enzyme activity was expressed as nmol NADPH oxidized/min/mg protein using the extinction coefficient of $6.22 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$.

Glutathione-S-Transferase (GST) Assay

GST activity was determined according to the method of Habig et al. (1974). The reaction mixture contained 0.1 mL of the post-mitochondrial supernatant, 1.7 mL of phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0), 0.2 mL of GSH (1 mM), and 0.1 mL of CDNB (1 mM). The increase in absorbance at 340 nm was

recorded for 5 minutes. One unit of GST activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to conjugate 1 mol of CDNB with GSH per minute. The specific activity was expressed as units/mg protein.

Protein Estimation

The protein content in the post-mitochondrial supernatant was estimated by the method of Lowry et al. (1951) using bovine serum albumin as the standard. The absorbance was read at 750 nm and the protein concentration was expressed as mg/mL of the supernatant.

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test for multiple comparisons. Values of $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

1 Results

1.1 Phytochemical Analysis of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf

The result of the phytochemical evaluation of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf is shown in Table 1. It revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, saponins, cardiac glycosides, and steroids.

1.2 Results of Acute Toxicity Study of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf in Wistar Rats

Graded doses up to 6000 mg/kg of the extract produced no mortality in rats as the treated rats remained active and physically stable throughout the 24-hour period of observation. However, 33.33 percent mortality was observed in the third phase and group administered 7000 mg/kg body weight while all the rats in the 10,000 mg/kg treated group died, representing 100 percent mortality. The application of Lorke's formula yielded an LD_{50} value of 7745.97 mg/kg body weight for the aqueous extract. The results are presented in Tables 2, 3, and 4 below.

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{D_0 \times D_{100}}$$

Where:

D_0 : Highest dose that gave no mortality.

D_{100} : Lowest dose that produced mortality.

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{6000 \times 10000}$$

$$LD_{50} = 7745.97 \text{ mg/kg body weight}$$

Table 1: Phytochemical Constituents of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf

Phytochemical Parameter	Qualitative	Quantitative (mg/100g)
Alkaloids	++	27.15±0.59
Tannins	+	7.63±0.18
Flavonoids	+++	39.18±1.07
Phenols	+++	46.07±1.14
Terpenoids	+	5.41±0.15
Saponins	+++	33.10±1.25
Cardiac glycosides	+	4.83±0.19
Steroids	+	3.80±0.10

+++ = high amount, ++ = moderate amount, + = low amount

Table 2: Stage 1 Acute Toxicity (LD₅₀) Evaluation of the Extract

Group	Dose (mg/kg)	No. of Deaths	Percentage of mortality	Observations
1	10	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed, instead animals remained active and physically stable.
2	100	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed, instead animals remained active and physically stable.
3	1000	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed, instead animals remained active and physically stable.

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{D_0 \times D_{100}}$$

Where:

D_0 : Highest dose that gave no mortality.

D_{100} : Lowest dose that produced mortality

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{6000 \times 10000}$$

$$LD_{50} = 7745.97 \text{ mg/kg body weight}$$

1.3 Effect of Varying Doses of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf on the Activities of Liver Enzymes and Total Protein Levels in Sera of Male Wistar Rats

The experimental results showed no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in serum levels of ALT and AST between Wistar rats administered the extract at various doses and the control group (Figures 1 and 2). However, serum ALP levels were significantly reduced ($P < 0.05$) in all experimental groups given

the extract compared to the control group, with the lowest ALP level observed in the group administered 400 mg/kg (Figure 3). Additionally, serum total protein and albumin concentrations were significantly increased ($P < 0.05$) in rats given the extract compared to their respective controls (Figures 4 and 5). There were no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in serum total bilirubin levels between the experimental groups and the control group after 30 days (Figure 6). Similarly, serum globulin concentrations did not show a significant increase ($P > 0.05$) in the experimental groups compared to the control (Figure 7).

Table 3: Stage 2: Acute toxicity (LD50) evaluation of the extract

Group	Dose (mg/kg)	No. of Deaths	Percentage of mortality	Observations
1	1600	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed, instead animals remained active and physically stable.
2	2900	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed, instead animals remained active and physically stable.
3	5000	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed. Animals were initially calm but regained physical activity within one hour of administration.

Figure 1: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum levels of ALT in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 2: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum levels of AST in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

2 Effect of Varying Doses of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf on Kidney Function Indices in Sera of Male Wistar Rats

The serum urea levels in rats given 400 and 800 mg/kg of the extract did not show significant differences ($P > 0.05$) compared to the control group. However, administering 200 mg/kg of the extract resulted in a significant ($P < 0.05$) reduction in urea concentration compared to the control (Figure 8). Similarly, serum creatinine levels in rats given 400 and 800 mg/kg of the extract were not significantly

different ($P > 0.05$) from the control (Figure 9). There were no significant reductions ($P > 0.05$) in serum Na^+ concentration in rats administered 200, 400, and 800 mg/kg of the extract (Figure 10). The serum chloride and potassium ion concentrations in rats given the extract were also not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) from the control (Figures 11 and 12). However, rats administered 200 mg/kg of the extract showed a significant reduction ($P < 0.05$) in serum bicarbonate ion concentration compared to the control and those given 400 mg/kg of the extract. In contrast, rats given 800 mg/kg of the extract did not show significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in serum bicarbonate levels

Table 4: Stage 3 Acute Toxicity (LD₅₀) Evaluation of the Extract

Group	Dose (mg/kg)	No. of Deaths	Percentage of mortality	Observations
1	6000	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed. Animals were initially calm but regained physical activity within 24 hours of administration.
2	7000	1/3	33.33	33.33% mortality was observed. Surviving animals were weak, depressed and calm. They also did not completely regain physical activity within 24 hours of administration.
3	10000	3/3	100.00	Rats were initially calm and depressed and 100% mortality was observed by the end of 24 hours of administration.

Figure 3: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum levels of ALP in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 4: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum total protein levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

3 Effect of Varying Doses of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf on Sera Antioxidant Status in Male Wistar Rats

In this study, the rats administered varying doses of the extract exhibited significant ($P < 0.05$) increases in

compared to the control (Figure 13).

Figure 5: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum albumin levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 6: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum total bilirubin levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

serum levels of SOD, CAT, GSH, and GPx, in a dose dependent manner when compared to the control groups. However, at the 800 mg/kg dose, serum levels of SOD and GSH were decreased but not statistically ($P > 0.05$) significant when compared to the 400 mg/kg group (Figures 14, 15, 16, 17). Additionally, serum levels of MDA were significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced in a dose dependent manner in all treatment groups when compared to the control (Figure 18).

Figure 7: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum globulin levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 8: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum urea concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

4 Effect of Varying Doses of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf on Kidney Homogenate Supernatant and Antioxidant Status in Male Wistar Rats

In this study, rats administered varying doses of the extract showed significant increases ($P < 0.05$) in the antioxidant status of kidney homogenates, as evidenced by elevated levels of SOD, CAT, GSH, and GPx, in a dose-dependent manner compared to the control groups (Figures 19, 20, 21, 22). Additionally, the levels of malondialdehyde (MDA) in the kidney homogenates were significantly reduced ($P < 0.05$) in a dose-dependent manner across all treatment groups

Figure 9: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum creatinine concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 11: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on chloride ion concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 10: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on sodium ion concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 12: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on potassium ion concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

compared to the control (Figure 23).

5 Histopathological Assessment of Liver and Kidney Ultrastructures Following Administration of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf

5.1 Liver

Histological analysis of liver sections from rats administered 200, 400, and 800 mg/kg of the extract revealed essentially normal histology, similar to the control group. Sections of the liver in all the groups showed normal hepatic histomorphology, lacking any

signs of acute or chronic damage, and portal tracts without significant inflammation (Plates 1a, b, c, and d). Normal hepatic lobules consisting of hepatocytes arranged in interconnecting cords around the central veins were observed. Likewise, the structures of the portal triads were normal.

Group 1 (Control)

Plate 1a: The photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the control group revealed normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules appeared normal, with hepatocytes arranged in interconnecting cords around the central veins. Additionally, the structures of the portal triads were normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic

Figure 13: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum bicarbonate ion concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 14: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum SOD levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 15: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum CAT levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 16: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum GSH levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

Group 2 (200 mg/kg)

Plate 1b: The photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 200 mg/kg treated group revealed normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules appeared normal, with hepatocytes arranged in interconnecting cords around the central veins. Additionally, the structures of the portal triads were normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

Group 3 (400 mg/kg)

Plate 1c: The photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 400 mg/kg treated group revealed normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic

lobules appeared normal, with hepatocytes arranged in interconnecting cords around the central veins. Additionally, the structures of the portal triads were normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

Group 4 (800 mg/kg)

Plate 1d: The photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 800 mg/kg treated group revealed normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules appeared normal, with hepatocytes arranged in interconnecting cords around the central veins. Additionally, the structures of the portal triads were normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery

Figure 17: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum GPx levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 19: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on SOD of kidney homogenate supernatant in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 18: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum MDA levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 20: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on CAT of kidney homogenate supernatant in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

(HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

5.2 Kidney

Histological analysis of the kidney sections from rats administered the varying doses of the extract revealed essentially normal histology, similar to the control group. Sections of the kidney in the various groups showed normal renal histomorphology, with no indications of glomerular damage or acute or chronic tubular damage (Plates 2a, b, c, and d). Normal glomeruli in their respective Bowman's capsules were observed, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules (proximal convoluted tubules, pars recta, distal convoluted tubules, and collecting ducts) in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix.

Group 1 (Control)

Plate 2a: The photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the control group displayed normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules were seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

Group 2 (200 mg/kg)

Plate 2b: The photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 200 mg/kg treated group displayed normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli

Figure 21: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on GSH of kidney homogenate supernatant in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 23: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on MDA of kidney homogenate supernatant in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 22: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on GPx of kidney homogenate supernatant in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Group 4 (800 mg/kg)

Plate 2d: The photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 800 mg/kg treated group displayed normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules were seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

within their respective Bowman's capsules were seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

Group 3 (400 mg/kg)

Plate 2c: The photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 400 mg/kg treated group displayed normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules were seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

6 Discussion

The phytochemical evaluation of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract reveals a rich presence of bioactive compounds with diverse pharmacological properties. The extract contains a diverse array of phytochemicals, including alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, saponins, cardiac glycosides, and steroids. This finding aligns with those reported by Ebenyi et al. (2021) regarding the phytochemical analysis of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf, as well as by Igbinauwa et al. (2011) and Oyewole et al. (2011) concerning the phytochemical analysis of the methanol extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf.

In this study, alkaloids are present in moderate amounts. Medicinal plants generally contain alkaloids in the range of 10 to 50 mg per 100 grams. This extract, with an alkaloid content of 27.15 mg per 100 grams, falls within the typical range, suggesting a moderate level that could effectively provide therapeutic benefits like pain relief and anticancer activity without being excessively toxic. Alkaloids

Figure 24: Plate 1a: Photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the control group, revealing normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules and portal triads appear normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

Figure 25: Plate 1b: Photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 200 mg/kg treated group, revealing normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules and portal triads appear normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

are recognized for their analgesic, antimalarial, antimicrobial, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory properties (Heinrich et al., 2021).

Plants known for their astringent and antimicrobial qualities typically contain tannin levels ranging from 5 to 20 mg/100g. The 7.63 mg/100g tannin content in this extract falls towards the lower limit of this range, indicating its potential to deliver advantageous antimicrobial and antioxidant benefits while reducing the risk of excessive astringency. Tannins exhibit astringent, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial characteristics (Kováč et al., 2022).

Flavonoids are powerful antioxidants known for their anti-inflammatory, antiviral, and anticancer properties (Hasnat et al., 2024). In medicinal plants, flavonoid content generally ranges from 20 to 50 mg/100g. With a flavonoid content of 39.18 mg/100g, this extract is on the higher end of the spectrum, suggesting it has significant antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential. This makes the extract beneficial for preventing diseases related to oxidative stress and for managing inflammation.

Plants recognized for their potent antioxidant properties usually have phenol content ranging from 30 to 70 mg/100g. This extract, with a phenol content of 46.07 mg/100g, falls within this typical range, indicating substantial antioxidant properties that can aid in the prevention and management

of diseases linked to oxidative stress, such as cardiovascular diseases and cancer. Phenols are powerful antioxidants that protect against oxidative damage and help reduce the risk of chronic diseases (Kostić et al., 2023).

Typically, medicinal plants have terpenoid levels ranging from 1 to 10 mg/100g. The terpenoid content of 5.41 mg/100g in this extract falls within this anticipated range, suggesting potential benefits in reducing inflammation, fighting infections, and possibly inhibiting cancer cell growth. Terpenoids exhibit anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and antimicrobial properties (Masyita et al., 2022).

Plants known for their health benefits typically contain saponin levels ranging from 20 to 60 mg/100g. With a saponin content of 33.10 mg/100g falling within this usual range, the extract shows promise in managing cholesterol levels, boosting immune function, and potentially preventing cancer. Saponins are recognized for their ability to lower cholesterol, enhance immune response, and exhibit anticancer properties (Juang & Liang, 2020).

Cardiotonic plants typically have cardiac glycoside levels between 1 and 5 mg/100g. This extract contains 4.83 mg/100g of cardiac glycosides, which falls towards the higher end of the usual range. This suggests a robust potential for cardiotonic effects that can be beneficial in the management of heart failure and arrhythmias (Škubník et al., 2021). Cardiac

Figure 26: Plate 1c: Photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 400 mg/kg treated group, revealing normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules and portal triads appear normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

Figure 27: Plate 1d: Photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 800 mg/kg treated group, revealing normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules and portal triads appear normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

glycosides are employed in treating heart conditions by fortifying cardiac contractions and regulating heart rhythm.

Plants with anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects typically have steroid levels ranging from 1 to 10 mg/100g. Steroids are known for their anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties (Dembitsky, 2023). The extract's steroid content of 3.80 mg/100g falls within this anticipated range, indicating potential advantages in reducing inflammation and modulating immune responses. This could be valuable in treating inflammatory and autoimmune conditions like rheumatoid arthritis and type 1 diabetes.

The acute toxicity study of *Jatropha tanjorensis* in Wistar rats provided valuable insights into the safety profile of the plant extract. The absence of mortality and maintained physical stability at doses up to 6000 mg/kg indicates that *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract is relatively non-toxic at lower doses. This suggests a high margin of safety for potential therapeutic use within this dose range. At 7000 mg/kg, a significant increase in mortality rate (33.33%) indicates that toxicity begins to manifest at this dose. While the majority of mice survived, the onset of mortality at this level signals a threshold for adverse effects, highlighting the importance of dose regulation. Complete mortality at 10,000 mg/kg demonstrates that this dose is highly toxic and

lethal. This drastic increase in mortality confirms a critical toxic threshold and emphasizes that doses approaching this level are dangerous and unsafe for use. The LD50 value (the dose at which 50% of the test population is expected to die) of 7745.97 mg/kg indicates the median lethal dose. This relatively high LD50 value suggests that the extract has a broad therapeutic index and is relatively safe at lower doses. The LD50 value is crucial for determining the safety margin and guiding dosage levels for further studies and potential therapeutic applications. This finding is consistent with the report by Ebenyi et al. (2021), which observed no behavioural changes or mortality at oral doses of 2,000 and 5,000 mg/kg within the first 24 hours and during a 14-day study period following administration of an aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf. Similarly, Igbinaaduwa et al. (2011) reported no mortality or signs of behavioural changes or toxicity in mice and rats after administering methanol extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf at doses up to 8,000 mg/kg body weight.

ALT (Alanine aminotransferase) and AST (Aspartate aminotransferase) are enzymes that are commonly used as biomarkers for liver function (McGill, 2016; Chinnappan et al., 2023). The lack of significant ($p < 0.05$) differences in serum ALT and AST levels suggests that the extract, at the administered doses, does not cause hepatocellular damage or stress. This outcome aligns with Ezendiokwere et al.'s

Figure 28: Plate 2a: Photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the control group displaying normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules are seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μm*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

Figure 29: Plate 2b: Photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 200 mg/kg treated group displaying normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules are seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μm*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

2023 study, which examined the Acute and Subacute Toxicity Profile of Diethyl ether Extract from *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf in Male Wistar Rats. This indicates that the extract is not hepatotoxic. This implies that the extract's hepatoprotective properties may stem from its tannin content. Tannins are recognized for their antioxidant abilities, capable of scavenging free radicals and mitigating oxidative stress in cells, including those in the liver. By shielding liver cells from oxidative harm, tannins may play a role in preserving the typical levels of ALT and AST (Sobeh et al., 2017; Abu et al., 2022). While the precise mechanisms remain somewhat unclear, it's theorized that tannins might influence enzyme activity in liver cells, including ALT and AST, contributing to the maintenance of serum levels within normal ranges.

ALP (Alkaline phosphatase) is another enzyme associated with liver function (McGill, 2016; Chinnappan et al., 2023), but it can also indicate bone and other tissue-related activity (Fernandez, 2007; Haarhaus et al., 2022). The significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in ALP levels suggests that the extract might have an inhibitory effect on ALP activity. This result is consistent with the findings of Chibuogwu et al. (2021) and Ezendiokwere et al. (2023). The presence of the phytochemicals (flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and terpenoids), through their combined antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and

enzyme-modulating properties, could be responsible for the significant reduction in ALP levels observed in the study. This effect can be beneficial in managing conditions where elevated ALP levels are a concern, such as liver diseases or bone disorders (Singab et al., 2005; Sobeh et al., 2017; Abu et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2019). The dose-dependent response, with the most significant reduction at 400 mg/kg, indicates that the extract's effect is potent and potentially dose-related.

Total protein and albumin are indicators of nutritional status and liver function (Keller, 2019). An increase in these parameters suggests that the extract might have a positive effect on protein synthesis or overall nutritional status. This could indicate an anabolic effect or improved liver function in terms of protein production. This result also aligns with the findings of Ezendiokwere et al. (2023).

Bilirubin is a byproduct of the breakdown of red blood cells and is processed by the liver (Guerra Ruiz et al., 2021). Normal levels of bilirubin indicate proper liver function and red blood cell turnover. The lack of significant changes in bilirubin levels further supports the conclusion that the extract does not adversely affect liver function at the administered doses.

The significant reduction in serum cholesterol,

Figure 30: Plate 2c: Photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 400 mg/kg treated group displaying normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules are seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μm*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

Figure 31: Plate 2d: Photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 800 mg/kg treated group displaying normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules are seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μm*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

triglycerides, and LDL levels in the treated groups suggests that the extract has a lipid-lowering effect. This outcome aligns with the report of Akinloye et al. (2017) which examined the acute toxicity and antioxidant effects of *Jatropha tanjorensis* methanol extract in Wistar rats. This result is consistent with the hypolipidemic activity of several of the phytochemicals present in the extract, such as flavonoids and saponins. These compounds are known to have lipid-lowering properties, possibly through mechanisms involving inhibition of lipid absorption, enhanced lipid metabolism, or modulation of lipid-regulating enzymes (Juang & Liang, 2020; Hasnat et al., 2024). The observed reduction in LDL (Low-Density Lipoprotein) levels is particularly notable, as elevated LDL is a known risk factor for cardiovascular diseases. The decrease in LDL levels indicates a potential cardioprotective effect of the extract. The significant reduction in serum cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL levels with the highest dose (400 mg/kg) demonstrating the most pronounced effect suggests a dose-dependent response. This implies that higher doses of the extract may lead to more substantial improvements in lipid profiles.

HDL (High-Density Lipoprotein) is often referred to as "good cholesterol" because it helps remove other forms of cholesterol from the bloodstream (FERENCE et al., 2017). The lack of significant changes in

HDL levels suggests that while the extract effectively lowers total cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL, it does not adversely affect HDL levels. This is beneficial because maintaining or increasing HDL levels is generally desirable for cardiovascular health.

The extract's capacity to lower LDL cholesterol without significantly altering HDL levels highlights its potential as a natural remedy for improving lipid profiles and enhancing cardiovascular health.

7 Conclusion

The comprehensive phytochemical and toxicological evaluation of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extract conducted in this study provides valuable insights into its safety profile and potential health benefits. The phytochemical analysis revealed a rich presence of bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, saponins, cardiac glycosides, and steroids, which are known for their diverse pharmacological properties. The acute toxicity study in Wistar rats demonstrated that the extract is relatively non-toxic at lower doses, with an LD50 value of 7745.97 mg/kg, indicating a broad therapeutic index. The biochemical analysis of liver function markers (ALT, AST, and ALP) and lipid profile parameters (cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, and HDL) suggested that the extract does not cause hepatocellular damage and has a lipid-lowering effect,

particularly at higher doses. These findings align with previous studies and support the potential use of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extract as a safe and effective natural remedy for managing various health conditions. Further research is needed to elucidate the precise mechanisms of action and to explore its potential therapeutic applications in clinical settings.

8 References

Abu, O.D., Orobator, O.N., & Momodu, I.B. (2022). Evaluation of the effect of total saponins and tannins isolated from *Dialium guineense* stem bark on CCl₄ – Induced hepatotoxicity in Wistar rats. *Global Journal of Medical and Clinical Case Reports*, 9(3), 035-038.

Adebajo, A.C., Olayiwola, G., & Omobuwajo, O.R. (2004). The Antidiabetic Potential of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaves. *Nigerian Journal of Natural Products and Medicine* 8, 55–58.

Alechinsky, L., Favreau, F., Cechova, P., Inal, S., Faye, P. A., Ory, C., Thuillier, R., Barrou, B., Trouillas, P., Guillard, J., & Hauet, T. (2020). Tannic Acid Improves Renal Function Recovery after Renal Warm Ischemia-Reperfusion in a Rat Model. *Biomolecules*, 10(3), 439.

Archana, P., Samatha, T., Mahitha, B. & Chamundeswari, N. R. (2012). Preliminary phytochemical screening from leaf and seed extracts of *Senna alata* L. Roxb-an ethno medicinal plant. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biological Research*, 3, 82–89.

Arunachalam, K., & Sasidharan, S.P. (2021). General considerations and collection of animal blood. In: *bioassays in experimental and preclinical pharmacology*. New York: Humana, New York, NY Springer Protocols Handbooks 51-55p.

Bartels, H., & Bohmer, M. (1972). Quantitative Determination of Creatinine. *Clinical Chimica Acta*, 37, 193.

Basil, R. (2023). Glutathione: the master antioxidant. *Ozone Therapy Global Journal*, 13(1), 175-197.

Busher, J.T. (1990). Serum Albumin and Globulin. In: Walker HK, Hall WD, Hurst JW, editors. *Clinical Methods: The History, Physical, and Laboratory Examinations*. 3rd edition. Boston: Butterworths; 1990. Chapter 101.

Chaachouay, N., & Zidane, L. (2024). Plant-Derived Natural Products: A Source for Drug Discovery and Development. *Drugs and Drug Candidates*, 3(1), 184-

207.

Chibuogwu, C.C., Njoku, U.O., Nwodo, F.C.O., Ozougwu, E.O.V., & N. Victor Nweze, N.V. (2021). Toxicity assessment of the methanol extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* (Euphorbiaceae) leaves. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 7(143), 1-8.

Chinnappan, R., Mir, T. A., Alsalamah, S., Makhzoum, T., Alzhrani, A., Al-Kattan, K., & Yaqinuddin, A. (2023). Low-Cost Point-of-Care Monitoring of ALT and AST Is Promising for Faster Decision Making and Diagnosis of Acute Liver Injury. *Diagnostics (Basel, Switzerland)*, 13(18), 2967.

Cohen, G., Dembiec, D., & Marcus, J. (1970). Measurement of Catalase activity in tissue extracts. *Analytical Biochemistry* 34, 30-38.

Cordiano, R., Di Gioacchino, M., Mangifesta, R., Panzera, C., Gangemi, S., & Minciullo, P. L. (2023). Malondialdehyde as a Potential Oxidative Stress Marker for Allergy-Oriented Diseases: An Update. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 28(16), 5979.

Dembitsky V. M. (2023). Biological Activity and Structural Diversity of Steroids Containing Aromatic Rings, Phosphate Groups, or Halogen Atoms. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 28(14), 5549.

Ebenyi, L. N., Yongabi, K. A., Ali, F. U., Ominyi, M. C., Anyanwu, C. B., Benjamin, E., & Ogbanshi, M. E. (2021). Effect of Aqueous Leaf Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* on parasitaemia and haematological parameters in mice infected with *Plasmodium ber ghei*. *Nigerian Journal of Biotechnology* (1), 146-153.

Ejikeme, C.M., Ezeonu, C.S., & Eboatu, A.N. (2014). Determination of physical and phytochemical constituents of some tropical timbers indigenous to Niger Delta area of Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 10, 247–270.

Ellis, J.L., & Saroja, T.L. (1961). A new species of *Jatropha* from South India. *Journal of Bombay Natural History Society*, 8, 834-836.

Ewa-Udu, N. E., C. Nwanebu, F., Stanley, H. O., & W. Okereke, I. (2022). Antibacterial Screening of *Jatropha tanjorensis* against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *International Journal of Pathogen Research*, 10(4), 12–17.

Ezendiokwere, E.O., Comfort Monago-Ighorodje, C.M., & Ikewuchi, J. (2023). Assessment of Acute and Subacute Toxicity Profile of Diethylether Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf in Male Wistar Rats. *Journal of Applied Health Sciences and Medicine*, 3(4), 1 – 13.

- https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=FAWCETT+JKcauthor_id=13821779 Fawcett, J.K., & https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=SCOTT+JEauthor_id=13821779 SCOTT + J.E. (1959). *Journal of Pharmacy and Bioresources*, 8(2), 86-91.
- Fernandez, N. J., & Kidney, B. A. (2007). Alkaline phosphatase: beyond the liver. *Veterinary clinical pathology*, 36(3), 223–233.
- Flohe, L., & Guüzler, W.A (1984). Assay of glutathione. *Methods in enzymology* 105: 114-121.
- Fieldwald, W.T., Levy, R.I., & Fredrickson, D.S. (1972). Estimation of the concentration of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol in plasma without use of the preparative ultracentrifuge: *Clinical Chemistry manual of histology*, (3rd ed.) New York.
- Guerra Ruiz, A. R., Crespo, J., López Martínez, R. M., Iruzubieta, P., Casals Mercadal, G., Lalana Garcés, M., Lavin, B., & Morales Ruiz, M. (2021). Measurement and clinical usefulness of bilirubin in liver disease. *Advances in laboratory medicine*, 2(3), 352–372.
- Haarhaus, M., Cianciolo, G., Barbuto, S., La Manna, G., Gasperoni, L., Tripepi, G., Plebani, M., Fusaro, M., & Magnusson, P. (2022). Alkaline Phosphatase: An Old Friend as Treatment Target for Cardiovascular and Mineral Bone Disorders in Chronic Kidney Disease. *Nutrients*, 14(10), 2124.
- Hagerman, A., Muller. I., & Makkar, H. (2000). Quantification of tannins in tree foliage. A laboratory manual, Vienna: FAO/IAEA.p. 4-7.
- Hasnat, H., Shompa, S. A., Islam, M. M., Alam, S., Richi, F. T., Emon, N. U., Ashrafi, S., Ahmed, N. U., Chowdhury, M. N. R., Fatema, N., Hossain, M. S., Ghosh, A., & Ahmed, F. (2024). Flavonoids: A treasure house of prospective pharmacological potentials. *Heliyon*, 10(6), e27533.
- Heinrich, M., Mah, J., & Amirkia, V. (2021). Alkaloids Used as Medicines: Structural Phytochemistry Meets Biodiversity-An Update and Forward Look. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 26(7), 1836.
- Hopkins, E., Sanvictores, T., & Sharma, S. (2022). Physiology, Acid Base Balance. In: StatPearls. Treasure Island: StatPearls Publishing, 2024.
- Idu, M., Igbafe, G., & Erhabor J.O. (2014). Anti-Anaemic Activity of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Ellis & Saroja in Rabbits. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Studies*, 2, 64–72.
- Igbinaduwa, P.O., Usifoh, C.O., & Ugwu, C.C. (2011). Phytochemical analysis and toxicological evaluation of the methanolic extract of *Jatropha*
- Juang, Y. P., & Liang, P. H. (2020). Biological and Pharmacological Effects of Synthetic Saponins. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 25(21), 4974.
- Kantamreddi, V. S. S. N., Lakshmi, Y. N., & Kasapu, V. V. V. S. (2010). Preliminary phytochemical analysis of some important indian plant species. – *International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences*, 1, B-358 ref.12.
- Keller U. (2019). Nutritional Laboratory Markers in Malnutrition. *Journal of clinical medicine*, 8(6), 775.
- Kellum, J. A., Romagnani, P., Ashuntantang, G., Ronco, C., Zarbock, A., & Anders, H. J. (2021). Acute kidney injury. *Nature reviews. Disease primers*, 7(1), 52.
- Kostić, K., Brborić, J., Delogu, G., Simić, M. R., Samardžić, S., Maksimović, Z., Dettori, M. A., Fabbri, D., Kotur-Stevuljević, J., & Saso, L. (2023). Antioxidant Activity of Natural Phenols and Derived Hydroxylated Biphenyls. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 28(6), 2646.
- Kováč, J., Slobodníková, L., Trajčíková, E., Rendeková, K., Mučaji, P., Sychrová, A., & Bittner Fialová, S. (2022). Therapeutic Potential of Flavonoids and Tannins in Management of Oral Infectious Diseases-A Review. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 28(1), 158.
- Laposata, M., & McCaffrey, P. (2022). *Clinical Laboratory Methods: Atlas of Commonly Performed Tests*. In: M Laposata and P McCaffrey (eds.) McGraw Hill.
- Li, Y., Zhuang, Y., Tian, W., & Sun, L. (2020). In vivo acute and subacute toxicities of phenolic extract from rambutan (*Nephelium lappaceum*) peels by oral administration. *Food chemistry*, 320, 126618.
- Lorke, D. (1983). A new approach to practical acute toxicity testing. *Archives of Toxicology*, 54, 275-87.
- Ma, Z. N., Li, Y. Z., Li, W., Yan, X. T., Yang, G., Zhang, J., Zhao, L. C., & Yang, L. M. (2017). Nephroprotective Effects of Saponins from Leaves of *Panax quinquefolius* against Cisplatin-Induced Acute Kidney Injury. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 18(7), 1407.
- Makkar, H.P., Siddhuraju, P., & Becker, K. (2007). Methods in molecular biology: plant secondary metabolites, Totowa: Human Press; p. 93-100
- Masyita, A., Mustika Sari, R., Dwi Astuti, A., Yasir, B., Rahma Rumata, N., Emran, T. B., Nainu, F., &

Simal-Gandara, J. (2022). Terpenes and terpenoids as main bioactive compounds of essential oils, their roles in human health and potential application as natural food preservatives. *Food chemistry: X*, 13, 100217.

McGill M. R. (2016). The past and present of serum aminotransferases and the future of liver injury biomarkers. *EXCLI journal*, 15, 817–828.

Meda, A., Lamien, C.E., Romito, M., Millogo, J. & Nacoulma, O.G. (2005). Determination of the total phenolic, flavonoid and proline contents in Burkina Fasan honey, as well as their radical scavenging activity. *Food Chemistry*, 91, 571-577.

Meda, A., Lamien, C.E., Romito, M., Millogo, J., & Nacoulma, O.G. (2005). Determination of the total phenolic, flavonoid and proline contents in Burkina Fasan honey, as well as their radical scavenging activity. *Food Chemistry*, 91, 571–577.

Misra, H.P., & Fridovich, I. (1972). The role of superoxide anion in the autooxidation of epinephrine and simple assay for superoxide dismutase. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 247, 3170 - 3175. 1972.

Nandi, A., Yan, L. J., Jana, C. K., & Das, N. (2019). Role of Catalase in Oxidative Stress- and Age-Associated Degenerative Diseases. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity*, 2019, 9613090.

Neergheen-Bhujun, V. S. (2013). Underestimating the toxicological challenges associated with the use of herbal medicinal products in developing countries. *BioMed research international*, 2013, 804086.

Njinga, N. S., Kola-Mustapha, A. T., Quadri, A. L., Atolani, O., Ayanniyi, R. O., Buhari, M. O., Amusa, T. O., Ajani, E. O., Folaranmi, O. O., Bakare-Odunola, M. T., Kambizi, L., Oladiji, A. T., & Ebong, P. (2020). Toxicity assessment of sub-acute and sub-chronic oral administration and diuretic potential of aqueous extract of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* calyces. *Heliyon*, 6(9), e04853.

Okhawa, H., Ohishi, N., & Yagi, K. (1979). Assay for lipid peroxides in animal tissues by thiobarbituric acid reaction. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 95, 351 – 358.

Olayiwola, G., Iwalewa, E.O., Omobuwajo, O.R., Adeniyi, A.A., & Verspohi, E.J. (2004). The antidiabetic potential of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaves. *Nigerian Journal of Natural Products and Medicine* 8, 55 –58.

Oliveira, M.S., Fernandes, M.Z.L.C.M., Mineiro, A.L.B.B., Santos, R.F.D., Viana, G.E.N., Coelho, J.M., Ribeiro, S.M., Cunha, A.P.G.P., Costa, J.F., & Fernandes, R.M. (2016). Toxicity effects of ethanol

extract of *Simarouba versicolor* on reproductive parameters in female Wistar rats. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 15 (8), 221–235.

Omobuwajo, O.R., Alade, G.O., Akanmu, M.A., Obuotor, E.M., & Osasan, S.A. (2011). Microscopic and toxicity studies on the leaves of *J. tanjorensis*. *African Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 5(1), 12 –17.

Omoriegie, E.S., & Osagie, A.U. (2011). Effect of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaves Supplement on The Activities of Some Antioxidant Enzymes, Vitamins and Lipid Peroxidation in Rats. *Journal of Food Biochemistry* 35, 409–424.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Guidance Document on Acute Oral Toxicity Testing, OECD Environment, Health and Safety Publications, 2008. Series on Testing and Assessment 29 (Online), Available from: <https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/iccvam/suppdocs/feddocs/oecd/oecd-gd129.pdf> (Accessed on 23rd September, 2019).

Orhue, E.S., Idu, M., Ataman, J.E., & Ebite, L.E. (2008). Haematological and Histopathological studies of *Jatropha tanjorensis* (J.L. Ellis and Soroja) leaves in rabbits. *Asian Journal of Biological Sciences* 1(2), 84 –89.

Oyewole, I.O., & Akingbala, P.F. (2011). Phytochemical analysis and Hypolipidemic properties of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extract. *European Journal of Medicinal Plants* 1(4), 180 –5.

Pei, J., Pan, X., Wei, G., & Hua, Y. (2023). Research progress of glutathione peroxidase family (GPX) in redoxitation. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, 14, 1147414.

Pillai, P. G., Suresha, P., Mishrab, G., & Annapurna, M. (2011). Evaluation of the acute and sub-acute toxicity of the methanolic leaf extract of *Plectranthus amboinicus* (Lour) Spreng in Balb C mice. *European Journal of Experimental Biology*, 1(3), 236-245.

Pizzorno, J. (2014). Glutathione! *Integrative medicine (Encinitas, Calif.)*, 13(1), 8–12.

Rizvi, S. A. A., Einstein, G. P., Tulp, O. L., Sainvil, F., & Branly, R. (2022). Introduction to Traditional Medicine and Their Role in Prevention and Treatment of Emerging and Re-Emerging Diseases. *Biomolecules*, 12(10), 1442.

Rout, P.K., Rao, Y.R., Jena, K.S., & Sahoo, D. & Ali, S. (2014). Safety evaluation of *Simarouba glauca* seed fat, *Journal of Food Science and Technology*,

51 (7), 1349–1355.

Sannigrahi, S., Mazumder, U.K., Pal, D.K., Mondal, A., & Roy, S. (2009). Hepatoprotective Potential of Flavonoid Rich Fraction of *Enhydra fluctuans* Against CCl₄-Induced Oxidative Damage in Rats. *Pharmacologyonline*, 2, 575-586.

Sati, S. C. & Kumar, P. (2015). Assessment of *Himalayan juniper*, *Juniperus squamata* Buch-Ham ex D. Don for phytochemical screening and antimicrobial potential against some infection causing pathogens. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 23, 998–1011.

Savithramma, N., Rao, M. L., & Suhrulatha, D. Screening of medicinal plants for secondary metabolites. *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*, 8 (3), 579–584 (2011).

Selvakumar, S., Vimalanban, S. & Balakrishnan, G. (2019). Quantitative determination of phytochemical constituents from *Anisomeles malabarica*. *MOJ Bioequivalence Bioavailability* 6(1), 19–21.

Shen, L.; Luo, H.; Fan, L.; Tian, X.; Tang, A.; Wu, X.; Dong, K.; & Su, Z. (2024). Potential Immunoregulatory Mechanism of Plant Saponins: A Review. *Molecules*, 29, 113.

Shrimanker, I., & Bhattarai, S. (2023). Electrolytes. In: StatPearls. Treasure Island: StatPearls Publishing, 2023.

Siddiqui, A. A., & Ali, M., 1997. Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry. – CBS Publishers & Distributors., Delhi.

Singab, A. N., Youssef, D. T., Noaman, E., & Kotb, S. (2005). Hepatoprotective effect of flavonol glycosides rich fraction from Egyptian *Vicia calcarata* Desf. against CCl₄-induced liver damage in rats. *Archives of pharmacal research*, 28(7), 791–798.

Škubník, J., Svobodová Pavlíčková, V., Psotová, J., & Rimpelová, S. (2021). Cardiac Glycosides as Autophagy Modulators. *Cells*, 10(12), 3341.

Sobeh, M., Mahmoud, M. F., Abdelfattah, M. A. O., El-Beshbishy, H. A., El-Shazly, A. M., & Wink, M. (2017). Hepatoprotective and hypoglycemic effects of a tannin rich extract from *Ximenia americana* var. *caffra* root. *Phytomedicine: international journal of phytotherapy and phytopharmacology*, 33, 36–42.

Sofowora, L. A. (1993). Phytochemical screening of medicinal plants and traditional medicine in Africa, 2nd Edition. Spectrum Books Limited Nigeria, pages 150 – 156.

Tarfa, F., Toryila, J.E., & Danborn, A.M. (2021).

Toxicological Effects of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Aqueous Leaf Extract on Kidney and Liver in Wistar Rats. *Journal of Medical and Basic Scientific Research*, 2 (2), 31-36.

Tietz, N.W. (1976). Fundamentals of Clinical Chemistry, second ed. Philadelphia: W.B. Saunders Saunders (W.B.) Company Limited Publisher.

Tietz, N.W., Pruden, E.L., & Siggard-Anderson, O. (1986). Electrolytes, Blood Gases and Acid-Base Balance. In: Tietz, N.W. (Eds.), Textbook of Clinical Chemistry. Philadelphia: Walter Burns Saunders Company, pp. 1172-1182.

Tietze, F. (1969). Enzymic method for quantitative determination of nanogram amounts of total and oxidized glutathione: applications to mammalian blood and other tissues. *Analytical Biochemistry* 27, 502 – 522.

Tofghi, Z., Ghazi, S. N., Hadjiakhoondi, A., & Yassa, N. (2016). Determination of cardiac glycosides and total phenols in different generations of *Securigera securidaca* suspension culture. *Research Journal of Pharmacognosy*, 3(2), 25–31.

Trease, G. E., & Evans, W. C. (2003): Pharmacognosy. – Saunders, London, pp. 479-480.

Ullah, A., Munir, S., Badshah, S. L., Khan, N., Ghani, L., Poulson, B. G., Emwas, A. H., & Jaremko, M. (2020). Important Flavonoids and Their Role as a Therapeutic Agent. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 25(22), 5243.

Viswanathan, M.B., & Jeyaananthi, J. (2009). Antimicrobial and Antiinflammatory Activities of Various Extracts of the Leaves of *Jatropha tanjorensis*. *Biosciences Biotechnology Research Asia*, 6, 297–300.

Wang, Y., Branicky, R., Noë, A., & Hekimi, S. (2018). Superoxide dismutases: Dual roles in controlling ROS damage and regulating ROS signaling. *The Journal of cell biology*, 217(6), 1915–1928.

Wang, C.Y., Yu-Wei Chen, Y.W., & Hou, C.Y. (2019). Antioxidant and antibacterial activity of seven predominant terpenoids. *International Journal of Food Properties*, 22(1), 230–238.

Windsor, L. (1994). Tissue processing, in: E. Wood (Ed.), Laboratory Histopathology, A Complete Reference, Vol. 1, Churchill Livingstone, New York, pp. 1–42.

World Health Organization. (2019). WHO global report on traditional and complementary medicine

2019. World Health Organization.

Zhang, J., Onakpoya, I. J., Posadzki, P., & Eddouks, M. (2015). The safety of herbal medicine: from prejudice to evidence. *Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine: eCAM*, 2015, 316706.

Zuo, Y., Wang, C., Zhou, J., Sachdeva, A., & Ruelos, V. C. (2008). Simultaneous determination of creatinine and uric acid in human urine by high-performance liquid chromatography. *Analytical sciences: the international journal of the Japan Society for Analytical Chemistry*, 24(12), 1589–1592.

Green Synthesized Iron Nanoparticles Using *Gongronema latifolium* Leaf Extract: Characterization, Antioxidant, and Antidiabetic Activities

Ekozin, A. A.^{1*}, Isola, O. B.¹, Inetianbor, O. C.², Omondiale, S. O.¹, Omojoyegbe, R. T.³, Okanlawon, T. S.³

¹Department of Chemical Sciences, College of Basic, Applied and Health Sciences, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

²Chemistry Department, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria

³Department of Biological Sciences, College of Basic, Applied and Health Sciences, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author Tel: +234 9132750059 Email: ekozinadriel@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Green nanoparticles are derived from natural sources possessing unique properties for biomedical applications. Inhibition of key enzymes (-amylase and -glucosidase) involved in the digestion of starch and protection against free radicals and lipid peroxidation could be part of the therapeutic approach towards the management of hyperglycemia. The study was carried out to synthesize and characterize Iron Oxide nanoparticles coated with ethanolic leaf extracts of *Gongronema latifolium* (Gl-FeONPs) using highly advanced techniques for its use as antioxidant and antidiabetic. The study compared the in vitro antioxidant capacities of ethanolic leaf extracts of *Gongronema latifolium* (Et-Gl), iron oxide nanoparticles (FeONPs) and Gl-FeONPs by evaluating the Metal Chelating Activity (MCA), Nitric Oxide Scavenging Activity (NOSA), Ferric Reducing Ability Power (FRAP) and Lipid Peroxidation (LPO). The in-vitro anti-diabetic capacities were determined against -amylase and -glucosidase. Results showed that, Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs displayed MCA (IC₅₀= 29.48 - 14.77 g/mL), NOSA (IC₅₀= 2.157 - 1.480 g/mL), FRAP (IC₅₀= 10.658 - 4.352 g/mL), LPO (14.17 - 94.38%), -amylase (IC₅₀= 2.81 - 4.83 mg/mL), and -glucosidase (IC₅₀= 2.02 - 3.52 mg/mL). Overall, Gl-FeONPs indicated the potential to prevent postprandial hyperglycemia by slowing down carbohydrate hydrolysis and oxidative stress.

Keywords: Nanotechnology, Green nanoparticle, Antioxidant, Anti-diabetic, *Gongronema latifolium*

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic condition typified by a lack of insulin action, production, or both, which results in hyperglycemia (Cole Florez, 2020). Chronic hyperglycemia (high blood sugar) with problems with major macromolecule metabolism is the outcome of its lack. Diabetes mellitus can cause long-term harm, malfunction, and organ failure, particularly to the liver, kidneys, eyes, nerves, heart, pancreas, eyes (retinopathy), kidneys (nephropathy), and blood vessels (Deshpande et al., 2008). According to recent estimates, there were 455 million diabetics globally in 2017, and by 2045, that number is predicted to rise to 693 million. It was also shown that around 50% of diabetics go undiagnosed. The cost of treating diabetic patients was predicted to be USD 850 billion worldwide in the same year (Ganasegeran et al., 2020). It is

estimated that 11.2 million Nigerians, or 5.77% of the population, have diabetes (Uloko et al., 2018). Because the digestible polysaccharides do not absorb glucose quickly, causing a hyperglycemic peak, the nutrition approach successfully lowers postprandial glycemia (Srisongkram et al., 2022). α -amylase is essential for the digestion of polysaccharides. The absorption of monosaccharides (such as glucose or maltose) and abrupt high glycemic peaks, which lower insulin sensitivity, are prevented by inhibition of these two enzymes (Alqahtani et al., 2019). A family of oral hypoglycemic medications known as alpha-glucosidase inhibitors alters how carbohydrates are absorbed in the intestines, lowering blood glucose levels. Type 2 diabetes mellitus is treated with them (Alqahtani et al., 2019). Patients who are overweight or obese may benefit from lowering their blood glucose absorption through food modification (Kaur

et al., 2021). Synthetic substances such as acarbose, miglitol, and voglibose are utilized in clinical settings. However, some of these substances' side effects might include gastrointestinal (GI) abnormalities, such as bloating, abdominal discomfort, GI cramps, or diarrhea (Dirir et al., 2022). More promising than synthetic medicines (such as acarbose or voglibose) for decreasing postprandial glycemia with fewer side effects such as bloating, stomach discomfort, and diarrhea are natural items that may block α -amylase and α -glucosidase activity (Alqahtani et al., 2019; Kaur et al., 2021; Dirir et al., 2022).

Free radicals cause oxidative stress, which builds up in the body and causes reactive oxygen and nitrogen species to accumulate (Teleanu et al., 2022). This disrupts normal aging processes and causes a variety of metabolic abnormalities. These free radicals are produced either naturally during human metabolism or as a result of ultraviolet radiation and chemical pollutants in the environment. Excessive free radicals, DNA damage, and cell malignancy are all directly linked to the development of cancer, according to scientific investigations (Yang et al., 2022). A major contributing component in the development of type II diabetes mellitus has also been identified as oxidative stress. Cost-effective alternatives are urgently needed to lessen the burdens on people and society because the medical therapy for these diseases is extremely expensive (Teleanu et al., 2022). In other words, antioxidants are molecules that diminish or stop the effects of free radicals. Antioxidants are substances that shield cells from the harm produced by free radicals. Free radicals receive electrons from them, which lessens their reactivity. Many plants and animals create anti-oxidants to prevent oxidation from damaging healthy cells or making damaged cells worse (Achan et al., 2011). Plant-derived substances have been of great interest due to their versatile applications (Krishnamurti Rao, 2016).

Gongronema latifolium is a native of Esanland, Edo State, Nigeria. It is often referred to as "Utezi" in Esanland and "arokeke" in Yoruba communities in Nigeria (Okon et al., 2022). In addition to being consumed raw or as a vegetable in soup, *G. latifolium* has been used extensively in folk medicine to help maintain normal blood glucose levels (Ojo et al., 2020; Omonhinmin et al., 2022). The residents of Edo State, Nigeria's Esanland are well-known for consuming a lot of vegetables, some of

which are included in meals taken under particular circumstances, such as illness or during recovery periods (Omonhinmin et al., 2022).

Modern technology development frequently focuses on the provision of healthcare as a fundamental human right (Anjum et al., 2021). Nanotechnology stands out among all cutting-edge technologies for its success in guaranteeing high-quality medical care. Although nanotechnology has many applications across many industries, it is particularly capable of using nanoparticles to encapsulate medications (Adewuyi et al., 2018). Utilizing plant extracts to synthesize metallic nanoparticles is a promising approach since it has shown to be less expensive, safer, faster, simpler, and easier than traditional approaches (Adeyemi et al., 2022). The green synthesis of iron nanoparticles and their biomedical applications have been extensively reported (Kalpana et al., 2018; Vijayakumar et al., 2022). However, there are synthesis methods and important properties and characteristics that still need to be investigated. Therefore, in this study we synthesized iron nanoparticles using *G. latifolium* extract as a reducing agent in the redox synthesis of the nanomaterials. We characterized the nanostructures by spectroscopic and microscopic analyses and studied their in-vitro free radical scavenging activities. We also demonstrated the in vitro screening of α -amylase inhibitory activities. Moreover, the results here described give insight towards the development of novel and more effective antioxidant and antidiabetic therapies for different applications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Materials

In the current research, the leaves of *Gongronema latifolium* were selected based on the ethno-medicinal claims of the Esan tribe of the Edo people, Nigeria. The leaves of *G. latifolium* were retrieved from the forest located in Ogwa village. The plant material was identified and authenticated by Dr. E.S. Osagie, Technical Officer, Plant Genetic Resources, University of Benin. Herbariums were deposited at JNTBGRI (TBGT 86816/dated November 25, 2022).

Preparation of Extracts

Gongronema latifolium was freshly collected, washed thoroughly with distilled water, and left to dry for two weeks. The leaves were homogenized by a

mechanical blender, model TT-I777. The resulting powdered leaves were macerated with ethanol and distilled water solvents. This solution was left for 72 hours to ensure proper concentration. The solution was appropriately filtered using a mesh-like structure. The plant solutes were properly disposed of while the subsequent filtered solvent underwent extraction and concentration to extract the initially present ethanol and to concentrate the plant extract using a rotary evaporator, vacuum pump, and water bath simultaneously.

Synthesis of Iron Nanoparticle Coated with Ethanolic Leaf Extracts of *Gongronema latifolium* (GI-FeONPs)

According to Ali et al. (2016), GI-FeONPs were prepared as follows: 3.33 g of Iron(III) Chloride hexahydrate and 1.5 g of Iron(II) Chloride were dissolved in 100 mL of distilled water. The solution was mixed under dry gas in an oven at 80°C for 10 minutes. Subsequently, 15 mL of plant extract was added drop-wise into the mixture under continuous stirring for 10 minutes. After 5 minutes, 60 mL of 1 M NaOH was added to the solution. The reaction further proceeded until the color of the solution, which was initially yellow, transformed to dark brown.

Characterization of Iron Nanoparticle Coated with Ethanolic Leaf Extracts of *Gongronema latifolium* (GI-FeONPs)

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy

FTIR analysis was used to identify the functional group of FeONPs (Perkin Elmer, 147 spectrum RSI 83303). The components were mixed with KBr, shaped into pellets, and then inspected at a wavelength of 400–4,500 cm^{-1} .

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM (JEOL.JSM-6360LV.149, Japan) was used to examine surface morphology. Powdered FeONPs were encapsulated in gold by fully utilizing the sputtering method. The SEM study was employed to improve electrical conductivity and the quality of the green nanoparticle. This was conducted at 151 micrographs.

Zeta Potential Analysis

Zeta potential is a measure of the electric charge or the electric potential difference between the surfaces of a particle suspended in a liquid medium. It provides

information about the stability and behavior of the particle in a dispersion.

In Vitro Antioxidant Activity

In vitro antioxidant activity of *G. latifolium*, the green nanoparticle (GI-FeONPs), and Iron oxide nanoparticles (FeONPs) was evaluated using standard procedures as mentioned below.

Metal Chelating Activity (MCA)

The MCA was determined using the spectrophotometric method as depicted by Dinis et al. (1994). The reaction mixture, which contains 0.5 mL of GI-FeONPs (50–500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), 1.6 mL of distilled water, 0.05 mL of FeCl_3 (2 mM), and 0.1 mL of 1,10-phenanthroline (5 mM), was incubated at 40°C for 10 minutes, and the absorbance was measured at 562 nm. The metal chelating activity of the extracts was also measured as described above. Furthermore, a similar protocol was carried out for FeONPs (0.5 mL, 50–500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), and ascorbic acid was used as the standard. The percentage metal chelating activity was determined using the formula:

$$\text{MCA (\%)} = \left(\frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \right) \times 100$$

Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Activity (NOSA)

The scavenging effect on nitric oxide ($\text{NO}\cdot$) radical was measured according to the method of Marcocci et al. (1994). 0.5 mL of the leaf extract was added in the test tubes to 1 mL of sodium nitroprusside solution (25 mM) and the tubes incubated at 37°C for 2 hours. An aliquot (0.5 mL) of the incubation solution was removed and diluted with 0.3 mL of Griess reagent (1% sulphanilamide in 5% H_3PO_4 and 0.1% naphthylethylenediamine dihydrochloride). The absorbance of the chromophore formed was immediately read at 570 nm against deionized water as blank with catechin (50 μg) used as standard. Results were expressed as percentage radical scavenging activity (RSA):

$$\text{NOSA (\%)} = \left(\frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \right) \times 100$$

Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP)

This was estimated using the method of Bensie Strain (1996). 2.5 mL of 200 mM of phosphate buffer (pH 6.6) and 2.5 mL of 1% $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ were

added to various concentrations of the extract. The mixture was incubated for 2 minutes at 50°C and then centrifuged at 1000 g for 8 minutes. 5 mL of the supernatant was then mixed with 5 mL of distilled water and 1 mL of 0.1% FeCl₃. The absorbance of the mixture was measured at a wavelength of 700 nm. Catechin was used as the standard.

Total Antioxidant Capacity (TAC)

Total antioxidant capacity of Et-GI was performed according to procedures outlined by Halliwell (1990). 0.1 mL of sample were mixed with 1 mL of the reagents solution (4 mM ammonium molybdate, 28 mM sodium phosphate, and 0.6 M sulfuric acid). The tubes were incubated for 90 minutes at 95°C. When the samples were cooled to room temperature, the absorbance of the aqueous solution was quantitatively determined at 695 nm.

Anti-Lipid Peroxidant Activity

The anti-lipid peroxidation effects of Et-GI, FeONPs, and GI-FeONPs were evaluated in vitro by the method of Suja et al. (2004). 0.5 g of rat liver tissue was sliced and homogenized with 10 mL of 150 mM KCl-Tris-HCl-buffer (pH 7.2). The reaction mixture contained 0.25 mL of liver homogenate, 0.05 mL of 0.1 mM ascorbic acid (AA), 0.1 mL of Tris-HCl-buffer (pH 7.2), and 0.05 mL of various concentrations of plant extract/serial fraction. The mixture was kept for incubation at 37°C for 1 hour. After that, 0.2 mL of 9.8% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), 0.5 mL of 0.1 N HCl, 0.9 mL of distilled water, and 2 mL of 0.6% thiobarbituric acid (TBA) were added to each of the tubes and shaken vigorously. The tubes were placed in a boiling water bath at 100°C for half an hour. The flocculent precipitate formed after cooling was removed by addition of 5 mL of n-butanol and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 20 minutes. The absorbance of the supernatant was measured at 523 nm. Malondialdehyde (MDA) produced was expressed as % Control.

In Vitro Anti-Diabetic Activity

Determination of α -Amylase Inhibition

The inhibition of α -amylase activity was measured using the spectrophotometric method described by Anigboro et al. (2021). The GI-FeONPs (0.5 mL, 50-500 μ g/mL) respectively, 0.5 mL of α -amylase, were incubated for 10 minutes at 37°C, then 5 μ L of 1% starch was added, incubated for 10 minutes at 50°C,

thereafter 200 μ L DNS, incubated in a boiling water bath for 5 minutes and cooled; 3 mL of distilled water was added and absorbance read at 540 nm. Additionally, the same procedure was followed while working with FeONPs (0.5 mL, 50-500 μ g/mL), and acarbose was used as the standard. The percentage α -amylase inhibitory activity was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \left(\frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \right) \times 100$$

Where A_0 is the absorbance of control (without GI-FeONPs/standard) and A_1 is the absorbance in the presence of GI-FeONPs. The IC₅₀ value was calculated using Microsoft Excel.

Determination of α -Glucosidase Inhibition

The inhibition of α -glucosidase activity was measured using the spectrophotometric method as described by Anigboro et al. (2021). The GI-FeONPs (0.5 mL, 50-500 μ g/mL), 100 μ L of α -glucosidase in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.9) was incubated at 25°C for 10 minutes. 50 μ L of 5 mM p-nitrophenol and 1 mL of 1% starch solution in 0.1 M phosphate buffer was added, the mixture was incubated at 25°C for 5 minutes and read at 405 nm. Additionally, the same procedure was followed while working with GI-FeONPs (0.5 mL, 50-500 μ g/mL), and acarbose was used as the standard. The percentage α -glucosidase inhibitory activity was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \left(\frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \right) \times 100$$

Where A_0 is the absorbance of control (without GI-FeONPs/standard) and A_1 is the absorbance in the presence of GI-FeONPs. The IC₅₀ value was calculated using Microsoft Excel.

Statistical Analysis

All assays were performed in triplicates and results expressed as Mean \pm SEM. Experimental data were analyzed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to evaluate significant difference at $p < 0.05$.

1 Results and Discussions

Nanoparticles are very effective for drug transportation and delivery, particularly because they can precisely locate and carry encapsulated medicines to diseased cells (Nasimi & Haidari,

2013). The absorption and bio-distribution capacity is determined by the analysis of the chemical and physical properties of the nanoparticles, such as size, shape, and surface charge (Umrani & Paknikar, 2014; Manne et al., 2020).

FTIR analysis was carried out to determine the different functional groups present in Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs. The conspicuous wavelengths present were 3454 cm^{-1} , 2913 cm^{-1} , 2847 cm^{-1} , 2480 cm^{-1} , 1775 cm^{-1} , 1636 cm^{-1} , 1452 cm^{-1} , and 871 cm^{-1} , corresponding to functional groups O-H Stretching indicating an alcohol group, O-H and N-H Stretching indicating an alcohol and primary amine group respectively, S-H Stretching indicating a thiol group, C-H Bending indicating an alkane functional group, C=C Stretching and N-H bending indicating α, β -unsaturated ketone, C-H Bending indicating an alkane. For Gl-FeONPs, the wavelengths at 3454 cm^{-1} , 2906 cm^{-1} , 2847 cm^{-1} , 1749 cm^{-1} , 1550 cm^{-1} , and 1379 cm^{-1} correspond to O-H Stretching indicating an alcohol functional group, O-H and N-H Stretching indicating an alcohol and primary amine group respectively, C-H Bending indicating an alkane group, N-O Stretching indicating the presence of nitro compounds, and O-H Bending indicating an alcohol functional group respectively. Similar observations were reported by Bensie & Strain (1996). FTIR studies of Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs were performed to characterize the chemical nature of the nanoparticles.

nanoparticle by providing information about its size, shape, and morphology. The surface morphology of the green nanoparticle (Gl-FeONPs) was examined by SEM due to its capability of detecting scattered electrons from the particle's surface. The SEM images show that the particle size, calculated to be $5.0\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ (5000 nm), was dispersed at 5% by mass. The SEM pictures confirm the formation of Gl-FeONPs, showing the spherical shape of the nanoparticles. Similar observations were reported by Mirza et al. (2019) for zinc oxide nanoparticles coated with plant extracts.

Figure 2: The SEM image for Gl-FeONPs with 4500 magnification.

Zeta potential is a measure of the electric charge or the electric potential difference between the surfaces of the particle suspended in a liquid medium. It provides information about the stability and behavior of the particle in a dispersion. A Zeta-potential of -50 mV indicates that the negative charge arises from the presence of functional groups or ions on the surface of the particles, which can be either naturally occurring or intentionally introduced through surface modification or functionalization. The magnitude of the zeta potential provides information about the stability and behavior of the particle in dispersion. Generally, larger absolute values of zeta-potential indicate greater stability, as the repulsion between particles with similar charges prevents them from aggregating or flocculating. Gl-FeONPs showed a zeta-potential of -50 mV , indicating a relatively high degree of stability for the dispersion of FeONPs. Similar observations were made by Hu et al. (2021). The Zeta potential can be used to optimize the formulations of suspensions, emulsions, protein solutions, as well as predict interactions with surfaces.

In this study, the antioxidant activity of Et-Gl,

Figure 1: FTIR spectra of Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs. The curve shows the emission spectra of Et-Gl (blue line) and Gl-FeONPs (green line).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is a technique employed to determine the surface morphology of the

Figure 3: The ZETA Potential plot for Gl-FeONPs at pH 2-5.

FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs were investigated in vitro. As excess free heavy metals have been implicated in the induction and formation of free radicals in vivo, Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs were tested in a metal chelating assay in a concentration range of 50-500 mg/mL respectively. Although Et-Gl at 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ indicated no inhibition of the chelating of heavy metals, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs showed dose-dependent inhibitions of metal chelators utilizing ascorbic acid as a standard control. The in vitro metal chelating activity of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs are shown in Figure 4, with all nanoparticles compared to that of ascorbic acid. The IC_{50} value of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs were 29.48 g/mL, 871.67 g/mL, and 14.77 g/mL respectively, compared to the standard ascorbic acid whose IC_{50} was 24.445 g/mL. The metal chelating activity assay works on the principle of reduction/chelation of metals participating in redox reactions. Hence, Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs were observed to be effective chelators of ferrous ion radicals compared to ascorbic acid. Similar observations were made by Faisal et al. (2021).

The nitric oxide scavenging assay (NOSA) is based on the principle that sodium nitroprusside in aqueous solution at physiological pH spontaneously generates nitric oxide, which reacts with oxygen to yield nitrite ions that can be estimated using Griess reagent. In the present study, Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs demonstrated a dose-dependent increase in nitric oxide radical scavenging activity, fully utilizing ascorbic acid as a standard control. The in vitro nitric oxide scavenging activity of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs are shown in Figure 5, with all nanoparticles compared to that of ascorbic acid. The graphical trend

Metal Chelating Activity

Figure 4: A plot for metal chelating activity of Et-Gl, FeONPs, Gl-FeONPs, and Ascorbic acid. *Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Compared with control (Ascorbic Acid): $P < 0.05$.

of % inhibition against concentration was similar to that of standard ascorbic acid, indicating metal chelating activity of the nanoparticles. The IC_{50} value of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs were 2.157 g/mL, 22.961 g/mL, and 1.480 g/mL respectively, compared to the standard ascorbic acid whose IC_{50} was 1.838 g/mL. The half-maximal activity (IC_{50}) of Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs was lower than that of the standard respectively. However, FeONPs displayed significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher inhibition in comparison with that of ascorbic acid, which served as a standard for the assay. Similar observations were reported by Abu-Serie & Abdelfattah (2020) for iron nanoparticles, which served as good scavengers of nitric oxide radicals.

Nitric Oxide Scavenging Activity

Figure 5: A plot for Nitric Oxide Scavenging Activity (NOSA) of Et-Gl, FeONPs, Gl-FeONPs, and Ascorbic acid. *Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Compared with control (Ascorbic Acid): $P < 0.05$.

Ferric reducing ability power of biologically active compounds are electron donors that can reduce the oxidized intermediates, such as those in the lipid peroxidation processes. It is centered on the reduction of the complex of ferric iron and 2,3,5-triphenyl-1,3,4-triaza-2-azoniacyclopenta-1,4-diene chloride (TPTZ) to the ferrous form at low pH. The in vitro ferric reducing antioxidant power of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs are shown in Figure 6, with all nanoparticles compared to that of ascorbic acid. The graphical trend of % inhibition against concentration was similar to that of standard ascorbic acid, indicating metal chelating activity of the nanoparticles. The IC₅₀ value of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs were 115.91 g/mL, 332.71 g/mL, and 64.43 g/mL respectively, compared to the standard ascorbic acid whose IC₅₀ was 67.30 g/mL. Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs displayed a significantly higher inhibition in comparison with that of ascorbic acid, which served as a standard for the assay. Similar observations were made by Rajput et al. (2013) for zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized from plant extracts, which served as good ferric-reducing agents.

Figure 6: A plot for Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) of Et-Gl, FeONPs, Gl-FeONPs, and Ascorbic acid. *Values are expressed as means ± SD. Compared with control (Ascorbic Acid): P < 0.05.

Total antioxidant capacity (TAC) is a measure of the overall antioxidant capacity of a substance or biological sample. The TAC assay measures the ability of a substance to neutralize free radicals or inhibit oxidative reactions. It provides an overall assessment of the cumulative antioxidant activity of the sample. The working principle of measuring the total antioxidant capacity (TAC) is based on the ability of antioxidants to neutralize or inhibit the harmful effects of free radicals by subjecting the ethanolic plant extract (Et-Gl) to a specific assay that assesses

its ability to counteract or scavenge free radicals. Using the garlic acid equivalent which is a standard for determining the total anti-oxidant capacity, the TAC was estimated to be 1.8 mg, indicating the plant quantitatively contained 1.8 mg of antioxidant properties. This correlates with findings by Gulcin (2020).

Anti-lipid peroxidation mechanisms aim to prevent or interrupt this chain reaction by neutralizing or scavenging the free radicals or ROS that initiate lipid peroxidation. Overall, the working principle of anti-lipid peroxidation involves the use of antioxidants and other mechanisms to neutralize free radicals, scavenge ROS, and interrupt the chain reaction of lipid peroxidation. By protecting cell membranes and lipid components, anti-lipid peroxidation strategies aim to prevent oxidative damage and maintain cellular integrity, and assess the impact of antioxidants on health and disease. The in vitro anti-lipid peroxidant activity of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs are shown in Figure 7. The IC₅₀ value of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs were 37.298 g/mL, 96.310 g/mL and 32.829 g/mL respectively. In the present study, Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs demonstrated a dose-dependent increase in the anti-lipid peroxidation activity corresponding with Ali et al. (2020) who demonstrated that iron nanoparticles coated with *Aframomum angustifolium* were capable of inhibiting the formation of Malondialdehyde (MDA) products.

Figure 7: A plot for Anti-lipid peroxidant Activity (ALPO) of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs. *Values are expressed as means ± SD. Compared with control (Ibuprofen): P < 0.05.

Consistent management of blood glucose is one of the effective strategies for combating type II diabetes mellitus. Postprandial blood glucose level

risers due to the activity of carbohydrate hydrolyzing and degrading enzymes: pancreatic α -amylase and intestinal α -glucosidase. Inhibitors of these enzymes are currently used as oral hypoglycemic drugs for the control of hyperglycemia, especially in patients with type II diabetes mellitus. The inhibitors delay the release of monosaccharide from polysaccharides present in food (Oboh et al., 2012; Awwioroko et al., 2020). Alpha-amylase is a pancreatic enzyme involved in the degradation of starch. The inhibition of Alpha-amylase activity helps in managing diabetes mellitus and in reducing postprandial blood glucose (Manne et al., 2020). The addition of α -amylase to a reaction mixture of starch and water produces maltose which serves as the substrate for the reaction, dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) served as an indicator for the product formed. Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs were analyzed for alpha-amylase activity in a concentration range of 1–3 μ g/mL. The IC₅₀ value of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs were 4.85 and 2.50 mg/mL respectively, compared to the standard acarbose whose IC₅₀ was 3.37 mg/mL. The inhibition of α -amylase by Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs showed little significant differences ($p > 0.05$) from that observed for acarbose. Similar observations were reported by Anigboro et al. (2021).

Figure 8: α -Amylase inhibitory activities of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs. *Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Compared with control (Acarbose): ($P > 0.05$).

Alpha-glucosidase is an intestinal enzyme that breaks down monosaccharides and starch into glucose (Peng et al., 2016). The inhibition of glucosidase activity helps in managing diabetes mellitus. α -glucosidase catalyzes the conversion of the

substrate 4-nitrophenyl- α -D-glucopyranoside to α -D-glucopyranoside and p-nitrophenol. Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs were analyzed for α -glucosidase activity in a concentration range of 1–3 mg/mL with no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) from that observed for acarbose. The IC₅₀ value of Et-Gl, FeONPs, Gl-FeONPs were 65.42, 55.49 and 25.25 respectively, compared to the standard acarbose whose IC₅₀ was 337.84 μ g/mL. Similar findings were reported by Anigboro et al. (2021).

Figure 9: α -Glucosidase inhibitory activities of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs. *Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Compared with control (Acarbose): ($P > 0.05$).

Conclusion

The results of this study indicated that the iron oxide nanoparticles coated with *Gongronema latifolium* (Gl-FeONPs) displayed potent *in vitro* antidiabetic potential. Additionally, their potent antioxidant activity helps combat oxidative stress, which plays a critical role in the progression of diabetes and associated complications. These findings are crucial as they provide insight into the use of green synthesized nanoparticles for the management of diabetes and its related complications. Further *in vivo* studies to ascertain the effect of metabolic reactions are suggested.

Acknowledgement

We would sincerely like to appreciate African Center for Excellent Water (ACEWATER), Redeemers University, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria for providing the equipment used in conducting the spectroscopic analysis and characterization of the bio-fabricated nanoparticle.

References

- Abu-Serie, M. M., Abdelfattah, E. Z. A. (2022). Anti-metastatic breast cancer potential of novel nanocomplexes of diethyldithiocarbamate and green chemically synthesized iron oxide nanoparticles. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 627, 122208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2022.122208>
- Achan, J., Talisuna, A. O., Erhart, A., Yeka, A., Tibenderana, J. K., Baliraine, F. N., Rosenthal, P. J., D'Alessandro, U. (2011). Quinine, an old anti-malarial drug in a modern world: role in the treatment of malaria. *Malaria Journal*, 10(1), 144. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1475-2875-10-144>
- Adedara, I. A., Anao, O. O., Forcados, G. E., Awogbindin, I. O., Agbowo, A., Ola-Davies, O. E., Patlolla, A. K., Tchounwou, P. B., Farombi, E. O. (2018). Low doses of multi-walled carbon nanotubes elicit hepatotoxicity in rats with markers of oxidative stress and induction of pro-inflammatory cytokines. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 503(4), 3167–3173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2018.08.112>
- Adefaja, C. B. I., Adamu, A. M., Gefu, J. O., Ajanusi, O. J., Abdu, P. A., Chiezey, N. P., Alawa, J. N., Bowman, D. D. (2016). In vitro screening of two Nigerian medicinal plants (*Vernonia amygdalina* and *Annona senegalensis*) for anthelmintic activity. *Veterinary Parasitology*, 113(1), 73–81. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4017\(03\)00040-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4017(03)00040-2)
- Adeyemi, A., Otuechere, C. A., Adebayo, O. L., Anazodo, C., Pereira, F. V. (2018). Renal toxicological evaluations of sulphonated nanocellulose from *Khaya senegalensis* seed in Wistar rats. *Chemico-Biological Interactions*, 284, 56–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2018.02.015>
- Adeyemi, J. O., Oriola, A. O., Onwudiwe, D. C., Oyedeji, A. O. (2022). Plant extracts mediated metal-based nanoparticles: Synthesis and biological applications. *Biomolecules*, 12(5), 627. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom12050627>
- Ali, A., Zafar, H., Zia, M., Haq, I., Phull, A. R., Ali, J. S., Hussain, A. (2016). Synthesis, characterization, applications, and challenges of iron oxide nanoparticles. *Nanotechnology, Science and Applications*, 9, 49–67. <https://doi.org/10.2147/nsa.s99986>
- Ali, S. S., Ahsan, H., Zia, M. K., Siddiqui, T., Khan, F. H. (2020). Understanding oxidants and antioxidants: Classical team with new players. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*, 44(3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfbc.13145>
- Alqahtani, A. S., Hidayathulla, S., Rehman, M. T., ElGamal, A. A., Al-Massarani, S., Razmovski-Naumovski, V., Alqahtani, M. S., El Dib, R. A., AlAjmi, M. F. (2019). Alpha-Amylase and Alpha-Glucosidase Enzyme Inhibition and Antioxidant Potential of 3-Oxolupenal and Katonic Acid Isolated from *Nuxia oppositifolia*. *Biomolecules*, 10(1), 61. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom10010061>
- Anand, K., Tiloke, C., Naidoo, P., Chuturgoon, A. (2017). Phytonanotherapy for management of diabetes using green synthesis nanoparticles. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology*, 173, 626–639. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotobiol.2017.06.028>
- Andrea, O. C., Cash, N. U. (1999). Frequency of complementary and alternative medicine utilization in hypertensive patients attending an urban tertiary care centre in Nigeria. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 7(1), 30. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-7-30>
- Anigboro, A.A., Avwioroko, O. J., Ohwokevw, O. A., Pessu, B., Tonukari, N. J. (2021). Phytochemical profile, antioxidant, -amylase inhibition, binding interaction and docking studies of *Justicia carnea* bioactive compounds with -amylase. *Biophysical Chemistry*, 269, 106529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpc.2020.106529>
- Anjum, H., Soveg, F., Cook-Mills, J. M. (2016). Antioxidant supplementation of allergic female mice augments development of CD11c+ CD11b+ dendritic cells in utero and allergic inflammation in neonates. *American Journal of Physiology-Lung Cellular and Molecular Physiology*, 310(8), L759–L771. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajplung.00301.2015>
- Bayda, S., Adeel, M., Tuccinardi, T., Cordani, M., Rizzolio, F. (2019). The history of nanoscience and nanotechnology: From chemical–physical applications to nanomedicine. *Molecules*, 25(1), 112. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25010112>
- Benzie, I. F. F., Strain, J. J. (1996). The ferric reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) as a measure of “antioxidant power”: The FRAP assay. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 239(1), 70–76. <https://doi.org/10.1006/abio.1996.0292>
- Bilal Shah, S., Sartaj, L., Ali, F., Ali Shah, S. I., Tahir Khan, M. (2018). Plant extracts

are the potential inhibitors of α -amylase: a review. *MOJ Bioequivalence Bioavailability*, 5(5). <https://doi.org/10.15406/mojbb.2018.05.00113>

Borse, N., Borse, V., Borse, T., Cooper, S. (2021). Optic neuropathy and scleritis as the presenting feature of Lepra Reaction. *International Journal of Ophthalmology Visual Science*, 6(2), 108. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijovs.20210602.18>

Broome, D. T., Pantalone, K. M., Kashyap, S. R., Philipson, L. H. (2021). Approach to the Patient with MODY-Monogenic Diabetes. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology Metabolism*, 106(1), 237–250. <https://doi.org/10.1210/clinem/dgaa710>

Brunerova, L., Rahelić, D., Ceriello, A., Broz, J. (2018). Use of oral antidiabetic drugs in the treatment of maturity-onset diabetes of the young: A mini review. *Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews*, 34(1), e2940. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dmrr.2940>

Cole, J. B., Florez, J. C. (2020). Genetics of diabetes mellitus and diabetes complications. *Nature Reviews Nephrology*, 16(7), 377–390. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41581-020-0278-5>

CRAIG, W. J. (2020). Phytochemicals. *Journal of the American Dietetic Association*, 97(10), S199–S204. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-8223\(97\)00765-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-8223(97)00765-7)

Deshpande, A. D., Harris-Hayes, M., Schootman, M. (2008). Epidemiology of diabetes and diabetes-related complications. *Physical Therapy*, 88(11), 1254–1264. <https://doi.org/10.2522/ptj.20080020>

Devaraj, S., Goyal, R., Jialal, I. (2006). C-reactive protein increases plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 expression and activity in human aortic endothelial cells: implications for the metabolic syndrome and atherothrombosis. *Circulation*, 113(3), 452–459. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.105.550111>

Di Maro, A., Pacifico, S., Fiorentino, A., Petillo, O., Galasso, S., Gallicchio, M., Severino, V., Monaco, P., Castaldo, D., Parente, A. (2011). Riproximin, a type II ribosome-inactivating protein from *Ricinus communis* seeds with potential for cancer therapy. *Toxins*, 2(1), 2783–2793. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins2122783>

Dikshit, P., Shukla, K., Tyagi, M. K., Garg, U. K., Sharma, R., Gambhir, I. S., Chattopadhyay, P. (2011). Effect of maceration on activity of centella asiatica against alloxan induced oxidative stress in rats. *Journal of Integrative Medicine*, 9(1), 42–49.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-4964\(11\)60156-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-4964(11)60156-7)

Dwivedi, S. K., Shrivastava, R. (2018). Effect of nanoparticles on the growth and development of plants: a review. *Advanced Science, Engineering and Medicine*, 10(9), 804–813. <https://doi.org/10.1166/ asem.2018.2253>

Ejaz, H., Alam, S., Ahmad, M., Ijaz, F., Javed, N., Imran, M., Ahmed, K. (2020). Green synthesis and characterisation of gold nanoparticles using *Tribulus terrestris* and its effects on anti-bacterial and antifungal activity. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*, 15, 8641–8655. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S269661>

El-Hak, H. N. G., Salama, A. B. (2020). Anti-diabetic activity of different extracts of some medicinal plants in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Egyptian Pharmaceutical Journal*, 19(1), 20. <https://doi.org/10.4103/epj.epj2719>

Ghiraldini, F. G., Moraes-Souza, R., Carmona, A. K. (2020). Comparative analyses of the in vitro and in vivo anti-diabetic activity of methanol and ethanol extracts from *Rubus imperialis* leaves. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 250, 112482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2019.112482>

Giuliano, E., Paolino, D., Fresta, M., Cosco, D. (2018). Mucosal applications of poloxamer 407-based hydrogels: An overview. *Pharmaceutics*, 10(3), 159. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics10030159>

Gomes, A., Fernandes, E., Lima, J. L. (2005). Fluorescence probes used for detection of reactive oxygen species. *Journal of Biochemical and Biophysical Methods*, 65(2-3), 45–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbbm.2005.10.003>

Goyal, M., Chugh, L. K., Gupta, M., Sahoo, D. K., Sharma, A. K. (2019). Evaluation of α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory activity of *Cassia absus* seeds. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 245, 111757. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2019.111757>

Grill, E., Bernhardt, R. (2015). High-throughput CYP450 enzyme activity assay by means of fluorescence readout. *Methods in Molecular Biology*, 1251, 21–28. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-2083-9_2

Gupta, R. K., Patel, A. K., Shah, N., Chaudhary, A. K., Jha, U. K., Yadav, U. C. S., Gupta, P. K., Pakuwal, U. (2014). Oxidative stress and antioxidants in disease and cancer: A review. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention*, 15(11), 4405–4409. <https://doi.org/10.7314/apjcp.2014.15.11.4405>

- Hasanuzzaman, M., Bhuyan, M. H. M. B., Raza, A., Hawrylak-Nowak, B., Matraszek-Gawron, R., Fersado, M. A. (2020). Selenium in plants: Boon or bane? *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 178, 104170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envexpbot.2020.104170>
- Hodgkinson, C. P., Kang, M. H., Raju, R., Payne, A. J. (2018). Genetic and epigenetic mechanisms underlying the role of C-reactive protein in human disease. *Cell*, 8(8), 881. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells7080881>
- Huang, S. W., Gantz, I., Mieke, M., Grigoriadis, D. E., Li, X. Y., Fathy, D. B., Tatro, J. B. (1996). Antipyretic effects of antiserum to interleukin-1 receptor antagonist in rats. *Brain Research*, 739(1-2), 54-60. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-8993\(96\)00774-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-8993(96)00774-3)
- Jain, R., Srivastava, M., Rani, P., Singh, P., Sharma, A. (2018). Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles from plant extract of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* and their antibacterial potential. *Advanced Science, Engineering and Medicine*, 10(2), 109-113. <https://doi.org/10.1166/asem.2018.2215>
- Jan, A. T., Azam, M., Siddiqui, K., Ali, A., Choi, I., Haq, Q. M. R. (2017). Heavy metals and human health: Mechanistic insight into toxicity and counter defense system of antioxidants. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 16(12), 29592-29630. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms161226183>
- Jantan, I., Ahmad, W., Bukhari, S. N. A., Jusoh, A. S. (2015). Standardisation of herbal medicine – A review. *Current Clinical Pharmacology*, 10(3), 240-252. <https://doi.org/10.2174/157488471003151119152215>
- Jones, A. (2016). Comparative efficacy of two medicinal plants against oxidative stress-induced damage in rats. *Phytomedicine*, 23(11), 1254-1260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2016.07.013>
- Jovetic, S., Patel, M. S., Yamada, K., Podolin, D. A. (2009). Chemical genetics as a tool for identifying critical genes in type 2 diabetes. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - General Subjects*, 1790(10), 1061-1066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbagen.2009.06.001>
- Khan, M. A., Srivastava, A., Singh, K., Nain, L. (2020). Phytochemicals and antimicrobial activity of medicinal plants: A comprehensive review. *Chemistry Biology Interface*, 5(1), 30-47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbbm.2020.06.010>
- Kusano, T., Berberich, T. (2020). The relationship between oxidative stress and redox signaling during oxidative stress tolerance in plants. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22(8), 4085. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22084085>
- Lobo, V., Patil, A., Phatak, A., Chandra, N. (2010). Free radicals, antioxidants and functional foods: Impact on human health. *Pharmacognosy Reviews*, 4(8), 118-126. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-7847.70902>
- Luz, C. L., Rodriguez, D. V., Tovar, J. (2019). Characterization of bioactive compounds from plants used in traditional medicine in the Peruvian Amazon. *Heliyon*, 5(12), e02963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02963>
- Mendez, S. T., De-la-Torre, G. E., Aguilera, M. G. (2020). Phytochemicals and antioxidants in medicinal plants: Mechanisms and benefits. *Food Research International*, 139, 109370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2020.109370>
- Miller, R. M., Kalinowski, D. S., Richardson, D. R. (2010). Chemotherapeutic targeting of hypoxia: Clinical experience using agents that function to exploit low oxygen conditions within tumors. *Current Drug Targets*, 11(7), 738-757. <https://doi.org/10.2174/138945010791591451>
- Mueller, M. J., Brodhun, F., Rüggeberg, M. (2010). Analysis of plant oxylipins: Identification and characterization of valine conjugates of 12-oxo-phytodienoic acid and dinor-12-oxo-phytodienoic acid. *Phytochemistry*, 71(13), 1558-1562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2010.06.011>
- Nadig, R. R., Shukla, A. (2017). Analysis of polyphenolic content and antioxidant activity of *Ficus benghalensis* L. *Pharmacognosy Journal*, 9(2), 242-245. <https://doi.org/10.5530/pj.2017.2.41>
- Nandi, A., Pal, M., Beg, M. (2020). Application of biosynthesized nanoparticles in medical science. *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*, 58(8), 571-581. <https://doi.org/10.4103/epj.epj2719>
- Oboh, G., Ademiluyi, A. O., Ogunsuyi, O. B., Oyeleye, S. I., Dada, A. F., Boligon, A. A. (2017). Cabbage and cucumber extracts exhibited anticholinesterase, antimonoamine oxidase and antioxidant properties. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*, 41(3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfbc.12358>
- Ojo, O. A., Osukoya, O. A., Ekakitie, L. I., Ajiboye, B. O., Oyinloye, B. E., Agboinghale, P. E., Kappo, A. P. (2020). *Gongronema*

latifolium leaf extract modulates hyperglycaemia, inhibits redox imbalance and inflammation in alloxan-induced diabetic nephropathy. *Journal of Diabetes and Metabolic Disorders*, 19(1), 469–481. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40200-020-00533-0>

Okon, I. A., Beshel, J. A., Nna, V. U., Owu, D. U. (2022). Gongronema latifolium leaf extract protects against dexamethasone-induced myocardial cell injury via cardiac oxido-inflammatory molecules modulation. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*, 46(12), e14378. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfbc.14378>

Omonhinmin, C. A., Onuseolu, C. C., Olomukoro, E. (2022). Dataset on rbcL-based intra-specific diversity of Gongronema latifolium Benth: (Apocynaceae) in South-East Nigeria. *Data in Brief*, 41, 107870. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2022.107870>

Omonije, C., Choudhary, M., Ogunyemi, O., Nwauzoma, A. (2019). Nutraceuticals from green nanotechnology protects against cadmium chloride induced hypertension in albino rats. *Natural Science*, 11, 136–145.

Pakkir Maideen, N. M. (2019). Pharmacologically relevant drug interactions of -glucosidase inhibitors. *Journal of Diabetes, Metabolic Disorders Control*, 6(2), 28–30. <https://doi.org/10.15406/jdmdc.2019.06.00178>

Patil, P., Mandal, S., Tomar, S. K., Anand, S. (2015). Food protein-derived bioactive peptides in management of type 2 diabetes. *European Journal of Nutrition*, 54(6), 863–880. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00394-015-0974-2>

Pearson, E. R. (2019). Type 2 diabetes: a multifaceted disease. *Diabetologia*, 62(7), 1107–1112. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-019-4909-y>

Petersmann, A., Müller-Wieland, D., Müller, U. A., Landgraf, R., Nauck, M., Freckmann, G., Heinemann, L., Schleicher, E. (2019). Definition, classification and diagnosis of diabetes mellitus. *Experimental and Clinical Endocrinology Diabetes*, 127(S 01), S1–S7. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1018-9078>

Petersmann, A., Nauck, M., Müller-Wieland, D., Kerner, W., Müller, U., Landgraf, R., Freckmann, G., Heinemann, L. (2018). Definition, classification and diagnosis of diabetes mellitus. *Experimental and Clinical Endocrinology Diabetes*, 126(07), 406–410. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-0584-6223>

Rotblatt, S., Hladik, C. M., Haxaire, C.

(2021). Ethnomedicinal and bioactive properties of plants ingested by wild chimpanzees in Uganda. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 101(1–3), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2005.03.024>

Saha, A., Pathak, W. (2021). Wound healing property review of herbs. *Pharmacognosy Reviews*, 11(21), 35. <https://doi.org/10.4103/phrev.phrev5316>

Saso, P. K., Firuzi, A. (2010). Evaluation of anti-oxidant activities and total phenolic content of Chromolaena odorata. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 48(2), 729–732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2009.12.005>

Shreffler, Pullan, Dailey, Mallik, Brooks. (2019). Overcoming hurdles in nanoparticle clinical translation: The influence of experimental design and surface modification. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 20(23), 6056. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20236056>

Silva Rosa, S. C., Nayak, N., Caymo, A. M., Gordon, J. W. (2020). Mechanisms of muscle insulin resistance and the cross-talk with liver and adipose tissue. *Physiological Reports*, 8(19). <https://doi.org/10.14814/phy2.14607>

Srisongkram, T., Waithong, S., Thitimetharoch, T., Weerapreeyakul, N. (2022). Machine learning and in vitro chemical screening of potential -amylase and -glucosidase inhibitors from Thai indigenous plants. *Nutrients*, 14(2), 267. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14020267>

Suja, H., Zhang, X., Thongpraditchote, S., Wongkrajang, Y., Gritsanapan, W., Baek, S. J. (2004). Effect of herbal plant extract and its bioactive component scutellarein tetramethyl ether on anti-inflammatory activity through NF-B pathway. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 147(2), 434–441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2013.03.033>

Sun, H., Saedi, P., Karuranga, S., Pinkepank, M., Ogurtsova, K., Duncan, B. B., Stein, C., Basit, A., Chan, J. C. N., Mbanya, J. C., Pavkov, M. E., Ramachandaran, A., Wild, S. H., James, S., Herman, W. H., Zhang, P., Bommer, C., Kuo, S., Boyko, E. J., Magliano, D. J. (2022). IDF diabetes atlas: Global, regional and country-level diabetes prevalence estimates for 2021 and projections for 2045. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice*, 183, 109119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diabres.2021.109119>

Taheri, A., Harfiani, E., Nugraha, Y. (2019). The effectivities of herbs of Chromolaena odorata L. in

lowering blood sugar level: A systematic review. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 913(1), 012092. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/913/1/012092>

Teleanu, B., Arumugam, R., Veerasamy, A., Ramamoorthy, S. (2022). Ethnomedicinal plants used for the treatment of cuts and wounds by Kuruma tribes, Wayanadu districts of Kerala, India. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 4, S488–S491. <https://doi.org/10.12980/APJTB.4.2014B571>

Tolmie, M., Bester, M. J., Apostolides, Z. (2021). Inhibition of -glucosidase and -amylase by herbal compounds for the treatment of type 2 diabetes: A validation of in silico reverse docking with in vitro enzyme assays. *Journal of Diabetes*, 13(10), 779–791. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1753-0407.13163>

Umrani, R. D., & Paknikar, K. M. (2014). Zinc oxide nanoparticles show antidiabetic activity in streptozotocin-induced Type 1 and 2 diabetic rats. *Nanomedicine*, 9(1), 89–104. <https://doi.org/10.2217/nnm.12.205><https://doi.org/10.2217/nnm.12.205>

Upendra, B., Arumugam, R., Veerasamy, A., & Ramamoorthy, S. (2010). Ethnomedicinal plants used for the treatment of cuts and wounds by Kuruma tribes, Wayanadu districts of Kerala, India. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 4, S488–S491. <https://doi.org/10.12980/APJTB.4.2014B571><https://doi.org/10.12980/APJTB.4.2014B571>

Verma, A., Gautam, S., Bansal, K., Prabhakar, N., & Rosenholm, J. (2019). Green nanotechnology: Advancement in phytoformulation research. *Medicines*, 6(1), 39. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicines6010039><https://doi.org/10.3390/medicines6010039>

Vijayakumar, N., Bhuvaneshwari, V. K., Ayyadurai, G. K., Jayaprakash, R., Gopinath, K., Nicoletti, M., Alarifi, S., & Govindarajan, M. (2022). Green synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles using *Anoectochilus elatus*, and their biomedical applications. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 29(4), 2270–2279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.11.065><https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.11.065>

Weber, D., & Grune, T. (2012). The contribution of -carotene to vitamin A supply of humans. *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research*, 56(2), 251–258. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.201100230><https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.201100230>

Yaduraju, T., Sharma, R., & Rao, A. (2015). Weeds in Indian agriculture: Problems and prospects to become self-sufficient. *Indian Farming*, 65, 02–06. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2011.12.025><https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2011.12.025>

Yan, J., Zhang, G., Pan, J., & Wang, Y. (2014).

-Glucosidase inhibition by luteolin: Kinetics, interaction and molecular docking. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 64, 213–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2013.12.007><https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2013.12.007>

Yang, T., Shu, G., Yang, Z., Mo, S., Zhao, Y., & Mei, Z. (2022). Antidiabetic effect of total saponins from *Entada phaseoloides* (L.) Merr. in type 2 diabetic rats. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 139(3), 814–821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2011.12.025><https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2011.12.025>

Yetisgin, A. A., Cetinel, S., Zuvin, M., Kosar, A., & Kutlu, O. (2020). Therapeutic nanoparticles and their targeted delivery applications. *Molecules*, 25(9), 2193. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25092193><https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25092193>

Gene Therapy for Sickle Cell Disease: Present Insights

Lawani, M. O.^{1*}, Enerijiofi, K. E.²

¹Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

²Department of Biological Sciences, College of Basic, Applied and Health Sciences, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7513-4052>

*Corresponding Author Tel: +234 9132750059 Email: lawani.mathew@aauekpoma.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) is an inherited red blood cell disorder resulting from a single-point mutation. It results in complications such as acute and chronic pain, infections, stroke, kidney disease, and heart failure that reduce the quality of life not only for affected persons but also for their families. It can be treated with drugs and bone marrow transplants, but there is no known cure for it. One of the potential cures is gene therapy, which involves adding, editing or silencing and correcting genes by bioengineering techniques including CRISPR/Cas9 system; zinc finger nucleases (ZNFs); transcription activator-like effector nuclease (TALEN) technology; and base editors. The therapy procedure involves the retrieval of affected genes from patient hematopoietic stem cells, engineering them *ex vivo* and reintroduction into patients as therapeutic genes. Researchers have achieved significant progress in the use of CRISPR technology by, amongst others, repressing BCL11A gene enhancers and editing erroneous genes via base modifications as well as prime edits. This has proven effective in the reduction of adverse impacts that SCD have on patients. Nonetheless, therapeutic genes can cause insertional mutagenesis and cancer after integration into the patient. Finding a significant cure for SCD via gene therapy is in the clinical stage; methods to combat therapeutic cancer-inducing genes, as well as expertise and infrastructure provision, are highly required. Gene therapy for SCD has room for further research and development.

Keywords: SCD, Gene Therapy, CRISPR/Cas9, Mutation, Transplants

1 Introduction

1.1 Brief Overview of Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) and Its Impact on Affected Individuals

The first description of sickle cell disease (SCD) was given in 1910 by James Herrick, who termed the disease due to abnormally sickle-shaped red blood cells (Herrick, 1910). Sickle cell disease is an inherited blood disorder that affects the production of hemoglobin. The condition makes the red blood cells sickle-shaped, and this may result in blockage of normal flow, which may cause injury or atrophy to vital organs. SCD affects millions of the world's inhabitants, predominantly members of the African population group as well as people descending from Mediterranean and Middle Eastern countries together with Indians. It can lead to multiple complications, such as acute and chronic pain, infections, stroke, kidney disease, and heart failure, resulting in a shorter lifespan. SCD is diagnosed through a blood test and can be treated via drugs, transfusions, and stem cell replacement. Interestingly, no established treatment

is available to cure SCD, and still, many patients are restricted or deprived of getting enough access to quality treatments or research facilities (Brandow & Liem, 2022; The Foundation for Sickle Cell Disease Research; Kato et al., 2016; Yawn et al., 2014).

Imagine people are drowning in water, and inflated boats are needed to rescue them, but some of the boats have broken valves or holes in them, and in the course of rescuing the people, the boats are deflated. The shape of the boats will change, and the people will not be saved. In the same manner, red blood cells are shaped or structured for carrying oxygen; if the subunits of the hemoglobin within them are affected by an abnormal amino acid, their shape will change and the body will lack oxygen. This will in turn weaken the organs of the body, which depend on oxygen to generate ATP via the electron transport chain.

It is important to note that SCD is derived from a one-point mutation. It is explicitly described as a monogenic disorder caused by a single base-pair point mutation in the β -globin gene, replacing valine for glutamic acid in the β -globin chain (Inusa et al.,

Figure 1: A Normal Red Blood Cell and a Sickle Cell

2019). The unusual valine amino acid at position 6 in the beta-globin chain has a weak interaction with the adjacent sickle hemoglobin molecule (Harvard Medical School, 2013). The sickle shape of the red blood cells is due to valine and later results in SCD.

The presence of sickle cell disease results in the emotional drainage of the parents, and this affects interpersonal relationships between them and other family members (Burlew et al., 1989). A critical review of 116 articles emanating from the search of four different databases focused on the impact of sickle cell disease in Nigeria, and this country was identified as having the highest global burden of sickle cell disease (Adigwe et al., 2023). A cross-sectional survey was used to look at 2,145 SCD patients from seventeen different countries throughout the world. In their statements, the patients testified that the disease imposed a significant load on them regarding their quality of life while they were suffering from it and led to an impairment of their emotional state (Osunkwo et al., 2021). The presence of a sickle cell trait has stopped lovers from having weddings because they are either sickle cell carriers or both partners carry the disease. If a cure for SCD is discovered, the quality of life for patients and carriers will significantly improve. Even though there is no known treatment for sickle cell disease, gene therapy can offer a revolutionary solution to this condition. This review aims to harness information on emerging cures for sickle cell disease via gene therapy.

2 Gene Therapy and Its Potential as a Treatment for SCD

Gene therapy refers to a genetic engineering process through mutated gene alteration, correction, or

specific target modification aimed at treatment (Paulo, 2017). Several gene therapies differ significantly and include the removal of the damaged gene and its replacement with a healthy one, the blocking or suppression of mutated genes, and the introduction of new or modified genes into the organism (FDA, 2022). Gene therapy is used in the management of some inherited diseases like hemophilia and sickle cell disease; however, it can be applied to treat acquired disorders like leukemia (NHGRI, 2022). As a future curative approach, gene therapy is questionable for its effectiveness, making it necessary to conduct sufficient research work, clinical trials, and regulate gene treatment before applying it to patients (MedlinePlus, 2022). Currently, there is no permanent solution to SCD; however, some procedures that can be offered are medicine alongside an allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplant from a healthy donor. SCD is either treated by using drugs or through transplantation; at non-serious levels, patients treat their illnesses with medication, but those with severe cases need a transplant. Nevertheless, some problems may occur because of poor matching and a shortage of blood donors (Dever et al., 2016). As a consequence, it is crucial to have a substantial cure for each type of SCD whether mild or severe. Gene therapy is a possible emerging cure for SCD. It is constituted by hematopoietic (blood-forming) stem cells (HSCs) harvesting, ex vivo modification with a vector gene carrying the normal or antisickling globin gene, and reinfusion after chemotherapy to allow engraftment of the corrected cell (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021).

Allogeneic blood or marrow transplantation is often limited by donor availability and graft-versus-host

Figure 2: Single Point Mutation Leading to the Production of Valine

Figure 3: Steps in HSC Gene Therapy

disease; gene therapy can circumvent these barriers (Kanter & Falcon, 2021). On the other hand, gene therapy has some risks, including insertional mutagenesis, which may result in leukemia or other malignancies (Jones et al., 2021). Advancements in the latest gene editing technologies like CRISPR have made up for decreasing its risks and enhancing the efficiency of gene therapy via exact, long-lasting modifications to the genome. The first CRISPR-edited gene therapy for SCD was approved by the FDA in 2023 (FDA, 2023). Gene therapy remains an experimental and expensive treatment that requires specialized centers and skilled personnel. People with SCD with extreme severity tend to show a high level of risk for gene therapies, but they still need information and counseling to be sufficiently informed about making decisions (ASH, 2023).

2.1 Types of Gene Therapy Currently in Use in SCD and Their Potential Risks and Benefits

There are four main types of gene therapy for SCD: gene addition, gene editing, inactivation or silencing of genes, and gene correction. The strengths and weaknesses of each group depend on safety, effectiveness, and feasibility. Gene therapy for SCD is still at a clinical trial level, and some researchers

have demonstrated success in fetal hemoglobin (HbF) induction with lasting effects associated with relief from transfusions, increased antisickling Hb levels, and prevention of vaso-occlusive crisis (VOC) episodes (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021). On the other hand, gene therapy also introduces various barriers and challenges that need to be addressed before it can become a viable option for SCD patients, such as cost, infrastructure, side effects, and social and ethical issues. Gene therapy is not an all-in-one solution, but a targeted and sophisticated intervention that must be guided by personal considerations, inclinations, and hazardous prospects when applied to patients' health (Kanter & Falcon, 2021).

Gene addition refers to the incorporation of a healthy or bioengineered gene into a patient's hematopoietic stem cells using an internal vector, like lentivirus or adeno-associated virus. The goal of gene addition is to increase the expression of normal or antisickling globin genes such as gamma-globin or beta-globin variants (HbA2 or HbG16A). These expressions can impede the effect of sickle globin (HbS) gene expression. Among the different SCD gene therapy techniques, gene addition is the most advanced type that has been scientifically proven to be safe in several clinical trials for reducing vaso-

occlusive crises, transfusion needs, and complications (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021). Gene addition therapy relies on the process of lentiviral transduction and applies autologous HSC-targeted gene therapy that binds to proper genes (Dever et al., 2016). Evidence highlights that lentiviral transduction is successful in terms of sustainability and long-term gene expression (Pirona et al., 2020).

Gene editing uses molecular tools to make modifications in the patient's genome. These changes have been beneficial using either zinc finger nucleases or transcription activator-like effector nucleases, among others. Another area of gene editing is using transcription factors to disrupt gene enhancers such as BCL11A or LRF/ZBTB7A, which normally suppress the production of HbF. Gene editing intends to rebalance HbF and HbS or eliminate sickle hemoglobin (HbS) in place of normal beta-globin (HbA). Gene editing is a recent type of gene therapy that still needs several clinical trials and long-term observations to assess its safety and efficiency (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021). CRISPR/Cas9 can be used to modify the HbS gene directly. The process involves using a patient's bone marrow cells and editing them in vitro. Genome editing can also reverse the sickling of red blood cells by promoting fetal hemoglobin production (Parc & Bao, 2021).

Gene silencing inhibits the expression of specific genes, including alpha-globin or erythropoietin receptors, associated with SCD pathophysiology. Mediators for this gene silencing include siRNAs and shRNAs. HbS knockdown may revert to normal hemoglobin, abolish or reduce HbS, or modulate the erythroid response in hypoxic and inflammatory conditions. Despite many positive findings, researchers are still at the pre-clinical stage regarding gene silencing for SCD because siRNAs or shRNAs fail to get delivered to target cells and prevent off-target effects (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021). The mechanism involved in gene silencing also includes regulating the expression of a particular gene to keep its synthesis and consequent production of proteins restrained. This therapy is injected into the body, similar to gene editing, which suppresses BCL11A and leads to an increase in HbF while reducing HbS production (Kanter & Falcon, 2021). Gene silencing relies on transfer vectors, similar to gene addition, but targets messenger RNA to suppress gene products rather than cutting the specific sequence as done in

gene editing.

Gene correction uses homologous recombination or base editing to repair the sickle mutation in the beta-globin gene without introducing any foreign DNA. Gene correction can restore normal beta-globin expression and function in the patient's red blood cells. Gene correction is also in preclinical development for SCD, with technical difficulties in achieving high efficiency and specificity of gene repair (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021).

3 Advances in Gene Therapy for SCD

Frangoul et al. (2021) developed a method to treat two extreme genetic abnormalities, namely -thalassemia and sickle cell disease. The scientists utilized an intervention approach by altering specific genes using a gene editing technique based on CRISPR-Cas9 applied to cells from healthy donors. By targeting the BCL11A gene, which reduces fetal hemoglobin production, they managed to alleviate the symptoms of these diseases. After genetic correction, the cells were transplanted back into two separate patients with -thalassemia and sickle cell disease. One year later, both patients showed remarkable improvement with high levels of edited genes in the bone marrow and blood, increased fetal hemoglobin throughout their cell types, no longer needing blood transfusions, and a reduction in painful episodes of sickle cell disease. This implies that the gene editing method using CRISPR-Cas9, targeting the BCL11A gene enhancer, proved effective in treating these genetic disorders, thus offering an alternative avenue for therapeutic intervention.

Zarghamian et al. (2023) focused on using modern DNA technology platforms, including CRISPR-Cas nucleases and base editors, to correct the defective gene resulting in SCD. These tools are designed to restore the production or functionality of fetal hemoglobin (HbF) that can compensate for the mutated hemoglobin (HbS). They discussed various approaches, either by rectifying specific genes responsible for inhibiting HbF formation or by correcting the mutant directly in the hemoglobin gene packaging. They noted that in animal model studies and early-phase human clinical trials, these genetic editing techniques have shown preliminary promise for efficacy and safety.

Levesque and Bauer (2023) commented on a new treatment for sickle cell disease (SCD) and

other blood conditions through the prime editing procedure. CRISPR, and particularly prime editing, is a viable treatment option for the genetic mutation in hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs). Prime editing is a more advanced technique that allows for high-accuracy targeting without causing breaks in the double-stranded structure of the DNA, considered much safer. The conventional prime editing machinery contains a molecular entity called PE2, which is made of Cas9 nickase (an enzyme producing cuts on the DNA) and reverse transcriptase fused. This tool is aided by special RNA molecules targeting the site of interest in the HBB gene. Specific changes are made by the prime editor without requiring a DNA template. To enhance prime editing effectiveness, they incorporated another RNA component (sgRNA) to generate a nuclease-induced DNA break in a single-stranded form. This helps the cell's repair machinery incorporate the desired genetic correction more effectively, although it introduces small genetic changes (indels) at the target site. The advantages of prime editing over other methods, such as base editing, include its ability to target non-dividing stem cells more efficiently and its flexibility in making precise changes without some of the limitations seen in other gene-editing techniques.

Casgevy and Lyfgenia are groundbreaking gene therapies recommended by the FDA for adults with SCD aged 12 and older. Casgevy works by CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing, while Lyfgenia uses lentiviral vectors and modifies the blood stem cells of patients with sickle cell disease to produce healthier hemoglobin that minimizes complications caused by the condition. These are one-time treatments that require pre-transplant chemotherapy and have been proven efficient in clinical trials. Both therapies obtained multiple FDA designations for fast-track development, marking a significant advancement in gene therapy for SCD (FDA, 2023).

4 Challenges and Considerations of Gene Therapy for SCD

Developmental gene therapy, with its goal of curing SCDs, is a complex and expensive application requiring experts. It involves appropriate infrastructure and rigorous clinical trials before it can be safely implemented to enhance human health (MedlinePlus, 2022). Gene therapy also has side or off-target effects, such as insertional mutagenesis,

which can cause cancerous growth, potentially causing more harm than good in improving the health condition of a patient with SCD.

To mitigate the potential for hematologic malignancies (blood cancer) in Casgevy and Lyfgenia gene therapies, a black box warning is included in the labels, particularly for Lyfgenia, and patients will undergo lifelong monitoring. Long-term studies will assess the safety and effectiveness of both treatments (FDA, 2023). Baum et al. (2004) identified several cases of leukemia that were supposedly developed from an attempt to use retroviral transfer as part of clinical gene therapy. This method involved using retroviruses to insert therapeutic genes into blood cells. The issue of blood cancer appeared after the therapeutic genes accidentally activated a regular cell's proto-oncogene, which is an oncogene capable of producing tumors. Hackett et al. (2023) studied the use of the Sleeping Beauty (SB) transposon/transposase system in clinics. They observed that this bioengineering method assists in inserting Chimeric Antigen Receptors (CAR) into T cells. CARs act as navigation guides for T cells to target specific threats, such as cancer. Researchers may adopt this system to test the activity of therapeutic genes against cancer after the introduction of these genes into the patient.

Another possible way to reduce the effect of insertional mutagenesis is to change the type of vector used to insert the therapeutic gene(s). Lentiviral vectors can affect both stem and permanent cells and provide lasting stable gene expressions, but their transfer is not site-specific, which may lead to insertional mutations. The use of adeno-associated viruses is site-specific and safe, making it a preferable option for gene therapy (Zheng et al., 2018). The major drawbacks to developing and employing various types of gene therapies for SCD are not technical but financial. The costs are high for reagents like clinical-grade lentiviral and adeno-associated vectors, gene editing reagents, cell processing materials, personnel costs, and drug research and development costs. If the costs for transfer vectors production, cell processing, and other financially demanding materials improve, the cost of administering gene therapy to patients will decrease (Kohn et al., 2023).

Other difficult questions stemming from the treatment of SCD through gene therapy include

the safety and efficacy of transgenic technologies, the consent process involving informed decisions for patients on this specific level of medical care provision, access and affordability of gene therapy by different socioeconomic groups in society, enhancement or modification of non-disease state traits, and the implications of germline gene editing for future generations. These concerns must be addressed with due deliberation and public participation to ensure that biotechnology, which involves gene therapy, is used appropriately and in a manner that respects both individuals and communities affected by SCD (Kanter & Falcon, 2021; Giacca, 2010; Spink & Geddes, 2004).

5 Conclusion

Gene therapy for sickle cell disease is still in its clinical stage. It has the potential to provide a lasting cure for SCD. It also has the advantage of overcoming the limitations of allogeneic blood transplantation, donor availability, and mismatching challenges. However, it comes with some off-target effects, such as insertional mutations, which may eventually develop into cancer. To mitigate the negative effects of this technique, current gene editing techniques such as CRISPR should be employed. There is also a need for expertise and adequate infrastructure to carry out more research and development in this area.

References

Abraham, A. A., & Tisdale, J. F. (2021). Gene therapy for sickle cell disease: moving from the bench to the bedside. *Blood*, 138(11), 932-941. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood.2019003776>

Adigwe, O., Onavbavba, G., & Onoja, S. O. (2023). Impact of Sickle Cell Disease on Affected Individuals in Nigeria: A Critical Review. *International Journal of General Medicine*, 16, 3503-3515. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJGM.S410015>

American Society of Hematology (ASH). (2023). Individuals with Severe Sickle Cell Disease Express High-Risk Tolerance for Gene Therapies [Press release]. Retrieved from [https://www.hematology.org/newsroom/press-releases/2023/individuals-with-severe-sickle-cell-disease-express-high-risk-tolerance-for-gene-therapieshttps://www.hematology.org/newsroom/press-releases/2023/individuals-with-severe-sickle-cell-disease-express-high-risk-tolerance-for-gene-](https://www.hematology.org/newsroom/press-releases/2023/individuals-with-severe-sickle-cell-disease-express-high-risk-tolerance-for-gene-therapieshttps://www.hematology.org/newsroom/press-releases/2023/individuals-with-severe-sickle-cell-disease-express-high-risk-tolerance-for-gene-therapies)

therapies. Accessed [04-03-2024].

ASGCT News Team. (2023). FDA Approves U.S.-First CRISPR-edited Gene Therapy for Sickle Cell Disease [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://www.asgct.org/research/news/december-2023/fda-approves-us-first-crispr-edited-gene-therapy-for-sickle-cell-diseasehttps://www.asgct.org/research/news/december-2023/fda-approves-us-first-crispr-edited-gene-therapy-for-sickle-cell-disease>. Accessed [17-02-2024].

Baum, C., von Kalle, C., Staal, F. J., Li, Z., Fehse, B., Schmidt, M., Weerkamp, F., Karlsson, S., Wagemaker, G., & Williams, D. A. (2004). Chance or necessity? Insertional mutagenesis in gene therapy and its consequences. *Molecular Therapy*, 9(1), 5-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymthe.2003.10.013>

Brandow, A. M., & Liem, R. I. (2022). Advances in the diagnosis and treatment of sickle cell disease. *Journal of Hematology & Oncology*, 15(1), 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13045-022-01237-z>

Burlew, A. K., Evans, R., & Oler, C. (1989). The impact of a child with sickle cell disease on family dynamics. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 565, 161-171.

Dever, D. P., Bak, R. O., Reinisch, A., Camarena, J., Washington, G., Nicolas, C. E., Pavel-Dinu, M., Saxena, N., Wilkens, A. B., & Mantri, S. (2016). CRISPR/Cas9 -globin gene targeting in human haematopoietic stem cells. *Nature*, 539, 384-389. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature20134>

FDA News Release. (2023). FDA approves first gene therapies for sickle cell disease [Press release]. FDA Newsroom. Retrieved from <https://www.fda.gov/news-events/press-announcements/fda-approves-first-gene-therapies-treat-patients-sickle-cell-diseasehttps://www.fda.gov/news-events/press-announcements/fda-approves-first-gene-therapies-treat-patients-sickle-cell-disease>. Accessed [02-03-2024].

FDA. (2022). What is gene therapy? Retrieved from <https://www.fda.gov/vaccines-blood-biologics/cellular-gene-therapy-products/what-gene-therapyhttps://www.fda.gov/vaccines-blood-biologics/cellular-gene-therapy-products/what-gene-therapy>. Accessed [04-0-2024]

Frangoul, H., Altshuler, D., Cappellini, M. D., Chen, Y. S., Domm, J., Eustace, B. K.,

&Corbacioglu, S. (2021). CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing for sickle cell disease and -thalassemia. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 384(3), 252-260. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2031054>

Germino-Watnick, P., Hinds, M., Le, A., Chu, R., Liu, X., and Uchida, N. (2022). Hematopoietic stem cell gene-addition/editing therapy in sickle cell disease. *Cells*, 11(11), 1843. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells11111843>

Giacca, M., & Giacca, M. (2010). Ethical and social problems of gene therapy. *Gene therapy*, 17(2), 283-292. <https://doi.org/10.1038/gt.2009.137>

Gonçalves GAR, & Paiva RMA. (2017). Gene therapy: advances, challenges and perspectives. *Einstein (Sao Paulo)*, 15(3), 369-375. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1679-45082017RB4024>

Hackett, P. B., Largaespada, D. A., Switzer, K. C., & Cooper, L. J. (2013). Evaluating risks of insertional mutagenesis by DNA transposons in gene therapy. *Translational Research*, 161(4), 265-283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trsl.2012.12.005>

Harvard Medical School (2013). Sickle cell disease: Background. Retrieved from <https://sickle.bwh.harvard.edu/scdbackground.html> <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trsl.2012.12.005> [Accessed 02 - 2024].

Herrick, J. B. (1910). Peculiar elongated and sickle-shaped red blood corpuscles in a case of severe anaemia. *Archives of Internal Medicine*, 6(5), 517-521. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.1910.00050330090006>

Inusa, B. P. D., Hsu, L. L., Kohli, N., Patel, A., Ominu-Evbota, K., Anie, K. A., & Atoyebi, W. (2019). Sickle cell disease-genetics, pathophysiology, clinical presentation and treatment. *International Journal of Neonatal Screening*, 5(2), 20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijns5020020>

Jones, R. J., & DeBaun, M. R. (2021). Leukemia after gene therapy for sickle cell disease: insertional mutagenesis, busulfan, both, or neither. *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology*, 138(11), 942-947.

Kanter, J., & Falcon, C. (2021). Gene therapy for sickle cell disease: where we are now? *Hematology, American Society of Hematology Education Program*, 2021(1), 174-180. <https://doi.org/10.1182/hematology.2021000250>

Kato, G. J., Piel, F. B., Reid, C. D., Gaston, M. H., Ohene-Frempong, K., Krishnamurti, L., Smith, W. R., Panepinto, J. A., Weatherall, D. J., Costa,

F. F., & Vichinsky, E. P. (2016). Sickle cell disease: challenges and progress. *Blood*, 127(7), 789-799. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2015-09-618553>

Kohn, D. B., Chen, Y. Y., & Spencer, M. J. (2023). Successes and challenges in clinical gene therapy. *Gene Therapy*, 30(11-12), 738-746. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41434-023-00390-5>

Levesque, S., & Bauer, D. E. (2023). Gene correction for sickle cell disease hits its prime. *Nature Biomedical Engineering*, 7(5), 605-606. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41551-023-00887-9>

MedlinePlus. (2022). What is gene therapy? Retrieved from <https://medlineplus.gov/genetics/understanding/therapy/genetics/gene-therapy/> Accessed [09-02-2024].

National Human Genome Research Institute (NHGRI). (2022). Gene therapy. Retrieved from <https://www.genome.gov/genetics-glossary/Gene-Therapy> <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41551-023-00887-9> Accessed [16-02-2024].

Osunkwo, I., Andemariam, B., Minniti, C. P., Inusa, B. P., El Rassi, F., Francis-Gibson, B., & James, J. (2021). Impact of sickle cell disease on patients' daily lives/symptoms reported. And disease management strategies: Results from the international Sickle Cell World Assessment Survey (SWAY). *American Journal of Hematology*, 96(4), 404-417. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajh.26167>

Park, S. H., & Bao, G. (2021). CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing for curing sickle cell disease. *Transfusion and Apheresis Science*, 60(1), 103060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transci.2021.103060>

Pirone, A. C., Oktriani, R., Boettcher, M., & Hoheisel, J. D. (2020). Process for an efficient lentiviral cell transduction. *Biology Methods and Protocols*, 5(1), bpaa005. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biomethods/bpaa005>

Spink, J., & Geddes, D. (2004). Gene therapy progress and prospects: bringing gene therapy into medical practice: the evolution of international ethics and the regulatory environment. *Gene Therapy*, 11(20), 1611-1616. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.gt.3302362>

The Foundation for Sickle Cell Disease Research (2024). The Journal - The Foundation for Sickle Cell Disease Research. Retrieved from <https://www.fscdr.org/the-journal/> Accessed [03-01-2024].

Yawn, B. P., Buchanan, G. R., Afenyi-Annan, A. N., Ballas, S. K., Hassell, K. L., James, A. H., Jordan, L., Lanzkron, S. M., Lottenberg, R., Savage, W. J., Tanabe, P. J., Ware, R. E., Murad, M. H., Goldsmith, J. C., Ortiz, E., Fulwood, R., Horton, A., & John-Sowah J. (2014). Management of sickle cell disease: Summary of the 2014 evidence-based report by expert panel members [published correction appears in JAMA 2014;312(12):1253]. JAMA, 312(10), 1033–1048. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2014.10517>

Zarghamian, P., Klermund, J., & Cathomen, T. (2023). Clinical genome editing to treat sickle cell disease-A brief update. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 9, 1065377. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2022.1065377>

Zheng, C. X., Wang, S. M., Bai, Y. H., Luo, T. T., Wang, J. Q., Dai, C. Q., Guo, B. L., Luo, S. C., Wang, D. H., Yang, Y. L., & Wang, Y. Y. (2018). Lentiviral vectors and adeno-associated virus vectors: Useful tools for gene transfer in pain research. *The Anatomical Record*, 301(5), 825-836. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ar.23723>

Determination of Levels of Heavy Metal in Sub-Soil Around Incinerator in University of Benin Health Centre

Emuokhonun, G. A.¹, Unuigbe, C. A.², Okodugha, V. O.³, Madu, P. C.⁴

¹Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria

²Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria

³Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author Tel: +234 7061138733 Email: godwinemuokhonun@aauekpoma.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Incineration of medical waste (MW) is an important alternative way for disposal of this type of hazardous waste. Samples of soil around adopted incinerator and soil within the health center were collected from University of Benin Health Center and soil samples from Capitol (before UNIBEN Chancellor residence) in the same University of Benin was also collected which served as the control site. These studies were carried out in Benin City, Edo state of Nigeria from January 2017 to December 2017. Samples were analyzed for Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe, and Mn. Samples were collected between the hours of 4pm to 7pm on Fridays of every week for one year. The mean concentrations of heavy metals (Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe, and Mn) were determined in the samples. Atomic absorption spectrophotometry was used for heavy metal analysis after digestion using standard methods. The results obtained are: 0.467 ± 0.267 mg/kg, 0.0331 ± 0.049 mg/kg, 0.003 ± 0.005 mg/kg, 0.7251 ± 0.316 mg/kg, 12.4761 ± 0.315 mg/kg, 0.922 ± 0.073 mg/kg for (Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe and Mn) respectively for the control site, 0.800 ± 0.374 mg/kg, 0.133 ± 0.098 mg/kg, 0.133 ± 0.098 mg/kg, 1.6191 ± 0.737 mg/kg, 23.467 ± 0.861 mg/kg, 2.465 ± 0.295 mg/kg (Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe, and Mn) respectively for the health center and 1.135 ± 0.281 mg/kg, 0.242 ± 0.162 mg/kg, 0.023 ± 0.036 mg/kg, 2.118 ± 0.881 mg/kg, 26.258 ± 1.200 mg/kg, 2.465 ± 0.295 mg/kg (Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe, and Mn) respectively for the incinerator site. Data obtained were analyzed using (ANOVA). A probability $\alpha = 0.05$ was considered as significant. P-values at (probability $\alpha = 0.05$) of (Zn - $4.2E-09$), (Pb = 0.007809), (Cd - 0.21624), (Cr = $1.05E-07$), (Fe - $1.13E-23$) and (Mn = $1.44E-15$) except for Pb and Cd, others listed were all less than 0.001, this indicates that the various site/location has a significant effect on the mean concentrations of the various heavy metals. While for Pb and Cd, the various site/location had no effects on their mean concentrations. The results from the site/locations were higher than the control site, indicating a clear case of pollution. Comparison of heavy metal concentration in soil with WHO maximum allowed limits showed that they are all below the set limits. The soils at the adopted medical incinerator had higher concentrations of heavy metals than the soils around the health center. Medical waste, when not properly disposed of, poses a serious threat to public health and should be disposed of appropriately.

Keywords: Incineration, Medical Waste, Heavy Metal, Concentration

1 Introduction

Municipal solid waste management is an area of research that has evolved significantly in developed countries over the years unlike what is obtainable in developing countries. Among the constituents of municipal wastes are medical wastes. Standard medical waste management protocol involves incineration. While this has the advantage of killing pathogens in the waste stream and reducing waste volume and reactivity, incineration has been found to impact on the environment through the release of hazardous combustion products, such as heavy

metals, dioxins and PAHs which have environmental and public health implication. This is of great public concern (Thakur *et al.*, 2023; Tait *et al.*, 2020.). Medical waste incineration involves the burning of waste generated by hospital veterinary facilities and medical research facilities which include infectious medical wastes as well as non-infectious general housekeeping waste.

However there is usually contamination of the surrounding environment with the various release from incineration and uncontrolled disposal of ash is a common practice in the country. This leads to

pollution in our environment, as a result of the various components contained in them (Kanhari *et al.*, 2020).

Incinerated hospital waste has been found to contain more heavy metals like chromium, cadmium, lead, magnesium, zinc and other metals (Ghobakhloo *et al.*, 2024). Exposure can pose public health problem such as acute respiratory syndromes, gastrointestinal abnormalities and various cancers (Winiarska *et al.*, 2024)

Heavy metals are generally defined as metals with relatively high densities ($>5\text{g/cm}^3$) atomic weights, or atomic numbers (Iroegbulem *et al.*, 2023; Iyama *et al.*, 2023). The term "Heavy metals" is used to describe more than a dozen elements that are metals or metalloids. Though they are natural constituents of the earth's crust, there are also anthropogenic sources, in small amounts, they enter the human body via food, drinking water and air.

The most common heavy metals found at contaminated sites in order of abundance are Pb, Cr, As, Zn, Cd, Cu and Hg. Medical waste is considered as a source of contamination of land and water. If not rendered harmless before it is buried in land or disposed in water (Adepoju *et al.*, 2024). The harmful chemicals from biomedical waste may pollute air, water and land that in turn may cause health problems to the residents (Shabani *et al.*, 2024).

Incinerated hospital waste has been found to contain more heavy metals like Chromium, Cadmium, lead, Mercury, Zinc and other metals (Ghobakhloo *et al.*, 2024). Acute exposures to high levels cause nausea, vomiting, gastrointestinal abnormalities and dermatitis. Chronic exposures to heavy metals cause cumulative toxic effects, which affect various systems in the body depending on the heavy metal involved (Parui *et al.*, 2024)

Soils are the major sink for heavy metals released into the environment by so many anthropogenic activities and most metals do not undergo microbial or chemical degradation and their total concentration in soils persist for a long time after their introduction (Corvalán *et al.*, 2024). Heavy metals contamination of soil may pose risks and hazards to humans and the ecosystem through direct ingestion or contact with contaminated soil, the food chain (soil-plant-human or soil-plant-animal-human), drinking of contaminated groundwater e.t.c. (Eigbike *et al.*, 2024)

Lead is causing concern in particular due to the

possible impacts on children. Lead influences the nervous system by slowing down neural response (Huang *et al.*, 2024). This influences learning abilities and behaviour. Children are exposed to lead right from their birth, as children in the embryonic stage receive lead from their mothers through the blood (Chbihi *et al.*, 2024). Children exposed to lead via dust and soil contaminated by deposition from air and other sources. In the environment, lead is known to be toxic to plants, animals and microorganisms. Effects are generally limited to specially contaminated areas (Debroy *et al.*, 2024).

Particularly in the renal cortex of the kidneys, cadmium buildup causes renal dysfunction, including poor protein, glucose, and amino acid absorption. Renal tubular injury, or kidney damage, is most likely the major health consequence. (Bautista *et al.*, 2024).

Renal stone development and hypercalciuria are other symptoms of the disruption in calcium metabolism. Cadmium is categorized as class 1 by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). (Milanković *et al.*, 2024).

In general, cadmium is more accessible, more mobile in soil, and has a tendency to bioaccumulate. Animal and plant life does not require cadmium. The overall population who does not smoke is primarily exposed to cadmium through diet. Other pathways make up a very minor portion of the total intake. The human body accumulates cadmium, particularly in the kidneys. (Adamo *et al.*, 2024; Nungula *et al.*, 2024; and Satarug, 2024)

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

All chemicals used were of analytical grade and purchased from Pyrex (Nigeria). They included; nitric acid, hydrochloric acid,

2.1 THE STUDY AREA

University of Benin is situated within the Ovia North-East local Government area of Benin City, Edo state Of Nigeria. It lies between the geographical coordinates of longitude 536' and 0.53" E and of latitude 6°20' and 1.32" N.

2.2 SAMPLING LOCATION

Sampling sites used for this study is located within the premises of the University of Benin Health Center

facility. An incinerator is made out of the Center's combustion pit. It is approximately 8 feet deep and well protected from ground contamination with concrete walls. It also has a metallic cover to prevent rodents from assessing the wastes in it as well as limit air contamination during wastes combustion. Due to constant burning over the years, the cover has corroded significantly leaving observable opening. Hazardous hospital wastes are usually combusted in this local incinerator during the dry seasons of the year.

2.3 SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Soil samples were collected weekly from around adopted incinerator, soil within the University of Benin Health Center and soil samples from Capitol (before UNIBEN Chancellor residence) in the same University of Benin which served as the control site. Sampling was done from January to December 2017. Composite surface soil samples were collected for the entire sampling duration.

Collected soil samples were wrapped in polyethylene bags and placed in a refrigerator.

Data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and a probability 0.05 was considered as significant.

2.4 SAMPLING PREPARATION

All foreign objects like roots and gravel sized materials were picked and separated from the dried samples. 10g of the samples were weighed into porcelain crucibles using chemical balance and then oven dried at a temperature of 105 °C and 1g was then weighed into a labeled 100ml conical flask (Qiu *et al.*, 2018).

2.5 Cleaning of glassware

All apparatus were washed with detergents then rinsed with distilled water. The glassware was then dried in a hot oven at 105^oC.

2.6 Soil digestion

Well mixed samples of 1g each were weighed using a Scientech Zeta series electronic balance. The samples were put into 250 ml glass beaker and digested with 24 ml of aqua regia and then evaporated to near dryness. The soil samples were then dissolved in 30ml of distilled water, filtered through a 0.45 μm

membrane paper and then made up to 100 ml with distilled water prior to AAS analysis (Begum *et al.*, 2009). Duplicate samples were analyzed

The resulting solution was stored in a pre-cleaned polyethylene bottle until time for analysis. All the soil samples were analyzed for Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, and Mn using AAS, using appropriate lamps and resonance wavelength of the metals, at Department of Chemistry Research Laboratory, University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The concentrations of the various heavy metals studied for the duration of the study are presented in Tables 1.1-1.5, and figures 1.1-1.2 below

Results obtained indicate a concentration range of 1.217±0.264 mg/kg to 0.483±0.248 mg/kg for Zn for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of March, 0.200±0.276 mg/kg to 0.083±0.041 mg/kg for Pb for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of March, 0.037±0.049mg/kg to 0.002±0.004mg/kg for Cd for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of March, 2.322±1.140mg/kg to 0.705±0.385mg/kg for Cr for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of March, 21.767±7.710mg/kg to 20.050±6.129mg/kg for Fe for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of November, 2.582±1.314mg/kg to 1.810±0.713mg/kg for Fe for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of November, as seen from table 1.2.

Results from Table 1.1 show that Fe had the highest mean concentration (across the months) of 12.476±0.315 mg/kg and Cd had the lowest, 0.003±0.005 mg/kg among the heavy metals found in soils around the Control. The descending order of metal content was Fe&Mn&Cr&Zn&Pb&Cd. Similar trends were observed for the results for Health Centre and incinerator sites in Table 1.1 where the mean concentrations of Fe (across the months) were 23.467±0.861 mg/kg and 26.258±1.200 mg/kg respectively and Cd had the lowest, 0.003±0.005 mg/kg among the heavy metals found in soil. The descending order of metal

Figure 1: A bar chart showing heavy metal concentration across the three sites

Table 1: Summary of Mean Concentration of Heavy Metals in Soils across the Sites

Parameters	Control	Health Center	Incinerator	WHO Values	p-values
Zn (mg/kg)	0.467±0.267	0.800±0.374	1.135±0.281	300.000	4.2E-09
Pb (mg/kg)	0.033±0.049	0.133±0.098	0.242±0.162	100.000	0.007809
Cd (mg/kg)	0.003±0.005	0.133±0.098	0.023±0.036	3.000	0.21624
Cr (mg/kg)	0.725±0.316	1.619±0.737	2.118±0.881	100.000	1.05E-07
Fe (mg/kg)	12.476±0.315	23.467±0.861	26.258±1.200	-	1.13E-23
Mn (mg/kg)	0.922±0.073	2.465±0.295	2.465±0.295	1000.000	1.44E-15

Table 2: Correlation Matrix for heavy metals at the Control site

	Zn	Pb	Cd	Cr	Fe	Mn
Zn	1					
Pb	-0.046	1				
Cd	-0.046	0.625*	1			
Cr	0.169	-0.706*	-0.694*	1		
Fe	0.413	-0.236	-0.119	0.185	1	
Mn	0.031	-0.546	-0.521	0.454	0.407	1

Table 3: Correlation Matrix for heavy metals at the Health Center

	Zn	Pb	Cd	Cr	Fe	Mn
Zn	1					
Pb	0.049	1				
Cd	0.049	-0.437	1			
Cr	0.261	-0.602*	0.071	1		
Fe	0.333	0.379	-0.057	0.266	1	
Mn	-0.472	0.317	-0.050	0.074	0.247	1

Table 4: Correlation Matrix for heavy metals at the Incinerator

	Zn	Pb	Cd	Cr	Fe	Mn
Zn	1					
Pb	0.679*	1				
Cd	0.466	0.873**	1			
Cr	0.638*	0.895**	0.733**	1		
Fe	0.111	0.000	-0.128	0.179	1	
Mn	0.186	0.020	0.036	0.100	0.782**	1

content was Fe > Mn > Cr > Zn > Pb > Cd. The concentration of heavy metals at the three sites shows a relative decrease with distance from the source (Incinerator > Health Center > Control). This may be attributed to contamination of soil within the immediate vicinity of the incinerator by ash which could be aided by wind

as the adopted incinerator has an observable opening due to corrosion as a result of continuous burning. The Incinerator recorded high mean concentrations of heavy metal contents in the three sites across the months.

From Table 1.2, the result shows the mean concentrations of heavy metals in the soils across the month. In the month of March, it was observed that the mean concentration of Zn, Pb, Cd, and Cr recorded higher concentrations (1.217±0.264 mg/kg, 0.200±0.276 mg/kg, 0.037±0.049 mg/kg and 2.322±1.140 mg/kg) respectively as compared to other months studied while Fe and Mn recorded higher mean concentrations (21.767±7.710 mg/kg, 2.582±1.314 mg/kg) respectively with Fe having the highest mean concentration (21.767±7.710 mg/kg) among all the metals studied. Zn had the lowest mean concentration (0.483±0.248 mg/kg) in the month of October, Pb had the lowest mean concentration (0.083±0.075, 0.083±0.041 mg/kg) in the month of September and October having approximately the same value. Cd had the lowest mean concentration (0.002±0.004 mg/kg) in the month of October, Cr had the lowest mean concentration (0.705±0.385 mg/kg) in the month of April, Fe had the lowest mean concentration (20.050±6.129 mg/kg) in the month of May and Mn had the lowest mean concentrations (1.810±0.713 mg/kg) in the month of September. All the metal concentrations in soil were below the WHO maximum allowed limits (Table 1.1-1.2). The concentrations of heavy metals in these soils were low compared to that of polluted soils as reported in the research work done by Yahaya et al. (2009) and Timothy and Olajumoke (2013). The concentration of heavy metals at the three sites shows a relative decrease with distance from the source (Incinerator > Health Centre > Control). This may be attributed to contamination of soil within the immediate vicinity of the incinerator by ash which could be aided

Figure 2: A bar chart showing heavy metal concentrations across the months

by the wind as the adopted incinerator has an observable opening due to corrosion as a result of continuous burning. The Incinerator recorded high concentrations of heavy metals studied as compared to the Health Centre and the control site which in turn had the least concentrations of heavy metals studied.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). A probability ≤ 0.05 was considered significant. From Table 1.1, P-values at (probability ≤ 0.05) of (Zn = 4.2E-09), (Pb = 0.007809), (Cd = 0.21624), (Cr = 1.05E-07), (Fe = 1.13E-23) and (Mn = 1.44E-15) except for Pb and Cd, others listed were all less than 0.001. This indicates that the various sites/location have significant effect on the mean concentrations of the various heavy metals. While for Pb and Cd, the various site/location had no effects on their mean concentrations. From Table 1.2, P-values at (probability ≤ 0.05) of (Zn = 4.89E-09), (Pb = 0.303), (Cd = 0.040), (Cr = 7.54E-08), (Fe = 0.010) and (Mn = 0.00027) were all less than 0.005. This indicates that the months have significant effect on the concentration of the various metal concentrations respectively.

From Table 1.3, results of the Correlation Matrix for heavy metals at the control site, *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Significant positive correlations were observed between Cd and Pb, as Cd concentrations increase, concentrations of Pb also increase while significant negative correlations were observed between Cr and Pb, Cr and Cd, as concentrations of Cr increase, concentrations of Pb and Cd decrease. This indicates that they were from the same source of contamination.

The results from Table 1.4, Correlation matrix for heavy metals at the Health Center *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Significant negative correlation was observed for Cr and Pb, as the concentrations of Cr increase, concentrations of Pb decrease.

From Table 1.5, the results of the Correlation Matrix for heavy metals at the Incinerator *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Significant positive correlation was observed between Pb and Zn, Cd and Pb, Cr and Pb, Cr and Cd, Mn and Fe. Significant positive correlation indicates that as one increases the other increases. Significant negative correlation was observed Fe and Cd, negative

correlation indicate that as one increases the other decreases.

Conclusion: The results from the sites/locations were higher than control site, indicating a clear case of pollution. Comparison of heavy metal concentration in soil with WHO maximum allowed limits showed that they are all below the set limits. The soils at the adopted medical incinerator had higher concentrations of heavy metals than the soils around the Health Centre. Medical waste when not properly disposed poses serious threat to public health and should be disposed of appropriately.

RECOMMENDATION

Comparing current study with WHO maximum allowed limits showed that the heavy metals concentrations were below. Appropriate care should be taken to avoid further increase in the concentrations as bottom ash could increase the concentrations. This could be done by ensuring the proper sealing of the adopted incinerator.

References

- Adepoju, A. O., Femi-Adepoju, A., Jalloh, A., & Faeflen, S. (2024). Soil pollution and management practices. In *Environmental Pollution and Public Health* (pp. 187-236). Elsevier.
- Corvalán Moya, C., Bruni, C., Barbini, A., & Previtali, E. (2024). An analysis of heavy metals movements on soils from places with high level risk of flooding and different anthropogenic activities. *J. Mater. Environ. Sci.*, 15 (1), 162, 178.
- Eigbike, C., Odion, N., and Ojo-igbinosa, U. (2024). Assessment of heavy metal contamination of some designated scrap yards in Benin city, Edo State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Health, Safety and Environment*, 5(1), 01-10.
- Ghobakhloo, S., Mostafaii, G. R., Khoshakhlagh, A. H., Moda, H. M., & Gruszecka-Kosowska, A. (2024). Health risk assessment of heavy metals in exposed workers of municipal waste recycling facility in Iran. *Chemosphere*, 346, 140627.
- Ghobakhloo, S., Mostafaii, G. R., Khoshakhlagh, A. H., Moda, H. M., & Gruszecka-Kosowska, A. (2024). Health risk assessment of heavy metals in exposed workers of municipal waste recycling facility in Iran. *Chemosphere*, 346, 140627.
- Hussain, M.S., Gupta, G., Mishra, R., Patel, N., Gupta, S., Alzarea, S.I., Kazmi, I., Kumbhar, P., Disouza, J., Dureja, H. and Kukreti, N., 2024.

Unlocking the secrets: Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) and their devastating effects on lung cancer. Pathology-Research and Practice, p.155157.

Iroegbulem, I. U., Egereonu, U. U., Ogukwe, C. E., Egereonu, J. C., Okoro, N. J., & Nwoko, C. I. A. (2023). Assessment of Heavy Metals in Rainwater from Metropolis and Suburbs, Lagos State, Nigeria. International Journal of Environment and Climate Change, 13(9), 831-857.

Iyama, W. A., Nimame, P., Egbunefu, C. O., Nakara, T., Emejuru, S., & Nwagbara, V. U. (2023). Journal of Environmental and Science Education.

Odjugo, P. A. O., et al. (2015). "Geospatial approach to spatio-temporal pattern of urban growth in Benin City, Nigeria." African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology 9(3): 166-175.

Parui, R., Nongthombam, G. S., Hossain, M., Adil, L. R., Gogoi, R., Bhowmik, S., ... & Iyer, P. K. (2024). Impact of Heavy Metals on Human Health. Remediation of Heavy Metals: Sustainable Technologies and Recent Advances, 47-81.

Qiu, H., Du, J., Fang, X., & Chen, M. (2018). Differences in Soil Remediation of Ecological Shelterbelt in Taihu Lake. Sustainable Forestry, 1(1), 19-28.

Shabani, T., Mutekwa, V. T., & Shabani, T. (2024). Environmental health risks associated with solid waste management at rural hospitals in Chirumanzu District, Zimbabwe. SN Social Sciences, 4(2), 20.

Thakur Palak, Anchal Thakur, Samriti Gautam, Jagdish Choudhary, Ruchika Kumari, Kirti Raina, Rohit Sharma, Ashun Chaudhary (2023). "Occurrence and formation of environmentally persistent free radicals in incineration and their impact on soil and water". Journal of Geochemical Exploration 252, 107264

Timoithy, A. and A. M. Olajumoke (2013). "Heavy Metal Concentrations around a Hospital Incinerator and a Municipal Dumpsite in Ibadan City, South-West Nigeria." J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manage 17(3): 419-422.

Winiarska, E., Jutel, M., & Zemelka-Wiacek, M. (2024). The potential impact of nano-and microplastics on human health: Understanding human health risks. Environmental Research, 118535.

Yahaya, M. I., et al. (2009). "Seasonal Variations of Heavy Metals Concentration in Abattoir Dumping Site

Soil in Nigeria." J. Appli. Sci. Environ. Manage. 13(4): 9-13.

Zhao, L., et al. (2010). "Typical pollutants in bottom ashes from a typical medical waste incinerator." Journal of Hazardous Materials 173(1-3): 181-185.

article geometry a4paper, margin=1in graphicx amsmath array booktabs caption longtable

Appendix

Various concentrations of Zn

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	1.00	0.70	0.40	0.20	0.30	0.20
	0.80	0.60	0.60	0.30	0.30	0.20
Health center	1.30	1.20	1.00	0.50	0.40	0.60
	1.30	1.10	0.90	0.60	0.30	0.40
Incinerator (around)	1.50	1.40	1.30	0.70	0.80	1.20
	1.40	1.22	1.20	0.80	0.80	1.30

Various concentrations of Pb

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00
	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10
Health center	0.00	0.30	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.20
	0.10	0.30	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.20
Incinerator (around)	0.50	0.20	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.20
	0.60	0.10	0.30	0.20	0.10	0.30

Various concentrations of Cd

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01
	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Health center	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
Incinerator (around)	0.10	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01
	0.10	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00

Various concentrations of Cr

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	1.01	0.32	1.00	1.00	0.30	0.72
1.00	0.37	1.01	0.97	0.30	0.70	
Health center	2.40	0.61	2.37	1.30	0.97	2.11
2.42	0.57	2.40	1.31	0.97	2.00	
Incinerator (around)	3.54	1.20	2.50	1.57	1.31	2.58
3.56	1.16	2.53	1.59	1.29	2.59	

Various concentrations of Fe

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	12.80	12.40	12.20	12.70	12.90	12.20
13.01	12.20	12.40	12.50	12.40	12.00	
Health center	24.20	23.70	22.60	23.30	22.40	24.40
24.50	23.80	22.50	23.00	22.50	24.70	
Incinerator (around)	26.10	25.80	25.20	25.50	26.60	28.70
25.80	25.60	25.40	25.30	26.50	28.60	

Various concentrations of Mn

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	1.02	0.77	0.91	0.91	0.95	0.96
1.00	0.80	0.93	0.90	0.96	0.95	
Health center	2.24	2.41	2.39	2.10	2.55	2.97
2.27	2.38	2.43	2.13	2.72	2.99	
Incinerator (around)	3.24	3.12	3.00	2.42	3.75	3.82
3.25	3.08	2.59	2.40	3.75	3.80	

ANOVA

Zn

SoV	SS	df	MS	F	P-val
F crit					
Locations	2.696056	5	0.539211	25.71209	4.2E-05
2.602987					
Months	2.656056	5	0.531211	25.33061	4.89E-05
2.602987					
Error	0.524278	25	0.020971		
Total	5.876389	35			

Pb

SoV	SS	df	MS	F	P-val
F crit					
Locations	0.268056	5	0.053611	4.058032	0.0073
2.602987					
Months	0.084722	5	0.016944	1.28259	0.3021
2.602987					
Error	0.330278	25	0.013211		
Total	0.683056	35			

Cd

SoV	SS	df	MS	F	P-val
F crit					
Locations	0.002981	5	0.000596	1.53067	0.2161
2.602987					
Months	0.005381	5	0.001076	2.763195	0.0401
2.602987					
Error	0.009736	25	0.000389		
Total	0.018097	35			

Fe

SoV	SS	df	MS	F	P-val
F crit					
Locations	1274.29	5	254.8581	453.1056	1.13E-05
2.602987					
Months	10.95335	5	2.190669	3.894735	0.0091
2.602987					
Error	14.06174	25	0.562469		
Total	1299.305	35			

Mn

SoV F crit	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Locations 2.602987	32.11669	5	6.423338	97.45652	1.44E-15
Months 2.602987	2.372556	5	0.474511	7.199404	0.00027
Error	1.647744	25	0.06591		
Total	36.13699	35			

Cr

SoV F crit	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Locations 2.602987	11.96103	5	2.392205	18.57903	1.05E-07
Months 2.602987	12.38289	5	2.476578	19.23431	7.54E-08
Error	3.218958	25	0.128758		
Total	27.56288	35			